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**MEDIATION, MEDDLING, &
MICROMANAGEMENT**

**INDIA IN NEPAL'S PEACE
PROCESS AND POLITICAL
TRANSITION**

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Mediation, Meddling, and Micromanagement

India in Nepal's Peace Process and
Political Transition

Manoj Bhusal

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Abstract

This study examines India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition in the post-conflict era. The period of examination primarily focuses on, but is not strictly confined to, the years between 2005 and 2017. This timeframe marks a pivotal chapter in Nepal's history, characterised by transformative events such as the 2006 pro-democracy uprising (*Jana Andolan II*), the resolution of a decade-long Maoist insurgency that claimed over 17,000 lives, the abolition of the 240-year-old monarchy, the promulgation of a new constitution, and Nepal's transition from a unitary Hindu monarchy to a secular federal democratic republic. As the nascent republic navigated a series of political avalanches in the post-conflict transition, India was heavily involved in Nepal—often exhibiting a complex character, transmitting both assistance and assertion.

Although India's role in Nepal's peace process and political transition is widely recognised, the specifics of its involvement, such as its facilitation of the 12-Point Understanding, remain unclear. This study addresses that gap by offering an in-depth analysis of India's role in Nepal's political turmoil during the mid-2000s and its subsequent engagement in post-conflict Nepal. In doing so, it also provides a broader and critical re-evaluation of India–Nepal relations. While not the primary objective, the study also identifies and discusses key lessons from Nepal's peace process and political transition.

This study employs a three-layered theoretical framework, integrating concepts from peace and mediation research, critical international relations, and global development studies. The first layer examines peace mediation as a foreign policy tool, analysing mediators' motives alongside the concepts of 'power mediators' and 'pure mediators'. The second layer explores rising power behaviour, the paradoxes of South–South Cooperation, and the harsh realities of contemporary sub-imperialism. Lastly, world-systems theory and dependency concepts provide a broader historical and economic perspective, serving as effective reference points for conducting a thorough analysis of India–Nepal relations.

Methodologically, the study is rooted in critical realism and employs a single case study design. Data were collected from multiple sources, including semi-structured key informant interviews (n=18, 982 minutes), media materials (n=105, 750 pages), and video interviews and speeches (n=12, 360 minutes). Using an inductive approach based on grounded theory, the data were analysed using the qualitative content analysis method.

By analysing a series of political events in Nepal from as early as 2001, the study concludes that while India's facilitative role in the 12-Point Understanding was indeed helpful, it was Nepal's internal political dynamics, coupled with a Mutually Enticing Opportunity (MEO), that ultimately initiated the peace process. However, India was successful in portraying itself as a peace broker and in leveraging that narrative to strengthen its influence in post-conflict Nepal. During the post-conflict political transition, Indian influence grew significantly, as did Nepal's dependency on India, with India actively intervening and micromanaging Nepal's political affairs.

India consolidated its influence over Nepal's political, bureaucratic, and security institutions through a combination of soft and hard power strategies. This created a state of 'peace dependency,' where Nepali political actors became heavily reliant on India to resolve even mundane political stalemates and maintain post-conflict stability. However, in the later stages of the political transition, Nepal strongly

challenged and resisted India's hard power tactics, including coercive diplomacy and economic blockade, and demonstrated significant resistance to external domination.

This study situates India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition within a sub-imperialist framework and as rooted in a historically complex relationship marked by both cooperation and conflict. Analysing India's long-term engagement in Nepal reveals its intent to transform Nepal into a sub-imperialist domain. India seeks to gain control over Nepal's natural resources—particularly water—and promote a world system based on neoliberal capitalism and various forms of aggression. While India has gradually entrapped Nepal in a web of dependencies, its own relationship with global financial institutions and Western powers, particularly the United States, exhibits similar dependency traits. Furthermore, India's preoccupation with regional sub-imperialism is intertwined with its inclination for internal colonialism at home and its fixation with the Hindu-nationalist Hindutva ideology.

This study offers fresh insights into rising power behaviour by critically examining India's engagement in post-conflict Nepal. It challenges the assumption that the economic and political ascendance of a select few countries from the Global South paves the way for a more equitable world order. Instead, it demonstrates how these so-called rising powers engage with their less powerful neighbours, often cloaking their actions in the rhetoric of collective emancipation or South–South Cooperation (SSC). However, in practice, they frequently adopt extractivist and oppressive policies that perpetuate and reinforce unequal power relations. This undermines the long-cherished aspirations of particularly smaller and less powerful developing countries for a fairer and more equitable global order.

The study concludes with a critique of Nepal's peace and political transition process, acknowledging its notable achievements while highlighting critical shortcomings, such as the lack of an effective transitional justice framework and the failure to implement impactful socio-economic reforms. These findings provide valuable lessons for future peace processes in comparable contexts and contribute to the broader discourse on international mediation, post-conflict reconstruction, South–South relations, and the pressing issues of regional power rivalries and a shifting world order.

Keywords: Nepal peace process, India–Nepal relations, South Asian geopolitics, sub-imperialism, South–South Cooperation, rising power behaviour, critical realism, case study

Tiivistelmä

Tämä tutkimus tarkastelee Intian osallistumista Nepalin rauhanprosessiin ja poliittiseen siirtymään konfliktin jälkeen, keskittyen ensisijaisesti vuosiin 2005–2017. Tätä käännteentekevää ajanjaksoa Nepalissa leimasivat suuria muutoksia aikaansaaneet tapahtumat, kuten vuoden 2006 demokraattinen kansannousu (*Jana Andolan II*), yli 17 000 henkeä vaatineen kymmenvuotisen maolaisissiliikkeen päättymisen, 240-vuotisen monarkian lakkauttaminen ja uuden perustuslain säätäminen, jonka myötä Nepal muuttui yhtenäisestä hindumonarkiasta sekulaariksi demokraattiseksi liittotasavallaksi. Nuoren tasavallan kamppaillessa poliittisten mullistusten kanssa Intia toimi Nepalissa aktiivisesti ja monitahoisesti, yhdistäen avunannon ja määrätietoisin vallankäytön.

Vaikka Intian rooli Nepalissa rauhanprosessissa ja poliittisessä siirtymässä on laajalti tunnustettu, sen osallistumisen yksityiskohdat, esimerkiksi 12-kohtaisen yhteisymmärryksen (*12-Point Understanding*) aikaansaamisessa, ovat edelleen epäselviä. Tämä tutkimus tuottaa aiheesta uutta tietoa ja tarjoaa syvällisen analyysin Intian roolista Nepalissa poliittisessä myllerryksessä 2000-luvun puolivälissä sekä konfliktin päättymisen jälkeen. Samalla se arvioi uudelleen Intian ja Nepalissa suhdetta laajemmasta, kriittisestä näkökulmasta. Lisäksi työ tarkastelee ja nostaa esiin Nepalissa rauhanprosessin ja poliittisen siirtymän keskeisiä opetuksia.

Tutkimuksessa käytetään kolmitasoisista teoreettista viitekehystä, joka yhdistää rauhan- ja konfliktintutkimuksen, kriittisen kansainvälisen politiikan ja globaalin kehitystutkimuksen käsitteitä. Ensimmäinen taso tarkastelee rauhanvälitystä ulkopoliittikan välineenä, analysoiden rauhanvälittäjien motiiveja sekä rauhanvälitykseen liittyvää käsitteistöä ('power mediators' ja 'pure mediators'). Toinen taso pureutuu nousevien valtojen käyttäytymiseen, globaalin etelän maiden yhteistyön haasteisiin ja nykyisen subimperialismin realiteetteihin. Lopuksi maailmanjärjestelmäteorian ja riippuvuusteorian käsitteet tarjoavat laajemman historiallis-taloudellisen perspektiivin ja viitekehyksen Intian ja Nepalissa suhteen syvällisemmälle analyysille.

Menetelmällisesti tutkimus pohjautuu kriittiseen realismiin ja noudattaa yksittäisen tapaustutkimuksen mallia. Aineisto koostuu avainhenkilöiden puolistrukturoiduista haastatteluista (n=18, 982 minuuttia), media-aineistosta (n=105, 750 sivua) sekä videohaastatteluista ja puheista (n=12, 360 minuuttia). Aineisto on analysoitu induktiivista, grounded theory-lähestymistapaan perustuvaa laadullista sisällönanalyysia hyödyntäen.

Analysoidessaan Nepalissa poliittisia tapahtumia vuodesta 2001 lähtien tutkimus päättyy johtopäätökseen, että Intian toiminta edesauttoi 12-kohtaisen yhteisymmärryksen aikaansaamisessa, mutta varsinaisen rauhanprosessin käynnisti Nepalissa sisäinen poliittinen dynamiikka, joka tarjosi konfliktin osapuolille uusia mahdollisuuksia ja kannustimia. Intia onnistui kuitenkin esiintymään rauhanvälittäjänä ja hyödyntämään tätä narratiivia vahvistaakseen vaikutusvaltaansa konfliktin jälkeisessä Nepalissa. Poliittisen siirtymävaiheen aikana Intia puuttui aktiivisesti Nepalissa poliittisiin asioihin, mikä lisäsi Intian vaikutusvaltaa maassa ja syvensi sen riippuvuutta Intiasta.

Intia lujitti vaikutusvaltaansa Nepalissa poliittisissa, hallinnollisissa ja turvallisuusinstituutioissa yhdistämällä pehmeän ja kovan vallan strategioita. Tämä loi 'rauhanriippuvuuden' tilan, jossa Nepalissa poliittiset toimijat tukeutuivat vahvasti Intiaan ratkaistakseen jopa arkipäiväisiä poliittisia ongelmia ja ylläpitääkseen maan vakautta konfliktin jälkeen. Poliittisen siirtymän

myöhemmissä vaiheissa Nepal kuitenkin haastoi Intian vallankäyttöä vastustamalla esimerkiksi pakottavaa diplomatiaa ja taloussaartoa ja osoitti näin merkittävää vastarintaa siihen kohdistuneita ulkoisia valtapyrkimyksiä kohtaan.

Tutkimus sijoittaa Intian osallistumisen Nepalin rauhanprosessiin ja poliittisessa siirtymään subimperialistiseen viitekehykseen ja osaksi historiallisesti monimutkaista suhdetta, jolle ovat ominaisia sekä yhteistyö että konfliktit. Analyysi paljastaa Intian tavoitteen muuttua Nepal subimperialistiseksi vaikutusalueekseen. Intia pyrkimykset hallita Nepalin luonnonvaroja—erityisesti sen vesivaroja—tukevat samalla uusliberaaliin kapitalismiin ja erilaisiin voimankäytön muotoihin perustuvaa maailmanjärjestelmää. Vaikka Intia on vähitellen kietonut Nepalin riippuvuussuhteiden verkkoon, sen oma suhde globaaleihin rahoitusinstituutioihin ja länsivaltoihin, erityisesti Yhdysvaltoihin, ilmentää samankaltaisia riippuvuuden piirteitä. Intian subimperialistiset pyrkimykset kytkeytyvät myös sisäiseen kolonialismiin ja hindunationalistiseen Hindutva-ideologiaan.

Tutkimus tarjoaa uusia näkökulmia nousevien valtojen käyttäytymisen tarkasteluun analysoimalla kriittisesti Intian toimintaa konfliktin jälkeisessä Nepalissa. Se kyseenalaistaa oletuksen, että muutamien globaalin etelän maiden taloudellisen ja poliittisen vaikutusvallan kasvu loisi pohjan oikeudenmukaisemmalle maailmanjärjestykselle. Sen sijaan se osoittaa, kuinka nousevat vallat toimivat vähemmän vaikutusvaltaisten naapureidensa kanssa. Vaikka ne korostavat retoriikassaan kollektiivista emansipaatiota ja globaalin etelän maiden yhteistyötä, käytännössä ne usein tukeutuvat sellaisiin vallankäytön muotoihin, jotka ylläpitävät ja vahvistavat epätasaisia valtasuhteita. Tämä heikentää erityisesti pienempien ja vähemmän vaikutusvaltaisten globaalin etelän maiden pitkään vaalimia toiveita oikeudenmukaisemmasta ja tasapuolisemmasta maailmanjärjestyksestä.

Tutkielman loppupuolella arvioidaan myös Nepalin rauhanprosessia ja poliittista siirtymää kriittisestä näkökulmasta, tunnustaen sen merkittävät saavutukset mutta nostaen esiin myös keskeiset heikkoudet, kuten toimivan siirtymäkauden oikeudellisen viitekehyksen puuttumisen ja sosioekonomisten uudistusten toimeenpanon epäonnistumisen. Nämä havainnot tarjoavat arvokasta tietoa, jota voidaan hyödyntää rauhanprosessissa samankaltaisissa konteksteissa. Lisäksi ne edistävät keskustelua kansainvälisestä rauhanvälityksestä, konfliktin jälkeisestä jälleenrakennuksesta, globaalin etelän maiden suhteista, alueellisista valtakamppailuista sekä muuttuvasta maailmanjärjestyksestä.

Avainsanat: Nepalin rauhanprosessi, Intian ja Nepalin suhde, Etelä-Aasian geopolitiikka, subimperialismi, Etelä–Etelä-yhteistyö, nousevien valtojen käyttäytyminen, kriittinen realismi, tapaustutkimus

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This thesis is the end of a long, winding road, one that began in the dusty hills of rural Nepal, where I first witnessed my country stumble and bleed its way through history. As I grew from a boy into a young man, Nepal too was trying to grow, only it did so in the middle of an armed conflict, revolutions, and political storms that would humble even the hardest traveller. Somewhere along the way, I decided to make sense of that chaos, and this thesis is my modest attempt.

The journey here has been no smooth carriage ride. It has been a roller coaster—wild, rattling, and more than once, I thought the wheels might come off. But it has also been rewarding, even exhilarating, in the way that surviving a storm leaves you both exhausted and strangely grateful. Thus, I am deeply indebted to all who walked beside me on this journey, offering their support and steadying me in moments when the road grew rough.

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Manoj Bhusal

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Abbreviations

BBC	British Broadcasting Corporation
BIMSTEC	Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical & Economic Cooperation
BJP	Bharatiya Janata Party
BRI	Belt and Road Initiative
BRICS	Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa
CA	Constituent Assembly
CPA	Comprehensive Peace Accord
CPN (UML)	Communist Party of Nepal (Unified Marxist-Leninist)
CPN (M)	Communist Party of Nepal (Maoists)
CTGI	China Three Gorges International Corporation
DDR	Disarmament, Demobilisation, and Reintegration
ECLAC	United Nations Economic Commission for Latin America
EPG	Eminent Persons' Group
EU	European Union
EUR	Euro
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
G77	Group of 77
IBSA	India, Brazil, South Africa
IGP	Inspector-General of Police
IMC	Imminent Mutual Catastrophe
IMF	International Monetary Fund
INC	Indian National Congress
INGO	International Non-Governmental Organisation
INR	Indian Rupee
IR	International Relations
JNU	Jawaharlal Nehru University
MEO	Mutually Enticing Opportunity
MHS	Mutually Hurting Stalemate
MOFA	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
MW	Megawatt
NAM	Non-Aligned Movement
NC	Nepali Congress
NCP	Nepal Communist Party
NHPC	National Hydroelectric Power Corporation (of India)
NIEO	New International Economic Order
NNC	Nepali National Congress
NPR	Nepalese Rupee
OHCHR	Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights
PLA	People's Liberation Army
PSU	Public Sector Undertaking
RSS	Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh
SAARC	South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation
SDP	Small Development Projects

SPA	Seven Party Alliance
SSC	South–South Cooperation
TRC	Truth and Reconciliation Commission
UK	United Kingdom
UNMIN	United Nations Mission in Nepal
UPF	United People's Front
US	United States
USD	United States Dollar
ZoP	Zone of Peace

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1. Introduction

‘International politics, like all politics, is a struggle for power.’

– **Hans J. Morgenthau, *Politics Among Nations* (1978: 29)**

‘There is some self-interest behind every friendship. There is no friendship without self-interest. This is a bitter Truth.’ – **Chanakya, 371 BC.**¹

This study examines India’s engagement in Nepal’s peace process and post-conflict political transition (2005–2017). While this serves as the primary focus, the study also explores broader themes, including the nature of contemporary India–Nepal relations, India’s emergence as a rising power, its internal contradictions, and the way it engages with its less powerful neighbours. Moreover, the study investigates how conflict and political mediation can be used as foreign policy tools to achieve certain foreign policy goals. Finally, it enlists and reflects on lessons from Nepal’s ostensibly completed yet fundamentally flawed peace process. At its core, this study is about a conflict, its resolution, and its disenchanting stakeholders. It is a narrative of contemporary South Asian geopolitics—a story of rising and declining powers, of dependencies and defiance, and of the enduring interplay between resilience and resistance.

The study focuses on one of the most defining and crucial periods of modern Nepal, the period between 2005 and 2017. During this period, Nepal experienced both painful and rejuvenating political events, witnessing its own version of a political Renaissance. After a decade-long armed insurgency that claimed over 17,000 lives, the Maoist rebels laid down their arms in 2006 and entered mainstream politics. Following a brief but disastrous authoritarian interlude, Nepal’s 240-year-old monarchy was abolished in 2008, and Nepal was declared a federal democratic republic. The nascent republic then experienced a series of additional political avalanches—a protracted political transition, social and economic chaos created by two massive earthquakes, and a humanitarian catastrophe caused by India’s economic blockade.

As Nepal navigated one of the most challenging episodes in its modern history, the presence of neighbouring India—marked by both assistance and assertion—was profound. While India’s role was considered critical and emphatic, the specifics of its engagement in post-2005 Nepal remain unclear. For instance, India’s role in facilitating the pivotal 12-Point Understanding between the Maoists and a group of seven Nepali political parties, known as the Seven Party Alliance (SPA), remains largely unclear. Other episodes of Indian engagement, for instance, its role in the 2006 people’s movement (*Jana Andolan II*)², the subsequent peace deal, the constitution-making process (2008–2015), and more than a decade-long post-conflict political transition also remain largely unexplored.

This thesis revolves around these very issues. Simply stated, this is a (re)examination of India’s role in the Nepali peace process and the post-2005 political transition and an attempt to offer a fresh perspective on the Nepali peace process. While doing so, this study contributes to the broader scholarship on India–

¹ Cited in Sharma (2023)

² *Jana Andolan I* was a pro-democracy movement in Nepal during the 1990s.

Nepal relations. It prompts a critical re-evaluation of a long and complicated relationship marked by both cooperation and conflict, and a plethora of political, economic, and cultural interactions. Equally, it provides a new perspective on India's evolution as a rising power and sheds light on how it engages with its less powerful South Asian neighbours.

Theoretically, this study adopts an interdisciplinary approach, integrating concepts and perspectives from various theoretical strands. Theoretical concepts drawn from three domains—peace and mediation research, global development studies, and critical theories of international relations—constitute the theoretical framework of this study (Chapter 3). As conflict mediation and political transition processes are also often deeply linked to geopolitics and broader political and economic processes, the combination of different theoretical strands was not only helpful, but also necessary.

Methodologically, this is a singular case study based on a critical realist approach (Chapter 2). Data were accumulated from four sources: 1. Semi-structured key informant interviews (n=18), 2. Video materials, mostly consisting of talks and speeches of key informants unavailable for interview, 3. Opinion pieces and media interviews, mainly of key informants unavailable for interview, and 4. Articles collected from Nepali media archives. This way, in addition to 18 key-informant interviews totalling 16.36 hours (982 minutes), this study draws on 12 videos (360 minutes) and 105 textual sources—including opinion pieces, interviews, news articles, and in-depth reports—amounting to 750 pages of data. For data analysis, the study adopted an inductive approach based on grounded theory and used the qualitative content analysis method (Chapter 2).

Most key informants interviewed for this study were prominent political figures directly involved in Nepal's peace process and political transition. These individuals, for instance, participated in official and behind-the-scenes negotiations and contributed to drafting the 12-Point Understanding, the 2006 Comprehensive Peace Accord (CPA), the 2015 Constitution, and other significant political agreements. Their involvement spanned both domestic and international dimensions of the post-peace agreement era. The perspectives, insights, and experiences they shared hold substantial practical significance. Thus, the findings of this thesis will be particularly valuable to political negotiators, mediators, mediation organisations, policymakers, and most importantly, peace and international relations researchers. This study primarily contributes to peace and mediation research. However, its findings also enrich other theoretical domains, including various critical strands of international relations and global development studies.

By exploring the genesis of the Nepali peace process (Chapter 5) and examining India's extensive engagement in Nepal following the 2005 12-Point Understanding and the 2006 CPA, this study reveals how peace processes and political transitions can be moulded and influenced by external interests and geopolitical motives. Overall, this study enhances our understanding of the complexities of contemporary peace and post-conflict political transitions, which are increasingly shaped by geopolitical, security, economic, and resource interests, as well as the presence of multiple global and regional actors, rising powers such as the BRICS

(Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa)³, and expanding geopolitical interests, among others.

This study also sheds light on a ‘rising India,’ its domestic dilemmas, and its foreign policy contradictions. By exploring India’s engagement in Nepal as a case of contemporary sub-imperialism, this study offers a fresh critical perspective on India–Nepal relations (Chapter 7). At the core of this investigation is an attempt to demystify how regional and global power dynamics can transform ostensibly benign instruments, such as conflict mediation, into handy tools for perpetuating dependency, advancing sub-imperialist pursuits, fulfilling resource interests, and achieving specific foreign policy goals. In other words, the later chapters of this thesis portray a picture of an unequal relationship between two distinctly different countries co-existing in a tumultuous relationship within the contemporary Global South—a regional giant with significant military and economic ambitions, and a smaller, less powerful neighbouring country, which constantly struggles for its sovereignty and survival.

Moreover, this study enriches the mediation literature by investigating India’s involvement in Nepal’s peace process and political transition in detail and proposing a new theoretical concept of ‘peace dependency’ (Chapter 9). Peace dependency illustrates how peace mediators/facilitators’ prolonged engagement in post-conflict scenarios can sometimes undermine political stability in recipient countries and compromise their political agency and national sovereignty. Finally, although it is not the focus of this study, I have also made an attempt to compile and reflect on the lessons learnt from the Nepali peace process (Chapter 10). The purpose of this chapter is to offer practical insights and practitioners’ perspectives to enhance the practices of peacemaking and peacebuilding. After all, the fundamental goal of peace research is to help build lasting peace.

1.1 India in Nepal’s Peace Process and Political Transition

In the autumn of 2015, Nepal faced one of the most challenging periods in its modern history: the aftermath of two devastating earthquakes and a humanitarian crisis caused by India’s economic blockade. In the spring of that year, two deadly earthquakes rocked the country, which took nearly 9000 lives, ravaged thousands of homes, destroyed numerous historical sites, and caused landslides and avalanches in the Himalayas. The earthquakes left Nepal’s relatively small and weak economy in shambles. The cost of damage was estimated to be about USD 7 billion, about 30% of Nepal’s nominal Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at the time (Government of Nepal, National Planning Commission 2015).

As Nepal was still reeling from the shocks and aftershocks of the earthquakes, the country was forced to grapple with a massive man-made disaster. This time, the blow came from an economic blockade imposed by neighbouring India.⁴ India’s unofficial economic blockade—apparently imposed as a punishment for promulgating a new constitution without addressing India’s concerns and

³ In 2024, Iran, Egypt, Ethiopia, and the United Arab Emirates became full members of the BRICS bloc, followed by Indonesia in early 2025. Since 2024, the terms BRICS+ and BRICS Plus have been informally used to denote the bloc’s expanded membership. In addition, 34 more countries have applied for BRICS membership (see Seli 2024).

⁴ India officially rejected allegations of an economic blockade and pointed fingers at a group of Nepali protestors of Madhesi origin who were unsatisfied with Nepal’s new constitution. However, India’s official claim was contested by Indian media, Indian civil society, and the government of Nepal. See Chapter 6 for more on this issue.

interests—took a heavy toll on Nepal. The economy further deteriorated, and the post-earthquake rehabilitation and reconstruction work was severely affected as the blockade ‘choked imports of not only petroleum, but also medicines and earthquake relief material’ (Arora 2015b). Aid agencies began declaring Nepal a humanitarian crisis. The United Nations Children's Fund, for instance, warned that more than three million children under the age of five were at risk of death or disease due to a ‘severe shortage of fuel, food, medicines and vaccines’ (UNICEF 2015).

As the blockade continued, the anti-Indian sentiment in Nepal also peaked. Demonstrations and protests outside the Indian embassy in Kathmandu became frequent. So did chants and placards depicting phrases such as ‘Back Off India’. In unison with the furious people in the streets, even senior political leaders in Nepal started becoming vocal against India’s ‘interferences’ in Nepal (Pattison 2015, Ghimire 2015). This was rather an unusual development, for India had been credited with playing a crucial and positive role in ending the Maoist armed insurgency and facilitating Nepal's post-conflict political transition (see, for instance, Muni 2012, Jha 2012).

India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition, which practically began with the signing of the 12-Point Understanding in New Delhi in November 2005, lasted till 2017. However, the nature of this involvement has been a subject of speculation and debate in both countries. While sensationalised media portrayals and conspiracy theories have proliferated, there is still a scarcity of objective academic research on this subject. Despite numerous books and articles addressing various aspects of this issue (see Chapter 4), India's precise role and influence during these critical years remain largely shrouded in mystery. The existing literature often presents conflicting accounts, highlighting the need for more rigorous academic analysis to demystify this crucial chapter in India–Nepal relations.

The scholarship on external engagement in Nepal’s peace process and the political transition has indeed centred around India. However, while India's role in Nepal’s peace process and political transition is undeniable, the precise nature and extent of its decade-long, predominantly covert and assertive engagement remain poorly understood, and, thus, warrant further investigation. This investigation is both necessary and relevant, as much of India's influence during this period was both ‘unclear and questionable’ (Subedi & Bhattarai 2017: 95).

What is well-known, however, is India’s inconsistent and contradictory role during the Maoist armed insurgency, in which it supported and supplied both sides of the war, perfecting the art of divide and rule (Shah 2004: 223). For instance, even though India declared the Nepali Maoists a terrorist organisation, it showed little interest in curbing their activities (Bhattarai 2005: 34, Upreti 2009: 223). The Maoists received training in India from various guerrilla groups (Bhattarai 2005: 32), and senior Maoist leaders lived and operated from India throughout the armed conflict (Mishra 2004: 638).

India's contentious role during the decade-long insurgency is well-documented and extensively analysed (see, for instance, Shah 2004, Mishra 2004, Bhattarai 2005, Whelpton 2005, Whitfield 2008, Upreti 2009, Destradi 2010, Sharma 2013, Adhikari 2017, and Dhungel 2019). However, confusion persists regarding its precise role in the background negotiations leading to the 12-Point Understanding, and subsequent negotiations that took place during the peace process and political transition years. In other words, while its role in the conflict has been extensively analysed, its contribution to the resolution and its actions in the aftermath remain unclear. One of the focuses of this study is this specific area.

There is a consensus among scholars, civil society members, and politicians in both Nepal and India that India played a role in uniting the Maoist rebels with the Seven-Party Alliance (SPA) to oppose the autocratic monarchy in Nepal. Scholarly works, especially those produced during the political transition years, provide numerous examples of India's involvement in shaping Nepal's political landscape (see Upreti 2009, Sharma 2013, Adhikari 2014). However, accounts often vary and contradict regarding the nature and extent of India's role. Comprehensive academic studies that thoroughly address and explain India's involvement in Nepal during the early stages of the peace process and its aftermath are almost nonexistent. This study seeks to address this gap in the existing literature.

Though with limitations, some scholars have attempted to broadly analyse India's engagement in Nepal's peace process and political transition. Initially, scholarly interest primarily focused on analysing the origins of the conflict and predicting its potential outcomes (see Karki & Seddon 2003, Thapa & Sijapati 2004, Hutt 2004). However, with the onset of the peace process, academic attention shifted to wider issues of peacebuilding, such as constitution-making, state restructuring, inclusivity, development, and the discourse of a 'new Nepal'.

The role of international actors in the Nepali conflict has been studied both during the conflict and in the aftermath. Among others, India's role in Nepal's peace process and political transition has been described as aggressive (Adhikari 2017: 32), facilitative (Destradi 2010:17, Shrestha 2012: 211, Ghimire 2018a: 6), and one that provided tacit support (Whitfield 2008: 6). Some have also portrayed India as a coercive mediator (Poudel 2018: 7), preoccupied with its security-oriented concerns (Anderson 2014: 11) and self-interests (Bhattarai 2018). Others see India's role in Nepal as being driven by a commitment to promoting democracy in the region (Janjua 2007, H.B. Jha 2014), or simply as a means for becoming South Asia's 'benevolent hegemon' (Destradi 2012: 289).

However, as I discuss in Chapter 4, the previous literature on India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition has five notable limitations. First, much of the research conducted during and after the conflict focuses on narrow timeframes or isolated aspects of the issue. This lack of a holistic approach has led to an incomplete and fragmented understanding of the subject. Second, some lack the necessary critical perspective and simply portray India's actions as malevolent, benign, or even pro-democratic without providing detailed analysis or sufficient critical scrutiny. Third, the tendency to romanticise India's role—often presenting it as a supportive neighbour and suggesting its involvement was purely for peace, democracy, and stability—is also common. Fourth, some scholars have adopted an overtly Indo-centric view, attributing all political events in Nepal to Indian influence. This trend overlooks the stories of Nepali resistance and the agency that Nepali actors consistently exercise. Lastly, many scholars have confined themselves to narrow theoretical fields, such as international relations, overlooking valuable insights from other theoretical strands, such as peace and conflict studies, mediation studies, global development studies⁵, and South–South relations. Theoretical narrowness is not inherently problematic, but it does not necessarily capture or convey the full complexity of an issue as vast as India–Nepal relations. This research addresses these limitations by adopting a more comprehensive, critical, and interdisciplinary approach.

⁵ Some of the issues that I discuss in later chapters, such as natural resource expropriation, micromanagement, sub-imperialism, and peace dependency, can also be considered to be part of global development studies.

1.2 Mediators' Might: Conflict Mediation as a Foreign Policy Tool

This study examines Nepal's peace process and post-conflict political transition primarily from a peace and mediation research perspective. Studying mediation as a foreign policy tool provides valuable insights into how states tackle and make use of complex international conflicts and leverage them to advance their strategic interests. While traditional views of mediation often emphasise neutral third parties, examining it through a foreign policy lens reveals how states use mediation as a strategic tool to exert influence and advance specific foreign policy objectives (see Touval 1992, 2003; Bercovitch 2011, Butler 2018). This perspective is critical, given the uneven pattern of conflict mediation globally, because some conflicts receive excessive mediation attention while others are neglected and allowed to escalate (Greig & Diehl 2012; Svensson & Onken 2015: 69–70). This indicates how mediation efforts can be driven by foreign policy calculations rather than purely by an authentic concern for peace.

As I discuss in Chapter 3, 'power mediators' often use mediation as a foreign policy instrument (Harris & Reilly 1998, Svensson 2007: 230). Regional powers, such as India in this context, can employ 'power mediation' strategies and exercise various tactics, such as incentives and punishments, and pressure conflicting parties to accept a compromise (Harris & Reilly 1998). Power mediators leverage their power and resources to influence outcomes. They can use conflict management, mediation, and diplomacy as soft power strategies (Kurlantzick 2007, Nye 2009). Other soft-power strategies, such as rhetoric, persuasion, and agenda setting, can also be used (Rothman 2011: 50). When soft-power strategies fail to yield the desired outcomes, states often resort to more forceful approaches, such as coercive diplomacy (Keohane & Nye 1989, Jakobsen 2016).

Mediation, when used as an extension of a state's broader foreign policy objectives, diverges from its idealised principles. Analysing mediation and conflict resolution in this foreign policy context, as this study has done, is essential for understanding contemporary mediation and peacemaking efforts and making sense of the complex interplay between conflict resolution and geopolitical manoeuvring.

While the mediation literature forms the core of this study, the theoretical exploration goes beyond it. Given the complex research context and the multifaceted nature of the questions, I adopt a three-pillar theoretical framework (Chapter 3). As previously mentioned, this framework integrates insights from mediation literature and various other theoretical strands, including critical international relations and global development studies. The diversity of theoretical perspectives is essential, as no single theory fully captures the complexity of the research questions. This study thus serves as an example of theoretical experimentation, too. Instead of restricting the analysis to a narrow field of international relations or mediation studies, it ventures into different theoretical domains, exploring linkages and possibilities. For instance, South–South Cooperation as a theoretical lens has rarely been used to examine peace processes in the contemporary Global South, a task undertaken in this study.

1.3 Evaluating an Unpredictable Rise of Rising Powers

The global power balance is undergoing a significant shift, primarily driven by the emergence of new economic powers from the Global South (see, for instance, Schwarzer 2017, Denisov et al. 2019, Grix et al. 2019). Initially, the rise of non-

Western powers, such as the BRICS bloc—originally comprising Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa— inspired hope and was even referred to as the beginning of ‘the rise of the rest’ (Zakaria 2013). Over time, however, the so-called rise of the emerging powers has become increasingly unpredictable, raising a sense of suspicion and uncertainty.

Historically, the formation of the Group of 77 (G77) in 1964 had its roots in the aspirations of developing countries to challenge the prevailing Western-dominated global economic order⁶ and to establish a more equitable international system (Geldart & Lyon 1980). At its inception, G77 countries collectively envisioned a New International Economic Order. This was intended to address historical inequalities between the West and ‘the rest’, reform global trade and financial systems, and promote economic development in the Global South. The G77 was also expected to reform international institutions and challenge Western hegemony through various means, including advocating for fair trade practices, technology transfer, debt relief, and increased development assistance. Guided by principles of solidarity, collective self-reliance, and effective South–South Cooperation, the G77 was supposed to reshape global economic governance and ultimately create a multipolar world order.

Although the G77 did not achieve the level of progress that was anticipated during its early years, the 21st century has nonetheless witnessed a profound shift in the global landscape. This shift has particularly involved the economic and political rise of a handful of non-Western countries, such as China, India, Brazil, and South Africa. Once firmly positioned within the developing world, these countries have now emerged as significant global economic and political powers. However, whether these countries have upheld the G77’s collective cause and the spirit of South–South solidarity is questionable. Concerns that these countries have evolved into new forms of economic and political dominance, resembling the very systems they once sought to challenge, warrant careful examination.

Principles, practices, and the increasing rhetorical use of South–South Cooperation (SSC) also require re-evaluation. Proponents who view SSC as an emancipatory agenda (see Mawdsley 2012, Carmody 2013, Cheru 2016, Muhr 2016, Bergamaschi et al. 2017) are increasingly overshadowed by critics who argue that the SSC rhetoric adopted by rising powers in the Global South is merely symbolic, aimed at securing a stronger position within the US-centred world order (see Vanaik 2013, Bond & Garcia 2015, Bond et al. 2021). Furthermore, rising powers’ sub-imperialist tendencies also demand serious scrutiny (see Çağlı 2009, Bond 2015, Valencia 2017, Bond et al. 2021).

In recent years, the study of rising power behaviour has emerged as a distinct field of inquiry. This is mainly driven by the rapid political and economic rise of a few Global South countries. The focus of this study, India, for instance, is no longer the poor developing country it used to be. It is an economic powerhouse, an assertive regional force, and a leading member of the BRICS grouping. With its robust and consistent economic growth, expanding regional influence, and increasing global ambitions, contemporary India embodies many of the complexities and contradictions associated with rising powers. Analysing India’s

⁶ While developing countries’ broader political agenda was primarily guided by the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM), the G77 and the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development drove their economic agenda (Alden et al. 2010).

foreign policy behaviour and strategies provides a unique perspective on the behaviour of rising powers. Therefore, in this study, India is examined not only as Nepal's powerful neighbour, but also as a rising power and a key player in regional and global affairs. India is a compelling case that embodies the complexities and unpredictability of rising powers. By focusing on India, this research aims to enhance the understanding of rising power behaviour, highlighting the factors that influence contemporary India's actions and their implications for the changing global order.

1.4 Research Questions, Aims, and Objectives

This study revolves around India's engagement in Nepal's peace process and post-conflict political transition (2005–2017). In other words, the study aims to demystify India's role—both as a regional power and as an unofficial peace mediator/facilitator in Nepal—at the beginning of the peace process and in the aftermath. The primary aim is to offer a new perspective on India's engagement in Nepal's peace process and political transition and re-evaluate contemporary India–Nepal relations.

This re-evaluation of India–Nepal relations is critical because the relationship between the two countries has taken tumultuous turns over the last two decades (Dahal 2018, Aryal & Pulami 2024). Domestic political upheavals in both countries, China's growing influence, and a gradual change in regional and global power dynamics have all contributed to shaping and shifting the 'special' relationship between India and Nepal.

Therefore, the main research question addressed in this thesis is:

What role did India play in Nepal's peace process and political transition from 2005 to 2017? Moreover, what does India's involvement reveal about contemporary Indo–Nepal relations and the shifting global order?

To address the primary research question, it is essential to resolve the sub-questions outlined in each analysis chapter of this thesis. These sub-questions, which align with the main research question, are as follows:

1. What role did India play in the formation of the Maoist-SPA 12-Point Understanding, and how did that shape Nepal's peace process and political transition? (Chapter 5)
2. How did India engage with post-conflict Nepal, and what strategies did it employ to shape the peace and political transition processes? (Chapter 6)
3. What strategic interests drive India's engagement in Nepal, and how do these interests reflect broader geopolitical patterns? (Chapter 7)
4. What is the nature of India's engagement in contemporary Nepal, and what are its ultimate objectives? (Chapter 8)
5. What does India's engagement in Nepal's peace process and political transition reveal about long-term external engagement in post-mediation and post-conflict contexts? (Chapter 9)

6. What key lessons can be learnt from Nepal's peace process and political transition? (Chapter 10)

To address these research questions, the analysis is structured into three layers. The first layer explores India's engagement in Nepal before the 2006 peace deal, specifically between 2005 and early 2006. The second layer examines India's role during the peace deal period in 2006. Finally, the third layer focuses on the post-peace-deal years, covering Nepal's political transition from 2006 to 2017, the year of the first post-transition parliamentary elections.

This study has a few objectives in line with the research questions presented above. In addition to clearly defined research questions, having a set of research objectives is crucial, as they guide the research design, influence sample size calculations, and shape the overall scope and structure of the study (Hanson 2006, Farrugia et al. 2010).

Thus, the main objectives of this study are:

- To assess the extent of India's engagement in Nepal's peace process and post-conflict political transition (2005–2017), analyse its underlying motives, and offer a fresh perspective on contemporary India–Nepal relations.

- To illustrate how peace mediation, facilitation practices, and the management of political transitions vary across different contexts and are shaped by historical factors, economic interests, and geopolitical motives.

- To provide a clearer understanding of rising power behaviour, their strategic actions, influences, and interactions within their geopolitical domains.

1.5 Key Concepts and Definitions

In this thesis, I use a variety of terms and key concepts related to the topic of investigation and the study's theoretical framework. Concepts such as peace mediation, peace process, third-party intervention, and conflict/peace negotiation are extensively used. Furthermore, key terms related to the theoretical concepts discussed in the study, including dependency, sub-imperialism, and South–South Cooperation, are frequently mentioned. Some of these concepts are discussed in detail in the theoretical framework chapter (Chapter 3). The concepts included here are the most recurring and relevant ones that are not separately covered in that chapter. Beyond the key concepts discussed here, other relevant terms appear throughout the thesis, with their contextual meanings explained within the respective chapters.

Peace Process

The term *peace process* is widely used in peace and mediation research, with scholars offering various definitions and interpretations. For instance, Saunders (2001: 483) describes it as 'a political process in which conflicts are resolved by peaceful means.' His notion of a peace process includes a 'mixture of politics, diplomacy, changing relationships, negotiation, mediation and dialogue in both official and unofficial arenas'. Tonge (2014) emphasises the need to look beyond mere ceasefires and the absence of war. Under the umbrella of a peace process, he

integrates broader aspects such as post-conflict reconstruction and truth and reconciliation efforts. Ball (2001: 721–722) presents a two-phased understanding of a peace process, beginning with negotiation and the cessation of hostilities, followed by an expanded focus on consolidated peacebuilding.

In short, a peace process is an intricate dance of steps that usually starts with confidence-building measures and progresses through designing new political institutions—ultimately exchanging war for peace (Sisk 2001: 787). For this study, I adopted a broader perspective on the peace process—one that extends beyond mediation and the signing of peace agreements. It includes sustained, long-term peacebuilding efforts and the pursuit of a more just and equitable society. As Ball (2001) suggests, these efforts and aspirations usually include pre-agreement and post-agreement steps.

However, every peace process is unique and often shaped by a complex interplay of political, social, and economic realities on the ground. A successful peace process must also involve a comprehensive political and constitutional framework. As Darby and MacGinty (2000: 8) argue, the absence of such a framework leaves any peace process fundamentally incomplete.

Nepali Peace Process and Political Transition (2005–2017)

Nepal's peace process began in 2005 with extensive mediation and negotiation attempts. While it largely concluded by 2017, issues surrounding transitional justice continue to remain in limbo. Key milestones include the signing of the CPA in 2006, the completion of an army integration process in 2013, the elections for two Constituent Assemblies in 2008 and 2013, the promulgation of a new constitution in 2015, and the successful completion of the first post-war parliamentary elections in 2017.

I use the term *Nepali peace process*, or simply *the peace process*, to collectively refer to the resolution of the Maoist armed insurgency and the associated political events and processes that predominantly took place between 2005 and 2017. As noted above, during this period, the Maoist armed insurgency in Nepal reached a negotiated settlement, effectively ending a long period of political instability, internal conflict, and over a decade of social unrest.

Nepal's peace process remains a work in progress for many, as issues of transitional justice and truth and reconciliation remain unresolved (see Chapter 10). While post-conflict governments have struggled to address these challenges effectively, they remain on the peace process agenda and have not been entirely sidelined. Nearly all key informants I interviewed for this study expressed that, aside from a few unresolved concerns like transitional justice, the peace process is essentially complete and was considered broadly successful.

Conflict / Peace Mediation & Negotiation

In this study, I explore mediation and negotiation within the context of armed conflict and its resolution. In Chapter 3, I provide an overview of mediation and negotiation practices and discuss a variety of theoretical concepts related to these processes. The practice of mediation dates back as far as the conflict itself. Mediation is widely used as a conflict resolution tool across various domains, not just in political contexts. Mediation is used to settle business conflicts, heal sour family relations, address labour issues, and resolve political tussles. In an armed conflict context, mediation is 'a mode of negotiation in which a third party helps the parties find a solution that they cannot find by themselves' (Zartman & Touval 2007: 438). In Fisher's (2001: 4) words, mediation is 'essentially a pacific, non-

coercive and non-binding approach to conflict management’.

Mediation, in the simplest terms, is an activity or a set of activities initiated by a third party to resolve an ongoing conflict or a dispute. However, the third party in question is expected to use ‘persuasion rather than coercion’ and should aim to find ‘a solution acceptable to the (primary) parties’ (Wallensteen & Svensson 2014: 316). Thus, a constellation of activities fits under the umbrella of mediation. Such activities might include—but are not limited to—rapport building, contact and communication, conflict analysis, dialogue, facilitation, and so forth.

Peace negotiation is an act of dialogue or bargaining that disputing parties undertake at the negotiating table. Pfetsch (2007: 9) defines negotiation as ‘a social process in which two or more parties interact in the search for an acceptable position with regard to their differences and concerning the same issue of conflict’.

Though closely related, mediation and negotiation are different. Third-party actors might play a valuable and decisive role in mediation. In contrast, disputants or conflicting parties sit at the negotiating table and attempt to find a mutually acceptable solution to their differences. However, this does not mean that mediators are absent from the negotiating table. Negotiation is an interaction process in which disputants ‘try to meet their needs or accomplish their goals by reaching an agreement with others who are trying to get their own needs met’ (Mayer 2000: 142).

In the context of this study, peace negotiation refers to the activities that take place at the negotiation table. Meanwhile, mediation per se happens all along the line—to bring the conflicting parties to the negotiating table, persuade them to engage in dialogue faithfully, and help them find a mutually acceptable solution. Mediation work itself is pivotal in setting up a conducive environment. However, it is during a negotiation that the act of ‘give and take’ occurs (Lewicki et al. 1999: 8).

Third-Party Intervention and Third-Party Actors

In its simplest form, intervention can be understood as an action or a set of actions taken under certain circumstances with a definite purpose or an anticipated outcome. In the context of this study, in particular, and in peace and conflict studies, in general, ‘intervention’ signifies a range of diplomatic, military, economic, and humanitarian methods that external parties employ or exercise in an armed conflict or post-conflict scenario. ‘Third-party’ refers to entities that are not involved in the dispute. These parties may include domestic and foreign entities, such as mediators, foreign governments and militaries, international organisations, diplomats, and more.

Starkey et al. (2005: 36) define third-party intervention as introducing an external party into a negotiation when it is apparent that progress cannot be achieved without some form of outside involvement. Third-party interventions have been broadly categorised into two: coercive and non-coercive.⁷ Coercive interventions often include military threats and/or limited force, whereas non-coercive or diplomatic measures might include persuasion, rewards, and assurances (Jakobsen 2016). However, some interventions may be considered to be ‘hybrid,’ often combining military or coercive measures with non-coercive or diplomatic approaches (Mac Ginty 2011, Mac Ginty & Richmond 2016).

Third-party involvement in conflicts can be complicated and problematic for

⁷ For an elaborate analysis of coercive interventions and diplomacy, see Chapter 3 and, for instance, George (1991).

various reasons, such as geographic proximity and vested interests, which increase the likelihood of postwar involvement (Chen & Beardsley 2021). Even though some scholars argue that third parties do not often intervene to exacerbate or prolong conflict (see Regan 1996: 340), the interests and actions of those intervening can significantly affect peace processes and postwar outcomes.

Recent trends show that there has been a decline in multilateral third-party engagements and a rise in more isolated interventions by powerful states (Badanjak 2023). The dual role of some actors, such as Russia's position as both a conflict party and mediator in post-Soviet conflicts, and the involvement of private military companies, like the Wagner Group sponsored by Russia, adds to the complexity (Badanjak 2023). Interstate factors also contribute to the expansion of conflict through third-party interventions (Bremer 1992), and major powers tend to drag one another into ongoing conflicts (Corbetta & Dixon 2005).

In this study, third-party intervention refers primarily to India's involvement and actions in Nepal during the Maoist armed insurgency, the peace process, and the subsequent political transition. However, whenever relevant, I also touch upon interventions of other third-party actors, such as the United States (US), the European Union (EU), the United Nations (UN), China, and other international actors, such as international non-governmental organisations (INGOs).

Global South

In the field of international development, 'Global South' is a term used to refer to low and middle-income countries located in Africa, Latin America, Asia, the Caribbean, and Oceania. The term was coined in 1969 by Carl Oglesby, an American writer and activist, in a special issue of the Catholic journal *Commonweal* that focused on the Vietnam War. Oglesby argued that centuries of dominance from the Global North over the Global South had created an unbearable social order (see Oglesby 1969: 90). The term has a political connotation and does not necessarily refer to the geographical south (Hollington et al. 2015). Over time, it has emerged as an alternative to phrases such as 'third world', 'developing countries', or 'underdeveloped countries' (Satterthwaite & Mitlin 2012: 13–14).

Historically, the term Global South is linked to anti-colonial movements and conceptually, it denotes solidarity among postcolonial and developing countries. It is also linked to the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM), the Group of 77 (G77), and their advocacy for economic self-determination. Moreover, it is connected to the agenda of the New International Economic Order, which aimed to reform global economic structures but ultimately faltered due to neoliberal resistance (Hogan & Patrick 2024).

While the term Global South is useful in portraying shared histories of colonisation and exploitation, it has been criticised for being patronising and reductive. Some criticism has, in fact, focused on its colonial connotation and the historical baggage it carries (Díaz Gras 2024). Eriksen (2015), for instance, highlights its fundamental vagueness as a blanket term, while Patrick & Huggins (2023) argue that it problematically homogenises diverse nations with vastly different economic, political, and cultural circumstances. For instance, the two countries examined in this study, India and Nepal, both belonging to the Global South, differ significantly in terms of size, economic capacity, power projection, and their national aspirations. Moreover, the grouping of countries as disparate as Malaysia, Zambia, Uruguay, and Nigeria under a single label risks perpetuating oversimplified narratives and obscuring crucial distinctions in wealth, governance systems, and geopolitical alignments (Patrick & Huggins 2023). This

oversimplification can mask the unique challenges, opportunities, and strategic interests specific to each nation.

In addition, critics have noted that the term 'Global South' often serves the interests of elite classes within Global South nations, who frequently exploit South–South economic and political relationships to further their own agendas rather than advancing the collective interests of the broader population (Wolvers et al. 2015). As is evident in my analysis in the latter chapters, this seems to be increasingly the case. This raises questions about the term's utility and even legitimacy.

While acknowledging its limitations, I use the term 'Global South' in this thesis as a collective reference. Despite the limitations, this term reflects a historical context and shared experiences of developing countries, not just those of today, but dating back to the time of the Bandung Conference (1955) and the NAM era. While this term is used for its historical and contextual relevance, I also critically examine the divisions and dichotomies in the contemporary Global South, and how a handful of powerful countries, such as India and China, have increasingly misappropriated the term, often positioning themselves as the sole leaders or representatives of the Global South, or the developing world.

South–South Cooperation/South–South Relations

South–South Cooperation (SSC) involves two or more developing countries engaging in bilateral or regional cooperation (Ugwuja et al. 2014). Such cooperation can be diverse (Rosseel et al. 2009). The terms 'Global South' and 'South–South Cooperation' have a shared history. The term 'Global South' emerged in part to help developing nations collaborate on various political, economic, social, environmental, cultural, and technical issues. This collaboration gradually began to be known as South–South Cooperation (SSC). With SSC, developing countries aimed to support each other in their social, political, and economic development efforts. In addition, they wished to reshape the global system to reflect their interests better, rather than just those of the Global North. In other words, with SSC, they sought to achieve global economic changes that were mutually beneficial for countries in the Global South and foster greater solidarity among disadvantaged nations worldwide (Gray & Gills 2016).

The terms 'South–South Cooperation' and 'South–South relations' have often been used interchangeably as similar concepts, but their connotations differ. The term 'South–South Cooperation' highlights and emphasises the collaborative efforts among developing countries, whereas 'South–South relations' carries a more formal tone associated with international relations. Chapter 3 offers a comprehensive theoretical analysis of South–South Cooperation and discusses its gradual evolution and complexities inherent in the practice.

Micromanagement

Another key term frequently used in this thesis is 'micromanagement'. The Merriam-Webster Dictionary (2024) defines micromanagement as 'to manage especially with excessive control or attention to details.' Chambers (2009) argues that micromanagement could include a bullying approach in the level of control and influence. Micromanagers might resort to micromanagement deliberately and for strategic reasons, often taking credit for positive results and shifting the blame for negative results to others (Thomas 2010).

Micromanagement, as a concept, has been used only sparingly in foreign policy, diplomacy, mediation, and peace research literature. Nonetheless, in international politics, micromanagement refers to a situation where a country or an international

organisation excessively controls or influences the internal affairs of another country or organisation. This could manifest in various ways, such as imposing strict conditions on foreign aid, closely monitoring and controlling the decision-making processes of another country's government, or intervening in the internal conflicts of another country. As I discuss in Chapter 6, when used in the context of foreign policy practice, micromanagement—as a form of interference in the internal affairs of another country—can undermine sovereignty and limit the ability of political actors to make their own decisions.

In this thesis, I apply the term 'micromanagement' within the context of foreign policy. Following the signing of the Comprehensive Peace Accord between the Maoists and the Government of Nepal in 2006, 'micromanagement' emerged as a significant buzzword in Nepal. The term frequently appeared in the media stories and opinion pieces used as data in this study and was also widely referenced by the key informants during interviews. For this thesis, 'micromanagement' refers specifically to India's intricate and manipulative interventions in Nepal during the peace process and the subsequent political transition.

While the lexicon of international relations frequently employs terms like power diplomacy, coercive diplomacy, and the combination of soft and hard power to characterise the involvement of stronger nations in the affairs of weaker ones, the act of micromanagement can be a deliberate tool used, often with other similar tactics, to achieve larger strategic goals.

1.6 Thesis Structure

This thesis consists of eleven chapters. **Chapter 1** presents the research questions, aims, and objectives, while also briefly introducing and defining key concepts used throughout the thesis. Additionally, this chapter highlights the research gap and outlines the structure of the thesis.

Chapter 2 connects methods to theory and data, and justifies the methodological approaches adopted in the study. It outlines the study's ontological and epistemological foundations and lays out the research design. The methods used, the data accumulation process, and issues related to validity, reliability, research ethics, and researcher positionality are thoroughly discussed. The chapter explains the methodological choices and how they align with the research objectives and the theoretical framework of the study.

Chapter 3 outlines a detailed theoretical framework for the study. It begins with an introduction to a triangular theoretical framework and includes a critique and evaluation of the three main theoretical strands used in the study. The theoretical domains covered in the chapter are: 1. Conflict mediation and third-party engagement, 2. South–South Cooperation (rising powers, sub-imperialism), and 3. Dependency and World-systems approaches. As previously stated, including a different set of theoretical perspectives is essential for a study of this type, because contemporary peace processes and political transitions are inherently complex. They should be studied not in isolation, but in relation to global and regional power relations, as well as the broader political, societal, and economic realities of our time.

Chapter 4 reviews the existing literature and provides a detailed background of the research context. It begins with a section on the history of modern Nepal and discusses how India's presence has always been felt in Nepal. It discusses the human and economic costs of the Maoist armed conflict, as well as the radical paradigm shift it prompted in the Nepali political landscape. Important details

concerning pre-2005 mediation and negotiation attempts, and the role of international involvement, are provided. Finally, a review of the previous literature gives insight into scholarly work on the Nepali peace process, the political transition, and India–Nepal relations during and after the Maoist armed insurgency. This section also identifies gaps in the existing literature and justifies the need for this study.

Chapter 5 explores the genesis of the Nepali peace process by elaborating on the circumstances that led to the signing of the 12-Point Understanding between the Maoists and the SPA in New Delhi in November 2005. The pact between the two opposition factions was instrumental in ending both the armed conflict and King Gyanendra’s direct rule in Nepal. The 12-Point roadmap ultimately ended Nepal’s 240-year-old monarchy, and Nepal became a federal democratic republic. My focus in this chapter is to locate and analyse India’s role—as an unofficial mediator and facilitator—in forging the 12-Point Understanding and in orchestrating subsequent political events in Nepal. The chapter highlights the Six-Point Agreement, signed in October 2005 in Nepal’s Rolpa District, which laid the groundwork for a coalition between the Maoists and the SPA, ultimately leading to the 12-Point Understanding.

Chapter 6 details India’s extensive and prolonged engagement in Nepal during the post-conflict and political transition years. It shows that during Nepal’s political transition, India intervened extensively, using both soft and hard power to control Nepal’s political, bureaucratic, and security institutions. In the later years, India faced significant opposition from Nepal against its hard power tactics, such as coercive diplomacy and an economic blockade. India’s efforts to mould Nepal’s 2015 constitution in its favour and to reinstate Nepal’s identity as a Hindu nation also failed.

In **Chapter 7**, India’s motives behind its intensified engagement in Nepal’s peace process and political transition are thoroughly analysed. In this chapter, I argue that India’s involvement in Nepal’s peace process and political transition was neither sudden nor an isolated event. Rather, it was an ‘inflamed’ episode in the long and complex relationship between the two countries. As a dominant player in this relationship—often marked by periods of cooperation and co-dependency as well as coercion and conflict—India’s undeclared Nepal policy since the 1950s has been to reduce it into a meek and pliable client state. After discussing India’s geopolitical, security, economic, and resource interests in Nepal, I argue that India’s actions in Nepal were mainly aimed at turning Nepal into one of its sub-imperialist destinations. This allowed India to gain control over its natural resources—especially water—and to perpetuate a world system based on neoliberal capitalism and various forms of aggression.

In **Chapter 8**, I examine India’s sub-imperialism in Nepal and the mindset inherent in the so-called ‘rising India’. The chapter explains how India has historically exerted control over Nepali politics, domestic markets, and natural resources, mainly to further its own interests. While India has entangled Nepal in a web of dependencies, its relationships with Western powers and global financial institutions also display similar dependency patterns, essentially reinforcing its sub-imperialist position. This chapter also explores how India’s sub-imperialism in South Asia is intertwined with its internal colonial practices at home—a strategy that has served well to the growth of Hindu-nationalist Hindutva political ideology and an unabated proliferation of extractivist corporate capitalism. The chapter concludes with a discussion of the rising power dilemma. I argue that, contrary to initial hopes, the economic and political rise of some countries in the Global South

has not challenged Western hegemony. Instead, these rising powers, such as India, have increasingly adopted extractivist and oppressive foreign policies and have contributed to the maintenance of neoliberal regimes. This undermines the hopes for inclusive and empowering South–South relations and the goals of creating a New International Economic Order. However, grassroots movements focused on anti-imperialist and anti-hegemonic resistance provide a glimmer of hope for smaller and less powerful developing countries like Nepal.

In **Chapter 9**, the thesis revisits the peace and conflict research domain, in which the consequences of India’s post-conflict engagements in Nepal are analysed. By using several examples, I demonstrate that India’s influence and Nepal’s dependency on India significantly increased in the post-conflict context. By capitalising on the mediator narrative—that it had initiated the Nepali peace process by facilitating the 12-Point Understanding—India consolidated its influence in post-conflict Nepal. Gradually, the Indian embassy in Kathmandu and India’s intelligence operatives gained significant leverage in shaping Nepal’s post-conflict political landscape. As a result, Nepal found itself in a state of ‘peace dependency’, with its political actors increasingly relying on India to resolve post-conflict crises and maintain internal stability. The concept of ‘peace dependency’ adds to mediation literature by providing a useful perspective for understanding and assessing the complexities of post-conflict environments.

Chapter 10 critiques the Nepali peace process and outlines a few valuable lessons. Since most of the key informants interviewed for this study were directly involved in the peace process and post-conflict political transition, the practitioners’ insights will be helpful for peace workers, mediators, and negotiators involved in resolving future conflicts in Nepal and elsewhere. The main takeaway of this chapter is that Nepal’s peace process achieved significant technical and political milestones—including a cessation of hostilities agreement, a comprehensive peace agreement, completion of a Disarmament, Demobilisation and Reintegration (DDR) process, state restructuring, and a new constitution. However, even after nearly two decades after the CPA, the absence of a functioning transitional justice framework and unresolved socio-economic transformation issues continue to cripple the peace process, and leave Nepal vulnerable to further social unrest and future conflicts.

Finally, in **Chapter 11**, I offer an executive summary of the main findings and make a few concluding remarks. The final section of this chapter offers recommendations for future research. These recommendations might be useful for researchers in peace and conflict studies, mediation studies, South–South relations, dependency, and international relations.

2. Research Methodology and Methods

In this chapter, I discuss the methodological standpoints adopted in this study. I begin by describing the ontological and epistemological underpinnings I have chosen and then proceed to explain the methodical choices I have made. I also describe the data accumulation process and address validity, reliability, research ethics, and researcher positionality issues. Issues concerning translation and data accumulation from the Internet are also discussed.

Any academic research demands that the research methods used are sound, relevant, and methodologically rigorous. At the same time, they need to correspond to the research questions being investigated. In that sense, selecting the right research methods is important for any research. However, for a study of this type, which deals with as complex an issue as India's engagement in Nepal, arming oneself with the right research methods is even more important.

This study is qualitative, and its methodological foundation is built on qualitative tools. Epistemological and methodological foundations typically guide a researcher's choice of methods, and that is what I will do here. In addition, a researcher selects methods that help him or her find answers to research questions, and that very conviction guided my choice of particular research methods.

Whether qualitative methods are suitable for this type of research is a point worth considering. Snape & Spencer (2003: 5) present qualitative research as a 'blend of empirical investigation and creative discovery' and argue that 'qualitative methods are used to address research questions that require explanation or understanding of social phenomena and their contexts'. In addition, they argue that qualitative research is particularly suitable for 'exploring issues that hold some complexity and to studying processes that occur over time'. This explanation is relevant in this study, as it explores an issue that does hold some complexity and focuses on events and processes that occur over time (i.e., mostly between 2005 and 2017). Similarly, Sofaer (1999: 1101) argues that qualitative research methods are best suited to providing 'rich descriptions of complex phenomena' and 'illuminating the experience and interpretation of events by actors with widely differing stakes and roles.' This, too, is the case with this study.

From a methodological point of view, qualitative research 'involves an interpretive' and 'naturalistic approach to the world' (Denzin & Lincoln 2000: 3). In practice, this means that qualitative researchers 'study things in their natural settings, attempting to make sense of, or to interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them' (Denzin & Lincoln 2000: 3). Qualitative methods are particularly suited for capturing the complexity of social phenomena and providing in-depth insights into processes such as conflict resolution, diplomatic interactions, and relations between different actors. Though quantitative research methods are common in data-driven studies in peace and global development research, qualitative research methods are also equally robust and widely utilised. Qualitative research methods—such as interviews, observation, and case studies—

have been extensively used in both peace and international relations research,⁸ as well as in global development research.⁹

Before providing a detailed description of the research methods used in this study, it is helpful to examine the research paradigm adopted. A research paradigm consists of ontology, epistemology, methodology and methods. Ontology 'relates to being, to what is, to what exists' (Hay 2002: 61), or it is a 'vision of the world as it really is' (Gerring 2007: 53). While ontology is about reality, epistemology is about the ways of knowing that reality (Guba 1990). In Hay's (2002: 62) words, epistemology 'is the science or philosophy of knowledge'. Similarly, Schwandt (2001: 71) defines epistemology as 'the study of the nature of knowledge and justification'.

Epistemology is instrumental in guiding methodological choices and is moulded by 'research objectives, questions, and study design' (Carter & Little 2007: 1). On the other hand, a methodology is 'a theory and analysis of how research should proceed' (Harding 1987: 2). In that sense, a methodology is a justification and explanation for methods, and not a method itself (Kaplan 1964: 18). Methods are tools and techniques for gathering data and evidence (Harding 1987: 2) as well as their analysis.

This study adopts a critical realist approach as its philosophical and epistemological vantage point. Critical realism, initially developed by the Indo-British social scientist and philosopher Roy Bhaskar¹⁰ in the 1970s, provides a strong philosophical grounding for science, and offers a credible alternative to positivist and interpretive/constructionist approaches (Alvesson & Sköldbberg 2017: 39–40).

Understanding critical realism and its relevance in today's complex social world is easier when it is compared to its alternatives: positivism and social constructionism. While positivism is more or less fixated on the empirical analysis of objective phenomena and demonstrating causal relations between different variables, constructionism focuses on the subjective interpretation of reality. Constructivist approaches emphasise that 'knowledge and reality do not have an objective or absolute value or, at the least, that we have no way of knowing this reality' (Murphy 1997: 5). Their focus, thereby, is on inventing or creating the properties of the world, rather than discovering them (Kukla 2000). While constructionism can be useful in revealing insights into how people interact with the world (Creswell 2009), some might consider its fixation on subjective human interpretation of the world as a limitation.

Critical realism argues that 'there is a real world out there' (Joseph 2014: 1) and that 'reality exists independently from researchers' ideas and descriptions of it' (Alvesson & Sköldbberg 2017: 41) or from 'people's perceptions, language, or imagination' (O' Mahoney & Vincent 2014: 2–3). Like positivists, critical realists

⁸ See, for instance, Wiener (2009), Klotz & Prakash (2008) for qualitative research in IR, and Millar (2018), Höglund & Oberg (2011) for a broader understanding of the use of qualitative research methods in peace research.

⁹ See, for instance, Skovdal & Cornish (2015) for how qualitative research methods have practical implications for international development research and practice, and Morrow & Crivello (2015) for an elaborate understanding of how qualitative longitudinal research offers significant insight into issues related to international development. In addition, detailed country case studies by Colletta et al. (1996) in Ethiopia, Namibia, and Uganda offer a comprehensive picture of the intricate nature of political, economic, and sociocultural issues in countries transitioning from war to peace.

¹⁰ Though initially proposed by Bhaskar, critical realism has evolved as a collective enterprise of various scholars, including Margaret Archer, Mervyn Hartwig, Alan Norrie, and Tony Lawson. While some argue that the Marxist notion of science heavily influences critical realism, others reject its alleged affinity with Marxism.

also attempt to seek causal explanations, but their emphasis is not necessarily on showing predictable patterns or establishing causal links. In critical realism, 'relations are complex and causality can exist on different levels' (O' Mahoney & Vincent 2014: 42). Elaborating on the critical realist view of reality, Danermark et al. (2002: 26) argue that 'reality exists and is what it is'. However, they emphasise that 'the kind of knowledge that is produced depends on what problems we have and what questions we ask in relation to the world around us'.

Bhaskar (1975: 56) advocated for a stratified ontology, in which reality consisted of complex, overlapping layers. He used three domains to clarify the notion of reality: the empirical, the actual, and the real. The *empirical* encompasses elements that can be observed or activities that take place in our immediate experience. The *actual* is rather broader, something that takes place independently of the observer, and the *real* encompasses mechanisms that are productive of different events and other 'surface phenomena' (Alvesson & Sköldbörg 2017: 40).

For critical realists, the aim of scientific or scholarly work is 'to investigate and identify relationships and non-relationships, respectively, between what we experience, what actually happens, and the underlying mechanisms that produce the events in the world' (Danermark et al., 2002: 21). The realist notion thereby absolves researchers from what critical realists call the 'epistemological fallacy', a situation in which the real world is reduced to the knowledge we have of it, a notion dearly cherished in the positivist and constructivist traditions (Joseph 2014: 2). However, critical realists advocate for a broader understanding of the real, something that goes beyond mere objects and objectification, and encompasses other seemingly abstract elements, too. As Alvesson & Sköldbörg (2017: 41) put it:

The real is central to critical realism. There is a strong conviction regarding the real and the possibility of identifying it. Something is real if it has a causal effect, that is, if it affects behaviour and makes a difference. Reality does not just consist of material objects. Ideas and discourses are real and can have causal effects.

Critical realists argue that causal processes are present not only in the natural world but also in the social world. Because of that, an attempt must be made to identify causal explanations in interactions and interplays in different social processes (Elder-Vass 2012: 10). Critical realism thereby embeds elements of positivism, such as the interest in the 'objective world, patterns, generalization and finding causalities' (Alvesson & Sköldbörg 2017: 40). However, critical realists do not limit themselves to what is observable and measurable, but attempt to go deeper, to analyse complex and 'invisible' dimensions. In essence, critical realists argue against the practice of reducing a complex world to mere observable objects and facts. While accepting some tenets of objectivism/positivism, they strive to unearth underlying structures that engender various outcomes, including causal events.

There is a growing need for social scientists to incorporate both realist and social constructionist approaches to analyse today's complex political and social processes. This can be done successfully within the domain of critical realism. If necessary, the combination of the two could also be termed 'realist social constructionism' (Elder-Vass 2013).

Against this backdrop, this study takes a critical realist approach to explore India's engagement in Nepal's peace process and political transition, primarily between 2005 and 2017. The critical realist approach is particularly suitable in a case study such as this one because what I explore and analyse in this study expands beyond mere subjective interpretation. As documented in later chapters, the period

I covered marks the end of an armed insurgency in Nepal that claimed more than 17,000 lives. Although the pains from that time are fading, they can still be felt today. The country also experienced various other disruptive events, including a massive people's movement, the end of a 240-year-old monarchy, the establishment of a new state structure, two devastating earthquakes, and an economic blockade by India, which led to a humanitarian crisis.

Even though the expressions and interpretations of these fateful events might vary, the experiences of nuisance and loss, struggle and victory, and conflict and suffering are real. They each have their own ontological position, existence, and meaning. So do mass movements, treaties, agreements, ideologically motivated armed struggles, and the experiences of pain, joy, freedom, or exploitation that millions of people experience and feel. This is where critical realism serves as a philosophical approach to looking at these sophisticated, multilayered ontologies.

The critical realist approach is commonly used in international relations as well as in peace and mediation research. Joseph (2014: 4), for instance, argues that since critical realism adopts a 'pluralistic approach to research methods', it can be an excellent choice for researchers investigating relations between countries. Critical realists argue that different research methods can be used to explore different aspects of ontological reality, thus challenging the primacy of method. As Patomäki (2019: 189) puts it, critical realism provides a 'plausible, rationally evolving framework for politics, political economy, and other social sciences'. In Kurki's (2008: 378) words, critical realism directs international relations (IR) theorists 'towards more holistic, reflective and methodologically pluralistic causal theories'. Similarly, critical realism has been argued to be particularly suitable for researching transformative changes over time (Alderson 2019: 54), which is the case with this study.

Finally, it is important to emphasise, in a critical realist fashion, that there can be multiple interpretations of 'the truth'. The data I gathered and the arguments and analysis I offer in this study constitute only one perspective, which might have been affected by various elements, including my position as a Nepali researcher. If I were using a different methodological approach, relying on different theoretical domains, and collecting data using different methods and from sources other than the ones used here, then I would be offering a different perspective, but not necessarily a less important one.

2.1 Case Study Research and Its Components

This study employed the case study method as the principal research approach. This study presents a focused case analysis of India's role in Nepal throughout the latter's peace process and political transition between 2005 and 2017. The case study is based on data collected from the following sources: semi-structured key informant interviews, media materials collected from media archives, opinion pieces and media interviews of key informants, and an analysis of video interviews and speeches of key informants retrieved from the Internet (see Appendix 1).¹¹

The case study method is frequently employed as a research approach within the fields of peace and conflict studies, international relations, and global development studies. The case study method has been defined and characterised in various ways, both as a distinct research approach and as an intersection of multiple research methodologies. For instance, Yin (2018: 50) defines a case study as 'an empirical

¹¹ A detailed description of how these methods were selected and used is provided later in this chapter.

inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident'. He emphasises that adopting the case study method for an empirical investigation of a contemporary phenomenon also demands multiple sources of evidence. Other scholars also emphasise the importance of multiple sources of evidence in case study research (see, for instance, Stake 1995, Gerring 2007, Woodside 2010).

The justification for adopting the case study method, along with its suitability and applicability in research design, is closely tied to the research questions. In other words, not every study can be classified as a case study. The application of the case study method requires justification, must connect to the research questions and design, and should address key issues of validity and reliability.

Many scholars have argued that the case study method is suitable, or rather preferable, in studies that are complex and demand a thorough investigation. In other words, it is particularly suitable for studies that demand answers to 'why' and 'how' questions (Rowley 2002: 16–17, Yin 2003). Gerring (2007: 49) argues that the depth that the case study method offers can be understood as 'the detail, richness, completeness, wholeness, or the degree of variance in an outcome that is accounted for by an explanation'.

The topics case study research can cover vary widely. It can be employed to study 'programs, events, persons, processes, institutions, social groups, and other contemporary phenomena' (Hancock & Algozzine 2017: 15–16). The underlying idea behind case study research is conducting 'an intensive study of a single case (or a small set of cases) with an aim to generalise across a larger number of cases of the same general type' (Gerring 2007: 65). However, generalisation is not always the aim, nor is it a requirement. As already indicated above, case studies can be used to get an in-depth understanding of an issue, events, processes or an ongoing phenomenon. Case studies offer an empirical foundation for theoretical analysis, but they also 'stand in their own right as historical explanations' (George & Smoke 1974: 105).

Even though it has been argued that case studies have to be suitable for both theory building and as theory testing (Woodside 2010: 11), some scholars argue that they are particularly useful in generating new hypotheses (Gerring 2007: 38). Eisenhardt (1989: 548–549), for instance, argues that case studies are particularly well suited for research areas for which existing theory seems inadequate. Eisenhardt's argument aligns with the objectives of this study. This study's purpose is not theory testing, but to provide a nuanced interpretation and analysis of a complex topic. For instance, by adopting this analytical approach, I developed the concept of 'peace dependency', which I discuss in Chapter 9.

When it comes to methodical practice, case study research often includes 'collecting and interpreting stories individuals tell about their lives and events that they believe that they know about' (Woodside 2010: 41). Often, case study research is 'richly descriptive', 'grounded in deep and varied sources of information' and employs data, such as, 'quotes of key participants, anecdotes, prose composed from interviews, and other literary techniques to create mental images that bring to life the complexity of the many variables inherent in the phenomenon being studied' (Hancock & Algozzine 2017: 16).

Case studies have been divided into various subtypes and sub-categories, and

there are several variations of this method.¹² One of the more notable and widely cited categorisations is that of Yin (2003). He divides the case study research design into three parts: exploratory, descriptive, and explanatory. According to him, exploratory case studies are often used to define questions and hypotheses, usually to carry out further research. Descriptive case studies are useful in describing a particular phenomenon within a context, whereas explanatory case studies focus on exploring causal relationships. However, I found it difficult and unnecessary to categorise this study into one of these subtypes. While it is a singular case study focused on a specific topic, it includes explorative, explanatory, and descriptive components at different stages. Since there is no intrinsic need to categorise this study into a particular category, I prefer to use simple nomenclature, referring to it simply as a ‘case study.’

Despite its widespread popularity, especially in various disciplines of the social sciences, case study research has been criticised on various grounds. One of the more common criticisms has been centred around the idea that case study research has no boundaries and that it can accommodate anything, and anything can be made to call a case study. Maoz (2002: 164–165), for instance, argues that case studies have been synonymous with ‘some sort of free-form research that can embed basically everything and anything, and the researcher does not necessarily feel compelled to justify why certain cases are selected, which data are used and which data are ignored, and how data processing and analysis is achieved’.

In addition, as Idowu (2016: 184) argues, case study research has been ‘often charged with causal determinism, non-replicability, subjective conclusions, absence of generalizable conclusions, biased case selection and lack of empirical clout’. Idowu further argues that one of the most frequent criticisms of case study research is that case studies often depend on ‘single cases’; thus, they lack scientific or scholarly rigour and are unable to provide a generalising conclusion (p. 185). Case study research has been criticised for its potential verification bias, which means that case studies often confirm the researcher’s preconceived notions and ideas (Idowu 2016). Similarly, Feagin et al. (1991: 7) argue that ‘irrespective of the type, purpose, unit of analysis, or design, rigour is a central concern in case study research’.

However, some of these criticisms are unfounded, or they do not accurately characterise the case study method. For instance, the lack of methodological rigour in specific research or by a particular researcher can stem from a flawed research design or negligence. It should not be seen as an inherent flaw in the research method itself. This is particularly relevant when there are plenty of case studies that are both rigorous and reliable. Criticisms, such as those of Maoz (2002), that everything goes with case studies and that case study researchers are exempt from justifying their case selection, also do not reflect the true picture of case study research, or how many researchers have used this method. Without a thorough justification of the choices made and a detailed explanation of all research procedures—including methods for sampling, data collection, data processing, and analysis—any study, regardless of whether it is a case study or not, cannot meet scientific and scholarly standards.

However, the case study method does have its drawbacks. Like any other

¹² Zainal (2007: 1–6), for instance, categorises case studies into two types: interpretive and evaluative. Stake (1995) proposed dividing them into three types: intrinsic, instrumental, and collective. Whereas Dul & Hak (2008) argued that case studies could be simply of two types: the single case study and the comparative case study.

research method, it has limitations, potential pitfalls, and biases. Nevertheless, there are systematic strategies that researchers can employ to minimise these issues. This can enhance rigour and reliability during research design as well as in data collection, processing, and analysis. This is the approach I took in this study.

An exhaustive analysis of the pros and cons of the case study method is beyond the scope of this thesis. However, the bottom line is that, despite its limitations, the case study method remains widely used in contemporary social and political research. Case studies provide a valuable and in-depth understanding of a phenomenon and can also influence policy, practices, and future research (Merriam 2001). In response to critics who highlight methodological rigour as a concern in case study research, various techniques and approaches have been suggested by its proponents. These recommendations help ensure that case study research is thorough, reliable, and methodologically rigorous.

Improving validity and reliability has been suggested as one of the strategies for ensuring methodical rigour in case study research, and that is the approach I have taken in this study. In practice, this means demonstrating a match between operational measures and the subjects being investigated and establishing a connection between the collected data and the research questions (Rowly 2002).

The qualitative field is characterised by a diversity of paradigms and methodologies, making it challenging to establish universal criteria for validity. A simplistic approach that attempts to define global qualitative criteria would be inaccurate and risk oversimplifying the complex and nuanced nature of qualitative research. Moreover, methodologies within the qualitative field also emphasise other quality criteria such as credibility, transferability, trustworthiness, and authenticity. These criteria help ensure rigour and trustworthiness in qualitative research (see, for instance, Lincoln & Guba 1985, Miller 2008, Given 2008). The validity of all research can be improved by 'ensuring that research procedures remain coherent and transparent, research results are evident, and research conclusions are convincing' (Miller 2008: 910).

I have used three methods to enhance the validity, reliability, and credibility of my research. These are: 1. Data triangulation, 2. Reflexivity, and 3. Ensuring transparency and maintaining a chain of evidence. Data triangulation involves the use of multiple data sources and is an excellent way to enhance validity (Yin 2003, Adolphus 2011). As part of this strategy, I used data from the key informant interviews, but also accumulated relevant articles, speeches, opinion pieces, and videos from Internet archives. My other strategy has been the implementation of reflexivity at every step of the research process.

Applying reflexivity in the context of this research meant becoming more self-aware and critically examining my own biases, assumptions, and positionality as a native Nepali researcher with certain socio-political beliefs and inclinations. Reflexivity also helped me better understand the social, cultural, and historical context in which I was investigating this particular topic. As Davies (2012) points out, reflexivity helps researchers carry out more informed and introspective research, which also reflects my experience during this research process.

Reflexivity was a continuous and deliberate practice throughout this research. For instance, after each interview, I engaged in personal reflections to critically assess how my positionality, assumptions, or emotions may have influenced the interaction and interpretation of the data. These reflections often formed the basis for subsequent discussions with my supervisors, where I openly examined the methodological and ethical choices I had made and invited their critique to identify potential blind spots. I also took proactive steps to recognise and address possible

biases during the sampling process, particularly by striving for diversity in perspectives and ensuring that participant selection as well as the media sources I chose were not overly influenced by convenience or prior familiarity. Moreover, I employed data triangulation—drawing insights from multiple sources and methods—to enhance the credibility of the findings and to ensure that interpretations were not overly reliant on any single narrative or viewpoint. Through these strategies, reflexivity was not simply an abstract ideal, but a practical tool embedded in the design, execution, and analysis of the research.

Finally, ensuring transparency and maintaining a chain of evidence improved the overall validity and reliability of this study. Reliability in qualitative research is often achieved by thoroughly documenting research procedures and keeping good records (Rowly 2002, Adolphus 2011). In this regard, I have provided a detailed explanation of the procedures, including my fieldwork, the interview contexts, the sampling methods I used, the methods I applied to collect and analyse data, and the impact of my positionality on the analysis presented in this thesis.

2.2 Data Sources and Collection Methods

In this section, I discuss the data accumulation strategy used in this study and provide a detailed description of the data collection process. I also critically evaluate the tools employed for data accumulation and outline the ethical standards I adhered to throughout the study. Additionally, I explain the data analysis methods utilised and conclude the chapter by addressing important issues related to research ethics.

Figure 1 Data sources used in this study (see Appendix 1 for a detailed description of the data used).

As illustrated in Figure 1, the data for this study was obtained from four sources:

1. Semi-structured key informant interviews
2. Opinion pieces and media interviews (primarily from key informants unavailable for an interview)
3. Video talks and speeches by selected key informants who were unavailable for an interview but had significant involvement in issues covered by this study
4. Articles collected from Nepali media archives

2.2.1 Semi-Structured Key Informant Interviews

Interviews of individuals or groups allow researchers to get rich, personalised information (Mason 1996). Interviews are also ideal for investigating or analysing the events of the past (Weiss 1995: 1). In addition, as May (2001: 120) points out, interviews provide ‘rich insights into people’s biographies, experiences, opinions, values, aspirations, attitudes and feelings.’ Seldon (1988: 9) argued that ‘warm, vivid contemporary history has almost always been written by authors who have conducted interviews.’ One advantage of an interview, especially an in-depth interview, is that it captures how respondents form their opinions. While researchers cannot observe respondents’ underlying mental processes, they can interpret these processes through the way respondents ‘ramble, hesitate, stumble, and meander as they formulate their answers’ (Chong 1993: 868).

In this study, I conducted 18 semi-structured key informant interviews. Semi-structured interviews are in-depth interviews with respondents answering preset, open-ended questions (Jamshed 2014: 87). Such interviews are planned and are often carried out with the help of an interview guide¹³ (DiCicco-Bloom & Crabtree 2006). According to Hancock & Algozzine (2017: 40), semi-structured interviews are particularly suitable for case study research as they allow interviewees to ‘express themselves openly and freely’. In addition, researchers can use semi-structured interviews to ask predetermined but flexibly worded questions and pose follow-up questions designed to probe further (Hancock & Algozzine 2017).

Cohen & Manin (1994: 271) define semi-structured interviews as ‘a conversation initiated by the interviewer for the specific purpose of obtaining research relevant information, and focused by him on content specified by research objectives of systemic description, prediction or explanation’. In semi-structured interviews, the researcher’s main focus is not on testing hypotheses, but on ‘understanding the experience of other people and the meaning they make of that experience’ (Seidman 1991: 3).

In short, key informant interviews involve interviewing a selected group of individuals who are likely to provide needed information, ideas, and insights on a particular subject (Kumar 1989: 1). To obtain the information needed from a key informant, a researcher can talk with them informally, use formal techniques, such as written questionnaires, conduct telephone interviews, personal interviews, group interviews or community forums and public hearings (McKillip 1987).

As was the case with the key informants I interviewed, key informants are often experts on an issue who act as ‘owners’ of important contextual information or knowledge (Sharrock 1974). Interviewing them is particularly useful for obtaining ‘insider’ knowledge, even on sensitive topics (McKenna et al. 2011: 118). As

¹³ Various types of interviews are used in qualitative research, including structured, semi-structured, and unstructured interviews. In addition, there can be different variations within these categories, such as a semi-structured life history interview or a structured in-depth interview.

'information comes directly from knowledgeable people, key informant interviews often provide data and insight that cannot be obtained with other methods' (Kumar 1989: 9). This was the case in this study. Interviewing high-profile politicians directly involved in Nepal's peace and political transition process was one of the best ways to gain insight into the events and processes that often occurred behind closed doors.

However, one of the problems with key informant interviews is that 'findings can be biased if the informants are not carefully selected' (Kumar 1989: 9). Cossham & Johanson (2019) argue that difficulty in finding appropriate and reliable respondents, potential issues of power imbalances, and issues related to confidentiality, privacy, and the issue of knowledge use and intellectual property rights constitute some additional challenges in key informant interviewing.

Finding key informants, reaching out to them, and convincing them to agree to an interview was challenging for me as well. Some key informants did not respond to my interview requests, while others agreed to meet but declined to participate in the interview. For instance, despite making a few attempts, I could not interview Pushpa Kamal Dahal 'Prachanda', the leader who led the Maoist armed insurgency, nor could I find a way to contact Nepal's deposed former King, Gyanendra Shah. However, I have included their speeches and media interviews as part of the data, which provide insights into their thinking processes, perspectives, and opinions on the issues discussed in this thesis.

Another central figure in the peace process and political transition, Girija Prasad Koirala (aka G.P. Koirala), passed away in 2010, so I could not include his firsthand perspective in my analysis. However, I have incorporated a 51-minute interview he gave to BBC Nepali, in which the interviewer asked some of the questions I would have asked him. In addition, I managed to interview his only daughter and political aide, Sujata Koirala, who also provided details of her father's thought process that motivated him to make certain choices, such as signing a political pact with the Maoists and steering Nepal towards republicanism.

Despite these hurdles and limitations, I met and interviewed 18 key informants who provided valuable information and illuminating insights that ultimately helped me answer my research questions. Among others, my respondents included negotiators and signatories of the 12-Point Understanding, and a government minister who sat at the formal peace talks with the Maoists, representing the government of Nepal. In other words, most of these key informants (see Appendix 1 for a detailed list) were at the crux of the political processes that shaped Nepal's peace process and post-conflict political transition.

I began compiling the list of key informants in spring 2016, and over time, the list evolved. I closely followed political developments in Nepal for years before I started my doctoral degree at the University of Helsinki, and that proved helpful in the compilation process. I grew up in Nepal at a time when the Maoist armed insurgency had paralysed the country amidst an increasing polarisation between the monarchy and democratic political parties. As an eyewitness to the turmoil and political transition that occurred in post-1990 Nepal, I knew the protagonists of events and processes that shaped Nepali politics. In addition, as someone interested in politics and later as a student of the social sciences, I read plenty of books and magazines and have been a regular consumer of Nepali media for over two decades. This expanded my understanding of Nepali politics, the Maoist armed insurgency, the subsequent peace process, the people's movements in Nepal, and India's role during these critical moments.

When I began my doctoral degree, I started reading even more extensively. I

explored materials from various perspectives and sources. While my previous reading had been rather passive and narrow, as a doctoral student, I embarked on a journey of active reading. As a researcher, my reading also included research reports, policy papers, and many scholarly works. I gradually modified my key informant list based on the knowledge I acquired from my reading and a deeper exploration of Nepali politics.

Methodically speaking, I used the stratified purposive sampling method to select the key informants. In total, 40 key informants were selected, of whom 18 were interviewed. Key informants were selected from three broad categories to ensure a diversity of perspectives. First, prominent political leaders, peace negotiators, and politicians who played a key role in Nepal's peace process and political transition from 2005 to 2017 were chosen as political influencers. The second group consisted of scholars and civil society activists who actively participated in Nepal's democratic and peace processes, either as civil society members or scholar-activists. Finally, the third group included investigative journalists and peace researchers with extensive publication and engagement records on Nepal's peace process, political transition, and issues related to India–Nepal relations.

The purposive sampling method, also known as judgement sampling, is the 'deliberate choice of an informant due to the qualities the informant possesses' (Tongco 2007: 147). As Tongco emphasises, this non-random sampling method does not require underlying theories or a fixed number of respondents. When using the purposive sampling method, the researcher makes a judgmental decision, as I did in this study, in light of the research questions, what needs to be known, and proceeds to find respondents who would provide information and insights based on their knowledge, experience and expertise (Bernard 2011: 145, Etikan et al. 2016: 2–3). Identifying and choosing well-informed respondents who possess deep knowledge of the issue being studied is key in purposive sampling (Cresswell & Plano Clark 2011). In addition, choosing key informants should not be done too quickly and in haste (Bernard 2011). In this case, it took almost two years for me to finalise my key informant list and conduct the interviews.

Some scholars argue that one of the potential drawbacks of purposive sampling is that, since it is a non-random sampling method, respondent selection might be affected by the researcher's subjective biases (Heckman 1979, Berk 1983). In addition, this method is not regarded as ideal for making inferences about a population or for drawing generalised conclusions (Etikan et al. 2016: 4). One of the ways to deal with these limitations is to acknowledge them clearly when the results are analysed and interpreted, and by doing so readers will be prevented from drawing generalised conclusions (Tongco 2007: 154, Bernard 2011).

Despite its inherent limitations, purposive sampling provides 'reliable and robust' data and, when used properly, can be more effective than random sampling (Tongco 2007: 154–155). Guarte & Barrios (2006: 284), for instance, computed the estimate of bias supposedly inherent in purposive sampling and concluded that, despite the bias criticism it has faced, purposive sampling could produce reliable and rigorous results. Purposive sampling is a widely used method in key informant interviews, and its very strength lies in its presumptive weakness, i.e. the selection bias (Tongco 2007: 154–155). For instance, the key informants interviewed in this study included influential political leaders who held central roles and crucial positions during Nepal's peace process and political transition. They had decades of political experience and, thereby, a deep understanding of the complex political processes in Nepal. They were selected based on this virtue that they possessed. The case with other key informants was similar.

Rivera (2019: 5) proposes a two-stage sample selection process in purposive sampling to ensure diversity of perspectives, and that is the approach I adopted. On that basis, the key informants were selected not solely based on my subjective or 'intuitive' judgement, but through an assessment of documented evidence available about them (for instance, their media coverage, their engagement in certain political events and processes, participation and contributions evident in media, research outputs, etc.). While no numerical value was attached to these properties, key informants with more experience and expertise were preferred over those with less experience and supposedly lesser expertise.

Furthermore, to ensure a diversity of perspectives, purposive sampling was enhanced with an additional layer of stratified sampling. While using stratified sampling, 'the researcher first selects the particular categories or groups of cases that he/she considers should be purposively included in the final sample. The sample is then divided up or 'stratified' according to these categories, and a target number of participants is allocated to each one' (Robinson 2014: 32).

My initial key informant sample consisted of nearly 100 key informants, all chosen subjectively based on my acquaintance with the research area and the readings I had done over time. Given the limited time and resources, conducting as many key informant interviews as that would have been extremely challenging. Therefore, the sample was narrowed down to 40. As mentioned earlier, stratified sampling was used to ensure the diversity of perspectives. Thus, the key informant sample was stratified into three categories:

1. **Political influencers**, primarily high-profile political leaders, peace negotiators, and politicians who played significant roles during the peace process and political transition years (from 2005 to 2017).
2. **Scholars and civil society activists**, who were actively engaged in Nepal's democratic and peace processes, either as civil society members or scholar-activists.
3. **Investigative journalists and researchers**, who have extensively written and published on Nepal's peace process, political transition, and related issues, including India–Nepal relations.

There is no consensus on an ideal number of participants for key informant interviewing. Tongco (2007: 147) argues that key informant interviewing does not require a fixed number of respondents, while McCracken (1988) emphasises that around eight interviewees should suffice if the interviews are long and in-depth. Kumar (1989: 9), on the other hand, argues that, as a rule of thumb, 15 to 35 key informants are sufficient for most studies, and if the investigation is to be combined with other data collection methods, such as surveys and document content analysis, even fewer key informants may suffice. My interview experience was similar—what is important is not just the number of key informants, but the quality of the data or 'input' they provide. Ultimately, what mattered most was that the data I collected helped address the research questions.

2.2.2 Interviewing Elites: Pros, Cons, and Methodological Approaches

Many of the key informants I interviewed were in prominent political or highly influential professional positions. The interviewees included a former prime minister of Nepal, former deputy prime ministers, former ministers, members of the Constituent Assembly and members of parliament, prominent civil society

actors, and editors of national broadsheets (see Appendix 1). Many of these respondents would have easily crossed an 'elite threshold' if such a concept were used.

Interviewing elites has both advantages and disadvantages, and there is a small but growing body of literature on the topic. Since a significant portion of my data comes from these 'elites', it is important to discuss the theoretical issues surrounding this. The term 'elite' has a wide-ranging meaning in the social sciences, and scholars have used various synonymous terms. Zuckerman (1972: 160), for instance, distinguishes between different levels of elites and uses the term 'ultra elites' to describe a 'subset of particularly powerful or prestigious influentials'. Lilleker (2003: 208) attempts to offer an umbrella definition and argues that elites are those with 'close proximity to power or policymaking'. According to this notion, elites would be 'all elected representatives, executive officers of organisations and senior state employees' (p. 208), or any other people with particular expertise (Burnham et al. 2004).

While interviewing elites is not always easy or possible, elites tend to agree to be interviewed when they have something valuable to say (Berry 2002). Elite interviewing is particularly useful for understanding complex political processes that often take place behind closed doors. This method gives access to data that would be otherwise difficult to get from other sources. While most of the benefits of elite interviewing are similar to those of key informant interviewing, elite interviewing requires extra caution and preparation, as it has some inherent challenges. For instance, while interviewing an elite key informant, the balance often is in favour of the respondent (Burnham et al. 2004: 205), and the respondent may even seek to control the agenda (Bygnes 2008).

In addition, elite respondents might use the interview opportunity to 'present themselves in a good light' and also to convey a particular version of events, to get arguments and points of view across, to deride or displace other interpretations and points of view' (Ball 1994: 97–98). Elites could even feel threatened in an interview, especially in situations that are not straightforward to prepare (Harvey 2011: 433). Similarly, some elites might use tactics to derail the interview by shutting down, deflecting questions or weaving alternative narratives of justification (Batteson & Ball 1995: 203). In addition, it is quite typical for elite respondents to highlight some issues and omit or dismiss others (Lilleker 2003) and to amplify or exaggerate their roles and contributions (Berry 2002).

Being aware of the potential pitfalls of elite interviewing, I considered these issues before, during, and after the interviews. Similarly, while conducting the interviews, I did encounter some of the situations described in the literature. For instance, some respondents, especially top political leaders, tended to exaggerate their roles in various political processes. On many occasions, the desire to glorify their own or their party's work was also visible, as was blaming other political parties or actors for mistakes or mishaps. However, I did not get the impression that the respondents had felt threatened in the setting of an academic research interview (see, for instance, Harvey 2011) or that they had resorted to any tactics for derailing the interview by shutting down or deflecting questions (see Batteson & Ball 1995: 203). Overall, the respondents were friendly, cooperative, and willing to share their thoughts, opinions, and experiences. They exuded the impression that they were happy to be interviewed or that it was their responsibility to share 'the truth' they knew or had access to.

2.2.3 The Data Collection Process

The data collection process of this study began in mid-2017. I spent 2016 and the initial months of 2017 mostly reading about the research topic, making data collection plans, establishing contacts for interviews, and finalising fieldwork preparations. I spent the summer of 2017 (June, July, and August) in Nepal, during which the semi-structured key informant interviews (n=18) were conducted.

As presented above in Figure 1, the study draws from a dual data collection approach, harnessing insights from two primary sources: key informants and media materials. Interviews were conducted with 18 key informants. Additional data were obtained from both interviewed and non-interviewed key informants, including opinion pieces, interviews given to other media outlets, and analyses of selected video interviews and speeches.

Furthermore, in the second stage of the data accumulation process, media articles from Nepali media outlets were compiled and analysed. A targeted keyword search within media archives helped gather and examine relevant articles related to the study's focus.

2.2.4 Key Informant Distribution and Key Information Interviews

As explained above, the key informants were chosen using a stratified purposive sampling method, and their distribution was as follows.

Table 1: Distribution of Key Informants

Sample category	Number
<p>1. Political actors and influencers</p> <p>High-profile political leaders, peace negotiators, and politicians who were in various influential positions during Nepal's peace process and political transition (i.e. from 2005 to 2017).</p> <p>The list includes a former prime minister who oversaw the implementation of some crucial aspects of the peace process and led Nepal for 20 months as prime minister during the political transition. The list also includes one former deputy prime minister, one former deputy prime minister and foreign minister, members of parliament, former ministers, and a government negotiator officially representing the government of Nepal in the 2006 CPA process.</p> <p>A senior communist leader and former deputy prime minister interviewed had informally facilitated talks with the Maoists years before the 12-Point Understanding was signed in India. I also interviewed the only female member of the Central Committee of the Maoists when the party decided to launch the armed struggle in 1996. She was also the only female member of the 'dialogue committee', headed by the Maoist chairman Pushpa Kamal Dahal (Prachanda), and formed by the rebels to negotiate a peace deal with the government of Nepal.</p>	8
<p>2. Peace & security experts and civil society activists</p> <p>In this category, I interviewed two peace and security experts involved in Nepal's peace process. The other key informants were civil society activists who played active roles in Nepal's democratic</p>	5

and peace movement. One of the interviewees served as an independent observer during the 2006 peace negotiations between the Maoists and the representatives of the government of Nepal in Kathmandu.

3. Investigative journalists, Peace & IR researchers 5

In this category, I interviewed journalists and researchers who have extensively written and published on Nepal's peace process, political transition, and India–Nepal relations.

I began to contact the key informants in spring 2017 as my trip to Nepal was already confirmed, and the interviews were scheduled for the summer. Initially, I used email and social media to contact the key informants. In emails and social media messages I sent, I introduced myself and explained the aims and scope of my research and my willingness to interview them. I received an encouraging response from journalists, researchers, and civil society activists. Political leaders, however, barely responded.

Once in Nepal, I collected telephone numbers of the political leaders I wanted to interview. For this, I used a contact information booklet of Nepal's parliament, which was available online. In addition, I used my political contacts in Nepal to be in touch with high-profile political leaders whose contact information was not publicly available. High-profile political leaders were mostly contacted through their personal secretaries and assistants. In general, sending text messages to political leaders or their assistants—detailing who I was and why I wanted to interview them—proved to be the most effective strategy to get a response from them.

Trust building is a key strategy for getting quality data, particularly from elite interviews, and being transparent is a prerequisite for trust building (Ostrander 1993). I also experienced that being open and transparent about my own identity, the research I was conducting, and its aims, scopes, and objectives was an excellent way to build trust with the key informants. In addition, as Lilleker (2003: 214) suggests, being well-prepared, well-organised, tactful, professional, and exuding confidence also helped.

Most interviews took place in the informants' homes or offices. One was held discreetly in a quiet café due to logistical constraints, but the setting felt less conducive. I recommend prioritising home or office environments for greater stability. The interviews were conducted one-on-one, fostering a direct and personal interaction between me and the key informants. However, occasional visits by personal secretaries of some leaders were not uncommon. Although not directly involved in the conversations, their presence added a layer of interruption to the interview process. Nonetheless, the essence of the interviews remained unaltered—the focus rested solely on the exchange between me and the key informants, ensuring a private and exclusive dialogue.

One of the issues I repeatedly encountered while conducting the interviews was that the respondents struggled with remembering facts. The issue was mostly with dates, but, on occasion, confusion also occurred with names and places. However, this appears to be a common issue in key information interviews. I adopted the recommendations of Davies (2001) for dealing with possible data incongruity caused by the respondents' memory issues. He recommends a triangulation strategy to minimise such errors. The recommendations include cross-referencing

interview data with published firsthand accounts or other documentary sources and verifying them with published secondary source material (p. 77–79). For important dates and facts, I cross-checked and verified the information provided by the key informants by consulting available official documents. When such verification sources were unavailable, I relied on reliable published sources and, on occasion, on media sources.

The interview data collected from the 18 key informant interviews totalled 16.36 hours (i.e., 982 minutes). On average, each interview lasted 55 minutes and 55 seconds. The longest interview was 91 minutes, and the shortest lasted for 20 minutes.¹⁴ An interview guide was used to conduct the interviews, with questions customised for each candidate based on their previous experience and area of expertise. Even though each key informant received slightly modified questions, the interview theme was largely consistent across all participants. The interviews began with a question about the key informants' own experiences and involvement in the peace process before transitioning to the broader issues explored in this study. In the end, each key informant was asked to discuss briefly some key lessons from the Nepali peace process that could be useful in other post-conflict scenarios. Nearly all interviews ended with this question.

Even though my key informant list included 40 key informants, meeting and interviewing everyone on the list was impossible. As 2017 was an election year in Nepal, some key informants who had promised to give an interview informed me at the last minute that they were too busy. Moreover, some key informants, especially those holding high-profile political positions, were reluctant to be interviewed. For instance, a senior government minister, who had played a visibly important role in the peace negotiation process, agreed to meet me at the ministry office. However, when I briefed him about my study and its themes, he politely declined the interview request. He mentioned he was too busy for an interview that day and that his assistants would contact me within a week. Despite my repeated follow-ups, my attempt to interview him was unsuccessful. He might have genuinely been busy as a senior government minister, but it is also possible he wanted to avoid my questions. Talking about India's involvement in Nepal is often difficult for Nepali politicians, especially when they are in a position of power.

2.2.5 Media Materials from Internet Archives

To supplement the data from my key informant interviews, I developed an additional data accumulation strategy. This time, I explored online archives of popular print and digital Nepali media outlets and looked for opinion pieces and interviews featuring my key informants. While doing so, my main priority was to cover the key informants I had been unable to interview. In addition, I also incorporated materials such as news, opinion pieces, and works of in-depth reporting that were not strictly linked to my key informants but were relevant to the research questions.

I began this stage by identifying targeted keywords and relevant phrases. In this process, I ensured that the keywords and phrases selected captured the key concepts and themes under investigation. The keywords and key phrases I used

¹⁴ Even though each key informant received almost the same number of questions, a few key informants preferred answering only briefly, and as a result, some interviews were significantly shorter than the average length of the interviews, which was 55 minutes and 55 seconds.

were both general and specific.¹⁵ Predominantly, I used Nepali keywords and key phrases since most of the content relevant to this research was written in Nepali. I also included some English key phrases because some of the media portals I explored had content in English.

Table 2: Media material sources and their distribution

Media sources	Number of texts/articles selected
Kantipur Dainik	34
Onlinekhabar	20
Setopati	12
Ratopati	8
Annapurna Post	6
Lokaantar	6
Nepallive	4
Nepal Magazine	3
My Republica (<i>English</i>)	3
Nepali Times (<i>English</i>)	2
The Himalayan Times (<i>English</i>)	1
The Kathmandu Post (<i>English</i>)	1
Dristi Weekly	1
HimalKhabar	1
Nagarik Daily	1
Nepal Aaja	1
Hamrakura	1
Total	105

Of the 105 pieces selected, 98 were written in Nepali, while seven were in English. Data were gathered from 17 media sources (see Table 2) using two search engines (Google and Bing) and the internal archives of six media outlets: Kantipur Daily, Onlinekhabar, Setopati, Ratopati, Annapurna Post, and Lokaantar.

One of the challenges I faced while accumulating data using the search engines was navigating through the massive amount of content. With the apparent explosion of online media in Nepal over the last two decades, the Nepali online media space has become crowded with a vast amount of content. Even for a relatively experienced media consumer like me, it is not always easy to distinguish between facts, distorted facts, and fake news. During online data accumulation, I encountered several low-quality news sites that thrived on false information, fake

¹⁵ For instance, I began with general key phrases such as “Nepali peace process,” “India’s involvement in Nepal’s post-conflict transition,” “India–Nepal relations,” and “2015 Nepal blockade.” I also used very specific phrases such as “participants of the 12-Point-Understanding,” “India in the Katalaw case,” and “Jayshankar’s Nepal visit.”

news, and an exaggerated and sensational catering of conspiracy theories.

To avoid collecting misleading information or 'distorted' facts, I took four steps. First, I ensured that all the online media sources I used were registered with the Department of Information, as mandated by Nepal's media law. For print and online media, I confirmed that they had received a top ranking from the Press Council Nepal, an autonomous media regulatory body established by the Government of Nepal. Second, I drew on my experience of consuming Nepali media for over two decades. Using purposive sampling, I selected materials that were deemed relatively more independent and widely trusted. Third, when I encountered highly controversial, partisan, and opinionated content, I examined it more closely and considered alternative perspectives. Fourth, whenever I came across facts (such as dates, names, or historical events), I cross-checked them with reliable sources and made a sincere effort to verify their accuracy.

By following the procedures outlined above, I collected 105 pieces of text. The data included opinion pieces, interviews with key informants conducted by reporters and journalists, opinion and news pieces, and several in-depth reporting works. The materials gathered were then converted into PDF format, and digital copies were saved for analysis. Media materials were collected in two phases, in 2018 and 2020. In both cases, a separate document was used to record relevant metadata, including the title, publication date, author names, and URLs. The length of accumulated media text was 750 pages in total. The pieces collected ranged from 2009 to 2019, even though most of the texts were from 2015 to 2018.¹⁶

2.2.6 Speeches and Video Talks

A small but important data component includes video speeches and video interviews of some of my key informants. These videos were gathered using the snowball sampling method. I found them referenced or referred to in the articles I read, or they were recommended during the key informant interviews I conducted earlier. In this category, I used 12 videos (five speeches, five media interviews, one conference presentation, and one video commentary/documentary). The length of the videos totalled 360.1 minutes (i.e. 6 hours). All twelve videos were accessed on the video-sharing site YouTube (see Appendix 1).

This strategy was especially effective in capturing the viewpoints of important but hard-to-reach key informants. For instance, my attempt to meet Pushpa Kamal Dahal 'Prachanda', the founding chairman of the CPN (Maoists) and the Commander-in-Chief of the People's Liberation Army, was unsuccessful. However, I found a lengthy speech in which he discussed the early days of the Maoist insurgency, detailing how the movement slowly gained both domestic and international attention. He explained how the party formed seemingly odd alliances, not always out of camaraderie, but also for tactical and strategic reasons to build strength and exert political power. In the same speech, he openly talked about India's role in Nepal's peace process and political transition. Undoubtedly, his speech became an important piece of data for this research.

Similarly, G. P. Koirala, who had successfully led the 2006 people's movement

¹⁶ There are several reasons for this. First, many Nepali media outlets only started to archive their media content in recent years. Second, the number of media outlets offering digital or online content was comparatively low during the initial years covered in this study. Third, many online news portals that offer vibrant discussion on the topic of this study were established only during the later years of the last decade. Fourth, after the 2015 economic blockade, discussions on India's influence in Nepal intensified at an unprecedented scale. Hence, pieces from the post-blockade years dominated the data.

(*Jana Andolan II*), was the most influential figure in the peace process and political transition saga. He would have unquestionably been an ideal key informant for this research. Mr Koirala, however, passed away in 2010, years before this study began. I interviewed his two close political aides, his daughter Sujata Koirala and nephew Shekhar Koirala, and their input was important in understanding Mr Koirala's decisions and political choices. In addition, I also came across a 51-minute video interview conducted in 2007 by the BBC (Nepali) *Sajha Sawal* programme, in which Mr Koirala was asked several questions related to Nepal's peace process and political transition. Even though I could not interview Mr Koirala myself, incorporating that video into this study helped me understand his perspectives and opinions and offered some important insights into the political processes he had led.

In addition, I was unsuccessful in interviewing the former King, Gyanendra Shah, as I could not locate a communication channel through which to deliver my interview request to him. After being stripped of his royal status, he led a surprisingly private life, making only occasional and minimal media appearances. Although I was not able to interview him myself, I found and included a rare television interview he gave in July 2012 to Nepal's News24 TV. In the interview, among other things, the former King claimed that the Seven Party Alliance had agreed to keep the constitutional monarchy intact as *Jana Andolan II* peaked in 2006. This piece of information was difficult, if not impossible, for me to get from elsewhere.

Other speeches and interviews included in the study serve a similar purpose. Although I did not personally conduct these interviews or listen to the speeches firsthand, their inclusion in the study was crucial in addressing the research questions. They offer valuable insights and greatly enhance the overall depth of analysis. Utilising these externally sourced speeches and interview data contributes significantly to the robustness of this study and ensures a thorough exploration of the research objectives.

2.2.7 Media Sources as Research Data: Uses and Implications

Using media sources as data in research comes with several caveats and considerations. Media outlets often have their own biases, which can influence the information they present. They can, deliberately or accidentally, mould the story they are presenting by injecting their views, perspectives, and prejudices.

The Nepali media houses whose media materials I have used as data in this study have often been vocal about their guiding principles and political positions. For instance, nearly all major mainstream media outlets in Nepal openly criticised both King Gyanendra's direct rule and the Maoist armed insurgency. They actively participated in *Jana Andolan II*, which ultimately ended King Gyanendra's direct rule, and brought the Maoists to peaceful mainstream politics. In other words, during Nepal's peace process and political transition, the media was not merely a collection of passive reporters; instead, it consisted of active participants who played a crucial role in guiding Nepal towards a new political direction. Nepali mainstream media backed and promoted what is often referred to as progressive agendas, including liberal democracy, the rule of law, human rights, and nonviolence. As the agenda-setting theory has highlighted, media structures do indeed play an active role in crafting, moulding, and steering the public agenda (see, for instance, McCombs 2005, Towner & Muñoz 2020), which was indeed the case in Nepal.

Big media houses often have corporate interests that inherently influence how they report—or choose not to report—on specific issues and events. As Lazaridou & Krestel (2016) argue, media houses tend to intentionally promote some stories while giving little or no space to others. These values, choices, agendas, and interests are often reflected in their works and the issues they cover or fail to cover. While this limitation is also inherent in the data I have accumulated, the rise of independent and journalist-owned digital media platforms (such as Setopati, Ratopati, Nepallive, and Lokaantar in this context) is changing this dynamic.

It is also crucial to address limitations concerning accuracy and reliability. For instance, not all media outlets prioritise fact-checking or accuracy. Journalists often rely on human sources for information and may not always have the tools to confirm the veracity of the information they receive. Time and resource constraints can also compel them to reduce investigative efforts or depend on PR (public relations) professionals and other parties as information sources (Gandy 1982, Hallin 2005). As Godler et al. (2020: 218) explain:

Human sources pose knowledge-related problems for journalists: journalists can never enter an eyewitness's head, they cannot always (and can never with certainty) gauge a whistle-blower's intentions or sincerity, they cannot challenge a scientist's claims like her peer, and they might not have the professional leeway to verify every single claim by a politician or a spokesperson.

Similarly, media reports also tend to have temporal and spatial limitations. In this case, media coverage might vary temporally and spatially, focusing on certain events or regions while neglecting others. Even the most careful journalists may portray a partial and often biased representation of large, irregular, and important events (Woolley 2000: 171). This can ultimately create a skewed understanding of broader trends or realities. Media reports do not always provide the full context or depth essential for rigorous research. In addition, oversimplification of events or topics can be a problem, leading to an incomplete representation of subjects requiring in-depth portrayal.

Strategies such as cross-verifying information from multiple sources, considering biases inherent in media content, and triangulating findings using diverse data sets are some of the strategies that researchers have used to mitigate the limitations associated with using media sources in research (see, for instance, Woolley 2000, Hill et al. 1997). As is evident in this chapter, I have also used cross-verification, data triangulation, thorough acknowledgement of potential biases, and diligent attention to the quality of data sources as strategies for dealing with limitations inherent in media sources used in this study.

Despite some of the limitations discussed, the media materials I used provided excellent insights and proved to be remarkable data sources to answer the research questions. Diplomatic tensions often unfold behind closed doors, but it was primarily the media that took on the task of unravelling these tensions and illustrating the strained and escalating India–Nepal relations in the years following the 2006 peace deal. In other words, media outlets frequently served as the main platforms on which discussions and debates about Indian micromanagement in the post-conflict context were openly discussed and debated from various perspectives.

2.2.8 The Internet as a Data Destination

As is already clear, I used the Internet to accumulate some of the data used in this research. The use of the Internet as a source of information or as a platform for data

accumulation has several implications, both positive and negative. As other scholars have also pointed out, Internet-based research offers ample opportunities, particularly for a study of this type. Internet-based research is valuable for investigating interpretive frames within a limited time frame¹⁷ (Baumgarten & Grauel 2009: 116). It allows for research in a naturalistic setting without the interference of an intrusive researcher (Nosek et al. 2002: 174) and helps reach populations that are difficult to reach (Duffy 2002: 87, Hash & Spencer 2009).

As far as this study is concerned, one of the remarkable benefits of the Internet was that it offered extremely valuable data from diverse sources. For instance, I used newspaper archives and video materials from several sources and from a period spanning many years. Had these materials not been on the Internet, data accumulation from such diverse sources would have been long, cumbersome, and expensive. This straightforward accessibility allowed me to explore various perspectives and gather data quickly and efficiently. By accumulating data from the Internet, I could include the perspectives of people who were unavailable or inaccessible for an interview. In addition, I also frequently used various sources available on the Internet to tally and verify the factual information that the key informants provided during the interviews.

As Askitas & Zimmermann (2015) have argued, the Internet can be a great tool for researchers, particularly as a source of data advancement. This was the case in this study as well. While I did accumulate a significant portion of primary data from the key informant interviews, the data obtained from the Internet helped me broaden my perspectives. This also supported my analysis and argumentation. This was then ultimately instrumental in addressing the research questions. As others have also noted (see, for instance, Adair et al. 2006: 545, Alessi & Martin 2010: 128), data obtained from Internet sources, particularly first-person narratives, can provide rich and in-depth perspectives and are excellent qualitative data sources. I also had a similar experience conducting this study. Some personal narratives and pieces of investigative reporting that I incorporated as my data in this study provided in-depth insights that were immensely valuable in addressing the research questions.

Internet-based data accumulation practice has a few shortcomings and limitations, some of which I also experienced. As Deacon (2007: 14) has argued, the use of computerised search engines in data collection is not only convenient but also helpful in locating and identifying deeply buried information, for instance, in an in-depth article. This was mostly true in my case, too. However, some keywords generated extensive data that were virtually impossible to process. In such cases, narrowing down and making the keywords more specific or using a restrictive search was helpful. Similarly, only keyword matching sometimes did not produce any useful content. In other words, there were several cases of false positives. On occasions, locating the context of searched content also posed a challenge. News articles and opinion pieces are produced in a particular context and to respond to certain socio-political developments. Understanding those contexts and complexities was in itself a challenging task.

Karlsson & Sjøvaag (2016) argue that since Internet-based research is a relatively new practice, old and established methods might not be sufficient for studying and analysing digital media content. There is a need to develop new

¹⁷ As is typical with interpretive framing, my analysis of the complex and multifaceted India–Nepal relations revolves around political aspects, whereas other aspects of India–Nepal relations, such as cultural and linguistic, have not been highlighted.

common standards and protocols to address inherent limitations. These limitations, however, do not mean that ‘web researchers should be allowed to have lax standards’ (Herring 2010: 246). In fact, they ‘need to hold *themselves* to high standards of conceptual clarity, systematicity of sampling and data analysis, and awareness of limitations in interpreting their results’ (p. 246). According to Nosek et al. (2002: 175):

The challenges of the Internet should not deter investigators from taking advantage of this powerful medium for discovery and education. Yet the responsibility for conducting research that meets the highest standards for ethical treatment and advances science is first and foremost the responsibility of scientists themselves.

Deacon (2007: 23) recommends a wide range of measures for improving the reliability of an analysis centred around digital searches, and I also took some of those measures. For instance, I checked the accumulated data for duplicated items and false positives and carefully scanned the titles and the time span selected. In addition, as I have already explained, data triangulation is one of the strategies researchers commonly use to compensate for shortcomings in a particular data collection method. I also adopted that strategy in this research. As a result, the Internet-sourced data is used in tandem with firsthand key informant interviews, and this strategy not only ensured data variance, but also helped bolster data analysis and the study’s reliability.

2.3 Data Analysis

Researchers use various analytical approaches and methods to analyse qualitative data. In case study research, an analytical strategy aims to link case study data to ‘some concepts of interest’ and then use those concepts to achieve a sense of direction in the process of data analysis (Yin 2003).

For dealing with qualitative data and constructing an analytical framework, Yin (2003: 109–139) presents four strategies: 1. Relying on theoretical propositions (i.e., constructing an analytical framework based on theoretical vantage points used in the study), 2. The inductive strategy (i.e., taking the ‘ground up’ approach of analysis), 3. Developing case descriptions (especially when concepts and categories cannot be developed from the data), and 4. Examining rival (plausible) explanations. As an analytical strategy, this study adopts the inductive approach based on grounded theory.¹⁸ The analytical framework also draws inspiration from McCracken’s (1988) recommendations for analysing long qualitative interviews.¹⁹

Yin (2018: 278) argues that a researcher can develop their own analytical strategy based on the research questions and the nature of the data. Nonetheless, Yin recommends starting with research questions and not with data. The aim, he argues, is to ‘play with the data’ and look for patterns, insights, or concepts that seem promising. Schmidt (2004: 253) also encourages researchers to develop their own appropriate modes of analysis and argues that ‘the analytical techniques that are selected for semi-structured interviews within the framework of an

¹⁸ Grounded theory is a methodology developed by Glaser & Strauss (1967) and is primarily used for building theoretical constructs from data.

¹⁹ McCracken (1988) proposed five stages of analysis for analysing long qualitative interviews: 1) treat each data item independent of other items, 2) develop observations by themselves then align with other findings and then per literature review, 3) examine connections between second-level observation, considering literature and culture review, 4) scrutinise this collective form to determine inter-theme consistency and contradiction, and 5) use patterns and theme displayed across findings into a final form of analysis.

investigation will depend on the goals, the questions and the methodological approach’.

Particularly in qualitative studies, the timing of data analysis is also important. There is no consensus among scholars on when data analysis should begin. Some argue that data analysis should begin only after all data is collected, ensuring the researcher can assess the amount and quality of the data. Others believe that data analysis and data collection can occur simultaneously (see, for instance, Hartley 1994).

Against this backdrop, I adopted a middle-way approach. While the final, comprehensive data analysis began many months after the data collection, a 'preliminary analysis' took place already during the data collection stage. When collecting data from the key informant interviews and later from the Internet, I wrote field notes and reflexive remarks, which aided the final analysis. In the grounded theory tradition, the use of notes and memos has long been advocated (Corbin & Strauss 2007) as they can provide clues, ideas, hints, and suggestions that are useful for conceptualising data in the analysis stage (Lempert 2011). Analytic aids, such as memos and field notes, not only enhance analysis, but also contribute to ensuring that the final coded product is both valid and reliable, or, in other words, credible and confirmable (Guba & Lincoln 1989).

2.3.1 Content Analysis

As Dey (1993: 31) puts it, the researcher’s aim in qualitative data analysis should be to describe different phenomena, classify them, and observe how concepts interconnect. While the analytical fabric of this study is based on grounded theory, the data were analysed using the qualitative content analysis method. Content analysis offers tools and techniques for systematic text analysis and is a widely popular method of data analysis that has been in practice since the 18th century.²⁰ Krippendorff (1969: 103) defines content analysis as the ‘use of replicable and valid method for making specific inferences from text to other states or properties of its source’. In the words of Mayring (2000), content analysis is an approach of empirical, methodological, controlled analysis of texts within their context of communication, following step-by-step models and analytical rules and without relying on reckless quantification. Content analysis is ‘the longest established method of text analysis among the set of empirical methods of social investigation’ (Titscher et al. 2000: 55). Qualitative content analysis involves searching for underlying themes in the data being analysed and is presumably the most prevalent approach to the qualitative analysis of documents (Bryman 2017).

Broadly speaking, content analysis is of two types: Quantitative content analysis and qualitative content analysis. Quantitative content analysis relies on methods such as frequency counts and objective analysis of coded frequencies (Cracauer 1952), whereas in qualitative content analysis, patterns are prioritised. Qualitative content analysis is generally inductive and begins with open research questions. Thus, it is not so much about testing a hypothesis (White & Marsh 2006). While some have raised concerns about the qualitative content analysis method, noting its potential for impressionism and the need for greater systematic rigour (Krippendorff 2018), it remains a valuable and insightful approach to data analysis. This method enables rich and nuanced interpretations of complex data, enhances

²⁰ In the beginning, the content analysis method was mainly used to analyse quantitative data, but since the 1950s, it has been used to analyse both quantitative and qualitative data.

the rigour, validity, and reliability of a study, and is particularly well-suited for case study research (Kohlbacher 2006).

After reviewing the literature on different content analysis methods, I developed a 6-step process for analysing the data in this study. The steps are as follows:

1. Taking notes and memos during data collection
2. Labelling and storing data
3. Transcribing and translating data
4. Coding
5. Identifying thematic patterns/categories of codes and establishing theoretical linkages
6. Writing up the findings, analysis, and developing new theoretical insights (inductive/grounded theory approach)

As per this model, field notes, memos, and reflective remarks were created after each key informant interview. The same technique was used while collecting interviews, opinion pieces, video talks, and speeches from online sources. In stage two, the data were labelled and securely stored in a password-protected computer, and a backup was kept on an encrypted hard drive. The key informant interviews, conducted in Nepali, were transcribed verbatim, and only the relevant parts were translated into English. The interview transcripts and the media documents were read numerous times, and several codes were established (see Appendix 2). The codes were both specific (such as India's role in the 12-point agreement) and more general (such as the peace process, democratic movement, and so forth). In the next stage, several thematic patterns were identified (such as micromanagement and mediation rhetoric), and the codes were categorised accordingly. The final stage of this process was writing up the findings, during which theoretical linkages were explored using an inductive approach.

2.3.2 Translating Data Text

Collecting data in one language and presenting and analysing it in another requires making translation-related decisions that can impact the overall quality of research. In social sciences research, several factors can affect the quality of translation, including the translator's linguistic competencies and knowledge of the culture and the people under study (Frey 1970, Kirkpatrick & Van Teijlingen 2009). The translator's autobiography and the circumstances in which translation is carried out also have an impact (Vulliamy 1990: 166, Birbili 2000). Translation, in that sense, is much more than simply substituting words in one language with words in another language. It involves the transmission of meaning and sense that the translator wants to impart (Cúc 2018).

The best way to deal with translation-related issues is to be open and explicit about decisions, procedures, choices, and any resources used during the translation process (Birbili 2000). This is the approach I have adopted in this study. As Ervin & Bower (1952: 597–598) put it, the ultimate aim of a good translation process is to prevent pseudo-information or the loss of important information.

I am a native speaker of the Nepali language and deeply understand the cultural context in which the study was conducted. As a result, I did not need to use an interpreter or a translator. Since the interviews were conducted in the respondents' and the researcher's native language, many potential occurrences of misunderstanding, miscommunication, and misinterpretation were avoided. Even

though many respondents were fluent in English, conducting interviews in Nepali, their native language, provided a relaxed environment where they did not have to worry about expressing themselves in a foreign language. They could instead totally focus on the subject matter of the interview.

Later, while translating from Nepali to English, I encountered situations in which finding a direct lexical equivalent for several Nepali words was impossible. In such cases, I focused less on lexical comparability and aimed to find ‘conceptual equivalence’ in English, a strategy that several scholars have recommended for handling similar situations. (See, for instance, Deutscher 1968: 337, Broadfoot & Osborn 1993, Temple 1997: 610).

Similarly, some scholars have emphasised the use of translation aids, such as dictionaries, thesauruses, field notes, and other references, to enhance the overall quality of translation (see, for instance, Putri 2019: 21). I used an online Nepali-to-English dictionary and thesaurus service²¹ and consulted my field diary regularly. Both these techniques helped me to ensure better and higher-quality data translation.

2.4 Research Ethics

There has always been some emphasis on research ethics in the academic and scientific tradition; however, such emphasis has intensified in recent years. Hammersley & Traianou (2012: 2) argue that the use of new technologies in research—such as burgeoning digital tools and the Internet—and widening data protection legislation—which affects how data is stored, reported, archived, and reused—have made research ethics even more important than before. In addition, the growth of ethical regulation and the division and fragmentation of research along political and philosophical lines have necessitated an added emphasis on research ethics (Hammersley & Traianou 2012).

Gorman (2007: 8) warns of the danger of research ethics being ‘reduced to an easy means of managing institutional risk rather than something that is intrinsically valuable to the research process.’ Ethics, she argues, is at the crux of good scholarship and goes beyond merely adopting simplistic solutions. Research ethics, in essence, provides a useful framework for asking meaningful questions (Gorman 2007). Research ethics demands thorough consideration not only because researchers need to consider what is being investigated, but also because they should be aware of how the investigation is carried out and what possible consequences it may produce (Brouneus 2011: 141).

Adhering to ethical norms is not only necessary, but also beneficial to researchers and their work. As Resnik (2011) points out, research ethics helps to promote one’s research aims and improves trust, fairness, accountability, and public support. In addition, ethical research practice also furthers moral and social values, such as social responsibility and human rights (Resnik 2011).

Ethical standards were a top priority in this study, guiding every step from design to reporting, to ensure thoroughness and rigour. Two works largely shape the research ethics framework of this study: the guidelines for conducting responsible research provided by Shamoo & Resnik (2009) and the idea of ethics ‘reflexivity’ proposed by Guillemin & Gillam (2004). In addition, I also went through the research ethics guidelines of the University of Helsinki,²² and ensured

²¹ https://www.lexilogos.com/english/nepali_dictionary.htm

²² Available at: <https://www.helsinki.fi/en/research/services-for-researchers/research-ethics>

that my practices aligned with the University's stance on ethical research and ethical research reporting. As per the university's ethical guidelines, this study did not require research permission or an ethical review by the Ethics Committee. Similarly, I did not need research or administrative permission to conduct fieldwork in Nepal.

Shamoo & Resnik's (2009) recommendations for conducting responsible research encompass 16 components, 15 of which are relevant to this study.²³ Their guidelines address issues such as honesty, objectivity, integrity, carefulness, openness, confidentiality, responsible publication, respect for intellectual property, and protection of human subjects. Their recommendations were thoroughly followed in the various stages of this research. For instance, integrity was upheld by ensuring consistency between the research objectives and the methodologies used and avoiding any practices that might have compromised the validity of the findings. Similarly, transparency is demonstrated by providing a detailed account of the research methods and decision-making processes, which allows others to replicate or evaluate the study's findings. While a comprehensive analysis of their recommendations exceeds the scope of this thesis, these principles were diligently followed at various stages of the research process.

In addition, I utilised the concept of 'ethical reflexivity' as a complementary component. Guillemin & Gillam (2004: 261) identify two dimensions of research ethics: procedural ethics and ethics in practice. As a way of dealing with both these ethical dimensions, they propose the notion of reflexivity. While procedural ethics are rather bureaucratic (such as securing approval from an ethics committee), ethics in practice²⁴ focuses on the everyday ethical issues a researcher faces (p. 263).

The concept of reflexivity in research is not new, and I have already discussed how this has been used in this study. However, Guillemin & Gillam's (2004) idea of ethical reflexivity attempts to apply the reflexivity concept as a means of dealing with ethical encounters and dilemmas in a research setting. In that sense, the principles of what is traditionally known as reflexive research are expanded to include research ethics.

I encountered various ethical issues, particularly during the key informant interviews. For example, in one conversation, the topic of 'wartime memories' arose, and one of my questions made the respondent emotional. While the key informant's response to that question would have been valuable for this study, given the emotional response it triggered, I skipped that question and quickly moved on to another one. After the interview, I reflected on the incident, the question I had asked, and how I had handled the situation.

On another occasion, a high-ranking political leader was prepared for an interview but wanted to include two party cadres who were already sitting in the room. The respondent claimed that the two individuals could also provide valuable insights based on their local experience of the peace process.²⁵ I also had a moment when a key informant repeatedly struggled to remember a few facts, particularly dates, and requested that I remove an earlier recording. In such instances, I engaged in reflexive ethical retrospection, contemplating what had occurred and

²³ The one component that is not relevant to this study is ensuring animal care in research.

²⁴ Komesaroff's (1995) notion of *micro-ethics*, a term coined to denote the everyday ethical issues in research practice, is similar in many ways to Guillemin & Gillam's (2004) idea of 'ethics in practice'.

²⁵ The two party-cadres are not included in this study's key informant list since they did not fulfil the key informant criteria and were not interviewed as such. While the key informant was being interviewed, they made a few remarks that did not add any additional value to the information that the key informant provided.

what could have been improved. I never insisted that my respondents should do anything; respecting their wishes was my guiding principle.

I used an interview guide during the key informant interviews, which helped steer the data collection process. It was useful in keeping conversations focused and preventing them from straying for too long. Moreover, maintaining transparency was one of my main ethical strategies throughout the interviews. I began each interview by sharing detailed information about the study and myself: my identity, my academic institution, my research focus, the purpose of the research, the expected length of the interview, how the data would be utilised, and where the findings would be published.²⁶ In other words, the respondents were thoroughly briefed about the study's aims, objectives, and scope. They were also briefed about the possible knowledge contribution the study would make upon its completion.

Most of my respondents were prominent public figures who willingly gave me oral consent to record the interviews and quote their names and titles. The 'non-political' respondents did the same. However, I informed each respondent that their right to privacy, confidentiality, and anonymity would be fully respected if they chose to remain anonymous.

In addition, when some respondents were unwilling to respond to some of my questions, I did not insist further. Some respondents wanted an 'off-the-record' conversation at the end of the interview, and I respected their wishes. There were three brief, off-the-record conversations that were quite complementary in nature. These exchanges did not provide any new information; instead, the key informants summarised their earlier comments more informally. Overall, the respondents were treated with the highest respect. Special attention was paid to culturally sensitive issues, such as Nepali greeting customs, and respectful language was used throughout all communication.

As already mentioned, research ethics goes beyond ethical data collection. It also encompasses data protection, thorough analysis, and making decisions about what to publish and what to withhold (Brouneus 2011: 142). These ethical aspects were thoroughly considered in the post-data collection phases as well. For instance, the interview data were securely stored on a password-protected computer, and a backup of the data was kept on an encrypted external hard drive. In addition, I was equally careful to avoid errors, inconsistencies, and possible misquotes while transcribing, translating, and analysing the data.

Deciding whether to name the key informants was a crucial aspect of the reflexive research ethics practice applied in this research. It was also a delicate decision made with careful consideration. With legislation such as the EU's General Data Protection Regulation, anonymising all interviewees is often the default practice. However, this approach has been frequently challenged by counterarguments emphasising the interviewees' agency, as well as concerns regarding validity, reliability, and research transparency.

Although anonymity is often considered a default ethical standard in academic research, some scholars argue that it is not always beneficial or necessary (see Macleod & Mnyaka 2018). As Macleod & Mnyaka (2018) and Ellersgaard et al. (2022) have noted, anonymisation should not be applied automatically, especially in research involving political and professional elites. Moreover, ensuring anonymity can prove to be a significant challenge, especially for participants with a

²⁶ Even though each respondent was already informed about me and the study I was conducting, I provided these pieces of information at the beginning of each interview.

public profile. Even without their names, they may still be identifiable (Joseph 2023).

Having reflected on the experience of interviewing professional elites and ultra-elites in different research projects, Ellersgaard et al. (2022: 673) argue that masking interviewees can lead to conflicts regarding the presentation of results, research transparency, and the interviewees' ability to respond or engage. When sources are anonymous, it can be more difficult for other researchers to verify claims or cross-reference information, which can reduce the overall accountability and reliability of the research. For instance, taking a quote out of its original context can hinder readers' ability to make sense of the information or lead to unwarranted generalisations (Bickford & Nisker 2015).

In contrast, quoting elites by name can enhance research reliability and credibility by providing essential context, accountability, and depth to the analysis of elite behaviour and decision-making processes. For instance, when researchers attribute statements to identifiable sources, readers are provided with a clear pathway to verify claims and understand the context in which the remarks were made. This transparency not only bolsters the overall trustworthiness of the findings but also enables future scholars to trace and critique the original discourse. For example, King et al. (2021) argue that clear attribution in qualitative research significantly contributes to the replicability of studies and ensures that assertions are grounded in verifiable evidence.

Others have examined the practice of naming interviewees through the lens of interviewee agency and the power dynamics inherent in the researcher–interviewee relationship. As Guenther (2009: 413) argues, 'because names are powerful, choosing to use—or to alter—them is also an act of power'. In Ukiwo's (2011) view, the desire to safeguard the identity of the informant arises from the belief that informants are neutral, disinterested parties in social research. The researcher is then regarded as a proactive individual seeking to extract information from the informant. However, this assumption overlooks the agency and interests of informants, and that they, too, as rational actors, have agendas they wish to promote (p. 137).

Naming informants has other benefits, too. For instance, they gain the opportunity to voice their perspectives while also enabling journalists and other scholars to contact them, enhancing the possibilities for reproducibility and follow-up studies. This approach challenges researchers and fosters a more open, collaborative co-creation of knowledge (Jerolmack & Murphy 2017).

Moreover, it is not uncommon for some participants to express a preference for being identified (Wiles et al. 2008), a sentiment echoed also by some of my key informants. For instance, for scholar-activists, which were interviewed also in this study, engaging with researchers and sharing their views openly with the world is often the primary reason they agree to interviews. Therefore, the decision to anonymise them—despite their explicit, informed consent to use their names—can be perceived as patronising, stripping them of their agency, and, to some extent, dehumanising them. This approach risks diminishing their identities, undermining their names, and devaluing their struggles. As Alvesalo-Kuusi & Whyte (2018: 141) note, the protection of privacy is tied to a perception of the relative powerlessness of the research subjects, which is not quite applicable when interviewing elites.

Given this context, some scholars have advocated for maximising participants' agency in determining the level of risk they are comfortable accepting (see Joseph 2023), while others have proposed rethinking ethics through a collective

understanding of public interest (see Alvesalo-Kuusi & Whyte 2018). I, however, chose a middle-ground approach: partial anonymisation.

In this study, the dilemma of anonymity also emerged as a double-edged sword. While protecting the identities of key informants could be considered necessary to avoid potential repercussions, complete anonymity could also undermine the transparency and traceability of the information presented. Without the ability to verify the source of a claim, readers might question the authenticity of the findings, thereby weakening the study's overall impact. Undoubtedly, opaque sourcing can erode the credibility of research outputs, and this demands an approach that balances protection with transparency.

Amidst these considerations, adopting a strategy of partial anonymisation emerged as a pragmatic solution for this research. This method allowed me to safeguard sensitive information without entirely obscuring the identity of influential political figures, scholar-activists, and other key informants. By selectively anonymising certain details while still providing enough context for source verification, I attempted to maintain a balance between ethical responsibility and methodological rigour.

As with the other aspects of this study, I adopted a reflexive approach when deciding whether to include the names of respondents while quoting them. All informants provided informed consent for being quoted by name in the thesis; however, each quotation was meticulously assessed to identify any potential repercussions associated with name attribution. In cases where disclosure was deemed likely to result in harm or elicit concerns, identifying information was redacted.

In line with the University of Helsinki's data protection guide for researchers, a risk assessment based on the Finnish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity²⁷ and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) was conducted from the perspective of the key informants participating in the study. This assessment carefully evaluated the potential harm that the exposure of their identity might cause, including physical or mental distress, fraud, reputational damage, social harm, or feelings of insecurity. In addition, it considered, as per the University's guidelines, whether revealing their identity could compromise fundamental freedoms and rights, such as the right to privacy, freedom of political opinion and belief, and freedom of movement. As previously noted, my aim in undertaking this assessment was to ensure that ethical concerns were addressed while still maintaining transparency and accountability in data collection and reporting.

Moreover, when deciding to retain the names in some of the quotes, I also carefully examined whether the political elites had shared the same information with other publicly accessible sources, such as newspapers, television interviews, or other media outlets, either before or after my interviews. This cross-verification ensured that the information I attributed to them was not uniquely sensitive or private, thereby minimising potential risks. Extra care was taken when handling statements that were not already available in the public domain or information that the respondents shared almost exclusively with me. In such cases, ethical considerations and data protection principles guided the decision on whether to partially anonymise or contextualise the quotes to prevent unintended harm.

Finally, with the publication of this thesis, I recognise that a new dimension of ethical practice begins. Issues like how and where I share my findings, as well as

²⁷ Available at: https://tenk.fi/sites/default/files/2023-11/RI_Guidelines_2023.pdf

how I apply this knowledge in academic and professional settings, will hold significance. My dedication to embracing ethical practices will guide me towards making responsible choices now and in the future.

2.5 Researcher Positionality

Particularly in this type of research, it is essential to recognise how my own background and biography influenced my work. Similarly, it is important to be open and honest about how my background has shaped and influenced my choices and actions, the questions I asked and possibly avoided, and the interpretations I have presented in this thesis. My positionality also influenced the level of access I had to my key informants and the responses I received from them.

To help the reader understand my perspective and the stance I have taken in this study, it is important to cover the following elements: my background, the reasons behind my pursuit of a doctoral research project, my insights as a researcher from Nepal, and the opportunities and challenges I encountered during my fieldwork in Nepal.

I was born and raised in Nepal, shaped by the Nepali culture and identity, but also exposed to certain political narratives. My parents were members of a leftist political party, and I have clear memories of politics being a regular topic of discussion at home. I remember my father discussing India's economic blockade on Nepal in the early 1990s. That was how, at the tender age of five, I was first introduced to the subject of India's influence in Nepal. I later realised that India was part of the picture whenever there was a politically significant event of a massive scale in Nepal—a royal massacre, an armed insurgency, a people's movement, or a peace deal.

As the Maoist insurgency was at its peak in Nepal, I graduated from high school and moved to the capital city to study further. As the conflict became increasingly violent, my entire family was displaced from our ancestral village. Even though my parents were left-leaning, they did not subscribe to the Maoists' radical ideology, and as a result, the rebels often targeted them. When I was studying in the capital city, Nepal's political landscape went through a drastic makeover. A massive people's movement in 2006, in which I also participated, overthrew King Gyanendra's direct rule. This opened avenues for the Maoists to end the armed insurgency through a negotiated settlement and join peaceful mainstream politics. This was the time my political consciousness began to mould and evolve, and I started to cherish the ideals of democracy, freedom of speech, human rights, the rule of law, and good governance. I also began to see the Maoists not as a terrorist organisation—as the Nepali state had often portrayed them under the King's direct rule—but as a political force fighting to bring about positive change in Nepal. My view of the Maoists as agents of change, despite their flaws, limitations and wartime atrocities, is amply reflected in the analysis and interpretations presented in this thesis.

I left Nepal in late 2007 to study for a degree programme in social services at a university of applied sciences in Finland. I then completed a master's degree in social sciences from the University of Helsinki in 2014. Throughout these years, I have actively followed political developments in Nepal. For my master's thesis, I analysed South Sudan's post-conflict peace policies, which triggered my interest in the post-conflict issues of my own country. For my PhD, my initial idea was to study India's involvement in Nepal's peace process as a case study of South–South Cooperation. However, as I was preparing my PhD research plan in 2015, India

openly intervened in Nepal's constitution-making process, which was strongly resisted by Nepali political actors (see Chapter 6).

An enraged India then imposed an economic blockade on Nepal, creating a humanitarian catastrophe in the country. In particular, this incident motivated me to revise my research plan and take a more critical look at India–Nepal relations. When I started reading more about the subject, I gained a better understanding of the tumultuous relationship between the two countries. In the late 2000s, as a young man, I had understood that India played a positive role in ending the Maoist armed insurgency in Nepal. However, I was unaware of the inherent complexities, geopolitical and economic interests, and other subtle nuances involved in India's engagement in Nepal. As I explored India–Nepal relations more critically, themes such as historical dependency, micromanagement, resource interests, and economic and political subjugation began to emerge. This exploration and understanding have significantly shaped my thinking and the analysis presented in this thesis.

Though I have lived outside Nepal for over seventeen years, I remain a Nepali citizen and consider Nepal my home. There are both advantages and disadvantages to researching the country of your origin or one you know well (see, for instance, Ite 1997: 83, Mandiyanike 2009: 70, Mckenzie 2019). In my case, as a researcher, one of the biggest advantages was my ability to speak the local language, i.e., Nepali. As a native of the country I was researching, I possessed a deeper understanding of critical institutional and contextual factors, as well as the networks that facilitated access to key informants. In addition, my proficiency in Nepali and Hindi granted me access to a vast body of existing literature on India–Nepal relations written in these languages.

Being a native Nepali also came with some disadvantages. Mandiyanike (2009: 70) discusses suspicions regarding the purity of the researcher's intentions, a sentiment I also encountered. For instance, two influential key informants on my interview list agreed to meet with me and inquired about the purpose of my research and the research questions. After hearing my brief description, they declined to participate in the interview. They said they did not have enough time for the interview, even though their secretaries had informed me there would be enough time for an interview. Since both key informants were prominent political leaders, one being a senior government minister at the time, they may have declined the interview due to the politically sensitive nature of the topic or because they were suspicious of me as a researcher based in the West and conducting research at a Western university.

Some key informants, however, openly praised this study and thanked me for my efforts. They often mentioned that there had been many misunderstandings, especially regarding the 12-Point Understanding, and it was commendable that a Nepali researcher had decided to explore the topic more thoroughly. Some even commended me, saying that I was disseminating the success story of the Nepali peace process to a global audience through this study.

It is incontestable that my own identity and biography, at least to some extent, affect my analysis in this thesis. I am also aware that the questions I posed to the respondents were of my construction, and to a certain degree, they reflect my interests and predilections. As Harding (1986, 1987, 1991) points out, as researchers, we should be aware that our social and political positions, affiliations, and predilections affect how we conduct research. Our interests, the questions we ask and refrain from asking, the type of research design and methodology we adopt, the theoretical framework we use, the participants we choose or fail to choose, the

way we interpret or analyse data, all of this is subtly linked to who we are and what is our social and political location (Guillemin & Gillam 2004: 274).

I have utilised reflexivity to address these issues and as a method of critical reflection. This is the case in both contexts: the type of knowledge produced and the way how that knowledge is generated. In reflexive research, 'the researcher should constantly take stock of their actions and their role in the research process and subject these to the same critical scrutiny as the rest of their data' (Mason 1996: 6). In other words, a reflexive researcher goes beyond just reporting the 'facts', and engages in constructing interpretations ('What do I know?'), and questions how those interpretations were formulated ('How do I know what I know?') (Hertz 1997: 8). In the domain of research ethics, practising reflexivity involves placing oneself and one's practices under constant scrutiny, and acknowledging ethical dilemmas and the entire process of knowledge creation (McGraw et al. 2000: 68). In this context, reflexivity is an active and ongoing process that influences all aspects of research. As a researcher, I am not only aware of this, but have also applied reflexivity at every stage of this study.

2.6 Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study has a definite scope and some limitations, which must be acknowledged and addressed. First, as the title of this thesis clearly indicates, the main scope of this study is the investigation of India's engagement in Nepal's peace process and political transition, primarily between 2005 and 2017. This was the timeframe when Nepal's peace process culminated, and the country got out of a protracted political transition. My investigation and analysis primarily focus on the years mentioned above. However, whenever relevant and necessary, I also refer to events that occurred before or after the selected timeframe.

Second, in this study, I adopted a particular theoretical approach, and that naturally shaped its scope. There are numerous ways to study peace processes, third-party engagements and influences, or the complexities of modern international relations. This is also true while studying the relationship between two neighbouring countries that share much more than just a common border. Researchers can select from various theoretical frameworks and methodological perspectives to study these phenomena. Among many options and combinations, I used a triangular theoretical approach (Chapter 3), which forms the theoretical foundation of this study. The point of departure of my theoretical framework has been theoretical issues surrounding mediation and third-party engagement, followed by rising power models (South–South Cooperation and sub-imperialism), and concepts drawn from world-systems approaches and dependency theories.

Third, even though theoretical inputs have been taken from a diverse range of fields, this study, at its core, remains within the domain of global development studies. Peace and international relations research are distinct fields on their own, but can also be incorporated under the interdisciplinary umbrella of global development studies. Most of the theoretical concepts I use throughout this thesis, such as dependency and sub-imperialism, have been extensively used in the global development scholarship. Mediation, along with post-conflict peace and political issues, has also been examined through the lens of global development studies.

Moreover, this study has a few limitations that need thorough acknowledgement. First, the subject of this study—India's influence in Nepal during the peace process and political transition years—is undoubtedly complex. India, a military and economic giant and a shrewd regional player in South Asia, has always

been influential in Nepal. India's influence has been felt in Nepal in major political developments and upheavals, especially since the early 1950s.²⁸ Similarly, Nepal and India share a complex relationship that has developed over many generations and covers many areas. No set of theories or data can fully capture the intricacies and depth of the vast connection between these two countries. That fact is undeniably one of this study's major limitations. So, this study is not an exhaustive and all-encompassing examination of India–Nepal relations, but rather a small step towards understanding India's influence and actions in Nepal primarily during the peace process and political transition years (i.e., between 2005 and 2017).

Second, the period I chose to examine spans from 2005 to 2017, covering the most significant events of the peace process and the post-conflict political transition that took place during these years. However, my focus on this rather narrow timeframe leaves out some other significant incidents and developments that occurred before this period. For instance, India's role during the Maoist insurgency in Nepal (1996–2005) deserves a thorough re-evaluation, as does its nearly three-decade-long silent support of the *Panchayat* authoritarian regime in Nepal. Whenever applicable, I do refer to historically relevant cases and incidents; however, such references do not compensate for an exhaustive analysis. Hence, that becomes yet another limitation of this study.

Third, the key informants interviewed for this study were all Nepali citizens. My initial plan to include the 'Indian side of the story' by interviewing Indian leaders and diplomats was later discontinued primarily due to logistical constraints and my intention to avoid a cumbersome research design. Therefore, this study lacks a thorough representation of the Indian perspective. Similarly, the secondary data that I have used—newspaper articles and videos—were mostly written or produced by Nepali nationals. I have used works of Indian scholars, too, but their representation overall is marginal.

Fourth, most of the key informants I interviewed were public figures, many of them political elites holding prominent political posts. Despite some pitfalls, elite interviewing is widely used in political and peace research. In short, interviewing elites can pose challenges for two main reasons. On one hand, elites are 'less accessible' and, on the other hand, 'more conscious of their own importance' (Richards 1996: 200). In my elite interviews, it is possible that the narratives they provided may have been inaccurate and influenced by their prejudices or vested interests. Their statements might have been shaped by their desire to present themselves as 'patriotic' leaders who oppose any form of foreign meddling and interference in Nepal. While I took steps to address any potential impact from this, mainly by verifying their statements against facts from other reliable sources, it was impossible to confirm the authenticity of all their claims.

Before conducting the fieldwork, I was aware of the shortcomings inherent in elite interviewing. I understood that it is important for politicians to safeguard their public image and to refrain from divulging sensitive or controversial information that might put them in trouble. I attempted to address these issues by using tips and techniques recommended by other scholars engaged in elite interviewing (see, for instance, Richards 1996, Berry 2002, Harvey 2011). I included such techniques

²⁸ For instance, in February 1950, King Tribhuvan, enraged by his powerless position under the Ranas, left Nepal and sought refuge in India. A compromise was reached between the King, the Rana rulers, and representatives of the Nepali Congress, a political party fighting for democracy in Nepal. The Delhi Agreement was brokered by the then-Indian Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru. Since then, India has been steadily present in almost all major political events and processes in Nepal.

in the Interview Guide (see Appendix 3), which I consistently used while conducting the interviews. One such technique was to offer the respondents complete or partial anonymity, and yet another was to use data triangulation to improve consistency and reliability.

Fifth, as is typical with elite interviewing (see, for instance, Richards 1996), my interview sample of 18 key informants is relatively small. My initial list of respondents included over 40 key informants. However, it was impossible to interview everyone on the list for several reasons. Some key informants ignored my request for an interview, while others agreed to meet, but then found excuses to avoid being interviewed. They often claimed to be too busy or unavailable for a lengthy discussion. I conducted most of these interviews in the summer of 2017, which was an election period in Nepal, and some key informants on my list were extremely busy with election campaigns.

There are also limitations concerning the use of secondary data. Since the secondary data I used were collected online from media sources, in terms of editorial policy and practice, their editorial bias is potentially reflected in the data I used. Owners of media outlets, journalists, editors, and even bloggers can, either intentionally or unintentionally, inject their personal views, prejudices, and perspectives into the stories they present. They also have the power to decide which stories receive space or airtime and which do not. They may choose to promote certain stories while omitting others (Lazaridou & Krestel 2016). Moreover, some articles and videos that could have been included as data in this study are missing because not all of them were available online, especially from the earlier years of the peace process.

Finally, since this study primarily focuses on Nepal's peace process and political transition from 2005 to 2017, any generalisations I make in later chapters are based solely on this case study. As all peace processes and political transitions are unique, my analytical and theoretical arguments in this thesis may not apply or necessarily extrapolate to other scenarios. This is also the case because India's role as a peace mediator/facilitator in Nepal is quite distinct and does not conform to traditional notions of mediation. Moreover, India's influence in Nepal has been long and extensive, which may have shaped how India positioned itself as a 'power mediator' (see Chapter 3) to help resolve the Maoist armed insurgency in Nepal. In this context, India's role may have diverged from the established norms typically observed in mediation cases. As a result, India's role in Nepal as a 'conflict mediator' may differ from typical mediation efforts involving professional mediators, mediation organisations, and relatively independent countries that have little or no vested interests in the countries receiving mediation.

2.7 Chapter Summary: Connecting Methods to Theory and Data

This chapter provided a detailed overview of the methodological approaches adopted in this thesis. It began by outlining the ontological and epistemological foundations that underpin the research, thus crafting a clear philosophical framework for the study. The chapter then detailed the rationale behind the methodological choices made and explained how these align with the research objectives and theoretical framework presented in Chapter 3.

After that, the data collection process was described in detail, encompassing key informant interviews and media materials. Critical research considerations, including validity, reliability, ethical concerns, and the researcher's positionality, were also thoroughly discussed. Issues related to elite interviewing, the use of media

content in research, translation, and data accumulation from Internet sources were addressed. It also discussed the use of qualitative content analysis as the primary analytical method applied to both interview transcripts and media materials. This choice was driven by the nature of the collected data and the research design. Overall, this chapter provided a thorough and transparent account of the research methodology, methods, data accumulation strategies, and ethical considerations made in the research process.

3. Theoretical Framework

‘The strong do what they can, and the weak suffer what they must.’
-Thucydides, *Melian Dialogue*, 5th century B.C.

This chapter outlines the theoretical framework employed in this study. The framework integrates multiple theoretical perspectives that serve as a theoretical reference point for investigating India's engagement in Nepal's peace process and political transition from 2005 to 2017 and navigating the complex and historically tumultuous relations between the two countries. By integrating conflict mediation theories, rising power behaviour models, and world-systems approaches, I aim to create a critical and comprehensive foundation for understanding India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition, as well as the tumultuous coexistence between the two countries. My central premise in selecting these diverse theoretical strands is based on the belief that phenomena like mediation, peace processes, and political transitions should not be studied in isolation but rather within the context of global and regional power relations and broader political, geopolitical, and economic processes.

Conflict Mediation Theories: One of the focal points of this study is India's role in the Maoist-SPA 12-Point Understanding signed in New Delhi on 22 November 2005. The 12-Point Understanding was equivalent to a de facto peace agreement that essentially sketched a roadmap for a negotiated settlement of the Maoist armed insurgency and political restructuring of post-conflict Nepal. Given the ambiguity surrounding India's role in the 12-Point Understanding and the opaque nature of its involvement, this study examines India's role first through the lens of conflict mediation. Thus, the investigation begins with India's meditative or facilitative role in the Maoist-SPA 12-Point Understanding.

The first theoretical pillar, therefore, revolves around conflict mediation issues. To this end, I draw upon conflict mediation theories, focusing on four key aspects: the initiation of mediation (Why are some conflicts mediated while others are not?), the timing of mediation (What point in a conflict does mediation occur?), mediator motivation (What drives actors to take on mediating roles?), and power mediation (How does the involvement of regional powers as mediators influence the dynamics and resolution of conflicts?). This also includes examining why some conflicts receive extensive mediation while others are almost ignored.

Moreover, it also involves investigating the timing and motives behind mediators' involvement. There is a particular emphasis on how regional powers, acting as power mediators, influence the progression and resolution of conflicts. In this study, this approach is crucial for understanding India's strategic motivations and actions in the Nepali peace process and political transition.

Thus, I begin the first section of this chapter by introducing theoretical concepts surrounding peace mediation literature, emphasising ripeness theory, which sheds light on ‘ripe’ moments for conflict resolution. In the same section, I introduce mediation as a conflict resolution tool and offer a brief overview of the global mediation scenario. In addition, I bring in theoretical concepts surrounding ‘power mediation’ and ‘pure mediation’, and borrowing from works of scholars such as Saadia Touval (Touval 1975, 1987, 1992), I support the argument that mediation can be used as a foreign policy tool to serve specific foreign policy interests. I

conclude the first section by arguing that even though ‘power mediators’ might successfully forge peace agreements, their possible vested interests and long-term post-peace deal activities need critical scrutiny.

Rising Powers, South–South Cooperation, and Sub-imperialism:

This study initially aimed to analyse India’s involvement in Nepal primarily through the lens of South–South Cooperation (SSC). While this plan was not abandoned altogether, the research expands to consider India not just as a country in the Global South, but also as a rising power with significant economic and political ambitions. Theoretically, this involves examining how the so-called rise of such powers, such as India, may simultaneously challenge Western hegemony in some instances and accelerate the expansion of their hegemonic aspirations. Therefore, throughout this thesis, India is examined not only as Nepal’s powerful neighbour, but also as a rising power with a multitude of foreign policy motives and global political and economic agendas.

After discussing the origins of South–South Cooperation (SSC) and connecting them to the developing world’s long-standing hope for creating a New International Economic Order, I critically examine how the contradictory behaviour of rising powers has threatened the prospects and promises of an emancipatory SSC. To portray a clearer picture of contemporary SSC, I evaluate both sides of the argument, looking at the viewpoints for and against it. As will be apparent in my discussion, while some continue to see a tremendous ‘emancipatory’ potential in SSC, others view it merely as a way of perpetuating and creating new forms of inequality and dependency. There is growing concern that SSC is becoming increasingly crippled and overshadowed by the sub-imperialist tendencies of the so-called rising powers in the Global South. Despite its prospects and pitfalls, my central argument, however, is that SSC should not be regarded as an isolated theoretical construct or as a novel mechanism that will ‘liberate’ the developing world. Rather, it should be evaluated critically on a case-by-case basis within the broader context of the current volatile international order and the neoliberal political and economic environment. Additionally, the focus should be not only on South–South Cooperation, but also on South–South conflict.

World-Systems and Dependency Theories: In the final section of this chapter, I examine world-system and dependency approaches. In analysing India–Nepal relations, I have chosen to emphasise world-systems theories over traditional international relations paradigms such as realism, liberalism, or constructivism. While traditional international relations theories do offer valuable insights into interstate relations, world-systems and dependency theories are better suited for a long-term historical view. World-systems and dependency theories offer several advantages for my analysis. First, they provide a long-term historical perspective crucial for understanding the long and tumultuous India–Nepal relations. Second, they emphasise economic relationships and global divisions of labour, which is particularly relevant given India’s extensive economic interest and influence in Nepal (see Chapter 8). Third, core, semi-periphery, and periphery concepts effectively frame the India–Nepal relationship, with India occupying a semi-peripheral position, exerting influence over Nepal as a peripheral state.

I conclude the chapter by arguing that dependency and world-systems approaches, while less prominent in contemporary academic discourse, still hold relevance. They are useful for analysing power asymmetries between countries and for situating regional dynamics within a global context. In the context of this study, this framing enables a more comprehensive understanding of how India’s actions in Nepal connect to broader global economic and political structures. Similarly,

their emphasis on (under)development and dependency helps explain Nepal's chronic economic reliance on India and its implications, among others, for Nepal's sovereignty and self-determination. Finally, the interdisciplinary framework that world systems and dependency theories provide is useful for a more comprehensive analysis of complex situations, such as peace processes and post-conflict political transitions.

3.1 Analytical Advantages of an Integrated Approach

Before moving on to the actual discussion of the theoretical vantage points adopted, it is useful to briefly discuss the analytical advantages of an integrated approach and why such an approach was essential in the first place.

As already argued above, the complex, multifaceted nature of India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition cannot be adequately captured by any single theoretical lens. Therefore, a theoretical integration was essential. The core analytical contribution of this thesis lies not in the simple layering of these fields, but in their active integration.

- **Peace/mediation Research** provides the foundational context. It offers the vocabulary and analytical tools to understand the mechanics of mediation, political negotiation, post-conflict political transitions, and transitional justice issues.
- **Critical IR** introduces the crucial dimension of power asymmetry, specifically through the lens of sub-imperialism. In other words, it allows the analysis to move beyond a simplistic view of India as a neutral mediator to an actor with its own geopolitical interests.
- **Global Development Studies**, particularly dependency and world-systems theories, offer a macro perspective, illuminating the structural and economic underpinnings of this power relationship. They expose and help elaborate the mechanisms of unequal exchange and resource control that solidify Nepal's subordinate position.

These 'layers' are not meant to remain as separate, parallel tracks of analysis. Instead, they are woven together to create a more robust, intricate, and holistic explanatory model. The true analytical power emerges at the intersection where these theories meet and inform one another.

This integration allows me to explain, for example, that India's 'micromanagement' is not merely a diplomatic strategy (an IR concept) nor simply a form of third-party mediation (a peace research concept). Rather, it is a specific mode of intervention where geopolitical ambitions, characteristic of sub-imperialism (Critical IR), are operationalised through the direct manipulation of post-conflict mechanisms (Peace Research), and are sustained by deep-seated structures of economic dependency (Global Development Studies). I argue that these concepts are not just layered; they are causally interlinked.

Ultimately, this theoretical integration culminates in the development of the thesis's central novel concept: 'peace dependency.' This term is a direct product of the synthesis of the layered frameworks. It describes a state where the very architecture of a nation's peace process becomes contingent upon the interests and influence of a sub-imperial regional power. 'Peace dependency' would be an incomplete concept if viewed only through the lens of peace research or dependency theory alone; it derives its explanatory force precisely from the above-mentioned

integration.

Therefore, while the thesis introduces its theoretical tools in a layered fashion for the sake of clarity, its central arguments and conclusions are the product of their synthesis. This integrated approach is what makes it possible to offer a comprehensive critique of South–South relations that accounts for power, politics, and economics simultaneously. Then it provides a richer understanding of the case study than any single discipline could offer alone.

3.2 Peace Mediation and Third-Party Involvement

In peace and conflict studies, mediation has often be defined as ‘a process of conflict management where the disputants seek the assistance of, or accept an offer of help from, an individual, group, state or organisation to settle their conflict or resolve their differences without resorting to physical violence or invoking the authority of the law’ (Bercovitch et al. 1991: 8). When categorised according to objectives, there are primarily two types of mediation. One focuses on short-term ceasefire agreements, which are initiated with the obvious aim of easing hostilities and preventing the loss of lives, and the second type focuses on the long-term goals of a peace deal and broader peace processes (DeRouen & Bercovitch 2012: 67).

Mediation has been used for centuries to facilitate peace negotiations and find peaceful solutions to conflicts. For instance, in modern times, the United Nations has been active in various mediation processes and continues to consolidate its presence in the international conflict mediation scene.²⁹ Among others, the UN has established a separate unit for mediation, the Mediation Support Unit. Other multilateral organisations, such as the EU and the African Union, also have conflict mediation programmes that facilitate dialogue, mediation, negotiation, and post-negotiation peacebuilding work. Some non-governmental organisations, such as the CMI- Martti Ahtisaari Peace Foundation based in Finland or the Swiss Peace Foundation in Switzerland, dedicate most activities to peace mediation, facilitation, and negotiation work. States also practise mediation as part of foreign policy. For decades, countries such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Russia, India, and South Africa have been influential players in international mediation (see Figure 4). Apart from economic, diplomatic, and military means, mediation has also been used as a tool for foreign intervention.

There is a growing consensus among scholars that mediation has, overall, a positive impact on conflict mitigation and resolution. Even in cases in which peace accords are not signed, mediation opens avenues for ceasefires, and as a result, cases of hostilities and casualties decline and opportunities for peace agreements increase, which ultimately pave the way for a successful conflict settlement. Reflecting on the importance of mediation, Bercovitch (2007: 291) argues that:

Success may be achieved if the parties in conflict feel empowered or feel that their concerns were addressed respectfully. There may be no successful outcome (in any sense of the word), but the parties still feel they have achieved success in the process. In the same way, there may be a process of mediation marred by many procedural disagreements and dissatisfactions, but it may lead to a cessation of violence and even a formal agreement.

The availability of mediators can also help transform intractable conflicts and reach peace agreements (Bercovitch 2004). Mediators bring unique skills and

²⁹ For more on UN mediation, peacekeeping, and preventive diplomacy initiatives, see Doyle & Sambanis (2006).

perspectives that can facilitate dialogue between opposing parties, fostering an environment conducive to understanding and compromise. In short, mediation is beneficial and should be promoted. However, the methods used and the intentions behind require careful examination, as the effectiveness of mediation can significantly depend on the approach taken and the underlying motivations of those facilitating the process.

3.2.1 Can Mediators Make Conflicts Ripe for Resolution?

From the perspective of mediation research, two questions are especially important as I explore the origins of the 12-Point Understanding, which ultimately initiated the Nepali peace process. First, what factors made the Maoist armed insurgency ‘ripe for resolution’ at that particular time? Second, did India, as a power mediator, use power diplomacy or other means, such as diplomatic leverage, to unite Nepal’s two opposition forces and create conditions favourable for conflict resolution? These questions are also crucial for understanding why some mediation efforts succeed while others fail and how foreign powers potentially exploit moments of ripeness in conflict resolution.

Much has been written about the preconditions of peace negotiations and when conflicts are ready to be negotiated and settled. The concept of ‘ripeness’ or ripeness theory, as it is generally known, was proposed by William Zartman (see, for instance, Zartman 1989, 2000, 2001, Zartman & Touval 1985). It remains highly influential in peace and mediation research. Other scholars have further developed ripeness theory over the years (see, for instance, Haass 1988, Rubin 1991, Stedman 1996, Pruitt 2005). Ripeness theory argues that conflicts can be negotiated and settled once they reach a ‘ripe’ moment. In such a context, the so-called ‘ripe moment’ can be construed as a psychological state of the warring parties, encouraging them to engage in bilateral or any mediated negotiation. Zartman (1989) argued that since the causes of conflicts are primarily local, conflict management and resolution strategies must depend on perception, creation, and the use of ‘ripe’ moments, which can often be fleeting.

Zartman (1989: 291, 2000: 229) further elaborates that two specific conditions are necessary for ‘ripeness’ to occur. First, a Mutually Hurting Stalemate (MHS)—a condition of costly deadlock in which warring parties cannot benefit by escalating the conflict—is necessary. In such cases, the desire to negotiate can be further strengthened by a recent, impending, or imminent mutual catastrophe (IMC). Second, a mutual perception that a negotiated solution is possible and that a way out can be found that is just and satisfactory is also required.

Crocker (1992) and Mitchell (1995) supplement the concept of Mutually Hurting Stalemate (MHS) by offering a counter possibility: a Mutually Enticing Opportunity (MEO). As opposed to a hurting stalemate, MEO focuses on leaders’ mindset and their ability to recognise and adopt an opportunity that is mutually enticing for both parties. Scholars such as Pruitt & Olczak (1995) and Ohlson (1998) have identified the importance of MEO not necessarily as an alternative but as a complement to an MHS. They argue that once an MHS pushes conflicting parties into negotiations, an MEO must provide prospects for an attractive future so that negotiations do not falter. Zartman (2005), too, accepts that the concept of MEO is useful but argues that such cases are few and are the result of a third party or negotiating party’s actions. He believes they do not result from external situations, such as in an MHS.

While a valuable concept for understanding conflicts and their prognosis and possibly helpful in resolving longstanding disputes, ripeness theory has been

criticised on many grounds—including for its ‘limited explanatory power’ (Coleman et al. 2008: 4). Pruitt (2005), for instance, criticises ripeness theory for its excessive focus on the psychological states of actors only. He suggests a shift from ‘ripeness’ to ‘readiness’, which would focus on joint psychological states and provide explanatory and predictive powers. This approach emphasises factors beyond pain and cost, as proposed by Zartman (1989, 2000). Pruitt (2005) further argues that other factors, such as motivation and leaders’ optimism, might be crucial in encouraging warring parties to find a solution through dialogue and mediation.

O’kane (2006: 283) offers a more elaborate critique of ripeness theory and argues that the theory is based on a one-size-fits-all model and is ‘too prescriptive’. In his view, ripeness theory attempts to ‘ascribe certainty and clarity in situations that are often uncertain and confused’. In addition, he points out the danger of inaction if the perception is that only ripe conflicts would be successfully negotiated. That, in his opinion, would offer an excuse for inaction. Similarly, his criticism of ripeness theory includes its inability to provide clear indications for spotting ripeness. The argument is that since only ripe conflicts can be solved, there is no point in attempting to solve other, supposedly ‘unripe’ conflicts, whereas the attempt must be to solve every ongoing conflict (O’kane 2006).

Lederach (2003) evaluates ripeness theory from a practitioner’s perspective. He argues that ‘ripeness’ in conflict is difficult to spot, because conflicts do not always follow a linear path but are both linear and circular. He argues that ‘the roadway of protracted conflict, it seems, may be more akin to dynamic, nearly amoeba-like spaces than the linear and predictable development of fruit’ (p. 32). Reflecting on his experience as a mediator of various peace negotiation processes worldwide, he emphasises that moments that are deemed ‘ripe’ might end up without producing any concrete progress, whereas unexpected progress or a breakthrough might emerge amidst hopeless deadlocks and frustrating situations.

He equates the concept of ripeness to a ‘rearview mirror’, which is hopelessly predictive in highly unpredictable situations and, thereby, has a ‘limited metaphor for practice’ (p. 31). Another concern that he raises is about the perception of ripeness itself, which is highly subjective. For him, ripeness is ‘something perceived by outsiders with the luxury of dispassionate facts and factors’ (p. 33). Beyond discussing the very existence of ‘ripeness’, other scholars (see, for instance, Rubin 1991, Hampson 1996) underscore the implementation part, arguing that the right moments need to be seized if they are to have any practical utility.

Although ripeness theory, or the concept of ripeness itself, has several limitations, it is a useful tool for assessing, analysing, and understanding conflicts, their developments, inherent dynamics, and the possibility of an ultimate resolution. Despite its flaws, it has practical applications in the real world. When conflicts present fleeting ‘ripe’ moments, they can be seized for meaningful outcomes. My theoretical curiosity, especially in relation to the subject of this study, does not focus on questioning the existence of ‘ripeness’ or highlighting its limitations. Instead, I am particularly interested in the role of external actors in strengthening or weakening the ‘ripeness’ effect. The key question is whether third parties can make a conflict ‘ripe’ for resolution, using tools, strategies, and exercising the power they have.

Scholars have argued that ripeness can be enhanced through deliberate actions—often augmented and employed by mediators. Crocker (1992: 471), for instance, emphasises that ‘the absence of ripeness does not tell us to walk away and do nothing. Rather, it helps us to identify obstacles and suggests ways of handling them and managing the problem until resolution becomes possible’. Coleman

(1997) suggests avenues for intervention and advocates for creating a ripe moment by presenting a social-psychological model for conceptualising ripeness. His model attempts to redefine ripeness ‘at the individual level as a commitment to change the direction of the normative social processes of the relations toward de-escalation’ (p. 81). Hancock (2001) recommends a combination of policy options and intervention actions for an enhanced ripeness. Aggestam (2005) makes similar recommendations, primarily focusing on enhancing motivation and opportunities for warring parties.

A few scholars have also examined the potential contributions of third-party mediators in fostering ripeness. They argue that third parties can influence and strengthen the conflicting parties’ convictions and perception of a ripe moment, often using communication or power (Aggestam 2002a, 2002b, 2005: 280, Bercovitch 2002). Third parties may even resort to coercive bargaining to impact power distribution, which might change adversaries’ expectations about bargaining and outcomes (Princen 2014). Even though initiated by third parties, a successful shift in the cost-benefit calculation of adversaries consolidates the perception of a ripe moment, which can trigger a transition from escalation to de-escalation (Aggestam 2005: 280–81). At times, it could indeed be ‘the whip of external pressure and the pain of unacceptable alternatives’ (Rubin 1992: 252) that ultimately drives warring parties to the negotiating table.

These concepts are valuable for understanding external interventions in conflict mediation processes. They, however, still lack some clarity. The issue of how mediators—or external actors disguising themselves as mediators or facilitators— influence and intervene to create ‘ripeness’ requires further investigation. Given that ripeness, as Zartman (1989, 2000) and others have suggested, is largely a psychological construct, it is crucial to explore how external actors, such as regional powers, may employ psychological or other tactics to persuade conflicting parties to believe in the existence of a ‘ripe’ moment and ultimately create a conducive environment for conflict resolution.

Spotting ripeness may still be a tricky issue, but the use of incentives to bring conflicting parties or dissidents to the negotiating table is a well-established practice. Numerous scholars have examined, documented, and advocated for such incentives (see, for instance, Cortright 1997, 2001³⁰, Vines 1998³¹, Bernauer et al. 1999³², and Klimesova 2016³³). While incentives and deterrence, including economic sanctions, have been extensively researched, the role of other subtle and covert strategies, such as power diplomacy and their use to influence outcomes in mediation and negotiation processes, remains poorly understood. Their potential contribution to creating ‘ripe’ moments also remains unclear. India’s role as an external facilitator in initiating the Nepali peace process—specifically through its involvement in the 12-Point Understanding—is a central focus of my investigation. The issue of incentives and external pressure for compromise in this particular context is examined in detail in the latter chapters (see Chapters 8 and 9).

³⁰ Cortright argues that even economic sanctions cannot be successful when incentives are lacking.

³¹ Alex Vines explores how Mozambique’s 1992 peace deal was shaped by financial incentives paid to insurgents by the chief executive of a UK-based multinational company.

³² They examine the positive role of incentives in Ukraine’s decision to turn over its nuclear arsenal and join the Nuclear Non-proliferation Treaty as a nonnuclear-weapon state in 1994.

³³ Martina Klimesova analyses the negotiation processes in Sri Lanka (Eelam), Indonesia (Aceh), and the Philippines (Mindanao) in depth. She concludes that third-party incentives linked, especially to the core conflict issues, are beneficial.

3.3 Conflict Mediation in Practice

External involvement in conflict mediation is a debated area, but it is not a new practice. Contrary to popular belief, and despite many organisations in the field, most conflicts worldwide do not receive mediation. When looked at on a global scale, mediation trends appear skewed and uneven. However, this does not indicate that there should be more actors in the field. Crocker et al. (2001: 51) call the mediation field ‘a crowded stage’ to indicate actors’ growth in the international mediation arena. However, the growth of actors does not automatically mean that all conflicts receive mediation interest and that all actors are actively engaged in conflict mediation.

Relying on the data sets of the Uppsala Conflict Data Program³⁴, Svensson & Onken (2015: 68) demonstrated that occurrences of conflict mediation are falling. They show that while 33% of conflicts were mediated in 1995, the mediation rate in 2010 was a mere 7%. Similarly, between 1989 and 2013, only an average of 11% of the total conflict dyad years were mediated (see Figure 2).

Lundgren & Svensson (2020) found similar results and argued that despite the improved preparedness of international mediators, the proportion of armed conflicts receiving mediation has decreased due to a mismatch between supply and demand in the international mediation arena, with many conflicts remaining beyond mediators’ reach. Both findings demonstrate that, contrary to popular belief, mediation as a means of conflict resolution is still underutilised.

Greig & Diehl (2012: 71–72) show that the global pattern of conflict mediation is uneven, as some conflicts are ‘under-mediated’ while others are ‘over-mediated’. In a similar observation, Svensson & Onken (2015: 69–70) find that between 1989 and 2013, Europe received the most third-party mediation (25%), while conflict dyad years mediated in the Middle East in the same period were just a little over 5%.

Figure 2 Percentage of Mediated Conflict Dyad Years (1989–2013). Source: Svensson & Onken (2015:67).

³⁴ The Uppsala Conflict Data Program has recorded ongoing violent conflicts since the 1970s and has extensive databases on different conflict issues. Visit ucdp.uu.se for more information.

They also find that minor conflicts and conflicts over territory were less likely to be mediated, while conflicts over government received more mediation attempts.

While the attempts and occurrences of mediation are declining, external engagement and interventions are on a different track. Regan et al. (2009) found that 69% of conflicts in Africa between 1989 and 1999 involved some form of external intervention. Their observation shows that while military interventions seemed to have declined, cases of diplomatic and economic interventions were rising (see Figure 3).

It is increasingly clear that mediation is linked with broader military, economic, and diplomatic interests and interventions of third parties. Third parties can use mediation as a political and tactical tool to halt or manipulate a conflict situation. The motives in such cases might surpass the obvious aim of bringing peace. The behaviour of mediators in post-peace agreement contexts has received relatively little scholarly attention. In particular, the question of what mediators do after a successful negotiation and the signing of a peace deal remains underexplored and warrants closer examination.

Despite the research community's general agreement on the positive impact of mediation in resolving conflicts, disagreements persist regarding the types of mediators and the methods they use to mediate. Previous research shows that not all conflicts appeal to mediators equally. The regional imbalances in mediation (as demonstrated in Svensson & Onken 2015) and a wide range of intervention strategies applied (see Regan et al. 2009) indicate the same: only some conflicts garner mediators' interests, while others are left to deteriorate.

Figure 3 Conflict intervention by decade. Source: Regan et al. (2009: 143).

3.3.1 Mediators' Motives and Mandate

As previously noted, this study examines India's role as a mediator or facilitator in the Nepali peace process. It explores India's motivations for engaging in mediation and the underlying interests that go beyond this particular role. Several scholars have investigated the motives of mediators and explained the choices and behavioural patterns of such actors. A plethora of academic research suggests that mediation overall has a positive impact on resolving conflicts with positive outcomes (see, for instance, Dixon 1994, Regan & Stam 2000, Walter 2002, Rauchhaus 2006).

However, more critical studies focus on the motives of mediators beyond peacemaking. They often argue that the underlying motive for peace mediation is to serve the mediators' own self-interests. Cunningham (2010), for instance, argues that in any form of external intervention, the main motive of mediators is typically to pursue their own agenda. Though accepting the self-interest part, Zartman & Touval (1996: 446) propose that while the primary interest of mediators and third parties might be to serve their own self-interest, they are motivated by a desire to make peace as well. They argue:

Third parties mediate based on their desire to make peace, and their own self-interest. Self-interest is the primary motivation for states. States are motivated by both defensive and offensive interests. Defensive interests include promoting international stability, and protecting the mediating nation's foreign interests. Often nations will attempt to mediate a conflict in order to prevent rival powers from intervening and expanding their influence.

In addition, they argue that non-state organisations that emphasise peacemaking as their primary motive are also motivated by 'an interest to upholding their reputations' (p. 450). These organisations, such as the UN, are often 'interested in a particular outcome, not because it affects them directly, but because they believe in its inherent desirability' (Zartman & Touval 1996: 450). Since attention, exposure, and reputation all matter, some mediators may find mediation appealing when 'it is least likely to be successful' (Greig 2005: 264). In addition, mediators are motivated to mediate when conflict continuance might affect their political interests (Bercovitch 2011: 74). This perspective is particularly relevant to this study as India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition began at a time when the Maoist armed insurgency began to hurt India's own interests (see Chapter 9).

Ultimately, it is important to recognise that mediation is inherently a political act, and mediators, as political actors, often carry a range of political motives and interests. As Bercovitch (2011: 74) puts it, mediators 'engage in mediation and expend resources because they expect to resolve a conflict and gain something from it'. It could be their international reputation or leverage in foreign policy actions. As Touval (1992) explains, mediation can work as a policy instrument which mediators can exploit to serve their own interests without causing too much suspicion and opposition.

3.3.2 Power vs Pure Mediators, and Mediation as a Foreign Policy Tool

Some scholars have attempted to define and differentiate between 'power' mediators and 'pure' mediators. They have also discussed how mediation can influence power diplomacy and broader foreign policy. Power mediators often include 'great powers, colonial powers, and neighbouring states' that initiate

mediation attempts, whereas ‘representatives of international, regional, or non-governmental organisations, individuals, and small and distant states, are classified as pure mediators’ (Svensson 2007: 230). Pure mediators often lack the power to influence situations outside the negotiation situation and limit themselves to strategies such as ‘reasoning, unforced persuasion, the control of information and the generation of alternatives’ (Harris & Reilly 1998: 109). Power mediators, however, can exercise a range of other strategies and options, such as ‘incentives and punishments’ to ‘persuade the parties to obey’, to adopt flexibility, and accept a compromise (Harris & Reilly 1998: 109).

Saadia Touval (1992, 2003) is a key advocate of the idea that mediation serves as a foreign policy tool, particularly when used by major powers. By situating mediation within a realist structure of international relations, he argues that powerful actors in the international system might use mediation as a foreign policy instrument to promote their self-interest or further their goals. In his view, big powers can use mediation as a tool to serve their defensive as well as expansionist interests (Touval 1992: 232–33). He further argues:

Because of their extensive global involvements, many conflicts in various parts of the globe are perceived by the superpowers as affecting their interests. Thus, they will often be motivated to intervene, and may choose mediation as a suitable instrument for intervention. Their political influence, and their vast material capabilities, enable them to apply sticks and carrots, and provide them with important resources for engaging in mediation (p. 233).

This discrepancy in the interests of big powers and their rivalries leads to a situation whereby conflicts in regions in which superpowers do not compete are neglected. However, intervention and peacekeeping attempts become increasingly common in areas where superpower influence and rivalry persist (Touval 1992: 247). This notion helps explain the ‘over-mediation’ and ‘under-mediation’ patterns in international conflict mediation (see Greig & Diehl 2012, Svensson & Onken 2015, Lundgren & Svensson 2020).

Based on the theoretical observations made above, it is argued that the involvement of third parties, especially regional powers and superpowers, in mediation, negotiation and broader peacebuilding processes might be unavoidable, inevitable or even desirable in some cases. However, mediators’ motives and possible vested interests demand careful and critical scrutiny. Particularly, when ‘mediation serves as a means toward achieving certain primary foreign policy goals’ (Touval 2003: 93), mediation’s aftershocks are likely to extend beyond a successful peace deal.

A key takeaway from this section is that mediation has been employed as a foreign policy tool by major powers, and they continue to do so. While mediation per se is beneficial for conflict resolution, it has other implications when used, particularly as a foreign policy tool. India, the focus of this study, is a significant power with global ambitions, and it has both officially and unofficially engaged itself in diplomatic interventions and mediated conflicts, particularly in the South Asian region, for many years (see Figure 4, Banerji 2023). Analysing India’s involvement in Nepal through the lens of mediation research sheds light on how major powers, particularly rising powers from the Global South, leverage mediation within broader global and regional political and economic contexts.

Figure 4 Diplomatic interventions in conflicts and frequent interveners. It covers 438 diplomatic interventions in 68 conflicts, from 1945 to 1999. (Source: Regan et al. 2009:140)

Mediation does not take place in isolation; it is deeply shaped by its surrounding contexts. This highlights the need for a broader approach to examining the interconnections between mediation and other influencing factors. For instance, to fully grasp India's role in Nepal's conflict resolution, it is essential to look beyond traditional mediation research. In the following sections, I will do just that—move beyond mediation and introduce other theoretical perspectives that help situate India's role in Nepal's peace process and political transition. Given their shared status as Global South countries, I first examine South–South Cooperation as a framework for understanding the relations between India and Nepal. I then introduce other critical theoretical perspectives, such as sub-imperialism and dependency theories, as more suitable frameworks for analysing the complex and often turbulent relationship between the two countries. This approach will help clarify India's role in Nepal's peace and political transition and beyond.

3.4 South–South Cooperation: An Emancipatory Agenda and an Avenue for Exploitation?

The initial aim of this study was to analyse India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition by using the theoretical framework of South–South Cooperation (SSC). In other words, India's involvement would be examined mainly as an example of contemporary South–South Cooperation. As the research progressed, the theoretical framework was expanded to incorporate more critical theoretical perspectives. Nevertheless, the SSC perspective was also retained due to its relevance and pervasive use in contemporary academic discourses, particularly in global development studies, which I am a student of. In addition, its increasing strategic use by the so-called rising powers of the Global South also necessitates the critical investigation and thorough re-evaluation of SSC.

Traditionally envisioned as a practice aimed at consolidating solidarity among countries of the Global South and empowering them through mutual support, SSC has often been heralded for its potential to foster cooperation and development for developing countries like Nepal. However, the critical question regarding South–South Cooperation today revolves around its practical application. In particular, two issues are at the crux of contemporary SSC. First, how powerful states in the Global South use SSC to advance their political and economic agendas, and second, whether countries with vastly different characteristics—such as size, power, population, economy, and military capacity—like Nepal and India—can genuinely engage in cooperation under the SSC framework.

The potential of SSC to foster South–South solidarity and promote equitable development stands in contrast to the risk of perpetuating existing hierarchies and inequalities. Therefore, a critical examination of both its opportunities and challenges is essential, which I attempt to do in this section. I start by examining the various arguments for and against SSC. I argue that SSC cannot be viewed in isolation from the wider global political and economic context, which includes power imbalances, conflicts, and existing economic disparities.

In other words, SSC should not be regarded as an autonomous or idealised framework detached from external contexts. Therefore, its success or failure is deeply intertwined with the broader global political and economic realities in which it is embedded and conditioned to operate. It is evident that SSC does not seek to radically transform existing global economic and political paradigms. Rather than dismantling the current system and constructing a new one, it aims to find solutions within the prevailing framework. This orientation, however, inherently places significant limitations on its scope.

3.4.1 Historical Aspirations and Contemporary Challenges

South–South Cooperation, particularly in the arena of international development, and South–South Relations, usually in the domain of International Relations, broadly indicate the cooperation or relations between countries in the Global South. Such cooperation includes partnerships, collaboration, and coordination in economic, political, social, cultural, and technical sectors. In recent years, SSC has gained significant attention at international development forums, and global development agencies have integrated the concept into their policy frameworks. For instance, the United Nations has established a separate body—the United Nations Office for South–South Cooperation—to promote and facilitate South–South and triangular (North–South–South) cooperation. Since 2004, the UN has also

celebrated 16 December as the International Day for South–South Cooperation (UNOSSC 2017).

Instances of SSC have been seen particularly in the areas of trade and foreign direct investments (FDIs). For instance, South–South trade increased from USD 600 billion in 1995 to USD 5.3 trillion in 2021, and its volume is higher than that of North–South trade (UNCTAD 2023). South–South trade in recent years has not only outperformed both global and North–South trade, but it is also believed to have contributed to reviving the world economy after the 2008 financial crisis (Priyadarshi 2015). SSC has typically flourished in areas of economic cooperation, technology flow, and sharing technical knowledge for capacity-building projects in the developing world. Policy recommendations have been made to broaden the scope of SSC and extend it into areas of peace and security, too (see, for instance, Mathur 2014).

The origins of SSC can be traced back to the Bandung Conference of 1955, at which newly independent Asian and African nations convened to discuss cooperative potentials among developing countries. This initiative led to the establishment of the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development in 1964, resulting in the creation of the Group of 77 to foster solidarity among the Global South countries. In 1974, the UN General Assembly, in its resolution 3251 (XXIX), approved the establishment of a special unit to ‘promote technical cooperation’ among developing countries (UNOSSC 2017). In the same year, developing countries presented their demand for a New International Economic Order at the United Nations. This period marked the height of the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM), as many developing countries were increasingly fed up with the bipolar global division and their unequal representation in the international system. Despite gaining political independence, they had realised that structures of subjugation persisted, albeit in new forms. The prevailing mindset among developing countries was that the path to overcoming their challenges lay in uniting and acting in solidarity. Thus, the concept of SSC somehow emanated from the NAM’s foundations and the collective aspiration of the developing countries to reshape the global order. The Buenos Aires Plan of Action for Promoting and Implementing Technical Cooperation among Developing Countries, adopted in 1978, further institutionalised SSC. In 1980, the United Nations ultimately established a High-level Committee on the Review of Technical Cooperation among Developing Countries, which was renamed in 2004 as the High-level Committee on South–South Cooperation (see Prashad 2007, Besada et al. 2019).

Although historically based on mobilising developing country solidarity, SSC has been revitalised by emerging economies primarily to advance their economic and strategic interests. With the political and economic rise of a handful of countries from the Global South, such as China, India, Brazil, and others, cross- and sub-regional cooperation in the Global South began to increase rapidly, particularly since the 1990s (Ekoko & Benn 2002). Though SSC was traditionally centred around anti-colonial political solidarity, technical cooperation, or the advocacy for a New International Economic Order, in later years, the focus shifted to trade and foreign direct investments, infrastructure financing, and development cooperation and aid programmes (Mawdsley 2012).

For instance, China adopted the SSC discourse in the early 2000s to differentiate itself from the traditional North–South cooperation model represented by the OECD’s Development Assistance Committee (Gülseven 2023). In 2015, it also established a separate fund, the Global Development and South–South Cooperation Fund, to finance its SSC projects. Similarly, India has also

adopted and leveraged SSC rhetoric extensively. For instance, it hosts annual Voice of Global South summits and has established the India–UN Development Partnership Fund. Through this fund, it has implemented projects in more than 50 developing countries, including in Nepal (UNOSSC 2024). Both China and India heavily frame their foreign aid programmes under South–South Cooperation (SSC) and actively use SSC rhetoric in their foreign policy communication. The ultimate aim of these initiatives, however, appears to be the enhancement of their regional and global influence.

Unsurprisingly, South–South Cooperation, both as a theoretical concept and a practical approach, has garnered widespread admiration as well as harsh criticism. The divided arguments often come from two camps. Some view SSC as a noble idea, a new source of hope, and a potential means of fostering self-reliance and independence for the Global South (see, for instance, Mawdsley 2012, Carmody 2013, Cheru 2016, Muhr 2016). Those in the opposing camp see SSC as a set of sugar-coated rhetoric that resembles a new scramble for Africa or thrives on the exploitation of poorer and weaker countries in the Global South (see Southall & Melber 2009, Moyo 2012). For some, SCC amounts to a form of neo-dependency (Aniche 2015), or even sub-imperialism (Bond 2015).

There seems to be a clear tendency among those romanticising SSC to view it as a single, homogeneous entity. However, as countries in the Global South vary greatly in size, power, and capabilities, SSC exhibits significant variation. For instance, Nepal’s collaboration with a similarly positioned country, such as Bangladesh or Bhutan, will differ greatly from its relationship with India—a regional power actively involved in the global superpower race. These variations mean that not all forms of SSC are created equal. Scholars who have glorified SSC often overlook these discrepancies and fail to address the vast asymmetries between countries in the Global South. There is a clear need to consider these power dynamics along with the political and economic realities when analysing South–South Cooperation, particularly within regional contexts.

South-South Cooperation has its roots in the aspirations of developing countries for a New International Economic Order, their desire to construct and participate in a non-aligned foreign policy movement, and their frustrations with underdevelopment and a persistent state of dependence, even after years of political independence from colonial powers. Today’s SSC, as a phrase, might still carry some connotation of solidarity, development, and progressive cooperation in the Global South. However, it has not certainly evolved into what was once expected. Nearly seven decades since the Bandung Conference, it is evident that South–South Cooperation has fallen short of its initial promises and aspirations. While certain sectors, particularly trade, have thrived under SSC, its original emancipatory vision has eroded significantly. Similarly, the non-alignment agenda that once defined it has largely been abandoned.

As Jouili (2021) has argued, contemporary South–South Cooperation has abandoned the emancipatory, sovereignty-driven vision of the Bandung project in favour of a neoliberal paradigm that renders the state apolitical and development challenges merely technical. At the same time, emerging powers, despite their growing institutional roles, primarily seek further integration into global capitalism and perpetuate traditional centre–periphery polarisation (Jouili 2021).

Indeed, South–South Cooperation has suffered from a mix of internal disparities (in capacity and institutional frameworks) and external shifts in the global economic and political landscape (particularly the end of the Cold War and the subsequent rise of neoliberal economic policies). The resulting environment has

often favoured more immediate, bilateral, or regionally confined partnerships over the broader, multilateral solidarity that was once envisioned for the Global South. As a result, while some countries in the Global South have ascended the global political and economic ladder by leaps and bounds, for other developing countries, widespread poverty, various forms of inequality, conflict, underdevelopment, and a form of frustration and hopelessness, which were present at the onset of the SSC, are still a stark reality.

Rising powers of the Global South, such as India, China, and Brazil, are significant contributors to the disappointing progress of the SSC solidarity agenda. While they continue to use SSC rhetoric more than ever, they have effectively sidelined South–South solidarity and the principles of the NAM. Instead, they appear to be actively engaging in hegemonic competition and mirroring the practices of traditional global powers. As a result, the developing countries that once saw an emancipatory potential in SSC have ended up in a situation in which the South–South rhetoric is increasingly used by powerful countries in the Global South, mainly to advance their own strategic political and economic interests. In this context, two things are clear. First, it is crucial to distinguish between rhetoric and reality. Do countries such as China and India genuinely represent the interests of the developing world, despite their firm assertions to do so? Second, accusations that rising powers in the Global South are increasingly behaving as sub-imperialist actors must be taken seriously and investigated thoroughly.

3.4.2 A Framework for Solidarity or Sub-Imperialism?

As argued above, there is a need for a thorough re-evaluation of South–South Cooperation, particularly in relation to its use by the so-called rising powers of the Global South. The accusation that these powers are employing SSC merely as a rhetorical tool to strengthen their own positions in the global power hierarchy is a serious and highly relevant question for this study (see Bond & Garcia 2015, Bond et al. 2021). An equally pertinent question is whether the economic and political ascent of a select few countries in the Global South holds significance for the emancipatory South–South project that many passionately advocate and continue to place their faith in (see, for instance, Mawdsley 2012, Carmody 2013, Cheru 2016, Muhr 2016, Bergamaschi et al. 2017).

The extent to which the rising powers of the Global South challenge the dominant political and economic governance systems remains a contentious issue. While some continue to see an emancipatory element in the so-called rise of the rising powers from the Global South, for others, they are strongly positioned or are simply part of the West-centred neoliberal world order (see, for instance, Gray & Murphy 2013, Vanaik 2013, Bond & Garcia 2015, Bond et al. 2021).

To begin with, events such as China's entry into the World Trade Organisation in 2001 indicated that 'rather than proposing an alternative to the US-centred Washington Consensus, China may conversely be in the process of internalising the rules of the West' (Beeson 2013: 188). At the fundamental levels, there appears to be no substantive ideological or intellectual rivalry among major global powers such as the United States, China, and Russia. As Peters (2023) has argued, they all operate within the broader paradigm of capitalism's political-economic structure and the intellectual foundations of secular liberalism. However, each country interprets these concepts differently and seeks to align them with its specific geopolitical interests.

Similar arguments can be made about 'middle power' countries such as India,

Brazil, and South Africa. They all seem very unpredictable in their dealings with the West. Bond & Garcia (2015), for instance, explore the contrarian positions of the BRICS within the world system. They argue that the rise of the 'Global South (and East)' has been uncertain, as it is sometimes cooperative with and sometimes antagonistic to the traditional powers. Providing numerous examples to support their claims, they challenge the notion that the BRICS bloc is an anti-imperialist force seeking to, what they call, 'overturn tables at the proverbial temple' (p. 1). Furthermore, they demonstrate how the BRICS have cooperated to maintain the neoliberal status quo. Examples include BRICS funding the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and establishing their own New Development Bank, with an IMF-style Contingent Reserve Arrangement. In addition, they also point out the neoliberal collaboration between Washington and the BRICS countries in global climate negotiations. Similarly, in 2016, China initiated the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank, the world's second-largest multilateral development bank and international financial institution, whose co-founders included the wealthiest European countries and the Bretton Woods Institutions (Bond & Garcia 2015).

Other scholars have made similar observations and have argued that the so-called rise of the Global South, often associated with the BRICS bloc, or IBSA (India, Brazil, and South Africa) is 'located within the Western global hegemony' and that their actions are aimed at securing a position at the 'table of global neoliberal economic governance' (Gray & Murphy 2013: 185). Vanaik (2013: 195–212) similarly argues that the firm discourse of South–South Cooperation adopted by rising powers in the Global South, like India and China, is merely rhetoric. Their aim, he emphasises, is not to challenge but to secure a stronger position within the US-centred world order.

One key characteristic of these rising powers is their unpredictability in dealing with established global powers. Their behaviour is marked by an interplay of cooperation as well as confrontation. While sometimes aligning with global powers on certain issues, when it suits their ambitions, at times, they also assert their independence and challenge the status quo. As Bond & Garcia (2015) have pointed out, there are several examples, for instance, of the BRICS bloc occasionally adopting 'inter-imperial' stances against Western powers. Among others, BRICS members have denied demands by Western countries to impose stricter intellectual property controls, especially in patents on medicines. Similarly, some BRICS leaders boldly challenged Washington in the Edward Snowden case. They also implicitly and collectively supported Russia in the conflict over Crimea (Bond & Garcia 2015). Moreover, China and India's deviation from the Western stance on Russia's invasion of Ukraine is another recent example (Menon & Rumer 2022).

Furthermore, BRICS' efforts to establish their own currency can be seen as a move to create an alternative, non-dollar-based global financial system. To some extent, this reflects their desire to reduce dependency on the USD and reshape the existing international financial order (Liu & Papa 2022). The most important question from this study's perspective, however, is how these rising powers engage with weaker, less powerful countries in their regions. In other words, how do countries like India and Brazil treat countries like Nepal and Venezuela?

The economic and political domination of BRICS' less-developed neighbours is a growing and legitimate concern. Since the so-called rise of most of these rising powers is largely based on an extractive, high-carbon economic model, their less powerful neighbours are prone to economic and resource exploitation. In addition, increasing evidence shows that minorities and marginalised populations within their own borders also suffer at the hands of their rulers. One example being that

the criminalisation of social movements and the oppression of dissidents in the BRICS countries are worse than in the G7 (Bond & Garcia 2015). China, for instance, continue to face international condemnation for its repression of the Uyghur ethnic minorities and those associated with the Free Tibet Movement. India faces equally serious accusations of ‘internal colonialism’ (see Roy 2011, Dey 2019) and has been lashed for its poor treatment of minorities, and for committing serious human rights violations in states like Kashmir and Manipur (see Chapter 8).

Some scholars have explored how the geopolitical interests of rising powers are reflected in their foreign policy practices. With a case study of Brazil, Christensen (2013) concludes that Brazil has sought to strengthen its geopolitical strategy in the Southern American region by creating a sphere of influence. Stuenkel (2013) argues that despite being two large democracies, neither India nor Brazil has promoted democracy in their neighbouring countries. Though India prides itself on being the world’s largest democracy, some accuse it of being primarily focused on economic and geopolitical power struggles, which raises serious concerns about its democratic motives and credentials (see Destradi 2010, Roy 2011, Anderson 2014, H.B. Jha 2014, Bhattarai 2018).

Though SSC had elements of solidarity, shared identity, and a joint aspiration for emancipation, it has long been influenced by powerful countries like India and China, whose economic and strategic interests significantly shaped its direction. The initial ideals have further eroded over time. This has led to the emergence of more interest-driven engagements and the reinforcement of existing hierarchies rather than challenging them. In other words, the rising powers of the Global South have abandoned South–South solidarity and have instead prioritised their own political and economic ascent. This is evident in two main ways: first, they seem to prefer creating and strengthening spheres of influence in their regions; and second, they act as sub-imperialist agents when necessary or when it benefits their interests. In other words, they act as intermediaries for global powers until they can pursue their own hegemonic ambitions fully. All of this leads to one clear conclusion: the rising powers’ sub-imperial tendencies, their changing posturing and positioning within the global order, and their contradictory actions demand thorough scrutiny. The fate of smaller, weaker nations within their spheres of influence—such as Nepal in this case—also deserves careful consideration. The experiences and challenges of these countries must not be overlooked when analysing rising power behaviour.

The concept of sub-imperialism associated with rising powers today is not a new idea. It was introduced in the 1960s and can be found in Brazilian economist and dependency scholar Ruy Mauro Marini’s work on Brazil. Marini developed the concept of sub-imperialism within the context of Marxist dependency scholarship. He used it to explain what he called the Brazilian expansionist policy in Latin America and Africa, which aimed to gain control over resources and raw materials from weaker countries on both continents (see Marini 1965, 1972). Sub-imperialism scholarship has somehow experienced a resurgence again, particularly in light of the actions, questions, and uncertainties surrounding the so-called rising powers. This resurgence is facilitated by growing scholarly interest in how regional powers mediate and extend hegemonic influence within an evolving multipolar world order, particularly amid the reconfiguration of global capitalism (economic nationalism, protectionism, trade wars, data and platform capitalism) and the decline of unipolar US dominance. Scholars such as Elif Çağlı, Adrián Sotelo Valencia, Claudio Katz, Patrick Bond, and Ana Garcia have contributed to the contemporary literature on sub-imperialism.

Marini proposed sub-imperialism not as a generic term for any powerful

regional state but as a specific concept derived from his Marxist analysis of dependency. He defined sub-imperialism as the form which dependent capitalism assumes upon reaching the stage of monopolies and finance capital (Marini 1972). The concept is built on a core internal contradiction. In a dependent economy, value is constantly transferred to the imperialist centre through mechanisms like unequal exchange. To counteract this drain and maintain profit rates, the peripheral bourgeoisie is compelled to resort to the super-exploitation of its domestic labour force. However, this very super-exploitation—by depressing wages below the cost of reproduction—restricts the size and purchasing power of the internal market, especially for durable goods produced by the monopoly sector. This creates a realisation crisis: capital cannot find sufficient profitable outlets at home.

This internal contradiction causes an expansionist drive. The sub-imperialist state and its monopoly capital are forced to seek external markets for their goods and capital, as well as cheaper access to raw materials and labour. This expansion is typically directed at the sub-imperial power's immediate geographic region, its 'hinterland'.

This expansion is not a break from imperialism but a new form of articulation with it. Marini described Brazil's relationship with the United States not as one of simple submission, but as a loyal 'bargain' or 'antagonistic cooperation' (Marini 1972). The sub-imperial power carves out a sphere of regional hegemony, acting as a junior partner or regional manager for the global imperialist system. It helps maintain order and facilitate accumulation in its region, serving both its own expansionist needs and the broader interests of global capital.

In its simplest form, sub-imperialism characterises a scenario in which a nation or a group of nations, though not imperialist powers themselves, serve as intermediaries for imperialist powers within their regions. They tend to leverage their influence to extract resources, control markets, and sway political dynamics in other countries, often working alongside major global powers. In that sense, sub-imperialism can be understood as a parallel and secondary form of contemporary imperialism (Katz 2021). Katz, who emphasises the military component of imperialism, argues that the entire imperial system, which guarantees the transfer of value from periphery to core, is ultimately undergirded by a 'coercive pillar', the use or threat of military force. While the US and its NATO allies form the primary axis of this military power, sub-imperial powers participate in this system at a regional level. Katz's contribution updates the concept of sub-imperialism by adding an explicit geopolitical-military dimension.

A sub-imperial power is not just an economic expander; it is also a regional gendarme. As is clear in India's sub-imperialism in Nepal, explained in the latter chapters, it uses its military and security apparatus—through arms sales, training, joint exercises, and direct intervention—to project power, secure its economic interests, and maintain order within its sphere of influence. In other words, sub-empires engage in economic and political exploitation of their regions, much like traditional imperialists, but their influence is geographically limited (see, for instance, Väyrynen & Herrera 1975, Çağlı 2009, Bond 2015, Valencia 2017, Bond et al. 2021, Katz 2021).

There is growing evidence that the emerging powers from the Global South, especially the BRICS nations, have demonstrated sub-imperialist behaviours and contributed to the maintenance of global hegemony and neoliberal regimes. They are engaged in capital accumulation, resource extraction, and market expansion in ways that reinforce existing power structures rather than challenge them. While they may assist, accommodate, and cooperate with existing global hegemons, their

ultimate ambition, however, seems to be to ascend the global power hierarchy and establish their own hegemony.

Arguing that the BRICS follow colonial and neo-colonial tracks, Bond (2015) elaborates on different facets of modern-day sub-imperialism. According to him, contemporary sub-imperialism includes semi-peripheral accumulation, hinterland exploitation, internal modes of super-exploitation, and the reproduction of a world system based on neoliberalism and military aggression. He identifies three additional roles of sub-imperialist regimes. The first additional role, he argues, is ensuring regional geopolitical stability in volatile areas. That is, playing the role of a regional 'deputy sheriff' and engaging in surplus transfers from the hinterland to the sub-imperialist capital city, and often from there to the imperialist headquarters. These are primarily located in advanced capitalist states, particularly the United States and other Global North economies, where major financial institutions, multinational corporations, and international organisations such as the IMF and the World Bank are headquartered.

Second, a sub-imperialist regime also advances the broader agenda of globalised neoliberalism. This includes launching institutions that may rhetorically oppose neoliberalism but, in practice, aim to do the opposite. Third, sub-imperialist regimes engage in super-exploitative practices within their hinterlands, following colonial and neo-colonial tracks. Proposing South Africa as an example, Bond (2015) argues that the core imperatives of sub-imperialism remain the maintenance of a liberal regime that permits the free flow of labour and capital and the maintenance of a superior security capability able to project into its region. According to him, South Africa acts as a regional facilitator of global capitalism. Its role is to keep African economies open to Western investment while suppressing alternative economic models. It enforces neoliberal policies from institutions like the IMF and the World Bank, integrating Africa into the global system in ways that benefit Western interests, including financial flows, trade routes, and structural adjustments. Its predominant methods are colonial policy, an international loan system, a policy of spheres of interest, and war (Bond 2015).

Marini and Bond both use the concept of sub-imperialism to critique how certain semi-peripheral states assert dominance within their regions while remaining subordinate to core capitalist powers. Marini developed the concept in the 1970s within the framework of Marxist dependency theory, using Brazil as an example of a country that, while dependent on US imperialism, also played a regional imperialist role by exporting capital and dominating weaker neighbouring economies. His analysis emphasised the structural contradictions of peripheral capitalism and the reproduction of imperialist dynamics within the Global South.

Patrick Bond, writing in the post-apartheid and neoliberal era, builds on and extends Marini's framework to analyse South Africa's role in southern Africa. Bond's approach is grounded in critical political economy and social justice activism, and often emphasises how South Africa, under the banner of South-South Cooperation, advances the interests of Western capital through regional dominance, military interventions, and neoliberal policy export. While both theorists agree that sub-imperial powers act as intermediaries in global capitalism, Bond focuses more on neoliberal governance and global financial structures, whereas Marini centres on structural dependency and class contradictions within capitalist development.

Katz's work also aligns with Bond's critique of neoliberal South-South relations, particularly in how states like South Africa operate sub-imperial within their regions. However, Katz is less focused on activist frameworks and more on

providing a comprehensive theoretical account of 21st-century imperialism. He cautions against romanticising multipolarity and suggests that the rise of new powers does not inherently challenge global capitalism but often reinforces imperial hierarchies through new forms of dependence and exploitation.

Sub-imperialist concerns are not limited to the BRICS or IBSA regions only. Çağlı (2009), for instance, notes that with rapid capital accumulation and regional hegemonic aspirations, Turkey, too, is an example of a sub-imperialist location. Despite its dependence on imperialist powers, she argues that Turkey has sought to build a sphere of influence in its region. Similarly, Uysal (2021) explores Turkey's sub-imperialist position in sub-Saharan Africa, where its actions appear both in harmony and in contradistinction with Western and Gulf countries.

These concerns about sub-imperialism clearly threaten the expected 'emancipatory' potential of genuine South–South Cooperation. While South–South Cooperation among relatively weaker, and more 'equal' countries—alongside civil society organisations, social movements, and non-governmental organisations—reflects more positive prospects, the involvement of larger economic and political powers with neoliberal and hegemonic ambitions presents a completely different story. This leads us to the argument I presented in the first section of this chapter: Even processes like peace mediation should not be studied in isolation, but within the context of broader social, political, economic, and regional realities. Equally, the theoretical perspectives used to examine these power and resource-driven relations of the Global South should be diverse and multifaceted. A deeper understanding of contemporary sub-imperialism is also essential, as currently, there is a clear lack of scholarly focus on it. For instance, Nepal has rarely, if ever, been examined as a sub-imperialist target within India's sphere of influence—a gap this study aims to fill.

To sum up, the gist of my analysis in this section is that the so-called rising powers are no passive actors within the global economic system, meekly subscribing to the US-led world order. The rise of regional powers has coincided with the relative decline of the US-led hegemony. With countries such as China and Russia pursuing their own imperial ambitions and establishing parallel structures of influence, the global order is undergoing significant changes and realignments. As Alexander (2018) has put it, imperialism is indeed not 'simply a label for the predatory behaviour of the strongest states. Nor is it the sole prerogative of the US and its allies.' Scholars examining sub-imperialism, including Marini himself, argued that imperialist centre and sub-imperialist states tended to co-exist in a relationship where conflicts and tensions were inherent. According to them, such conflict occurred within the framework of structural collaboration or antagonistic cooperation, and could not reach open hostilities (see Marini 1965: 12). Other scholars studying contemporary sub-imperialism, such as Katz (2021), argue that sub-empires do not harbour ambitions for global domination, and tend to restrict their actions to the regional sphere. This, however, does not seem to be the case in the current scenario. As already argued, the rising powers' actions do characterise an interplay between advocating for global reform and replicating the very patterns they oppose. However, they do not appear complacent with their current positions and seem unwilling to tolerate global superpowers indefinitely.

China, for instance, appears to be moving beyond a sub-imperialist role towards crafting and implementing its own imperial vision and brand. Russia, while not a Global South country, is an active and strong BRICS member and an alternative power that is already engaged in full imperial swing, waging wars, and occupying territories. Meanwhile, countries like India, Brazil, and Turkey may play sub-imperial roles, primarily aligning with US-led alliances. However, they are also

exploring alternative partnerships and harbour global hegemonic ambitions. They also appear very selective in the coalitions and alliances they build. For instance, when BRICS expanded in early 2024 to welcome new members like Iran, Egypt, Ethiopia, and the United Arab Emirates, other less powerful developing countries, such as Bangladesh, were not accepted despite their strong efforts and extensive lobbying (Hasib 2023). Following the G7's model, BRICS has also turned into an exclusive club for the wealthy and powerful.

This has led to a situation in which the rise of sub-imperial powers in the Global South could perpetuate and deepen the dependency relations traditionally seen between the Global North and South. This will likely create new divisions and dependency patterns and exacerbate the ones that already exist. This also highlights the ongoing importance of the dependency theory and world-systems analysis in evaluating how rising powers interact with their less powerful neighbours. These thoughts and propositions—which I discuss in the forthcoming section—offer valuable frameworks for analysing the emerging power imbalances and exploitation among countries within the Global South. In addition, they remain valuable for understanding how modern corporate capitalism works, what fuels its unchecked expansion, and the issues it faces from within.

3.5 Dependency Thoughts, World-System Analysis, and Contemporary Global Order

As already explained, the concept of South–South solidarity or South–South Cooperation emerged from developing countries' realisation of the unequal and exploitative relationship they had with the Global North. Two theoretical approaches developed in the last century—dependency and world-systems theories—attempted to address the questions of unequal and exploitative relationships that persisted and defined the North–South relations, and the inherent divide and dichotomies. Sub-imperialism, in fact, emerged from dependency scholarship and is closely tied to the Marxist strand of dependency theory.

Despite the criticism they have received, dependency and world-systems approaches are still relevant for understanding and analysing the relationships between the Global North and South, as well as increasingly strenuous relationships between countries within the Global South. This is particularly the case at a time when the so-called rise of rising powers of the Global South is firmly 'located within the Western global hegemony' (Gray & Murphy 2013: 185).

The intellectual history of dependency scholarship began in the post-World War II era with the work of the United Nations Economic Commission for Latin America (ECLAC, or CEPAL in Spanish) and its most influential figure, Raúl Prebisch. Emerging in the 1950s, ECLAC structuralism was a direct response to the failure of orthodox economic theories to explain or solve the persistent underdevelopment of Latin America.

Already in the late 1940s, Prebisch, who had previously served as the president of the Central Bank of Argentina and later as the Director of the United Nations Economic Commission for Latin America, was taken aback by the fact that growth in developed and industrialised countries did not result in growth for poorer developing countries—contrary to the predictions of neoclassical theory, which suggested that economic growth would eventually benefit everyone. Publishing a seminal work in 1950, *The Economic Development of Latin America and its*

Principal Problems, Prebisch concluded that poorer countries exported primary commodities to advanced industrialised countries, who ‘then manufactured products out of those commodities and sold them back to the poorer countries’ (cited in Ferrao 2008: 58).

Based on extensive empirical analysis of trade data, Prebisch and Hans Singer observed that the international economy was structurally divided into an industrial ‘centre’ (the developed nations of the North) and a primary-good-exporting ‘periphery’ (the underdeveloped nations of the South). The Prebisch-Singer hypothesis³⁵ suggested that, over the long term, the terms of trade for the periphery tend to deteriorate; the prices of their primary exports (minerals, agricultural products) fall relative to the prices of the manufactured goods they must import from the centre. This creates a continuous transfer of value from the periphery to the centre, making it structurally impossible for the periphery to develop by following the path of free trade recommended by classical economics. Moreover, with added technological advancement, industrialised economies were able to concentrate and retain the savings made (Prebisch 1949, Cypher et al. 2009: 172–180).

The policy prescription that followed logically from this diagnosis was Import Substitution Industrialisation (ISI). ECLAC advocated for an activist state that would use protectionist measures, such as high tariffs on imported manufactured goods, to nurture the growth of domestic industries. The goal was to break the dependency on primary exports by industrialising internally and creating a more complex national economy.

The political nature of this project is also worth mentioning. ECLAC structuralism was a heterodox and reformist critique of mainstream liberal economics. It did not advocate for radical alternatives, nor was it a Marxist theory. It sought to correct the imbalances of the global capitalist system to allow for national development within that system, and not to overthrow that. It aimed to create robust national capitalisms in the periphery, led by a progressive national bourgeoisie.

In the South Asian context, Mahbub ul-Haq (see Haq 1976, 1980), a prominent Pakistani development economist known for creating the Human Development Index, who spent several years at the World Bank and United Nations Development Program, echoed Prebisch's concerns, but argued that the state of ‘dependency’ was a legacy of centuries of colonial rule. In Haq’s (1976: 162) view, political independence in developing countries had not succeeded in eradicating ‘economic dependence’ and ‘intellectual slavery’ of the developing world.

Haq blamed the history of colonialism for dependence, whereas Prebisch saw the fault in Western industrialisation. However, when it came to finding solutions to the dependency debacle, they both saw options, or rather, restricted themselves, within the existing system. They argued that the state of dependency and concerns of the Global South could be addressed by reforming the international economic system. In their view, the North and the South had shared interests in the proposed reforms, and the North would arguably agree to join hands in order to secure its own interests (Bokhari 1989: 20–21). While thinkers like Prebisch and Haq saw solutions in reforming the dominant, existing system, there were others who believed that ‘autonomy could only be achieved outside the dominant system, through exit and revolution’ (Golub 2013: 1003).

³⁵ German economist Hans Singer reached a similar conclusion as Prebisch around the same time.

The Radical Break: Dependency Theory (1960s–1970s)

Dependency theories emerged in the 1960s and 1970s, largely as a critique of ECLAC's developmentalism. By the 1960s, it was becoming clear that Import Substitution industrialisation strategies were not working as hoped. While they spurred some industrialisation, they often led to new forms of dependence on foreign capital, technology, and finance, and failed to address the underlying social inequalities (Reyes Hernández & López López 2019).

This intellectual break was also fuelled by the turbulent political context of the era. The Cuban Revolution of 1959 offered a radical alternative to capitalist development. The rise of brutal military dictatorships in countries like Brazil (1964) shattered the ECLAC-aligned hope in a progressive national bourgeoisie and led to the persecution and exile of many critical intellectuals. These exiled scholars, many of whom gathered at institutions like the Centre for Socio-Economic Studies at the University of Chile, forged a more radical analysis (see Ahumada & Torres 2024).

One of the first definitions of dependency was provided in the early 1970s by Dos Santos, a revered figure in dependency scholarship. He defined dependency as 'a historical condition that shapes a certain structure of the world economy such that it favours some countries to the detriment of others, and limits the development possibilities of the subordinate economies' (Dos Santos 1973: 109).

The fundamental insight of dependency theory is that development and underdevelopment are two sides of the same coin; they are the joint products of a single, unified capitalist world-system. Underdevelopment is not a prior stage to development or a result of 'lacking' investment; it is the necessary and ongoing result of the development of the core. The core does not simply leave the periphery behind; it actively underdevelops it through mechanisms of exploitation and surplus extraction.

Dependency theory has two principal strands: Structuralist and neo-Marxist. Both camps—despite their differences in approach in terms of finding a solution to underdevelopment—emphasise 'the persistence of systemic asymmetries and constraints that reproduced international hierarchy and hollowed out the sovereignty of states that remained caged in subordinate positions in the world capitalist economy' (Golub 2013: 1003).

The central analytical contribution of Marxist dependency thought, represented by thinkers like Ruy Mauro Marini, Andre Gunder Frank, and Theotonio dos Santos, is the concept of 'super-exploitation' (Sotelo Valencia 2014). Marini argued that because peripheral economies constantly transfer value to the core through unequal exchange, local capitalists are forced to compensate by intensifying the rate of exploitation of their own labour force. This means paying workers wages that are below the value required to reproduce their labour power—that is, below what is needed for their and their families' subsistence and replenishment (see Latimer & Osorio 2022). Super-exploitation is thus the specific mechanism through which dependency is maintained at the point of production, and is an inherent practice in sub-imperialism. The political conclusion for this strand was that a break with dependency required a socialist revolution, as 'dependent development' within capitalism was an impossibility (Golub 2013).

Andre Gunder Frank, widely considered to be a neo-Marxist proponent of dependency thoughts,³⁶ has made significant contributions to the advancement of

³⁶ Although Frank did not identify himself as a Marxist, and some critics have questioned whether he could be labelled as one, other scholars place his work within a broadly defined framework of Marxist scholarship.

dependency ideas, starting from his seminal work, *The Development of Underdevelopment*. At a time when communist parties in Latin America were blaming widespread feudalism and limited capitalism for underdevelopment, Frank argued that Latin America's integration into the global capitalist system dated back to the 16th century. He claimed that it was this very capitalism that led to development in some countries (commonly referred to as the centre) and underdevelopment in others (often called the periphery) (Frank 1966, Dietz 1980: 751–52). In his view, development and underdevelopment can be viewed as two sides of the same coin, as developed nations are developed at the expense of the underdeveloped by extracting the surplus created in the peripheral countries (see Figure 5). To Frank, underdevelopment is, thus, a result of a historical process, not a condition (Frank 1966).

Frank claimed that global capitalist expansion had resulted in the creation of what he called the metropolis-satellite division of states, suggesting that the metropolis-satellite division was vital in determining the political, economic, and social/cultural norms in the satellites. Frank argued that since the purpose of absorbing surplus capital from the satellites was conducive this way, the condition would continue according to the metropolis' preference.

In addition, he proposed three hypotheses that defined the metropolis-satellite relations and determined the conditions for the creation of satellites. First, 'the development of the national and other subordinate metropolises is limited by their satellite status.' Second, the satellites achieve their greatest economic development when their ties to the metropolis are weakest, and third, the 'regions which are the most underdeveloped and feudal-seeming are the ones which had the closest ties to the metropolis in the past' (Frank 1966: 10–13). In essence, Frank argued that capitalism was the primary culprit behind the widespread exploitation of developing countries, located at the periphery of the global economic structure.

The structuralist dependency strand, represented by figures like Fernando Henrique Cardoso and Enzo Faletto, offered an alternative view. While agreeing on the structural constraints of the global system, they argued that some degree of 'associated-dependent development' was possible. They focused on how internal class structures and political arrangements within peripheral nations could mediate their relationship with the core, allowing for some industrialisation and development, albeit in a subordinated form.

The world-systems approach

The world-systems approach, developed by scholars such as Immanuel Wallerstein, Giovanni Arrighi, and Samir Amin, represents a further evolution that builds upon the insights of dependency theory but is analytically distinct. It emerged in the 1970s and shifted the primary unit of analysis from the nation-state to the singular 'capitalist world-economy', which Wallerstein traces back to the 16th century.

The world-systems approach primarily supported the arguments of dependency theory and explored further avenues for understanding the exploitative relationships in the world system. This approach recognises dependency concepts characterising the core–periphery relations or the metropolis-satellite division.

Wallerstein (1974a, 1974b, 1987), for instance, argued that the modern world system was characterised by an international division of labour, which consisted of a three-layered capitalist zone: Core, Semi-Periphery, and Periphery countries. In this layered division, he proposed, the industrialised or the so-called core countries controlled the world's wages and the production of manufactured goods, while the

peripheral countries provided raw materials to the core and semi-peripheries. The semi-peripheral zone, such as Brazil or China, resembled the core in many aspects—with their urban centres and vibrant economic activities—but also had rural and poverty-stricken areas (see Wallerstein 1974a, 1974b, 1987).

Figure 5 Depiction of Core-Periphery Relations as Proposed by Dependency Scholars. Figure by Author.

Unlike dependency theories, the world-systems approach expanded its unit of social analysis from nation-states to the 'world system'. Wallerstein, for instance, argued that paying exclusive attention to individual countries is not sufficient, as we live in an era in which both poor and rich countries are caught up in a 'modern world system' dominated by global economic institutions and corporations, which can be much more powerful than nation-states.³⁷ Semi-peripheral states are those that exhibit a mix of core-like and periphery-like economic activities. They are simultaneously exploited by the core and are exploiters of the periphery. This intermediate position is structurally crucial for the stability of the entire world-system. The semi-periphery acts as a political and economic buffer, preventing a unified, polarised opposition of the periphery against the core.¹⁸ The possibility of upward (or downward) mobility into or out of the semi-periphery provides a political safety valve that helps maintain the system's overall structure.

³⁷ Some of the classic readings on world-systems theory include Wallerstein (1974a, 1974b, 1987) and Hopkins & Wallerstein (1982). The Modern World System series by Wallerstein, published between 1974 and 2011, provides valuable insights into world-systems theory and modern capitalism.

The core-periphery relations proposed by the world-systems approach expand beyond national boundaries and exceed the already-proposed North–South dichotomy. Similarly, it is entirely possible to have all three capitalist zones—core, semi-periphery, and periphery—within a single country or region. This also applies to the core-periphery relations among countries in the Global South. This starting point is especially relevant and useful for this study, as I aim to examine and analyse the dependency patterns that characterise India–Nepal relations—two countries in the Global South with some significant similarities, but also vast differences.

Dependency and world-systems approaches have also faced substantial criticism. Over the years, the unprecedented upheavals in the global political landscape have significantly influenced dependency theory and world-systems approaches. As Sánchez (2003: 39) puts it, once influential across multiple disciplines and valued beyond academia, dependency ideas have fallen out of fashion and have been reduced to footnote status.

However, the so-called ‘demise of dependency’ was not sudden. Dependency thoughts suffered severe theoretical critiques from the developmentalist, structuralist, and mainstream economic fronts. Additionally, the lack of ‘verifiability’ in dependency ideas—being vague and difficult to test—raised questions about their real-life usefulness. As Stallings (1992: 48) sums up, ‘the combination of intellectual critiques and reinforcing international trends had a devastating effect on dependency analysis’. One of the main factors that made dependency theories nearly obsolete was their insistence that development and progress within the global capitalist system were impossible. However, these claims appeared to be contradicted by the reality on the ground. For instance, as Sánchez (2003: 39) elaborates:

The evolution of at least four economies—South Korea, Singapore, Taiwan and Hong Kong—showed two things radically at odds with dependency tenets: first, that attaining economic progress is very much possible; and second, that it is feasible via enhanced integration with the world economy.

In addition to these challenges, the fall of socialist/communist regimes worldwide served as ‘the nail in the coffin for the dependency movement’ (Sánchez 2003: 39). Similarly, dependency ideas were attacked for their preoccupation with the ills of capitalism while neglecting domestic forces of development—local actors, their agency, and their sphere of choices, and influence. Arguably, dependency theory’s portrayal of local actors reduced them to look like nothing more than pawns of external forces (Smith 1979: 257–58). Some critics have pointed out that countries like India appeared to have even benefitted from colonialism, particularly in terms of the expansion of their transportation and communication systems (see Manning 1974, Goldthorpe 1975). In contrast, other countries, such as Nepal or Ethiopia, which were never colonised and had remained somewhat disconnected from global capitalism, remained poorer and less developed³⁸.

As neoliberalism ascended to become the new theory of choice among mainstream economics scholars, underdevelopment in developing countries was

³⁸ The absence of formal colonisation did not mean that these countries were free from colonial influence. For instance, Nepal was never formally colonised, but it was not immune to colonial influence, particularly from the British Empire. Nepal was obliged to provide Gurkha soldiers for British military service, and its economy and external relations were largely shaped by British interests. Nepal’s foreign policy was also aligned with British objectives. This lack of formal colonisation allowed Britain to reap many of the benefits typically associated with colonial rule—such as access to resources and manpower—without the administrative burdens of direct control (see Mulmi 2017).

seen not so much as a centre–periphery problem. Instead, it was associated with a range of other issues, such as corruption in governments in the Global South, ethnic conflict, civil wars, landlocked geographical location, lack of inclusive institutions, cultural issues, and so forth (see, for instance, Collier 2008, Robinson & Acemoglu 2012).³⁹ The connection between development aid and the dependency discourse was also weakened, as influential neoliberal economists such as Jeffrey Sachs began to argue that many developing countries had benefited from aid programmes run by international aid agencies or Western governments. Unlike dependency scholars, neoliberal economists suggested that development aid could be an effective mechanism for eliminating poverty and underdevelopment from the developing world (see, for instance, Sachs 2005).

Against this backdrop, the relevance of dependency theory and world-systems approaches has been widely debated. On one hand, it seems that they are undoubtedly facing a crisis, challenged by shifts in academic focus and their dismal performance in predicting plausible outcomes. Yet, on the other hand, they are also experiencing a resurgence, facilitated by recent changes and uncertainties in the global landscape. The expansion of global capitalism, along with the rise of powerful multinational corporations and the increasing economic dominance of a few key players, has renewed interest in dependency perspectives. For instance, modern global supply chains, finance, and technology illustrate contemporary dependencies: developing countries typically provide low-value labour or raw inputs while core countries control innovation, finance, and market systems. Even with globalisation and the rise of emerging economies (such as the BRICS), dependency theory’s lens exposes how dominant countries maintain power—sometimes shifting the dynamics but not the fundamental structures of dependency.

While some have seemed to enjoy the limited respite offered by postcolonial thoughts,⁴⁰ many dependency scholars and others, nonetheless, continue to believe that dependency theory and world-system approaches are just as relevant today, especially when examining power relations in the 21st century and analysing the pressing issues crippling modern corporate capitalism.⁴¹

3.5.1 A Contemporary Defence of Dependency Ideas

Some criticisms of dependency theory stem from the confusion surrounding its understanding and the various forms and scope it encompasses. Sanchéz (2003), for instance, argues that the name itself is deceiving as dependency theory is not a

³⁹ Collier (2008), for instance, argues that poverty and underdevelopment cannot be reduced to a history of exploitation but can be linked to civil wars, ethnic tensions, and unfavourable geography. Similarly, Robinson & Acemoglu (2012) argue that the lack of inclusive institutions also hinders prosperity and development.

⁴⁰ Writings of scholars such as Edward Said, Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak, and Homi K. Bhabha offer some classic readings on postcolonial theory. See, for instance, O’Hanlon & Washbrook (1992), Dirlik (1994), Ahmad (1997), and Chibber (2014) for an extensive and critical review of postcolonial theory. Postcolonial theory has been criticised primarily for its shallow focus, if at all, on the role of capitalism and its insufficient attention to socioeconomic inequality and inconsistencies created by capitalist modernity. In short, postcolonial theory ‘approaches capitalism epistemologically,’ whereas, for dependency theory, ‘capital is foundational or ontological’ (Kapoor 2002: 658). In addition, scholars such as Chibber (2014) criticise postcolonial theory for its portrayal of cultures as fixed and static, its assumptions that the gap between the East and the West is unbridgeable—thereby denying people’s ‘universal aspirations—and for labelling all Enlightenment values as Eurocentric.

⁴¹ In a 2017 edition of *Ideas for Development* (eds. Kvangraven, Styve, Kufakurinani, & Santanta), dependency scholars such as Samir Amin, Adebayo O. Olukoshi, Miguel Angel Centeno, and Matías Vernengo renew their faith in dependency ideas and their relevance in the 21st century.

theory per se, but an approach to the study of underdevelopment. Understanding dependency as an approach instead of a theory omits the need to test and verify it for empirical validity. Sánchez further argues that the emergence of ‘flawed, prejudiced, or incomplete interpretations’ of dependency ideas might have been aggravated by the fact that scholars in the ‘centre’ predominately read only the dependency literature translated into English, leaving behind a lot of country-specific cases on the ‘domestic structure of dependence’ (p. 33).

Critics of dependency and world-systems approaches often cite examples of East Asian economies, particularly South Korea and Taiwan, to claim that rapid economic growth and development were possible while still being connected to the core. However, other scholars have questioned the accuracy of these claims. Samir Amin, a renowned dependency scholar, for instance, argues that the East Asian countries in question were, in fact, ‘allowed’ to move from the ‘periphery’ to the ‘core’ due to geostrategic reasons, mainly to avert the threat of China and North Korea (in Kvangraven 2017: 16). Similarly, the works of scholars like Petras & Hui (1991) and Medeiros (2004) illustrate how the United States practised ‘development by invitation’ by opening markets for certain East Asian countries while restricting access to other developing countries. Even when US concessions were not offered, such as in China, the road to development was reached with a combination of ‘central planning’ and ‘selective opening’ (Olukoshi, in Styve 2017: 24).

Before concluding whether dependency analysis is relevant in the 21st century, it is crucial to consider contemporary global political and economic contexts. Despite progress made in a handful of countries in the Global South, it is no secret that old lines of inequality and unequal power relations persist and prevail in various forms. Equally, ‘the fact that some countries seem to be breaking out of the dependency trap does not mean that a trap never existed’ (Glennie & Hassanaien 2012).

It is also important to emphasise that the dependency relationships of the 21st century may look quite different from those of the past. Referring to the proliferation of multinational corporations and the pervasive corporate capitalism, Strange (1994: 215), for instance, argues that ‘opting out of the world market economy is no longer an option’ and ‘that is what dependency means today’. Contrary to the arguments made by proponents of globalisation, the benefits of globalisation have not been distributed equally, and it has not been suitable for all. As Samir Amin argues, globalisation has been polarising, and the centres have shaped it in their favour (in Kvangraven 2017: 14). Farny (2016) makes similar remarks, arguing that global disparity along the North–South divide continues, and today’s dependency relations persist through trade deals, foreign direct investment, and development aid. Apart from the clear differences in income levels and living standards between developed and developing countries, capital flows from the periphery to the semi-periphery and ultimately to the core countries, facilitated by multinational corporations.

Similarly, poverty in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia is still pervasive. Rich countries at the ‘core’ continue to hold more power in international financial institutions, and mechanisms such as the Doha round of negotiations, which would have benefitted developing countries had it been successful, continue to falter. The developed world, in fact, ‘has used much political muscle in making sure the door to their agricultural markets remains shut’ (Sánchez 2003: 45–46).

What is even more concerning is the replication of dependency relations at multiple levels. As already mentioned, Western powers continue to maintain

renewed forms of dependency globally. At the same time, the rising powers of the Global South—or those acting as sub-empires—have recreated and reinforced the same patterns within their spheres of influence. It is also no secret that the world is not progressing towards greater equality; instead, the gap between the richest and the poorest continues to widen. The rise of tech giants as new agents of cross-border capital accumulation further exacerbates these disparities. This shows that dependency and world-systems approaches are becoming increasingly important for understanding contemporary global issues and how global corporate capitalism operates.

As already mentioned, the so-called rise⁴² of a few countries in the Global South, such as China, India, Brazil, and South Africa, arguably from the semi-periphery towards the ‘core’, has not eliminated, but created new and more aggressive forms of dependency relations within the Global South. As analysed in Chapters 7, 8, and 9 of this thesis, the dependency patterns between two unequal countries in the contemporary Global South—examined here through the case of India and Nepal—are shaped by geopolitical, economic, and resource interests. Often collectively expressed in the form of sub-imperialism, capital accumulation and surplus transfers are central to these unequal co-existences.

Other researchers have identified similar patterns elsewhere. Taylor (2016: 8), for instance, notes that the widespread hype claiming the rise of Africa is a myth, as the so-called rise is ‘based on an intensification of resource extraction whilst dependency deepens, inequality increases, and de-industrialisation continues apace’. In an analysis of Sino–Latin America trade relations, Skira (2007: 18) points out that while Latin America exported mainly raw materials and primary products to China, its imports from China were primarily manufactured goods. Noting that around 76% of Latin American countries’ exports to China constituted primary commodities, she concludes that ‘Sino–Latin American trade relations resemble in some ways the centre–periphery relationships outlined by Prebisch’ (p. 18).

This is a clear indication that dependency thoughts are still relevant today and can be used for ‘making sense of global inequalities in today’s globalised world’ (Farny 2016). Dependency thoughts are also helpful in recognising ‘structural imbalances and causes of underdevelopment’ in the contemporary world (Radovanovic 2012: 9). This is even more relevant, particularly when dependency deniers ‘offer no tangible exit from underdevelopment...other than a commitment to a policy and politics of mimicry’ (Olukoshi in Styve 2017). However, understanding the diversity of dependency as an approach is essential. When understood as an approach—despite any shortcomings inherent in the theory—it remains useful as a conceptual tool for analysing the past and the present.

As a concluding remark to this section, it is worth highlighting that dependency ideas can certainly be useful not only in analysing underdevelopment—as had been the case traditionally—but also to make sense of contemporary international relations, patterns of international trade, investment, development aid, and, more recently, the behaviour of the so-called rising powers of the Global South. No matter how they are presented or redefined, core–periphery relations continue to exist in various forms and have expanded from North–South to South–South levels. This has resulted in new patterns of dependency and exploitation that were once unimaginable, especially when a large group of developing countries had collectively envisioned creating a new international economic order and leading

⁴² The ‘rise’ of the Global South has been a contested issue in itself, as countries like India and China have held global power not only today but also centuries ago (see, for instance, Tellis & Mirski 2013).

their collective political and economic emancipation. In short, today's global realities necessitate a fresh theoretical inquiry, and dependency theories offer an excellent starting point. As evident in subsequent chapters, I use the dependency framework, with a particular emphasis on sub-imperialism, to analyse India's actions in Nepal and carry out a broader evaluation of India–Nepal relations. In other words, dependency theories are not obsolete, and their theoretical relevance continues to endure. They can help us comprehend core–periphery relations of the past but also of today.

3.6 Chapter Summary: Integrating Theoretical Perspectives

This chapter outlines the theoretical framework used in this study. The framework synthesises various theoretical perspectives later used to analyse India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition. By incorporating theories of conflict mediation, models of rising power behaviour, and world-systems and dependency analysis, this chapter constructed a theoretical framework suitable for analysing India's engagement in Nepal and re-evaluating contemporary India–Nepal relations. The first section introduced theoretical concepts related to peace mediation, particularly ripeness theory, which identifies optimal moments for conflict resolution. Mediation is presented as a tool for resolving conflicts, and an overview of the current global mediation landscape is offered. Drawing on works of scholars like Saadia Touval, concepts of 'power mediation' and 'pure mediation' are explored. Mediation as a foreign policy tool is thoroughly discussed, acknowledging that while 'power mediators' may broker peace agreements, their vested interests and post-agreement actions warrant critical examination. The chapter then moved on to the discussion of South–South Cooperation, highlighting differing scholarly views. Some see SSC as an emancipatory concept, while for others, it is a form of exploitation, neocolonialism, or even sub-imperialism. After discussing the sub-imperialist tendencies of the so-called rising powers of the Global South, I argue that SSC should be evaluated within the broader context of global political and economic processes rather than as a standalone innovation or a benevolent panacea. The final section elaborated on dependency and world-systems theories. Despite their current academic unpopularity, it is argued that dependency and world-systems theories are experiencing a resurgence for a reason and appear to be incredibly useful for analysing increasingly complex global political and economic relations of our time.

4. The Tumultuous Path to Peace in Nepal: A Literature Review

The Nepali peace process, which culminated in 2006 with the signing of the Comprehensive Peace Accord (CPA), had a complicated past. Previous attempts for peace bore no fruit, as the talks repeatedly stalled and failed. The attempts to find a military solution to the conflict ultimately backfired for King Gyanendra, who lost his throne and became the last king of the 240-year-old Shah dynasty. The 2006 peace deal promised a new and better Nepal for its citizens; however, amid post-conflict political wrangling, it took another nine years merely to promulgate a new constitution. As the political transition deepened, India's involvement in Nepal's post-conflict peace and transitional political processes became a pressing issue. Since this study focuses on the same topic, this chapter provides insight into the research context and reviews the relevant literature.

In the first section, I briefly examine Nepal's modern history, even though a thorough analysis of the historical past is beyond the scope of this thesis. I offer this brief voyage into history to demonstrate how Nepal has historically undergone a painful transformation. Nepal's evolution towards what one might now call a participatory and inclusive democracy has not been easy. Apart from its own domestic hurdles, India's presence and influence in Nepal throughout its modern history has been consistent, assertive, and sometimes even ruthless. Whenever one attempts to investigate, analyse, or critically assess India–Nepal relations, a brief review of the historical context is both necessary and helpful. That is what I aim to do in the first part of this chapter.

In the second part of this chapter, I provide a brief overview of the Maoist armed insurgency (1996–2006) and its impact on Nepali society. I discuss the origins and progress of the insurgency and assess the causes and consequences of the conflict. Again, the aim is not to offer an exhaustive analysis of the conflict—other scholars have already done that⁴³—but to offer some historical and geopolitical context of the armed conflict. In terms of its size and the damage it caused, the Maoist armed insurgency will be remembered as one of the most violent episodes in Nepal's modern history. The insurgency claimed more than 17,000 lives, left many wounded and traumatised, and severely impacted Nepal's economy. At the same time, it shook the foundations of Nepali state structures, transformed the political psyche of ordinary Nepalis, and triggered a radical paradigm shift in Nepal's modern political landscape.

In the third section, I provide a comprehensive review of the existing literature, focusing specifically on India's role in Nepal's peace process and political transition. I conclude the chapter by highlighting five significant issues that earlier studies have overlooked, thus justifying the need for this research.

⁴³ For a detailed understanding of the Maoist insurgency, its origin, ideological bases, development, and impacts on Nepali society, see, for instance, Karki & Seddon (2003), Thapa & Sijapati (2004), Hutt (2004), Onesto (2005), Lawoti & Pahari (2009), and Adhikari (2014).

4.1 A Brief History of Modern Nepal and the India Factor

The formation of modern Nepal dates back to the 18th century. Before the 18th century, a significant part of current Nepal comprised negligible states and territories—known as *Baise* and *Chaubise* states—each controlled by its own king (Sharma 2004: 10). In 1743, Prithvi Narayan Shah (hereafter P. N. Shah), a young king from a tiny principality known as Gorkha, began to expand his kingdom by attacking and annexing other tiny states.⁴⁴ Shah's first attack was on Nuwakot, where his father, Nara Bhupal Shah,⁴⁵ had been defeated in 1736 (Northey & Morris 1928: 30–31). In 1768, the Gorkha soldiers invaded the Kathmandu valley (Waller 2004: 171), and by 1775, the passing year of P. N. Shah, the annexation process had reached up to eastern Nepal and Sikkim (Whelpton 1997).

P. N. Shah played a significant role in the formation of the modern Nepali state. He is also remembered for his contribution to shaping Nepal's foreign policy. Before his death, he reportedly summoned notable noblemen, priests and his close aides known as *bhardars* to his side and offered a range of advice which was later documented and published as *the Divyopadesh*.⁴⁶ As evident in his teachings, Shah believed that Nepal's foreign policy should be based on non-alignment and neutrality, which many scholars argue still guide Nepal's foreign policy (see, for instance, Baral 2018, Khanal 2019). Shah's concerns about the presence of the East India Company and its dominance in India and the possibility of its eventual trespassing into Nepal are reflected in his teachings. In the *Divyopadesh*, he says:

This state (Nepal) is like a yam (gourd) between two stones. Keep a strong friendship with the Emperor of China; one has to maintain a friendship with the Emperor of the Sea (English Emperor) in the south. But he is very clever. He is occupying Hindustan. He is eyeing the plane area (of Nepal also). When Hindustani (Indian) people will wake up (not tolerate them), he may find it difficult to stay there. He might have been searching for a safe fort and there is every possibility that he may come here at any day (P.N. Shah, 1774, *Divyopadesh*, translation Nepal Law Commission 2018: 9).

Nonetheless, P.N. Shah's guidance to his successors was that Nepal should refrain from carrying out offensive acts against the 'English Emperor' and that any fighting against the British should be defensive (Shaha 1978: 104). His legacy guided Nepal's foreign policy for a long time. For many years, Nepal followed a policy of physical

⁴⁴ There is no consensus on whether P.N. Shah's policy of military conquest and annexation of other principalities was merely an expansionist project or an attempt to reunify Nepal, which was fragmented into small principalities. Some scholars have argued that Nepal was already as big as present-day Nepal during the Licchavi period and that P.N. Shah's motive was to reunify the old Nepal (see, for instance, Acharya 2005). Others argue that P.N. Shah was motivated by an expansionist urge and the desire to become a king of a big state, and reunifying the old Nepal was not his primary interest. Some also suggest that the formation of modern Nepal was driven by P.N. Shah's realisation that unless there was a relatively bigger and stronger state, the British India/East India Company would gobble up small principalities in the south and China in the north.

⁴⁵ Historical accounts show that Nara Bhupal wanted to expand his kingdom by annexing Nuwakot and other principalities in the vicinity. However, after being faced with a humiliating defeat in Nuwakot, he abandoned his expansionist ambition and instead decided to live the life of a religious devotee. After Nara Bhupal died in 1742, Prithvi Narayan ascended to the throne at age 20 and immediately started making plans for continuing his father's dream, i.e., to expand the Kingdom of Gorkha. See, for instance, Whelpton (2005) for a detailed overview of Nepal's pre-modern and modern history.

⁴⁶ The English translation of the word *Divyopadesh*, provided by The Nepal Law Commission, is 'celestial teaching.' Some authors have also translated it into English as 'divine teaching' or 'divine counsel'. P.N. Shah delivered these teachings as *pravachana* (discourses) reportedly during the last week of December 1774. Teachings in *Divyopadesh* include a wide range of subjects, including foreign policy, religion, economic practices, and defence policies. For more information, see, for instance, Acharya & Yogi (2013), and for the English translation of the document, see Nepal Law Commission (2018).

isolation as a survival strategy (Hasrat 1970). This meant the exclusion of foreigners and foreign powers (Atique 1983: 97). To compensate for the losses of this 'isolationist' strategy, self-determination and self-reliance were promoted, which, according to Kafle (2008: 139), can be considered a postcolonial response of Nepal.

At least in principle, 'neutrality' and 'non-alignment' have been important pillars of Nepal's foreign policy, and they continue to remain so.⁴⁷ Among other reasons, the geo-strategic location of Nepal—the fact that it is sandwiched between two giant Asian powers, India and China—and continuous political instability in the country have led Nepal to adopt such policies (Baral 2018: 25). Nepal's official texts on foreign policy have consistently emphasised 'neutrality' and 'non-alignment' as key principles. However, in practice, Nepal's proximity to India and India's influence in Nepal have always been significant. I will briefly explore this issue in this chapter and discuss it in detail in later chapters.

After P. N. Shah's death, his successors continued the expansion project under the leadership of his younger son, Bahadur Shah. By 1815, the Kingdom of Nepal extended to the North Indian territories of Kumaon and Garwal in the west and Sikkim in the east (Landon 1928: 67–69, Rose & Scholz 1980, Pradhan 2009). Nepal's relations with Tibet escalated over trade routes and the quality of copper coins supplied from Nepal. As a result, in 1788, Nepal invaded Tibet (Upadhyaya 2012: 22–23). A series of skirmishes continued between the two countries, and Tibet sought help from China⁴⁸ to quell Nepali aggression. China came to Tibet's rescue and provided massive military support. In 1792, the Treaty of Betrawati was signed, and Nepali forces retreated from Tibet (Landon 1928, Upadhyaya 2012: 26). In the south, Nepal was at odds with the East India Company as the dispute over controlling states that bordered Nepal mounted. The tussle between the two led to the Anglo–Nepali War (1815–16), in which both parties bore heavy losses. The war ended with the Sugauli Treaty, due to which Nepal lost more than one-third of its territories to the British East India Company (see Rose 1971).

The formation of a unified Nepali state and its expansion did not bring about positive changes in the lives of the Nepali people. The Shah kings preferred Kathmandu over Gorkha as Nepal's capital; thus, Kathmandu became the new power centre of Nepal. The new and 'unified' Nepal did not move towards inclusivity, social progress, or development, but was characterised by widespread corruption, nepotism, and the power struggles of a handful of Kathmandu-based elites that captured the entire state mechanism for their personal benefit. Basnett (2009: 14) notes that the post-unification period marked 'the beginning of unequal power imbalance in the country whereby control over land and political power was monopolised by a fragmented elite, centralised by the state'.

⁴⁷ As of September 2024, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Nepal states that the following principles guide Nepal's foreign policy: 1. Mutual respect for each other's territorial integrity and sovereignty, 2. Non-interference in each other's internal affairs, 3. Respect for mutual equality, 4. Non-aggression and the peaceful settlement of disputes, 5. Cooperation for mutual benefit, 6. Abiding faith in the Charter of the United Nations, 7. Value of world peace (MOFAN 2024).

⁴⁸ Tibet was annexed by China in 1951, and until then, it functioned as an independent state. However, whether Tibet was independent is debated, as the Chinese government and the Tibetan government in exile had their own versions of its independent status before 1951. For more on this, see, for instance, Goldstein & Rimpoche (1989).

4.1.1 The Rana Rule (1846–1951)

After the unification of Nepal in 1768, the beginning of the Rana oligarchy in 1846 is perhaps the most significant turning point in Nepal's history. In 1846, Jung Bahadur Kunwar⁴⁹, a royal bodyguard, and his brothers massacred around 29 statesmen in the notorious Kot Massacre⁵⁰ and got themselves high-ranking administrative and military posts. In the aftermath of the Kot Massacre, Jung Bahadur became Prime Minister and the Commander-in-Chief of the army. All other high-ranking and influential posts went to his brothers and cousins (Joshi & Rose 1966: 29–31). Jung Bahadur orchestrated yet another massacre, the Bhandarkhal Massacre⁵¹, and further consolidated his power. The position of Prime Minister became hereditary and was passed on to his descendants. The Shah kings became powerless figureheads, with their movements and daily activities closely monitored and controlled by the Ranas. Jung Bahadur's decisions prevailed in both domestic and international affairs. By 1872, he had successfully gained recognition for his regime from Nepal's two major neighbouring powers, India and China (Pandey 1973: 61).

The Rana oligarchy lasted for 104 years and is considered the darkest period in Nepal's history. The entire state apparatus was exploited for the benefit of the Ranas for over a century. The grievances of ordinary Nepalis went unheard and neglected. It is estimated that the Rana Prime Ministers used anywhere between 25% to 50% of total state revenue for personal benefits (Kumar 1967). The Rana oligarchy ruled by suppressing and systematically subjugating ordinary Nepalis, treating the country as if it were their private enterprise. Unsurprisingly, many of Nepal's resources were used for their private use. For instance, by 1950, merely three prominent Rana families had accumulated 227,105 acres of land—approximately 42.5% of the total cultivated Birta land in the plains of Nepal (Regmi 1971).

Jung Bahadur and his successors exploited the rifts and divisions among the monarchical factions to consolidate power for themselves. In addition, Jung Bahadur consolidated his grip on power and promoted his image as an absolute authority by waging war on Tibet⁵² in 1855 (Pandey 1973: 57–58) and successfully interpreting its outcome in his favour. In addition, he sought affinity with the British rulers in India while neglecting China, a declining power at that time (Lohani 2011: 3). In 1857, as uprisings against the rule of the British East India Company in India broke out, Jung Bahadur and his brother, General Dhir Shamsher, led Nepali troops and went to India to help the British rulers in

⁴⁹ Jung Bahadur Kunwar, who later secured the title of Rana, came from a prominent family in Gorkha. Historical accounts show that he was an ambitious, shrewd and ruthless man who did not hesitate to murder even his relatives for power. For an elaborate analysis of how Jung Bahadur rose to prominence, see, for instance, Pandey (1973) and Adhikari (1984).

⁵⁰ The Kot Massacre occurred in 1846 and is considered to be one of the bloodiest massacres in Nepal's history. After Queen Rajya Laxmi's close confidant and rumoured lover, Gagan Singh, was mysteriously killed, a high-profile meeting of royal counsels was organised at the *Kot* to hunt for his killer. As chaos escalated, Jung Bahadur and his brothers ran a killing spree. That day, more than 30 high-ranking personalities were killed, including Prime Minister Fateh Jung Shah, several ministers, and some top army personnel. For more on the Kot massacre, see, for instance, Vaidya (2000).

⁵¹ The Bhandarkhal massacre took place in 1806, in which more than 93 high-profile people were killed at the Hanuman Dhoka palace's Bhandarkhal garden. For more, see, for instance, Pandey (1973) or Karmacharya (2005).

⁵² The war concluded with the Treaty of Thapathali (1856), under which Nepal would be responsible if there had been any external attack on Tibet (Sahu 2015: 198). The war apparently ended due to mutual exhaustion, but Jung Bahadur was successful in projecting the end of the war as Nepal's victory, thus further consolidating his political image in Nepal.

suppressing the rebellion (Hibbert 1978: 358, Tyagi 1974: 80–81). They successfully sabotaged the uprisings in India, and the jubilant British East India Company rewarded Jung Bahadur by returning a part of the land⁵³ that Nepal had ceded to British India after the Anglo–Nepalese War. This success further solidified Jung Bahadur's absolute authority in Nepal. There was no one to challenge his power, and peace reigned in the country. However, 'that was the peace of the grave' (Pandey 1973: 59–60).

The Rana rulers focused on pleasing the rulers of India and kept Nepal in complete darkness for over a century. They crippled and stagnated Nepal's economy and kept the institution of monarchy within the four walls of the royal palace. Even though the British East India Company did not attempt to colonise Nepal after the Anglo–Nepalese War, it considered Nepal a buffer state against China and the USSR and integrated Nepal into its security parameters (Adhikari et al. 2013: 4). As a legacy from their colonial rulers, post-colonial Indian rulers continued this practice. Nepal's dependence on British India grew substantially during the Rana rule. Nepali youths started to be recruited as Gurkha soldiers in the British–India army. Nepal relied heavily on British India, among others, for foreign trade and international travel (Bhattarai 2005: 20). All these factors, along with the eventual fall of the British Raj in India in 1947, inspired a democratic movement in Nepal. This also led to India's increased engagement in Nepal, which I will briefly discuss in the next section.

4.1.2 Dawn of Democracy (1950–1960)

In 1936, a small group of Nepali activists formed a political group named *Praja Parishad*⁵⁴ with the aim of plotting a revolution and overthrowing the Ranas. However, in 1943, a plan to assassinate leading members of the Rana regime was exposed. As a result, members of the Parishad were arrested and executed, with their bodies displayed publicly to deter dissent. This act backfired on the regime, and dissatisfaction against the Ranas grew (Brown 2002: 16).

Nepalis who were living in exile in India participated in the Indian struggle for independence, while aspiring to liberate Nepal from the Ranas. For many Nepali political activists, Indian leaders fighting against the Raj were role models. The British Raj had been crucial for the sustenance of the Rana regime in Nepal (Basnett 2009: 15), and the fall of the Raj was detrimental to the survival of the Ranas in Nepal. Nepali intellectuals in exile in India and a group of disgruntled Ranas—who had been sidelined within the Rana hierarchy—were actively involved in waging an anti-Rana movement. The anti-Rana movement gained momentum in 1947 when the Nepali National Congress (NNC) party was established in India under the leadership of B.P. Koirala⁵⁵ (Rose 1971: 183). Two years later, in 1949, the Communist Party of Nepal was formed in Calcutta, India, under the leadership of Pushpa Lal Shrestha (Gurung 1977: 1850). Both parties sought to end the oppressive Rana oligarchy in Nepal and were inspired by and received support from anti-Raj movements in India.

Nepali political activists living in exile in India not only campaigned for democracy in Nepal but also actively participated in the Indian independence

⁵³ Four districts of today's Nepal—Banke, Bardiya, Kailali and Kanchanpur—were returned to Nepal as a reward for supporting the British in suppressing the Indian rebellion of 1857.

⁵⁴ *Praja Parishad* can be loosely translated into English as the People's Foundation or People's Federation.

⁵⁵ Tanka Prasad Acharya was appointed as the President of the party. However, the Ranas imprisoned Acharya in Kathmandu, which made B.P. Koirala the de facto leader of the party.

movement. In the wake of Indian independence, India's assistance to the pro-democracy movement in Nepal was minimal. Indian Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru put some pressure on the Ranas for reforms in Nepal, and with India's guidance, a new constitution was drawn up in Nepal in 1948 (Rose 1971: 181). However, when Padma Shamsher, a relatively liberal Rana Prime Minister, was replaced by Mohan Shamsher, a hard-liner, the road to reform was blocked. Ultimately, the 1948 constitution was scrapped, and the Nepali National Congress Party was banned (Brown 2002: 17).

At this point, the newly independent India had the opportunity to assist pro-democracy forces in Nepal and free it from the oppressive Rana rulers, but that is not what happened. The Ranas appeased the new Indian administration by sending in Nepali troops to quell uprisings in Indian territories, especially Kashmir and Hyderabad (Shaha 1990: 195). In addition, India was successful in persuading the Ranas to accept the 1950 Treaties of Trade and Commerce and Peace and Friendship, seen by many Nepalis to be unjust and unequal. These two treaties virtually 'drew Nepal within India's Himalayan security system and made the country, in practice, into an extension of the Indian economy' (Brown 2002: 17). Indian Prime Minister Nehru often described his Nepal policy as a 'middle way' policy, one that prevents any major upheaval and 'total uprooting of the ancient order,' but at the same time introduces 'some advance in the ways of democracy' (see, Jawaharlal Nehru's Speeches [1949–53] 1963: 176–77).

In terms of engagement and political engineering, Nehru's 'middle way' approach to Nepal became India's *modus operandi*, which his successors adhered to in the subsequent decades. After the 1990s, however, the 'middle way' approach was reshaped as a two-pillar political system: constitutional monarchy and multiparty democracy. In 2006, despite the political atmosphere in Nepal increasingly opposing the preservation of the monarchy in any form, India seemed hesitant to abandon the monarchy until the very last moment.⁵⁶ As seen in instances like these, India's claim to be the largest democracy in the world and a champion of democratic norms and values has not always led to corresponding actions in its immediate neighbourhood. In many cases, India's actions appear more focused on its own national interests rather than on promoting democratic values or the rule of law.

One extraordinary event on 6 November 1950 helped bring political changes in Nepal and gave India, for the first time, the role of an unofficial mediator to settle political disputes in Nepal. On that day, King Tribhuvan, whom the Ranas had virtually confined within the boundaries of the royal palace, sought asylum in the Indian Embassy in Kathmandu.⁵⁷ On the following day, the three-year-old Prince Gyanendra, who was not at the palace when the royals fled, was crowned king by the Ranas (Brown 2002: 18). Three days after Gyanendra's coronation, on 10 November, the royal asylum seekers were flown to New Delhi in a special aeroplane of the Indian Air Force (Joshi & Rose 1966: 74). As already mentioned, this was a unique moment in Nepal's history that openly invited and welcomed India's involvement in managing political disputes and discontent in the country. King Tribhuvan's refuge in India intensified the NNC-led pro-democracy movement in

⁵⁶ This is apparent in political statements that high-profile Indian officials made at the time. In 2006, when the pro-democracy movement was at its peak, India sent a special envoy, Karan Singh, who attempted to persuade Nepali political leaders to accept at least some form of monarchy (see Chapter 5).

⁵⁷ A number of King Tribhuvan's family members accompanied him, including his son and grandson, future kings Mahendra and Birendra.

Nepal. However, it also planted the seeds of India's influence in Nepali politics. In other words, this event arguably provided India with the tools and excuses for political engineering in Nepal.

India refused to recognise the baby king installed by the Ranas as the legitimate king of Nepal. Similarly, the NNC-led anti-Rana revolt intensified, especially in the eastern part of Nepal. The movement took up arms, which was not its original motive. After a series of armed attacks, the insurgents were able to capture seven major cities. After that, the insurgents claimed they were in control of one-third of the country and in a position to seize total power (Brown 2002: 19, Mahat 2005). It is noteworthy that the NNC insurgents used the Indian railway network, connected to the border of Nepal, to transport fighters and weapons, while India 'turned a blind eye' to this⁵⁸ (Basnett 2009: 16).

King Tribhuvan's exile in India, an intensifying armed struggle, and an internal rift within the Ranas substantially weakened the power base of the Rana regime. India had been a proponent of a 'middle-way' approach in Nepal and was somewhat complacent with the ruthless Ranas, for they signed unequal treaties that benefited India. They also provided military support whenever India needed it. This time, however, India sensed a shift in Nepal's political dynamics and was vocal about a democratic transition in Nepal. As a result, in February 1951, India brokered a tripartite compromise between the Ranas, King Tribhuvan, and the leaders of the democratic movement. The compromise, commonly known as the Delhi Accord, ended the 104-year-old Rana oligarchy in Nepal. In the aftermath, an interim government was formed, which included five ministers from the ousted Ranas and five from the democratic forces.⁵⁹ In addition, 'an Interim Government Act designed to usher the country onto the road to full democracy was promulgated' and 'among the principal provisions of the Act were provisions for the election of a constituent assembly' (Subedi 1998: 167).

The elections to a constituent assembly were not organised as agreed earlier. The Shah kings filled the power vacuum left by the Ranas, and their ambition to rule came into odds with the Nepali people's aspirations for democracy. From 1951 to 1959, the monarchy formed and dissolved several governments. Rising demands for a full-fledged democracy compelled King Mahendra to promulgate a new constitution in 1959, under which the first parliamentary elections were held in Nepal. In May 1959, the first democratically elected government took power with a two-thirds majority in parliament.

4.1.3 The Panchayat Era (1960–1990) and India's Contradictory Role

However, the lifespan of the first democratically elected government was very short. In over a year, King Mahendra dissolved parliament, dismissed the cabinet and imprisoned the Prime Minister and other prominent leaders. He also annulled the constitution and assumed absolute power through what has often been called a bloodless coup d'état. King Mahendra justified his actions by arguing that 'the parliamentary system of government was based on foreign and Western models and was not suitable for a country like Nepal (Subedi 1998: 167–168). He also accused the leaders of the party in power of corruption, leniency to India, and that the 'new

⁵⁸ India's nonchalant attitude towards insurgents in Nepal is something that was repeated decades later during the Maoist armed insurgency. This issue will be discussed further in the forthcoming pages.

⁵⁹ India was directly involved in the political arrangements that followed the Delhi Accord. When King Tribhuvan returned to Nepal, an Indian diplomat was sent with him. The diplomat worked as the king's secretary, attended the Nepal government's cabinet meetings, and influenced its decision-making (Ulak 2022).

system as a whole did not allow for the preservation of the social fabric and traditional strengths which had kept the country united and independent since its unification in 1769' (Subedi 1998: 168.). Some scholars, however, note that King Mahendra's claims were largely baseless. They argue that the democratic government was widely popular in the country and had initiated a wide range of reforms, including an extensive land reform scheme. It also intensified industrialisation efforts and secured foreign aid for development projects in Nepal (Mahat 2005, R.M. Nepal 2020).

India was initially critical of King Mahendra's decision to abolish democracy. However, within six months, it had established good relations with him and signed four agreements with Nepal (Whelpton 2005: 101, Rose 1971: 234). This was a clear sign that India's main concern was serving its own interests rather than consolidating a democratic process in Nepal (Mishra 2004: 631).

In October 1961, King Mahendra, during his visit to China, signed a road construction agreement with China. According to the agreement, the proposed Kodari Highway would link Kathmandu to the Nepal–Tibet border, and reduce Nepal's exclusive dependence on India for international transport and transit. India was vocal against the road construction project, claiming it would endanger its national security. The relationship between India and King Mahendra soured after this event. In the same year, the Congress-led armed struggle for the restoration of democracy in Nepal intensified with India's tacit support.⁶⁰ In addition, angered by Nepal's increasing ties with China, India imposed an unofficial economic blockade against Nepal in September 1962⁶¹ (Whelpton 2005: 99).

As King Mahendra's distance from India grew, so did his proximity to China. Being further ambitious and emboldened, in 1962, he promulgated a new constitution and introduced a new partyless system in Nepal, known as the *Panchayat*. Under this system, no political parties were allowed to function, even though people could vote and elect individual candidates as their representatives. The Nepali Congress Party (NCP) and various communist factions strongly opposed the *Panchayat* system. The hardline royal, however, used his image of a 'nationalist king' and the idea of 'Nepalism' to garner public support domestically. This tactic was somewhat successful during the initial *Panchayat* years. Initially, he sought to neutralise any opposition from India by seeking support from countries like China and Pakistan (Parajulee 2000: 51, Khanna 2018: 147). It has also been argued that under Mahendra's direct rule, Nepal began to project a 'non-aligned' image internationally and started practising an independent foreign policy (Lohani 2011: 5–6).

The Sino–Indian border war of 1962, in which India was defeated, altered the political dynamics of South Asia. In the aftermath of the border war, India was in a rather 'subdued mood' (Subedi 1998: 168). Through high-profile visits, it sought to amend the soured relations with Nepal. In a new geopolitical scenario, India craved cooperation with King Mahendra, and on Nehru's request, the Nepali Congress

⁶⁰ While prominent Nepali Congress leaders, such as B.P. Koirala and Ganesh Man Singh, were imprisoned by King Mahendra, the armed struggle was led by Subarna Shamsher, a Congress leader who happened to be in India during the royal takeover. The guerrilla force consisted of around 3,000 soldiers and was operated mostly by Nepali activists in exile in India. Total fatalities of this 'small-scale' armed struggle, nonetheless, stood merely around 130 (Whelpton 2005: 98–102).

⁶¹ India has, in fact, used unofficial economic blockades against Nepal on several occasions, the most recent one in 2015. As a landlocked country, Nepal has historically relied heavily on India for access to the sea. When India wants to pressure Nepal, it has taken advantage of this dependence by imposing unofficial economic blockades.

Party called off the anti-*Panchayat* armed struggle⁶² (Whelpton 2005: 99). By 1963, India's affinity with King Mahendra had grown tremendously (Rose 1964: 726). By 1965, India was successful in persuading him, through a secret agreement, 'not to purchase military equipment from other countries if this could be provided by India' (Whelpton 2005: 102).

Gradually, India began to remain silent about the partyless *Panchayat* system in Nepal, even though it was fully aware that the system was authoritarian, repressive, exclusive, exploitative, and corrupt. India asked anti-*Panchayat* Nepali activists living in exile in India to halt their activities against the royal rule (Mishra 2004: 631). The neighbour in the north, China, was never a fan of democracy or the rule of law, so there was little foreign opposition to King Mahendra's authoritarian rule. The initial *Panchayat* years were marked by relative stability, and King Mahendra also initiated some ambitious development projects. However, overall, the state mechanism was captured by the King and his loyalists, and with rampant corruption, nepotism, and a lack of transparency and accountability, the lives of ordinary Nepalis further deteriorated.

After King Mahendra died in 1972, his son, Birendra, carried on with his father's legacy, with occasional tweaks and turns on the way. Over the years, the leadership changes in India also impacted India–Nepal relations. The 1975 annexation of Sikkim to India and the state of emergency imposed by the Indira Gandhi administration in the same year impacted the Nepali activists working and operating from India. As the political atmosphere in India became somewhat murky under Mrs. Gandhi, key figures of the Nepali democratic movement, including prominent Nepali Congress leader B.P. Koirala, returned to Nepal and advocated for 'national reconciliation'. In practice, this meant cooperation with the monarchy.

In 1979, there were mass student demonstrations in the country, which ultimately forced King Birendra to declare a referendum on the system of government. A nationwide referendum was held on 2 May 1980, in which voters could choose between the partyless *Panchayat* system and a multiparty democratic system. The *Panchayat* system received 54.8% of the votes amid accusations that the referendum was rigged (Phadnis 1981: 447).

After the referendum failed to fulfil their aspirations for democracy, political parties fighting for democracy continued their non-violent campaigns. In 1988, king Birendra closed an arms-purchase deal with China, which angered India (Adhikari et al. 2013: 8). Shortly after this, in 1989, when it was time to renew the trade and transit agreement between the two countries, India chose to delay the process, which meant yet another economic blockade to Nepal (Lee 2009).

As the anti-*Panchayat* movement began to gain momentum, India reportedly forwarded a draft treaty to King Birendra. If signed, the treaty would require Nepal to seek India's consultation and agreement before entering a military alliance with a third country. India also demanded that arms and ammunition imports, training of armed personnel, and any expansion of military units should be done only following prior consultation with India. In addition, through the treaty proposal, India sought preferential treatment of Indian citizens in Nepal and strengthened India's involvement in exploiting Nepal's water resources (Kumar 1992: 144–47, Mishra 2004: 633).

The treaty proposal was sent as a precondition for extending its support to the

⁶² The Nepali Congress Party (NCP) is considered a largely pro-Indian political party in Nepal. While this perception has fluctuated over the years, the party still enjoys greater support from the Indian political establishment. The party was formed in India and modelled after the Indian National Congress Party.

collapsing *Panchayat* regime. Reportedly, Nepal did not accept the proposal, and, instead, in the spring of 1990, King Birendra decided to shun absolute power and reestablish democracy in Nepal after 30 years of authoritarian rule (Kumar 1992, Mishra 2004). As far as India's role in this saga is concerned, it is noteworthy that while India unofficially supported the democratic movement in Nepal, it was also ready to support authoritarian rule, given that its interests were addressed by the King. However, this was not the first time India had demonstrated contradictory behaviour in dealing with Nepal. It did so during the final days of the Ranas; it did so during the last hours of the *Panchayat* rule, and, as I will discuss later, it did so throughout the Maoist insurgency and during the final days of King Gyanendra's direct rule in 2006.

4.2 The Maoist Armed Insurgency (1996–2006)

As discussed in the previous section, after a series of nationwide demonstrations for democracy and waning international support, in 1990, King Birendra agreed to restore multiparty democracy in Nepal.⁶³ In the same year, a new constitution was promulgated, and the Nepali Congress Party and a majority of the Nepali Communist parties accepted constitutional monarchy and multiparty democracy as Nepal's new political pillars.⁶⁴ A relatively small communist faction, known then as the Nepal Communist Party (Masal)⁶⁵, called the new deal treachery and remained underground (Whelpton 2005: 119). Yet another communist faction, the United People's Front (UPF), led by Dr Baburam Bhattarai, took part in elections but maintained its radical image in parliament by calling for more progressive reforms.

The Nepali Congress Party secured a clear majority in the 1991 parliamentary elections, and a new government was formed under the leadership of G. P. Prasad Koirala. The party soon suffered internal rifts and divisions. The elected government collapsed before its five-year term, and Nepal plunged into a new era of 'democratic instability'. This was a major disappointment for ordinary Nepalis who hoped for stability, development and a better future in post-*Panchayat* Nepal.

On 4 February 1996, the communist party faction led by Dr Baburam Bhattarai submitted a 40-point demand to the new Nepali Congress government led by Sher Bahadur Deuba (see Appendix 5). At the bottom of the memorandum, they warned that if there was no positive response from the government within two weeks, they would be forced to launch an armed struggle against the state. The government, which was busy in parliamentary politics and already weak due to intra-party tussles, did not take the warning seriously. However, the UPF did not even wait till their own deadline. On 13 February 1996, four days prior to their ultimatum, they launched what they called a 'People's War' by attacking a police post in western Nepal (Bohara et al. 2006: 114).

The party was rebranded as the Communist Party of Nepal (Maoists), and the 40-point document became a 'war manifesto' of the rebels. Many of the demands listed in the memorandum—which still remains a widely referred and discussed political text in Nepali politics—included issues such as poverty and unemployment in Nepal. It is worth noting that the document was also fiercely critical of India. A

⁶³ King Birendra reportedly faced severe criticism from hardliners within the palace for agreeing to implement democratic reforms in Nepal. One of his fiercest critics was his wife, Queen Aishwarya.

⁶⁴ CPN (UML), the biggest communist party of the time, had reservations about the constitution's content. Still, it decided to join the ongoing political process and contested elections.

⁶⁵ The party was led by Mohan Baidhha (Kiran) and Pushpa Kamal Dahal (Prachanda), who later became prominent figures in the Maoist movement.

part of the opening paragraph of the document read:

Nepal has slid to being the second poorest country in the world; people living below the absolute poverty line has gone up to 71 per cent; the number of unemployed has reached more than 10 per cent while the number of people who are semi-employed or in disguised employment has crossed 60 per cent; the country is on the verge of bankruptcy due to rising foreign loans and deficit trade; economic and cultural encroachment within the country by foreign, and especially Indian expansionists, is increasing by the day; the gap between the rich and the poor and between towns and villages is growing wider.⁶⁶

The first nine demands of the 40-point memorandum deal, directly or indirectly, with India–Nepal relations. For instance, the very first demand calls for abrogating all discriminatory treaties between Nepal and India, including treaties signed between the two countries in 1950. Other demands include tighter control and regulation of the open border between India and Nepal, the closure of Indian Gurkha recruitment centres used for conscripting Nepali youths into the Indian army, and a prohibition on all vehicles with Indian licence plates. In addition, the memorandum also demanded a ban on ‘vulgar Indian films, videos and magazines’, and called for an end to the ‘invasion of imperialist and colonial culture’, an indirect reference to India and the West.

Using anti-India rhetoric as a tactical strategy or a tool to gain political support is quite common in Nepal. Political parties—ranging from the right to the left of the political spectrum—and the Ranas and Shah kings have employed similar strategies at various points in history. The Maoists' criticism of India was one of the harshest, if not the most critical, expressions used by a Nepali political organisation. Despite this rhetorical disdain and verbal opposition, top Maoist leaders took shelter in India and operated the insurgency from there. India, too, largely ignored their presence and seemed to prefer using them as a 'bargaining tool' for dealing with Nepal's political leadership.⁶⁷

4.2.1 Causes of the Maoist Armed Insurgency: Greed, Grievances, or a Bad Neighbour?

The Maoists launched their 'People's War' in Nepal in 1996, at a time when communist movements around the world were either disappearing or in declining and defensive states. With the fall of the Berlin Wall and the collapse of the Soviet Union, be it Peru's *Shining Path* or India's *Naxalites*, the climate for communists was unfavourable globally. During this time, Nepal's Maoists not only initiated an armed struggle but also achieved remarkable success in a short period. The Maoists, who had started the insurgency with a handful of weapons, controlled more than half of Nepal's districts within five years⁶⁸ (Upreti 2008: 113). In addition, they set up their own ‘people's governments’ across the country (Whelpton 2005: 209, Destradi 2010). Within years, the conflict had engulfed all the country's 75 districts, and nearly 70% of Village Development Committees, the basic units of the Nepali state, were in a non-functioning state (Whitfield 2008: 4).

What caused this exceptional growth of a radical communist ideology in a small developing country such as Nepal? While communist movements worldwide

⁶⁶ See Appendix 5 for the full text.

⁶⁷ India's dual approach in dealing with the Maoist rebels will be discussed more in the last section of this chapter.

⁶⁸ While the rebels controlled numerous rural areas of the country, the government had a fairly strong presence in district headquarters and bigger cities.

suffered unprecedented setbacks, what made it possible for Nepal's Maoists to rise as a strong political force, command an insurgency, and ultimately—though through a peace process—rise as Nepal's new rulers? There are no easy answers to these questions, and an exhaustive analysis of the Maoist armed conflict is beyond the scope of this study. However, it is useful to review a few major works that shed light on potential causes of Nepal's Maoist insurgency and the reasons behind the success it enjoyed in Nepal. In addition, India's contradictory engagement with Nepal's political forces during the insurgency has been the subject of much debate and speculation. Therefore, addressing this issue, even briefly, is essential and relevant to this study.

Writing in 1998, two years after the insurgency began, Baburam Bhattarai,⁶⁹ one of the senior-most Maoist ideologues, blamed India for Nepal's underdevelopment and argued that India kept Nepal in semi-colonial bondage (see Bhattarai 1998). He argued that India prevented the development of national capital in Nepal, eyed its natural resources, and imposed exploitative and oppressive behaviour through unequal treaties and agreements. To break the chains of this semi-colonial status, he concluded, the Maoists' People's War was launched. While blaming India for everything that happens in Nepal has its pitfalls, Bhattarai's arguments are not entirely baseless. Writing years before Bhattarai did, Blaikie et al. (1980) made a case of a semi-colonial Nepal that bore the burden of exploitation and dependence in its relationship with India. They also warned of an impending, large-scale political crisis in the country, which indeed later took place as they had predicted.

Various studies, conducted particularly during the later years of the armed insurgency, have looked at domestic causes of the Maoist movement in Nepal. Such studies can be broadly categorised into two types: those that use techniques such as cross-sectional regression to analyse how inequality, poverty, geography, and ethnic or linguistic differences contributed to the insurgency. In contrast, studies of the second type often emphasise the failures of post-1990 governments in Nepal and raise issues related to conflict incentives.

For instance, Murshed & Gates (2005) found that grievances, expressed in ethnic and caste discrimination, landlessness, and other inequalities, were the main catalysts for the Maoist insurgency in Nepal. Other scholars, such as Thapa & Sijapati (2004), Deraniyagala (2005), Bohara et al. (2006), Parwez (2006), Macours (2006), Tiwari (2009), Basnett (2009), Do & Iyer (2010), and Piya & Maharjan (2009) came up with similar findings. Deraniyagala (2005: 61), for instance, argued that 'a long history of agricultural stagnation, inequalities in land ownership, inadequate investment in human development and social and physical infrastructure and an extractive and predatory state' were responsible not only for uneven development and poverty, but also for the armed conflict. In addition, she noted that the Maoist armed insurgency began during a period of economic liberalisation in Nepal, which not only aggravated already existing inequalities, but also created new ones.

Using detailed casualty datasets, Do & Iyer (2010) found that conflict-related deaths were significantly higher in poorer districts and mountains, i.e. in areas favourable for running a guerrilla movement. They indicated that poverty made recruiting fighters cheaper for the insurgents, but a higher level of poverty also

⁶⁹ Mr Bhattarai was the second-most senior party leader, headed the rebels' 'people's government' and drafted the party's ideological documents. In 2015, when Nepal declared a new constitution through a constituent assembly, Mr Bhattarai declared renouncing the communist ideology, resigned from the Maoist party, and began forming a new 'non-communist' political group under his leadership.

meant 'a greater level of grievances against the government', and 'more support for insurgent groups' (p. 745). Indeed, the Maoists' strategy was to use both the mountainous geography and people's grievances. As Hachhethu (2005: 138) states:

The Maoists' internal party document prepared before the launch of the armed struggle demonstrates that the rebels planned to capitalise on Nepal's mountainous geography as well as on perceived grievances of ethnic groups, peasants, Nepalis in rural areas and in the Indian diaspora, who had often been forgotten by the state.

As in many other civil wars, the Maoist armed insurgency has also been viewed from the 'greed versus grievance' perspective. Proponents of the greed model⁷⁰, who mostly seem to come from the mainstream economic tradition, argue that civil wars are primarily fought not because of persisting inequalities or grievances, but because of potential financial incentives for rebel groups. These models portray insurgencies as economic activities rather than actions oriented towards pursuing ideological or political goals. In an attempt to analyse Nepal's armed conflict from this perspective, Acharya (2009: 17), for instance, argues that the rebel leaders and their subordinate soldiers engaged in a contractual relationship (akin to that of employers and employees) and the insurgency survived as long as the 'operating costs' remained low. He concluded that the Maoist armed insurgency in Nepal did not 'appear to be linked in any causal way to grievances, social factors or even ideology. It was incentives that mattered most' (p. 18).

However, many of the arguments presented by scholars who support the greed model do not appear to apply to the situation in Nepal. First, the argument that the rebels joined the insurgency merely for economic reasons is implausible. As far as their personal safety was concerned, being part of a guerrilla movement was a risky decision for the insurgents. The remuneration they received as a rebel soldier would be much less than what they could have earned by joining the government security forces or, in a desperate situation, selling their manual labour in India. In addition, these economic models fail to recognise that an insurgency is much more than recruiting militants and fighting one successful battle after another. As evident in Nepal's case, many people who joined the Maoist movement—be it party cadres engaged in non-combative work, women groups, students, peasants, and many others—received no remuneration. It is also worth highlighting that combatants are part of an insurgency, and though their role might be important, it is not always the most crucial one.

Another shortcoming of the greed model, which does not make sense in Nepal's case, is that they see armed insurgencies targeted at controlling lootable resources. They often argue that insurgencies do not progress when a lucrative natural resource is absent. To support this claim, they often cite examples of the so-called blood minerals from Africa, Afghanistan's opium, and the widespread drug production and smuggling in conflict-ridden Latin American countries. However, this was not the case in Nepal. There was no 'lootable resource' in Nepal that the rebels could have controlled and benefited from. Instead, the Maoist movement relied heavily on voluntary donations and finances from various extortion. In other words, the insurgency per se was not aimed at controlling or benefitting from a lucrative natural resource.

Finding the root causes of a conflict is difficult, as conflicts begin for a range of reasons. In Nepal's case, too, it can be argued that the Maoist armed conflict was a

⁷⁰ See, for instance, Collier & Hoeffler (1998) and Collier & Hoeffler (2004) for an in-depth understanding of the 'greed' model.

result of several causes, including poverty and underdevelopment (Thapa & Sijapati 2004), social exclusion of certain minorities and ethnic groups (Gurung 2007, Lawoti 2005), government suppression of the leftist political activities in the Midwestern region (Acharya 2009: 7), inequalities in land ownership, and social chasms created by post-1990 economic liberalisation (Deraniyagala 2005). Finally, an unequal relationship and deep dependency on its southern neighbour, India, also catalysed the conflict (Bhattarai 1998).

Overall, the Maoist armed insurgency expressed the widespread frustration of people in the post-1990s. After a long and difficult struggle, democracy was reestablished in Nepal in 1990, and ordinary Nepalis had high hopes in the new system. However, these expectations were shattered as mainstream political parties that rose to power following the democratic movement became entangled in ongoing power struggles. They failed to focus on solving the problems of the people. The grievances of historically marginalised and oppressed communities were never adequately addressed.

Some scholars have raised the issue of frustration and unmet expectations as potential triggers for the conflict. For instance, Parwez (2006) and Fujikura (2003) argued that a higher level of education in a democratic environment raised people's expectations. However, the lack of economic opportunities engendered public frustration and ultimately led to revolt and violence. Similarly, Tiwari (2009: 24) proposed that the insurgency was caused by a 'mismatch' between political and economic empowerment, because an equal level of economic empowerment did not accompany increased political empowerment in the post-1990 era. In a similar spirit, Shneiderman et al. (2016: 2042) argue that the Maoist conflict should be considered merely a single element in a much broader process of transformation that Nepal was going through. These transformative elements, they highlight, included democratisation, identity politics, migration, state restructuring, and the emergence of a remittance economy.

These explanations appear more plausible than those trying to squeeze the conflict within the oddly crafted greed-versus-grievances continuum. As I mentioned at the beginning of this chapter, the Maoist armed insurgency was a disruptive political event that emerged when Nepal was going through a significant socio-political transformation. It is also worth noting that the insurgency's inception happened in a particular political context. However, as the insurgency progressed, some elements⁷¹—such as the political instability, corruption, and the royal massacre of 2001—helped it become what it later became: a full-fledged civil war-like conflict. The later years of the insurgency were particularly marked by daily instances of violence, numerous casualties, and the government's gradual loss of territorial and administrative control.

4.2.2 Cost of the Conflict

The decade-long Maoist armed insurgency was the bloodiest and most violent

⁷¹ Political empowerment and the shift in people's consciousness in the post-1990 democratic era was certainly one element that made the Maoist armed insurgency possible. However, other political events also facilitated its growth and its ultimate spread. These events include the 2001 royal massacre (when Nepal's King, Queen, and other prominent members of the royal family were shot and killed), a confused government that lacked the political will and skills to deal with the insurgency when it was nascent, widespread rift and divisions within the mainstream political parties, and India's nonchalant approach towards the Maoist rebels taking shelter in its land. In later years, the insurgency intensified mainly due to the repressive approach taken by King Gyanendra, who refused to recognise the armed insurgency as a political issue and tagged the rebels as terrorists who had lost their way. He also sought international support to repress and defeat the rebels by force.

episode in Nepal's modern history. In terms of human lives that were lost and the physical damage and destruction it caused, the conflict was of immense scale. The armed conflict also left a deep scar in Nepal's social fabric that will take decades to heal. According to the figures released by Nepal's Ministry for Peace and Reconstruction (2013), in total, the insurgency took at least 17,886 lives.⁷² More than 3,000 people were abducted, and nearly 1,600 people disappeared during the violent decade (1996–2006). In addition, nearly 9,000 people were left maimed and disabled, and the number of displaced people stood at around 80,000.⁷³

In terms of physical damage, the conflict was equally destructive. It is estimated that nearly 17,500 individual properties were destroyed during the conflict (Ministry for Peace and Reconstruction, Nepal 2013). In addition, in an attempt to weaken the state, the Maoist rebels adopted an undeclared policy of destroying public property. As a result, more than 2,000 schools and nearly 4,000 public offices were demolished during the conflict (Ghimire 2013). The insurgents also destroyed bridges, burned down electricity plants, and demolished government infrastructure.

The conflict negatively affected economic activities, hampered economic growth, and was undoubtedly a severe blow to Nepal's fledgling post-1990 economy. For instance, the GDP growth rate during the early 1990s stood at around 5%. However, as the conflict progressed and peaked during the early 2000s, the GDP growth shrank sharply, averaging barely 2.5% per annum (National Planning Commission of Nepal 2003, Deraniyagala 2005: 57). The conflict had multisectoral impacts and badly affected vital sectors of Nepal's economy, such as tourism, agriculture, industry and commerce.

The armed conflict also altered Nepal's social and demographic structure. In search of safety, people started moving from villages to cities, some of them chased off by the rebels and tagged as 'class enemies'. Hit hard by the uncertainty and unemployment the armed conflict brought, many Nepali youths started migrating abroad—mainly to Middle Eastern and East Asian countries—to sell menial labour. As years passed, the migration trend intensified, ultimately changing the Nepali economy's entire outlook. Nepal's economy gradually shifted from being primarily an agricultural economy to a remittance economy.⁷⁴ Post-conflict Nepal has a new economic face, and so does its demography. The rapid international migration of Nepali youths has caused tremendous demographic and social changes, whose long-term impacts are yet to be seen.

As reported in various studies,⁷⁵ the conflict also left a huge psychological impact on ordinary Nepalis. Killing, abduction, torture, arbitrary arrests, rape, and the use of child soldiers were common war strategies adopted both by the rebels and government security forces.⁷⁶ As the conflict intensified, especially in the later years, children's rights, women's rights, and ordinary people's economic, social, and

⁷² This figure is disputed, as some other estimations show the casualties to be higher or lower than this one.

⁷³ While most people were internally displaced, some managed to leave Nepal for employment in India or Gulf countries. Some also sought asylum in various Western countries.

⁷⁴ In 1996, the year the conflict began, the proportion of remittances in Nepal's GDP was merely 0.97%. As the armed conflict intensified, there was a sharp increase in the number of Nepali youths travelling abroad for foreign employment. By 2006, the year the conflict ended, the proportion of remittances in the GDP was 16.06%, which further rose to 31.20% in 2016 (World Bank 2019).

⁷⁵ See, for instance, Thapa & Hauff (2005), Tol et al. (2010), and Kohrt et al. (2012) to get a detailed overview of the psychological and emotional impact borne by ordinary Nepalis because of the Maoist armed insurgency.

⁷⁶ For an elaborate analysis of conflict-related violations of international human rights law and international humanitarian law between February 1996 and 21 November 2006, see, for instance, OHCHR (2012).

cultural rights were severely compromised (Khanal 2017). In addition, since transitional justice issues and reconciliation processes were largely overlooked in the years following the CPA, a culture of impunity thrived in post-conflict Nepal (Jeffery 2017, Adhikari et al. 2014). Having been inspired by the Maoist insurgency and the political gains and spotlight it had received, Nepal also witnessed a rise and proliferation of other small armed groups, which perpetuated the culture of violence also in the post-insurgency years.⁷⁷

4.3 Locating India's Role in Nepal's Peace Process and Political Transition (2005–2017): A Review of Previous Research

As the Maoist armed insurgency emerged as a formidable force in Nepal in the early 2000s, academic interest in it also grew. Initially, scholarly interest was mainly limited to analysing the origins of the conflict and estimating its potential outcomes (see, for instance, Karki & Seddon 2003, Thapa & Sijapati 2004, Hutt 2004). However, in later years, with the onset of the peace process, academic focus also began to shift. More attention was given to broader peacebuilding issues, including constitution-making, state restructuring, inclusivity, development, and the rhetoric of building a 'new Nepal'.

The role of international actors in the Nepali conflict was analysed during the conflict and also in the aftermath. When it comes to Nepal's peace process, India has always been the elephant in the room. Other international actors, such as the US, the UK, China, the EU, and several other international organisations, were present, on and off, in the scene. However, as Jha (2012: 332) argues, they were mostly responsible for paying the bills of the peace process. In contrast, India had the strongest presence and ultimately received most of the credit for the relatively successful peace process (see Chapter 5).

Even though studies on international engagement in Nepal's peace process and political transition have centred around India, India's role in Nepal's peace process and political transition remains a poorly understood topic. For instance, Subedi & Bhattarai (2017: 95) argue that India's engagement in Nepal's peace process also needs further study because India's role has been both 'unclear and questionable'.

Previous literature that deals with India's engagement in Nepal's peace process and political transition can be broadly categorised into three. Works that assess India's involvement during the armed insurgency—before the 12-Point Understanding and the CPA—provide crucial historical insights into how India became a major player in Nepal's conflict resolution scene. Second, studies focusing on India's involvement during the crucial years of the peace process (i.e., between 2005 and 2008) are important because they provide insight into India's actual involvement in activities leading up to the peace deal and its immediate aftermath. Third, studies that emerged after the initial years of the peace process are also relevant because they investigate India's long-term engagement in the later years of political transition.

Scholars who have examined India's approach to the Maoist insurgency in Nepal generally agree that India's role during the insurgency was inconsistent and contradictory (see, for instance, Shah 2004, Mishra 2004, Bhattarai 2005, Whelpton 2005, Whitfield 2008, Upreti 2009, Destradi 2010, Sharma 2013, Adhikari 2017, and Dhungel 2019: 24). While Nepal's northern neighbour, China,

⁷⁷ See, for instance, Thapa (2017) and Rawski (2009) for an overview of the armed groups that were active in the wake of the Maoist armed insurgency.

saw the use of the term 'Maoist' as an insult to their leader Mao Zedong, labelled the Nepali Maoists as an 'anti-government outfit', and extended no concrete support to them (Upadhyaya 2012: 136), Nepal's southern neighbour, India took a different approach. Despite declaring the Maoists a terrorist group, India showed little or no interest in curbing their activities in India (Bhattarai 2005: 34, Upreti 2009: 223). The Maoist rebels not only received training from various guerrilla groups in India (Bhattarai 2005: 32), but the top rebel leaders mostly lived in various parts of India⁷⁸ and were able to operate from there with little or no restriction (Mishra 2004: 638).

In the later years of the conflict, India continued its paradoxical approach as internal polarisation intensified among major political forces in Nepal. On one hand, it denounced King Gyanendra's direct rule and advocated for a 'twin-pillar' political system in Nepal (i.e., constitutional monarchy and multiparty democracy). On the other hand, it also provided military assistance to Nepali security forces fighting the Maoists under the King's direct command. Similarly, it showed little interest in Maoist activities that took place in various parts of India. Instead of suppressing their activities, India kept in touch with the rebel leaders for a potential coalition-building between the Maoists and Nepal's mainstream political parties agitating against King Gyanendra's rule (Destradi 2010: 18, Adhikari 2017: 32, Sharma 2013). This way, 'by supporting and supplying both sides of the civil war in Nepal,' Shah (2004: 223) argued, India 'perfected the imperial art of divide and rule'.

India's indifference towards the Maoists, however, was not unilateral. The Maoists reciprocated by carefully avoiding activities that interfered with India's interests.⁷⁹ While the Maoists' political documents were riddled with anti-Indian rhetoric, in practice, nothing remarkably anti-Indian took place during the insurgency. This discrepancy between the words and actions of both India and the Maoists has been used by some scholars (such as Shah 2004, Mishra 2004) to advance the narrative that the Maoist movement was potentially a ploy employed by India to weaken the Nepali state and, as a result, to keep a more pliable regime in Kathmandu. In addition, Shah (2004: 202) went on to argue that uprisings and insurgencies that had no external backing did not survive and thrive in Nepal, which was not the case with the Maoist armed insurgency.⁸⁰

Arguments like these are undoubtedly useful for vilifying both India and the Maoists simultaneously. Such statements have been favourites of royalists and conspiracy theorists, both inside and outside Nepal. However, most of these arguments, such as the notion that the Maoist insurgency was potentially a foreign ploy, lack evidence. In the absence of credible evidence, such arguments serve no purpose and reduce a large-scale armed insurgency to a petty ploy of a nagging

⁷⁸ While many top Maoist leaders did live in India throughout the conflict, they have denied any support from the Indian establishment. They have often argued that since India is a vast 'ocean' of people, it was not hard for them to hide in Indian cities. This is both plausible as well as contradictory. India, indeed, is a densely populated country, and hiding in India would not be difficult. However, given that India has professional and well-established intelligence agencies, tracking down foreign rebels would not be that difficult, either. When willing to do so, India did, for instance, run a crackdown on Bhutanese dissidents hiding in and operating from India.

⁷⁹ For instance, in 1998, when the Kalapani border dispute between Nepal and India was at its peak, many political parties in Nepal used that as political capital and portrayed themselves as patriots who did not give in to Indian aggression. The Maoists, however, chose to neglect the issue and were absent from the scene altogether (Mishra 2004: 635).

⁸⁰ For this, he used the examples of Dr K. I. Singh's failed revolt in the wake of the 1950 Delhi Agreement, as well as the short-lived and failed armed campaign launched by a communist faction in eastern Nepal in the 1970s.

neighbour. In addition, they bluntly neglect and undermine the social and political psyche of post-1990 Nepal.

As already discussed, India acted in a contradictory manner when it provided an undeclared 'shelter' to the Maoists and supplied arms and ammunition to Nepali security forces loyal to the King. However, that does not mean that the entire insurgency was a plot designed and implemented by New Delhi. As Nepali Maoist leaders often tend to argue, they were simply using India to serve their political and tactical goals. India was likely doing the same, using the rebels to maintain its traditional grip on Nepal or to keep the country mildly unstable, as it has often been accused of doing in the past. For New Delhi, the Maoists indeed served as a bargaining tool that it could tactfully use in its dealings with Kathmandu. Using opposing political forces as leverage in Nepal is an old habit of India, and a quick look at Nepal's history shows this clearly. Throughout various junctures in history, India has utilised nearly all political forces in Nepal, including the traditional democratic parties, regional political groups, the Maoists, and the monarchy, whenever necessary.

The tendency to label the Maoists as India's pawns or to argue that New Delhi planted and cultivated the Maoist armed struggle undermines the Maoist movement's role in steering Nepal towards a progressive path. Democracy, the rule of law, secularism, and inclusivity are widely cherished ideals of contemporary Nepal. While one can be critical of or loathe the Maoists' violent politics, one cannot be oblivious to their contribution to shaping today's Nepal, which is significantly more progressive, more democratic, and more prosperous than it has ever been. The Maoist movement made not only a political contribution, but also a social one. As Adhikari (2014: 275) puts it, the rebels 'taught large sections of the population to organize and agitate in the face of injustice, instead of quietly accepting their position in the social hierarchy'.

The dubious role that India played during the Maoist insurgency is well-known and has been discussed in detail by several scholars. However, when it comes to India's involvement in the background negotiations that led to the 12-Point Understanding, confusion persists. This is also the case with India's involvement in the aftermath of the 2006 peace deal.

Interestingly, India's involvement in Nepal's peace process was predicted even before the process was conceived, long before the signing of the 12-Point Understanding in New Delhi. Writing at the peak of the armed conflict, Mishra (2004: 646), for instance, noted that 'any solution to the Maoist problem must involve winning the hearts and minds of the Indian authorities, perhaps more so than winning the hearts and minds of the Maoists themselves'.

While Mishra's (2004) arguments certainly appear to have been exaggerated and more provocative than realistic, nonetheless, it was evident that some form of Indian involvement would be unavoidable if a successful peace process was to be implemented in Nepal. Some scholars, such as Bhattarai (2005: 35), also noted that India was unhappy when it was not consulted during the 2003 peace talks and that India was unwilling to see a third-party involvement, except its own, in an eventual peace process that would take place in Nepal. Similarly, at the dawn of the peace process, Upreti (2006: 207) wrote:

India does not want to see any outsider being active in [the] Nepalese armed conflict. Considering itself as a regional power, it wants to handle all the issues arising in South Asia itself.

Similar predictions were made concerning India's eventual involvement in post-conflict Nepal. A year after the signing of the CPA, Janjua (2007: 86), for instance, warned that India's involvement in post-conflict Nepal would be an active one and that India could even put pressure on Nepali political parties to appoint ministers of its choice and implement pro-Indian policies. As I explore in subsequent chapters, these predictions, more or less, came true, and India's presence in Nepal rapidly grew in the peace process and political transition years.

Amid these predictions and various unverified anecdotes circulating in the media, confusion remains over India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition. This confusion is continuously reflected in works that have emerged after the 2006 peace deal. Some scholars, such as Adhikari (2017: 32), term India's role as an aggressive one, while others have used somewhat softer tones. Some of the common references, however, include terming India's involvement as a 'facilitative one' (Destradi 2010:17, Shrestha 2012: 211, Ghimire 2018a: 6), the one that provided 'tacit support' (Whitfield 2008: 6), or a mediator that took on the job intending to coerce the rebels to shun arms and to steer them towards mainstream politics (Poudel 2018: 7). It has also been argued that the 12-Point-Understanding, which sketched Nepal's post-conflict roadmap for peace and democracy, would not have been possible in the absence of India's support (Whitfield 2008: 6).

Having reflected on India's engagement from the early years of the conflict, Upreti (2009: 234) argued that among international actors, India's presence was the most extensive, so much so that, especially during the later years, Nepal became 'entirely dependent on India' for managing its peace process. As I will discuss in subsequent chapters, this state of dependency was not limited merely to conflict resolution. It had stretched to other domains, and some of the most critical Nepali state institutions had become victims of India's minute manipulation and massive micromanagement (see Chapters 6 and 7).

Often furthered by Indian scholars, there are also less critical, widely romanticised, and overtly optimistic versions of India's engagement in post-conflict Nepal. Mehta (2011), for instance, argued that against the backdrop of the conflict and democratic movement, India had been 'very actively' promoting democracy in Nepal. Similarly, Janjua (2007: 101) claimed that, though carried out with the consent of the UK and the US, India's engagement in post-conflict Nepal aimed to establish a 'full-fledged' democracy. H.B. Jha (2014: 57) argued that India had been acting out of its passion for safeguarding democracy and that, at times, its passion for democracy had been proved costly.

However, the narrative of India as a democracy promoter has been entirely rejected by other scholars. For instance, Destradi (2010: 3) argued that India's engagement in Nepal was guided by 'short-term stability concerns' and could not be considered to be an act of democracy promotion. In Bhattarai's (2018: 13) words, India's actions were aimed at 'taking control over decision-making processes in Nepal, and securing its own self-interests'. Similarly, Anderson (2014: 11) argued that India was motivated by security-oriented concerns rather than a desire to ensure a smooth democratic process in Nepal. India's use of the 'democracy card', however, is not surprising as it has also done so in the past to promote its interests in Nepal (H.B. Jha 2014: 57).

The issue of motive has also received some scholarly attention, and at the crux of it is the question: What motive does India have for its extensive engagement in Nepal? This is a difficult question, and the topic of India–Nepal relations is as vast as the history of the two countries. However, one thing is clear: India's interests in

Nepal are numerous and often complex. Whenever necessary, India has employed various forms of rhetoric, including democracy promotion, peacebuilding, development assistance, and its much-touted neighbourhood first policy. Reflecting on India's previous engagements in Nepal, Shah (2004: 201), for instance, argued that India harboured the habit of using its democratic credentials merely to 'give a moral colouring to its acts of economic and political manipulation in Nepal'. Arguments put forward during the later years of the political transition echoed similar undertones.

Referring to India's engagement in post-conflict Nepal, Musachhio (2018: 40), for instance, argues that, by 'presenting democracy through a discourse entailing development, New Delhi managed to corroborate its hegemony over Nepal by means of soft power'. He further argues that India portrayed its image as a democracy-promoter in an attempt to achieve its foreign policy interests, which included fostering its bilateral ties with the United States⁸¹, preventing a potential spread of Maoist insurgency in India, and securing a conducive environment for implementing projects with the economic interests of India. While arguments suggesting India's hegemonic tendencies may be plausible, there is a lack of detailed analysis on how these tendencies are executed on the ground. In addition, as I show in the next two chapters, India's self-portrayal was not limited to exhibiting itself as a democracy promoter. It was enamoured with its emerging reputation as a formidable actor in international mediation and peacebuilding—an identity it sought to cultivate as part of its global profile to advance its broader ambitions on the world stage.

Although limited, there have been some attempts to explore India's involvement during the peace negotiation phase, its aftermath, and the later years of the peace process and political transition. Over the last two decades, India has become a lucrative genre in Nepal's non-fiction publishing scene. Its actions in Nepal, both actual and perceived, have become popular subjects that simultaneously evoke fear, anxiety, and speculation. Unsurprisingly, books about India's presence in Nepal achieved tremendous commercial success in the growing book market of post-conflict Nepal. However, this has also led to some drawbacks. Enticed by the potential for profit, some authors have produced works that rely heavily on unsubstantiated anecdotes and conspiracy theories.

A few authors, especially Nepali investigative journalists such as Sharma (2013), Adhikari (2012), and P. Jha (2014), appear to have made a sincere attempt to investigate and analyse India's engagement in post-conflict Nepal. Their work, to a certain degree, demonstrates India's extensive engagement in post-conflict Nepal, which was not only affecting Nepal's everyday politics, but also gradually weakening Nepal's sovereignty. These works come across as overly journalistic and depend heavily on detailed descriptions of everyday political events. In short, they lack critical perspectives and an academic tone, often missing connections to relevant theoretical concepts. This study aims to bridge that gap by linking theory with practice through an inductive process while also making a theoretical contribution.

Though successful only in part, a few scholars attempted to investigate the issue more rigorously and with a critical academic tone. Adhikari (2014), for instance, offered instances of Indian micromanagement in post-conflict Nepal. His account includes how Indian embassy officials in Kathmandu were engaged in negotiating post-conflict political deals and 'containing' the Maoists. Similarly, Jha (2012) attempts to provide what he calls a 'Nepali perspective' on international

⁸¹ Among others, through an anti-terrorism coalition-building.

involvement in Nepal between 2005 and 2010 by covering crucial political events that occurred in that period. His assessment helps us understand how different international actors were involved in Nepal's peace process during its crucial phase. Though his focus is not exclusively on India, he successfully portrays the uneasiness and confusion among Nepali stakeholders regarding India's involvement. The way India's involvement was received and interpreted in Nepal is another vital issue he raises. He states:

Monarchists, sections of the military, and established parliamentary parties claim that Delhi provided the Maoists with a safe haven during the war, got them to Kathmandu, destroyed the monarchy, and effected regime change. Others praise India for helping end the war (Jha 2012: 333).

Similarly, Whitfield (2008) covered various political events between 2000 and 2008, a time span that covers early dialogue promotion to the first constituent assembly elections. Like Jha (2012), she attempts to analyse the roles of different international actors in Nepal's peace process and touches upon India's role. Even though her brief analysis of India's engagement is insufficient to offer an elaborate picture of India's extensive engagement in Nepal, she successfully demonstrates how other international actors suffered and were ultimately sidelined because of India. She, for instance, found that some international actors, especially the small ones, such as the Switzerland-based Centre for Humanitarian Dialogue and the US-based Carter Centre, had to put up, often by using policies of 'tolerance' and 'avoidance', with India's emphatic presence in Nepal (Whitfield 2008: 35). Whitfield's (2008) work offers a valuable insight into the roles of various international actors in Nepal's peace process. However, its main limitation is the timespan it covers. Many of India's interventions that had a tremendous impact in Nepal occurred mainly after 2008, something that is missing from her work.

A handful of studies have also examined India's engagement in the later years of the peace process and political transition. Bhattarai (2018), for instance, looks at India's role in Nepal's constitution-making process and identifies four strategies India employed to influence the content of Nepal's new constitution and the decision-making processes. According to him, India's four strategies were high-level dialogue, economic blockade, international coalition building, and targeted support for domestic oppositional forces in Nepal. He also touches upon India's uneasiness, impatience, and concern over China and Western countries' growing presence in Nepal. He notes how India was 'looking for avenues through which it could send a message of it being the most influential power in Nepal' (p. 5). Similarly, Ghimire (2018a) investigated security sector governance in post-war Nepal and found that India used elite-level interactions to advance its security interests. Ghimire's (2018a) findings help us understand India's influence on Nepal's security sector in the peace process years. However, his exclusive focus on the security sector is insufficient to tell a holistic story of India's influence in Nepal, which extends well beyond the security sector. As I explain in subsequent chapters, India's influence included political meddling and micromanagement that affected Nepal's day-to-day politics, bureaucracy, as well as state apparatuses and decision-making mechanisms.

Scholars such as Shah (2004) and Ghimire (2018b) have incorporated a broader theoretical dimension in their works to analyse the tumultuous India–Nepal relations of the 21st century, among other things. They view the relationship between the two countries as the reproduction of patron-client relationships that

world systems and dependency theories once fervently advocated to demonstrate the unequal and exploitative relationship between countries in the Global North and the Global South (see Chapter 3). Continuing with this theme, Destradi (2010: 289) reflects on India's desire to be an uncontested regional power. She argues that, through its carefully planned actions in Nepal, India aimed to be seen as a 'benevolent hegemon' in the region.

As mentioned above, there is a small but growing body of literature on India's role in Nepal's peace process and political transition. Although some promising works have emerged in the last two decades, the current literature has notable limitations, which I will outline in the following paragraphs.

First, most previous studies cover only a fraction of the peace process and political transition period. To the best of my knowledge, no study has covered the entire peace process and political transition period. A similar pattern is evident in the choice of topics. Instead of adopting a holistic approach, many studies have taken a narrow focus, confining themselves to specific areas. This has resulted, at best, in isolated fragments of the complete story.

Second, some studies appear blatantly naïve and lack the critical approach that the subject of this type demands. For instance, Destradi (2010: 23) sees India's so-called 'pro-democratic' activities in Nepal as 'quiet' in nature and also praises what she calls 'India's continued adherence to the principles of noninterference and sovereignty'. Similarly, Anderson (2014: 10) portrays India's image as a 'supportive larger neighbour' that is inclined not to be seen as an 'imposing regional hegemon'. Such arguments, often advanced by Western scholars lacking an in-depth understanding of South Asian regional dynamics, political complexity, and a grasp of the complex India–Nepal relations, do not sufficiently represent the ground reality. As I show in subsequent chapters, India's engagement has rarely been 'quiet' in Nepal. As evident in the experiences of the key informants I interviewed, for those who engage in everyday *realpolitik* or have to put up with India's dominance, there appears to be nothing in their experience that can be equated with quiet behaviour or silent diplomacy. Even a quick, superficial look at the history of India's influence in Nepal is sufficient to demonstrate bouts of Indian aggression and that India has rarely exercised a 'quiet diplomacy' in Nepal.

Third, as I briefly discussed above, some scholars have resorted to glorifying or romanticising India's involvement in Nepal by labelling its actions as value-based and often portraying them as 'benign' actions intended for peace, democracy, and stability in Nepal. These arguments often contradict the facts on the ground and have been challenged multiple times by other scholars. Shah (2004: 200), for instance, noted as early as the mid-2000s, that 'the overall thrust of New Delhi's policies towards Nepal has been inspired by narrow national interests and not universal values, even if concerns about democracy, human rights, and progress are occasionally raised to legitimize aggressive pursuits.'

Fourth, there is also a growing number of works that prefer presenting an overtly Indo-centric view of political events in Nepal (see, for instance, Muni 2012, Sharma 2013, P. Jha 2014). For scholars who adopt this approach, India is behind everything that happens in Nepal. Dwelling exclusively on an Indo-centric view for analysing the political realities of Nepal is problematic for several reasons. Chief among them is the failure to acknowledge the agency of Nepali political actors, who actively shape and influence the country's political landscape. While India's presence in Nepal has been significant, so too has been the resistance from the Nepali people and political actors. In this context, narratives that depict India as the 'sole' or 'ultimate authority' in Nepal are inaccurate and harmful. Such

portrayals, often advanced by an active Indian intelligentsia and a provocative media, undermine the resistance, resilience, and ongoing struggle of Nepali actors. As Nepal tries to break free from the so-called 'special relationship'⁸² with India—by proactively diversifying its foreign relations, opening new trade routes, or elevating its presence in international arenas—an insecure India is visible on many fronts. While stories of dominance and dependency are important, I argue that stories of defiance are equally essential. Excessive focus on the former has often led to neglecting the latter, which this study aims to address.

Finally, scholars examining India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition, or India–Nepal relations overall, primarily rely on international relations as their theoretical framework. While this might appear to be an obvious choice for analysing relations between two countries, limiting an analysis fixated on a single theoretical domain has its own pitfalls. Relations between countries are complex and multifaceted, especially in today's world. India and Nepal are no exceptions. In this situation, rather than sticking to the traditional 'realist' or 'liberalist' approaches of international relations, a multidisciplinary theoretical approach can better analyse the complex and multifaceted relationships between two states. In this study, I aimed to address this issue by broadening my theoretical approach beyond a narrow IR perspective. I incorporated insights also from other fields of the social sciences, including peace and conflict studies, mediation studies, global development studies, and South–South relations.⁸³

4.4 Chapter Summary: Nepal's Path to Peace, Historical Context and India's Engagement

In this chapter, I provided a comprehensive overview of the complex historical and political context of the Nepali peace process and political transition. In the first section, I critically examined Nepal's modern history and offered a brief but insightful look at the country's painful transformative process, which occurred particularly during the last century. This historical context is crucial for understanding Nepal's challenging post-conflict journey, India's long-term engagement in Nepal, and Nepal's road towards becoming a more participatory, inclusive, secular, and democratic federal republic.

In the second section, I provided an overview of the Maoist armed insurgency (1996–2006) and its profound impact on Nepali society. While I did not offer an exhaustive analysis, I critically examined the origins and development of the armed insurgency and briefly discussed its causes and consequences. I argued that the Maoist insurgency was one of the most violent episodes in Nepal's modern history. It claimed more than 17,000 lives and damaged the country's economy. However, it also significantly reshaped the structure of the Nepali state, elevated the political consciousness of the Nepali people, and altered the overall political landscape of post-conflict Nepal.

In the third section, I provided a comprehensive review of the existing literature on India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition. This review lays the groundwork for my analysis in the subsequent chapters and highlights the study's contributions to the field. I concluded the chapter by identifying five key issues that previous studies failed to address. That justifies the need for this

⁸² Which, in many ways, can be translated as a 'special dependency' or even a 'special bondage'.

⁸³ Though South–South relations could be considered to be a strand of IR, they differ significantly from traditional IR approaches in terms of their scope and origin (see Chapter 3).

research and highlights its potential to fill important gaps in the current understanding of India's role in Nepal's recent political history. The next chapter critically evaluates India's involvement in the 12-Point Understanding signed in November 2005 in New Delhi between the Communist Party of Nepal (Maoist) and the Seven Party Alliance.

5. Destined to be in Delhi? An Assessment of India's Role in the 12-Point Understanding Process

In this chapter, I offer a critical assessment of India's involvement in the processes that led to the signing of the 12-Point Understanding in November 2005 in New Delhi between the Communist Party of Nepal (Maoist) and a group of seven Nepali political parties, known as the Seven Party Alliance (SPA). The chapter begins by addressing some underlying issues related to the 12-Point Understanding. It emphasises the importance of critically assessing India's involvement in the 12-Point Understanding, as well as its role in Nepal's peace process and political transition over the past two decades. In addition, I provide a brief account of previous attempts for peace and discuss potential reasons why those attempts were unsuccessful. As I evaluate India's role as an unofficial mediator or facilitator, I provide an account of the active involvement of Nepali political actors in allying to oppose the autocratic rule of King Gyanendra. I conclude the chapter by arguing that while India's role in the processes that led to the 12-Point Understanding was primarily 'facilitative,' the credit it received or sought was significant. In an attempt to promote itself as an uncontested regional power and project its image as a peacebuilder, India resorted to pursuits that dimmed its image in Nepal. Similarly, by consistently trying to assert a stake in Nepal's peace process, India diminished the actions of Nepali political actors and undermined their agency.

5.1 The 12-Point Understanding: Debunking Myths, Mysteries, and Mayhem

On 22 November 2005, at an undisclosed location in New Delhi, India, a coalition of seven Nepali political parties, aka the SPA, and the Communist Party of Nepal (Maoists) reached a political 'understanding' which came to be known simply as the 12-Point Understanding (see Appendix 4). The ambitious and controversial 12-Point Understanding envisioned a new political roadmap for Nepal. As expected, it ultimately changed Nepal's political landscape permanently.

The 12-Point Understanding touched upon many areas, including human rights, the rule of law, and national sovereignty. At the crux of it, however, were two key issues. First, ending King Gyanendra's direct rule through nationwide mass protests and the establishment of 'full democracy'. Second, resolving the Maoist armed insurgency through dialogue and negotiation, and paving the way for 'permanent peace'.

The 12-Point Understanding became a cornerstone for the disruptive political changes that followed in the Nepali political landscape.⁸⁴ As envisioned in that document, a wave of nationwide mass protests compelled King Gyanendra to give up his direct rule and revive the parliament that he had dissolved.⁸⁵ In line with the roadmap sketched in the 12-Point Understanding, the Maoists declared a ceasefire, participated in formal peace talks, agreed to renounce violence, and ultimately became part of Nepal's political mainstream.

With the help of the 12-Point Understanding, Nepali political actors not only ended a long-standing armed conflict but also guided Nepal towards a new political reality. For the first time in Nepal's history, a people-elected constituent assembly drafted and ratified a constitution.⁸⁶ The 'new Nepal,' as some prefer to call it, is no longer a centralised Hindu monarchy; it has been reshaped and rebranded as a secular federal democratic republic.

The signing of the 12-Point Understanding was undoubtedly one of the most significant political events in 21st-century Nepal. Despite its colossal impact and the monumental changes it engendered, several questions about its evolution remain unanswered. First, even though various speculations have been made, it is unclear why the 12-Point Understanding had to be reached in New Delhi and not in Kathmandu or any other location in Nepal. Second, India's role in bringing the SPA and the Maoists together and fermenting the 12-Point Understanding has remained vastly unclear. Third, India's opaque involvement in the entire process has raised serious questions.

As discussed in Chapter 4, the previous literature has recognised some degree of Indian involvement in the formation of the 12-Point Understanding. However, since specific details of such an engagement are missing, confusion surrounding India's actual roles persists. In addition, some scholars, such as Subedi & Bhattarai (2017: 95), who have written extensively on Nepal's peace process and political transition, have argued that India's role in Nepal's peace process, starting from the 12-Point Understanding, has been 'unclear and questionable' and that it is a subject that needs further investigation. Similarly, Destradi (2008: 22) argues that India's role in Nepal's peace process was 'mixed and multifaceted'. Since most of the 'talks took place at the informal level, based on well-established personal contacts between Nepalese and Indian political elites' (Destradi 2008: 17), uncovering India's involvement became even more complicated.

The 12-Point Understanding was reached in New Delhi, the capital of India. However, India's involvement was neither public nor official, but the lack of official involvement does not imply that the Indian establishment was completely absent from the scene. Various accounts frequently reported in the media suggest that

⁸⁴ However, the 12-Point Understanding was not a peace agreement. As its name suggests, it was simply an 'understanding' between two Nepali political forces that were fighting separately against their common enemy, King Gyanendra. The King had grabbed absolute power through a coup d'état in February 2005 and seemed determined to contain both the Maoists and the SPA with the help of the national army that was loyal to him. Even though the Maoists joined formal peace talks much later and the Comprehensive Peace Accord (CPA) was signed only in November 2006, it was the 12-Point Understanding that sketched out a clear roadmap for peace. The CPA, in a sense, only approved the mandate of the 12-Point Understanding and provided legal foundations for it. This was required because the 12-Point Understanding was signed between two oppositional forces, and the government of Nepal was absent from the scene.

⁸⁵ The revival of the dissolved parliament was the bottom line of the SPA as they began protesting the King's direct rule.

⁸⁶ A people-elected constitutional assembly was a long-cherished political demand in Nepal. Pro-democracy political parties had already demanded it in the 1950s when democracy was introduced in Nepal for the first time. King Tribhuvan, who had reportedly agreed to fulfil that demand after the end of the Rana rule in 1951, however, never fulfilled that promise.

India was more than a passive onlooker when the 12-Point Understanding was reached.⁸⁷ Such media portrayals have often been shallow, fragmented, and unreliable. In other words, they have not provided a comprehensive and trustworthy depiction of the nature and extent of India's involvement.

India's involvement in Nepal, both during the 12-Point Understanding and throughout Nepal's peace process and political transition, consistently maintained an 'unofficial' status. India was never officially invited, appointed, or declared as a mediator or arbitrator. As a result, most of its engagement in Nepal's peace process and political transition was covert and opaque. Through its shrewd manoeuvring power and the political leverage it enjoyed in Nepal, India was nonetheless able to alter Nepal's political processes to a great extent. As covered in various investigative journalistic works (see, for instance, Sharma 2013, Adhikari 2014), most of the time, it was also successful in achieving the outcomes it inherently desired.⁸⁸

The Indian involvement in laying the groundwork for resolving Nepal's armed conflict raises another important question. While previous attempts to negotiate a settlement to the armed insurgency had failed, a process that started in India yielded decisive results. In other words, a plan hatched in India succeeded, while earlier attempts made in Nepal were unsuccessful. For many, this is not merely a coincidence, but a strong indication of India's strong presence in forming the 12-Point Understanding and creating a new roadmap for Nepal's post-conflict political future.

India's involvement in the 12-Point process and its success raises a few more questions. For instance, was the Maoist armed insurgency resolved not because it was truly 'ripe' for resolution, but because India's 'coercive diplomacy' forced the Maoists and the SPA to unite to end the monarchy, which appeared to be defiant and 'unruly' in India's eyes? Did India find it pointless to support a monarchy that was not only strengthening its ties with China but also trying to invite China as an observer in the 'India-led' SAARC?⁸⁹In other words, was the 12-Point Understanding part of India's malicious plan to set up its proxy rule in Nepal, take control of its natural resources, and carry out an incubatory experiment of regional hegemony? From another viewpoint, what if India was simply motivated by a desire to promote itself as a regional peacemaker? Could it be possible that India's involvement was merely an act of solidarity—a kind gesture extended to a struggling neighbour trying to overcome a prolonged political crisis?

There are certainly no easy answers to these complex questions. However, my attempt in this and subsequent chapters is to delve deeper into issues such as these. As mentioned earlier, this chapter focuses on identifying India's role in the processes that led to the signing of the 12-Point Understanding. My discussion particularly revolves around the following questions: Why did the 12-Point Understanding have to be reached in India? What was India's role in that process? Did Nepali political actors demonstrate the agency required to resolve the armed conflict and restore the democracy that had been dismantled?

⁸⁷ These accounts include various statements from Nepali and Indian political leaders, which I explore later in this chapter and in subsequent chapters.

⁸⁸ However, this was not always the case. India did face significant resistance for its actions from various Nepali actors, including the public (see Chapter 8).

⁸⁹ The South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) is a regional organisation in South Asia. Its members are Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, the Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka. As the biggest and most powerful SAARC member state, India has substantial influence over it (see Hossain 2002).

I will begin the next section by discussing India's claims and its self-projection as an *éminence grise* in the Nepali peace process. As already mentioned, India was never officially involved as a mediator or arbitrator in Nepal's peace process. However, as the peace process moved in a positive direction and the armed conflict finally ended in 2006 with the CPA, India did not shy away from taking credit for the actions it claims to have taken. This desire for credit and a constant stake-seeking mentality has created confusion and dismay in Nepal. It has also raised serious concerns about India's intentions and actions in the country.

5.2 Taking Undue Credit? The Indian 'Ownership' of the Nepali Peace Process

In September 2015, Nepal's Constituent Assembly (CA) was all set to promulgate a new constitution and put an end to years of political stalemate, stagnation, and indecisiveness that had paralysed the nation. A constitution from a people-elected Constituent Assembly was a dream of the Nepali people, a hope they held dear for over seven decades. It was also a key demand of the Maoists and symbolically represented the culmination of the peace process.

Three days before the scheduled constitutional promulgation date, on 17 September 2015, Indian Foreign Secretary Subrahmanyam Jaishankar landed in Kathmandu as Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi's special envoy. As events unfolding in the aftermath showed, Jaishankar came to Nepal with a single mandate: to prevent the new Nepali constitution from being promulgated on the scheduled date. Jaishankar, flanked by the Indian Ambassador to Nepal, Ranjit Rae, met with senior political leaders in Nepal, including the Prime Minister, Sushil Koirala, and top Maoist leaders, such as Pushpa Kamal Dahal 'Prachanda' and Baburam Bhattarai. It has been clear from various first-hand accounts (see, for instance, N.K. Shrestha 2017a) that when meeting Nepali leaders, Jaishankar crossed diplomatic boundaries. He warned Nepali leaders not to promulgate the constitution unless a green signal was received from New Delhi or until the demands raised by India and the Madhesi parties were duly addressed. Narayan Kaji Shrestha, Nepal's former foreign minister, who met with Jaishankar along with Maoist leaders Dahal and Bhattarai, described the meeting during a media interview as follows:

From the very beginning, the way he presented himself was not good. He said at the beginning, 'You are ready to declare the constitution overnight, aren't you? You are violating the entire process and declaring the constitution?' As a diplomat and an envoy of a head of government, he should not have talked like that. He not only violated diplomatic norms, but also dared to undermine the sovereignty of Nepal and the Nepali people. Going further, he said, 'I have come to Nepal as a special envoy of the Prime Minister and with a special mission and message. That is, you have to postpone the promulgation of the constitution for now...Otherwise, you will have to kill many people on the day the constitution is promulgated...He also said, 'What happens even when you declare the constitution? What happens even with the support of many countries in the world? Does your constitution work if India does not support it? Yes, you can declare the constitution, but don't you want development? And don't you need India's help for development? Has India's support been enough already?'

Indirectly, he threatened to retaliate if India's advice to stop the constitution's promulgation was not heeded. He also said, 'If we hadn't helped, you would still be in the jungle, and the monarchy would still be here. And that is now forgotten?' In short, it appeared that his

mission was to stop the promulgation of the constitution at all costs. This was not just a general request; it was a threatening order (N.K. Shrestha 2017a).

Jaishankar's short stint in Kathmandu was not as successful as he had probably hoped to be. Despite India's serious reservations, Nepal's Constituent Assembly promulgated the new constitution, with more than 90% of the CA members voting in its favour. While the regional Madhesh-based parties took to the streets opposing the new constitution, Jaishankar's prophecy of an eventual 'bloodshed in the streets' proved false. Many countries worldwide, including the US, China, and the EU, welcomed Nepal's new constitution. However, India merely issued a statement saying that it had 'noted' that a new constitution had been promulgated in Nepal and that it extended best wishes to the people of Nepal (MEA India 2015). Three days after India had extended its best wishes to the people of Nepal, perhaps intending to give Nepalis a 'lesson', India imposed an undeclared economic blockade on Nepal. The blockade lasted for five months. It strained the already fragile India–Nepal relations and created a humanitarian crisis in Nepal.

Jaishankar's visit during the final hours of the constitution promulgation process and the message he delivered clearly indicated that India viewed itself as a 'party' and a 'stakeholder' in Nepal's peace and political transition process. Jaishankar's message was clear: bypassing India's wishes was not an option that Nepali political actors should consider. Similarly, the economic blockade that followed his visit also clearly indicated that the Indian establishment was angered by the Nepali political actors' exercise of sovereign power. By intervening in the constitution promulgation process, India wanted to maintain its grip on Nepal and firmly hold the helm of political engineering.

Jaishankar was not the only high-profile Indian official who highlighted India's role in Nepal's peace process, seeking credit for it. Years earlier, in 2009, Pranab Mukherjee—India's Minister for External Affairs, who later became India's President—claimed in an interview with *Al Jazeera* that India had persuaded the Maoists to give up violence and participate in mainstream, peaceful politics. The Maoists, Mukherjee argued, had accepted India's admonition and ended up leading the government in Nepal (see *Al Jazeera* 2009). In the interview, Mukherjee projected India as a regional peacebuilder. Apart from Nepal, he also cited examples of other South Asian countries where India had been involved in building peace and stability.

In 2012, SD Muni, a professor at India's Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU), who had mentored the Maoist leader Baburam Bhattarai during his doctoral studies at JNU, revealed in a book that the 12-Point Understanding had 'emerged from the continuous parlays between the SPA and the Maoists, along the way informally consulting trusted interlocutors and officials in India' (Muni 2012: 328). According to him, New Delhi used informal channels to influence the content of the 12-Point Understanding.⁹⁰ The SPA and the Maoist negotiation team members showed him the draft of the document several times. Muni, however, rejected the allegations that New Delhi was the mastermind behind the 12-Point Understanding and that the Maoists and the SPA were presented with a final document draft merely to sign.

⁹⁰ He argued that India influenced the content of the 12-Point Understanding in three critical aspects. First, it was called an 'understanding' and not an 'agreement' to make sure that it was not a binding commitment for either side. Second, even though the Understanding was reached in New Delhi, it was not made public or signed jointly by the SPA and the Maoists. This was done to bar Maoists from the legitimacy they were seeking. Third, it was also made sure that the word 'republic' did not appear in the document and was replaced with phrases such as 'full democracy' or 'end of the autocratic monarchy' (Muni 2012: 317).

The Nepali peace process has served as a useful example or a marketing tool that Indian politicians, diplomats, and the Indian corporate media, obsessed with India's international image, have been using to portray India's image as a regional democracy-promoter and peacebuilder. Even Indian academics have done so. While India's 'marketing' of its involvement in the Nepali peace process appears to be working quite effectively, a careful analysis of the internal political events in Nepal does not quite add up to the story that India is telling the world. Before questioning the Indian version of events, in the next section, I analyse a series of political events in Nepal from as early as 2001. An analysis of these events offers a broader view of the evolution of the Nepali peace process. It demonstrates that internal political dynamics were much more crucial in initiating, steering, and accomplishing the 12-Point Understanding and a relatively successful peace process in Nepal.

5.3 The Conflict Conundrum and the Story of Two Failed Peace Processes

In July 2001, Sher Bahadur Deuba, a leader of the Nepali Congress party, who happened to be Nepal's Prime Minister when the Maoist insurgency began in 1996, rose to power again as Prime Minister. Deuba had completely ignored the Maoists' 40-point demands in 1996. However, within six years, the Maoist movement had proliferated to such an extent that this time, Deuba's survival as Prime Minister mostly depended on his ability to persuade the Maoists to participate in peace talks and to end the armed conflict with a negotiated settlement.

Two days after Deuba's appointment as Prime Minister, on 25 July 2001, a ceasefire was declared. After a little more than a month, on 30 August 2001, the first round of peace talks between the government and Maoist negotiation teams was held at a private resort in Lalitpur. Two weeks after the first talks, the second round took place in Bardiya, western Nepal (Upreti 2006: 120). At the negotiating table, the Maoists demanded, among other things, that a republican system be established in Nepal and that the 1990 constitution should be replaced by a new one. They demanded a people-elected constituent assembly to draft and declare a new constitution. The Maoists later dropped their demand for a republican state. However, the peace talks failed as the government was not ready to fulfil any of the Maoists' major demands, including elections for a constituent assembly. Mumaram Khanal, a senior Maoist leader at that time who had participated in several secret and informal talks that led to the 2001 peace talks, recalled why the talks had failed in 2001:

The first round of formal talks in 2001 stalled and failed over the issue of the constituent assembly (CA) election. There was disagreement over whether to organise CA elections with a condition or without any condition. The king wanted to ensure that his position was safeguarded even if elections for a CA were held. The condition was not a ceremonial monarchy, but a constitutional monarchy. The CPN (Maoists) did not accept that, and the talks failed.⁹¹

By mid-November 2001, the Maoists withdrew from the formal negotiation process, declared the ceasefire over, and announced that the armed struggle would resume. Within days, they attacked and captured an army barracks in Dang in the western Tarai (Whelpton 2005: 218). This was their first attack on an army base. In an

⁹¹ Interview with Mumaram Khanal (24.07.2017).

attempt to run a parallel government, the Maoists also declared a new body called the United Revolutionary People's Council of Nepal. Maoist ideologue Baburam Bhattarai led the People's Council (Thapa & Sijapati 2004: 122). The Deuba government responded to the Maoist offensives by declaring a state of emergency, curtailing civil liberties, and tagging the CPN (Maoists) and its sister organisations as terrorists. Some of the most brutal clashes between the Maoists and state security forces, including attacks and counterattacks, took place during the emergency period (see, for instance, Thapa 2002, Kräamer 2003).

The first peace talks were initiated and held in Nepal, and there is no credible evidence of any international involvement in these talks. However, a quick look at Nepal's political situation at that time is sufficient to understand why the 2001 talks failed. In essence, the 2001 talks were organised merely for tactical purposes. At that time, neither the Maoists nor the government seemed genuinely interested in resolving the conflict through a negotiated settlement.

The 2001 talks had begun in the context of major political upheavals in Nepal. On 1 June 2001, two months before the first ceasefire, ten prominent members of Nepal's royal family, including King Birendra and Queen Aishwarya, were killed in a mass shooting at their official residence in Kathmandu. In the aftermath of the shocking royal massacre, King Birendra's brother, Prince Gyanendra, was crowned the new king. Not long after his ascent to the throne, King Gyanendra, known for his hardliner image in contrast to his relatively liberal deceased brother, declared that he would not be a 'passive onlooker' like his elder brother had been.

The Maoists tried to use the royal massacre as an opportunity to garner support for their 'republic' agenda. Baburam Bhattarai, through an op-ed in a national broadsheet, argued that the legitimate monarchy had been obliterated in the royal massacre and that it was time to institutionalise republicanism in Nepal. Mr Bhattarai also portrayed the erstwhile king, King Birendra, as a patriotic figure with whom the Maoists had an 'undeclared strategic cooperation' over various issues (see Bhattarai 2001).

Bhattarai's argument raised concerns because King Birendra's approach towards the Maoists had indeed been ambiguous. When the G.P. Koirala government had requested mobilising the army against the Maoists, King Birendra dismissed the idea.⁹² When King Birendra was Nepal's head of state and the army's Commander-in-Chief, the Royal Nepal Army never left its barracks to suppress the insurgency.

G.P. Koirala, who was Prime Minister at the time of the palace massacre, again attempted to mobilise the army. By default, the army was loyal to the new King. As per the constitution, army mobilisation required the King's approval. When the new King also declined his request to mobilise the army, G.P. Koirala resigned as Prime Minister. Sher Bahadur Deuba, who replaced Koirala, ascended to power, promising that he could resolve the armed conflict through dialogue and negotiation and that, in his view, the insurgency was a political issue and demanded a political solution. In contrast to G.P. Koirala's suppression line, Deuba's promise of a peaceful resolution resonated well in the conflict-stricken Nepali society.

The Deuba government's survival depended on its ability to solve the armed conflict through a negotiated settlement. To justify his relevance, Mr Deuba had to declare a ceasefire and invite the Maoists to the negotiating table. The Maoists, too, saw this as an opportunity to bolster their image as a political entity. This was a perfect opportunity for them to show that they were a revolutionary political force

⁹² Interview with Beduram Bhusal (14.07.2017).

adept not only in violence and vandalism, but also ready to join peaceful politics if their concerns were seriously addressed.

The public image of the Maoists had begun to suffer because of the reckless acts of violence and destruction they had been carrying out since the insurgency was launched in 1996. In the wake of the shocking royal massacre and six years of Maoist violence, pressure for peace also came from the traumatised Nepali society. Civil society organisations represented that voice in various forms by lobbying and campaigning for peace.

The Maoists and the Deuba government probably knew very well that the ambitious and hardliner King would hardly budge from his position and that the peace talks would ultimately falter and fail. Still, the talks were held anyway because even the failed talks offered both parties temporary strategic benefits and some amount of political capital, which they could shrewdly use. The Deuba government justified its relevance by claiming it had stuck to its initial promise and brought the rebels to the negotiating table—an act that previous governments had failed to achieve. Similarly, the Maoists took advantage of the ceasefire to connect with and campaign among the urban population, a group that had been challenging to reach while operating from underground. In addition, as a precondition for creating a conducive environment for peace talks, the Maoists were able to negotiate the release of a significant number of their cadres from police custody and detention centres throughout the country. Moreover, since the Maoists appeared to know in advance that the talks were going to fail, they used the time that the ceasefire and the peace talks bought to reorganise themselves and to prepare for a major guerrilla attack as soon as the ceasefire was over.

A derailed peace process also served the ambitious King. Since ascending to the throne, he had clearly signalled that he wanted a more active role and appeared to be looking for the right moment for a major crackdown on political parties. The talks had failed primarily because the King refused the idea of unconditional CA elections.⁹³ However, the failed talks were used by the King and the royalists to weave the narrative that the elected representatives had been unsuccessful in tackling the insurgency and that the King had to step in to restore peace and order in the country.

On 4 October 2002, through a royal proclamation, King Gyanendra sacked Prime Minister Deuba, dissolved the Cabinet, and seized total executive power. In a televised address, the King accused the Prime Minister of being 'incompetent'.⁹⁴ Within a week, Lokendra Bahadur Chand, a staunch royalist, was handpicked by the King as Nepal's new Prime Minister.

Nearly four months after Chand was appointed Nepal's new Prime Minister, on 29 January 2003, a new ceasefire agreement with the Maoists was announced. The Chand government had persuaded the Maoists to rejoin the negotiating table. The Maoists, who had been on the offensive as they left the 2001 peace talks, had now ended up in a defensive abyss. They had borne heavy losses during the state of emergency. In the wake of the 11 September attacks in the US, the changing global political climate, especially the US's global 'war on terror', also affected them significantly. For instance, after 2001, the US military assistance to Nepal increased dramatically, reaching over 29 million USD between October 2001 and October

⁹³ Even though his designation was that of a constitutional monarch, since he enjoyed the loyalty of the army, the ultimate authority in Nepal at the time rested on him.

⁹⁴ Showing security reasons, Prime Minister Deuba had sought postponement of parliamentary elections scheduled for November. Instead of considering his request, the King dismissed him and his Cabinet.

2004 (HRW 2004: 84). In 2003, the United States also signed an anti-terror aid agreement with Nepal, enlisted the Maoists as a terrorist group in its 'watchlist', and provided 'counterterrorism' training to the Nepali army (TKP 2003a, TKP 2003b). Military assistance also came from other countries, including China, India, and the UK.⁹⁵

A series of peace talks was held in April, May and August 2003, but there was little progress regarding a negotiated settlement. The negotiation teams were reshuffled as the King replaced the Chand Cabinet with the one led by Surya Bahadur Thapa, yet another staunch royalist. The Maoists sat at the talks with three major demands, not very different from the ones they previously had: 1. A round table conference (of all Nepali political stakeholders), 2. Formation of an interim government, 3. Elections for a constituent assembly (Upreti 2006: 125).

Once again, negotiations stalled over the issue of the constituent assembly. The talks did not progress as the Maoists had hoped, even though they had been more flexible than before, and the demand for an end to the monarchical rule had been dropped to 'facilitate the peace process' (Pokharel 2003). It became increasingly clear that the government negotiation team, made up of long-time monarchists, was not authorised to address the major demands put forward by the Maoists. Without the King's direct participation, there was little progress in the peace talks. The Maoists demanded that, since the King choreographed everything from behind the curtain, there was no point in holding useless talks with the negotiation team, and that they wanted to hold a decisive talk with the King himself. Their demand, however, was neglected by the palace.

As political developments later revealed, amidst growing international support for the 'war on terror' and a gradual military defeat of the Maoists on the ground, the King was not in the mood for a compromise. The peace talks, it appeared, were barely a tactical orchestration performed while the King set the stage and tested the waters for an authoritarian adventure. On 17 August 2003, while the ceasefire was still in effect, the state security forces killed 15 Maoist cadres and two civilians while they were asleep in central Nepal's Doramba district (Tamang 2004). This was a clear sign that the peace talks were organised for the sake of organising. Particularly, the government team was neither interested nor committed to finding a peaceful solution to the conflict. A week after the Doramba incident, the Maoists gave an ultimatum of 48 hours to address the issue of the constituent assembly, to which the government did not respond. On 27 August 2003, the ceasefire and the peace talks were over as the Maoists withdrew from the process and declared the resumption of the 'people's war' (Lawoti & Pahari 2009: 336).

The 2003 peace talks occurred in a significantly different domestic and international political context. However, as with the 2001 talks, a genuine commitment to finding a negotiated settlement was absent again. The US-led 'war on terror' and increasing international support appeared to have convinced the King that the rebels could be crushed and defeated through aggressive military suppression—an act that had already been rehearsed during the state of emergency period.

This time, the Maoists were in a defensive mood and appeared much more resilient than they had been in the 2001 talks. Their resilience had a limit, and in the name of compromise, abandoning agendas that had defined and shaped their

⁹⁵ For an overview of military assistance that Nepal received during the early 2000s, see, for instance, HRW (2004).

political identity—such as their demand for constituent assembly elections—would have been equivalent to committing political suicide.

To sum up, both the 2001 and the 2003 talks failed because they were essentially destined and designed to fail. The 2001 talks were conducted because the Maoists wanted to buy time and strengthen their political and military prowess, whereas the Deuba government wanted to justify its political utility by keeping up with the promise it had made earlier. In addition, both actors had to respond to the pressure for peace that came in the wake of the 2001 royal massacre. Similarly, the 2003 talks stalled because King Gyanendra—who was gradually rehearsing his authoritarian moves—appeared convinced that in the changed global scenario, and with an aggressive mobilisation of the Royal Nepal Army, the rebels could be defeated. Therefore, he saw no point in compromising with them. In contrast, the Maoists were in a defensive state. However, dropping their most important demands and surrendering to the state was not an option they could choose. As a result, the peace talks failed, and new episodes of violent conflict resumed in Nepal.

5.4 King Gyanendra's Authoritarian Adventure

After experimenting with two handpicked governments in two years, in May 2004, King Gyanendra made an unusual public call for the Prime Minister's post. Anyone interested in the job could 'apply' for it by sending a request letter to the King. Out of several candidates, Sher Bahadur Deuba, whom the King had sacked in 2002 for being 'incompetent', was now reappointed as Prime Minister through the application process. Even though Deuba represented a political party, the Nepali Congress (Democratic), he was still a handpicked candidate, and there was no national political consensus for his appointment.⁹⁶ This way, the King continued undermining the relevance of mainstream political parties and showed no interest in restoring the democratic process, which had been derailed since his 2002 proclamation.

As far as the issue of the armed conflict and the protracted political impasse was concerned, there was little the Deuba government could do. The government's manoeuvring space was severely limited, since the government itself was just another 'experiment' of the King. Prime Minister Deuba, who had been a proponent of dialogue and peaceful resolution of the conflict before and during the 2001 talks, was now adamant about suppressing the Maoists by force. The Maoists, who had walked out of the peace talks feeling humiliated, were now aggressively engaged in lethal armed attacks, extortion, and abductions. Due to increased hostility and the security forces' aggressive suppression strategy, the rebels suffered some significant losses, but, at the same time, their outreach appeared to have significantly grown in the wake of the 2003 talks (Upreti 2006, Lawoti & Pahari 2009).

On 1 February 2005, the King finally revealed what he had been 'hatching' behind the walls. In a carefully planned coup d'état, with the support of the national army, the King dismissed the constitution, deposed the Prime Minister and his Cabinet, and consolidated absolute power for himself. In a lengthy televised address, he labelled the Maoists as individuals engaged in criminal activities who had lost their way. He urged them to surrender their weapons and join peaceful politics. In addition, he made it clear that he would chair the Council of Ministers

⁹⁶ The Communist Party of Nepal (UML) joined the Deuba government, arguing that the King's regressive move, which began in 2002 when he sacked Deuba, had been partially corrected with Deuba's reappointment. The Nepali Congress, a major political party led by Girija Prasad Koirala, however, rejected the King's move and continued its street protests.

as its Chairman, signalling the end of handpicked prime ministers and his desire to rule as an authoritarian ruler.⁹⁷

Under the King's direct rule, most senior politicians in the country were either arrested and placed in police custody or kept under house arrest. Human rights activists, journalists, and prominent civil society members were subjected to similar measures. For months, telephone lines were cut off, and the Internet was suspended from public use. Freedom of expression and civil liberties were severely curtailed. Media censorship was so extreme that military officers occupied the editorial desks of major newspapers and dictated what went to the press. One of the King's first decrees was to 'ban the reporting of news over the radio and to give the authorities the power to close down any media outlet' (Christou 2006: 98).

King Gyanendra's authoritarian anarchy was modelled on his father's autocratic *Panchayat* rule, which lasted for thirty years (1960–1990). Among others, the King appointed two hardliner *Panchayatis*, Tulsi Giri and Kirti Nidhi Bista, as Vice-Chairmen of his administration.⁹⁸ He filled most of the government ministries with illiberal figures with controversial histories, who had little political relevance in post-1990 Nepal.

In his February 1 coup d'état speech, King Gyanendra appeared very clear about his roadmap. He was going to use the anti-terrorism card to suppress the Maoists by force and sideline mainstream political parties by imprisoning their senior leaders on corruption charges. With that mindset, the King, however, failed to realise that 21st-century Nepal was significantly different from that of the 1960s. The democratic political changes achieved in the 1990s had significantly altered Nepal's social and political landscape. Though there was some level of frustration over how governments in the democratic era had (under)performed, ordinary Nepalis seemed to cherish the democracy and political freedom that the 1990s brought. The democratic change had also facilitated a rapid growth of a free press and a sprawling community of pro-democracy and pro-change Nepali diaspora, which contributed as strong antidotes to the King's authoritarian rule.

Similarly, unlike in the 1960s, Nepal in the 2000s had a vibrant civil society, as well as thousands of community organisations and non-governmental organisations working on various socio-political issues. A significant portion of the population that was not only educated, but also capable of independent thinking. With the rapid growth of globalisation and modern means of mass communication, Nepal was no longer an isolated mystical *Shangri-La* in the Himalayas. It had evolved into an active member of the global community that regularly interacted with the outside world.

In such a scenario, it was clear from the beginning that King Gyanendra's rule would not last long. However, the King appeared adamant in his pursuits and seemed confident in defeating the Maoists and mainstream political parties to consolidate his authoritarian regime. Ironically, King Gyanendra's autocratic ambitions and his blatant disregard for opposing political forces created the foundation for resolving the Maoist armed insurgency and ultimately led to the creation of a republican Nepal, which I will discuss in the next section.

⁹⁷ An unofficial English translation of King Gyanendra's proclamation is available at: <https://www.satp.org/satporgtp/countries/nepal/document/papers/05emergencyking.htm>

⁹⁸ Both Giri and Bista were senior figures during the one-party *Panchayat* rule, which lasted for three decades.

5.5 New Meeting Point for the Maoists and the SPA: Ending the King's Direct Rule

After King Gyanendra began his ultimate autocratic show through the February 2005 coup, the tectonic plates of Nepali politics began to shift. The parliamentary political parties that had happily accepted a constitutional monarchy in a political compromise in 1990 were appalled by the King's latest actions and his abject and repeated breach of the 1990 constitution. As the bond between the monarchy and the parliamentary political parties began to loosen, the possibility of an affinity between the parliamentary parties and the Maoists substantially grew.

Before the King's February 2005 move, the relationship between the Maoists and the parliamentary parties had been historically tense. The Maoists saw the parliamentary parties and their cadres as primary rivals on the ground. As a result, since the beginning of the armed conflict, party members of parliamentary parties became prime targets of the Maoists. They were killed, abducted, and forced to leave their homes. Similarly, the Maoists were a threat and political rivals that the parliamentary parties wanted to eliminate.

Even though the King's regressive move had started in 2002, the parliamentary parties were largely in a 'wait and see' mood until the King's 2005 takeover. Occasional street protests against the King's move were common, but their commitment to a constitutional monarchy was unabated, even though the King had clearly crossed the limits set by the 1990 constitution. There was a reason for this tolerance. The parliamentary parties were convinced that compromising with the King would be a better option than joining hands with a radical communist force, tagged by many countries as terrorists. After all, the Maoists sought to eradicate all their political competitors and establish a one-party communist dictatorship.

Ironically, the Maoists also attempted to reach a power-sharing deal with the King. After the 2003 peace talks had failed, the Maoist leadership was able to establish contact with the royal palace and requested a one-on-one meeting between the King and the Maoist chairman, Prachanda. Krishna Bahadur Mahara, a senior Maoist leader who was facilitating communication with the palace, accepted that they had, indeed, sought to hold a decisive dialogue with the King:

We had given the King two options to choose from: power or the throne. If he desired power, we told him, he would have to relinquish the throne and declare [Nepal] a republic state...and then he could become an executive head or president for five years. And we would support him. But if he needed the throne, we told him, he would have to give up all his power and accept the role of a titular monarch (Cited in Adhikari 2011).

The Maoists found themselves in an increasingly desperate situation and were looking for a way out. Reaching out to the King was one of their exit plans. In the new political scenario, both regional and global, it had become increasingly challenging for the Maoist leadership to operate from India. Both the United States and India had tagged the Maoists as 'terrorists'. In addition, worried about the spillover effects of the Maoist movement into its northern states, India had started to detain and extradite Maoist leaders to Nepal (J. Nepal 2020). As a result, senior Maoist leaders, such as Prachanda and Baburam Bhattarai, returned from India and lived in the Loshebang mountain in western Nepal (BC 2014).

Initially, the King, too, had been responsive to the Maoists' proposal and reportedly communicated with them via private messengers. Probably aware of the Maoist desperation, he ultimately neglected their request for a direct and decisive dialogue. The unrealised proposal of a monarchist-Maoist alliance, however,

created a deep division within the CPN (Maoists) party. While the faction led by Chairman Prachanda was in favour of cooperating with the King and sidelining the parliamentary parties, the second leader in the rank, Baburam Bhattarai, advocated for a partnership with the parliamentary parties and the abolition of the monarchy.⁹⁹

In advocating a coalition with the King, a flawed character of the Maoist leadership was apparent. In public, the Maoists maintained a minutely crafted image of a radical progressive force that was aiming to abolish the monarchy and establish a people's republic. That is how they persuaded and motivated thousands of Nepali youths to join the insurgency and sacrifice their lives. However, for potential political gains, they also secretly worked to build an 'unholy' alliance with the King.

However, the Maoists, who had been hoping to hear from the King, were shocked when the King, through the February 2005 declaration, not only called them strayed criminals, but also warned that he would take action against them. Against this backdrop, in September 2005, the Maoists' central committee conclave organised in Chunbang, a village in the Rukum district of western Nepal, took a U-turn in their position on the monarchy. The party approved Baburam Bhattarai's political line that they would coordinate with the parliamentary parties to abolish the autocratic monarchy. In addition, they also decided to drop, at least temporarily, the agenda of 'communist one-party rule' or the so-called 'people's republic' and replaced that with a new 'people's democratic republic', where democracy and periodic elections would be irreplaceable rules of the game (Adhikari 2014: 233, Shrestha 2016, J. Nepal 2020).

Behind this dramatic policy shift, there was, however, something more than the King's fledgling autocracy. The Maoists had realised that after nine years of guerrilla warfare, the movement was losing momentum, and the dream of capturing and controlling the entire Nepali state was becoming virtually impossible. Pampha Bhusal, a senior Maoist leader and an attendee of the Chunbang meeting, recalled why her party had taken that decision:

At that time, the national army was not in a position to go outside its barracks. The balance of power was such that we could not come to the cities, and they could not go to the villages. Even though 80% of the country was under our control, it was impossible for us to capture Kathmandu... Since we couldn't do that, we also needed a policy shift and an agreement... If we could not do that at that time, our movement would have ended like the communist movements of Peru, Malaysia, or the Philippines.¹⁰⁰

By adopting a policy of suppression, the King was gradually closing all potential avenues for dialogue and negotiation. The Maoists' decision to accept a 'democratic republic' and to engage with the parliamentary parties for a decisive fight against the autocratic monarchy totally changed Nepal's political course. Ultimately, the alliance between the Maoists and the parliamentary parties was announced via the 12-Point Understanding. Its foundations, however, were laid approximately a month earlier, not in a *darbar* in New Delhi, but in a tiny village of the Rolpa district in western Nepal.

⁹⁹ To advocate this line of thought, a Maoist politburo meeting held in January 2005 in Rukum took disciplinary action against Bhattarai. The meeting declared him a 'pro-Indian betrayer', expelled him from all party positions (except the party's ordinary membership), and was detained along with Hisila Yami, his wife, and Dinanath Sharma, a senior Maoist leader who had supported Bhattarai's line of thought. For more on this, see, for instance, J. Nepal (2020).

¹⁰⁰ Interview with Pampha Bhusal (03.08.2017).

5.6 The Rolpa Roadmap: A Precursor to the 12-Point Understanding

Nearly a month before the Maoists held the crucial Chunbang conclave, the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Nepal (Unified Marxist–Leninist), aka CPN (UML), a moderate mainstream communist party, met in Kathmandu in August 2005 and approved a new political line of a republic-oriented Nepal.¹⁰¹ This was a bold initiative from a party that was not only one of the largest political parties in Nepal but also a rare breed of Nepali communists who had accepted the existence of monarchy in Nepal and had learnt to coexist with it. As two competing communist parties, the UML and the Maoists had a largely antagonistic relationship. However, in the new political context, their interests converged, and they became part of the leftist group that opposed the monarchy and guided Nepal towards republicanism. The UML's decision helped create an environment in which discussions about a 'republic Nepal' were no longer taboo. Gradually, republicanism stopped being an agenda solely linked to the Maoists. The UML's decision also put moral pressure on other parliamentary parties to reconsider their stance on the monarchy.

The UML's General Secretary at the time, Madhav Kumar Nepal, was one of the few politicians who aimed to involve the Maoists in a peace process by actively, though informally, engaging with them since the early years of the insurgency. When the army repression against the Maoists was at its peak, Prachanda, his old acquaintance, called him to discuss potential alternatives for a safe landing of the armed conflict. Mr Nepal and Mr Prachanda started having regular phone conversations and met in person on several occasions. Mr Nepal recalled how most of these initial meetings took place, often informally and unceremoniously, in several Indian cities, including Siliguri, Patna, Gorakhpur, New Delhi, and Lucknow. To attend these meetings, he often travelled by road, incognito, trying all he could to avoid police surveillance both in Nepal and India. These meetings often took place in small local hotels or the homes of Nepali immigrants in India.¹⁰²

In October 2005, nearly a month after the Chunbang meeting, a group of senior Maoist leaders, including Pushpa Kamal Dahal 'Prachanda' and Baburam Bhattarai, gathered in a village called Gharti Gaun in Nepal's Rolpa district.

The Maoists wanted to talk to other political parties to forge an anti-monarchy alliance and had invited leaders from the CPN (UML) and the Nepali Congress. Madhav Kumar Nepal was an obvious invitee, but because he was unable to travel at that time, he sent Bam Dev Gautam, UML's Acting General Secretary, and Yuba Raj Gyawali, a senior UML leader, for the talks with the Maoists. Bamdev Gautam recalled his experience of attending the Rolpa meeting as follows:

Madhav Nepal told me about the scheduled Rolpa talks and asked me to go there with Yuba Raj Gyawali, who was already in Dang. From Kathmandu, I first went to Dang, and from there, with Yuba Raj Gyawali, to Rolpa. We used the excuse of attending a party programme in Holeri. The first night, we stayed in Naya Gaun, and the next day, we went to Gharti Gaun. We stayed there for two nights. They [the Maoist leaders] also came, and we had a meeting at night. We prepared and signed a six-point agreement there. From the Maoists, there were Prachanda, Baburam, and Krishna Bahadur Mahara. The agreement was that we would start a joint movement against the King's authoritarian rule. Our struggle would be peaceful, and

¹⁰¹ Interview with Beduram Bhusal (14.07.2017).

¹⁰² Interview with Madhav Kumar Nepal (11.07.2017).

we would also take other parties on board. In previous talks, we would normally just take memos, but this time we signed [an agreement].

It had somehow been revealed that I had attended that meeting, so a helicopter had been sent to track me and arrest me. The police had run a search operation, but I had already taken a night bus to Butwal and a flight from Butwal to Kathmandu.¹⁰³

The Rolpa meeting, which took place on 22–23 October 2005 (see Picture 1), was a remarkable feat in itself, as it laid the foundation for an alliance between the Maoists and the SPA. The Six-Point Agreement, which was signed at the Rolpa meeting, was a precursor to the 12-Point Understanding and contained similar themes (see BC 2014). In this context, the Rolpa meeting and the Six-Point Agreement, rather than the 12-Point Understanding, were the true origins of the Nepali peace process.

Picture 1: Photo of the CPN (Maoist)–CPN (UML) Rolpa Meeting Where the Six-Point Agreement Was Signed. From Right to Left: UML Leaders Yuba Raj Gyawali, Bamdev Gautam, and Maoist Leaders Pushpa Kamal Dahal 'Prachanda', Baburam Bhattarai, Krishna Bahadur Mahara, and Netra Bikram Chand 'Biplav'. Photo Credit: Dinesh Shrestha/Nepali Times

One of the limitations of the Rolpa meeting was that the representatives of the Nepali Congress (NC) party, the biggest among the parliamentary parties, were unable to attend it. Had they been present there, the alliance between the Maoists and the SPA, which was later formed in New Delhi, could have been announced from Rolpa as well. Shekhar Koirala, who used to accompany the NC president,

¹⁰³ Interview with Bamdev Gautam (15.07.2017).

Girijia Prasad Koirala (aka G.P. Koirala), in important political meetings, and who was assigned to attend the Rolpa meeting, described why he had been unable to reach Rolpa:

Prachanda's team proposed a meeting in Rolpa. They wanted Girijababu [G.P. Koirala] to travel to Rolpa and hold a meeting there. Girijababu, however, refused the proposal because he was concerned that if he went, the Maoist leaders would be arrested. Then the Maoists requested Girijababu to send me to Rolpa. Girijababu asked me and Mahanta Thakur to travel secretly to Rolpa. I talked with [the Maoist leader] Mahara, too. However, our plan had somehow leaked, and we could not go there.¹⁰⁴

In the wake of the Six-Point Agreement, a comprehensive and decisive agreement was essential between the Maoists and the SPA. Even though the Rolpa meeting had been partially successful, further talks with the Maoists in Nepal were challenging, especially for senior politicians of the SPA, like G.P. Koirala and Madhav Kumar Nepal. Because of their high-profile political status, state security personnel always accompanied them. In addition, since they had opposed the King's direct rule, the government intelligence agency kept a close eye on their movement.

Travelling to a distant place like Rolpa's Gharti Gaun would be one option, but G.P. Koirala's declining health prevented him from undertaking mountainous journeys. Reaching a place like Rolpa, on foot or on horseback, would be extremely difficult for Mr Koirala, who was 81 at the time and in poor health.¹⁰⁵ In addition, the national intelligence agency, which was under the King's control, would track his every movement. No matter where he went, the amount of media attention and interest would also be substantial.¹⁰⁶

Madhav Kumar Nepal, who had attended various secret and informal meetings with the Maoists in the past, recalled how he had travelled to other countries to find a suitable meeting place for the ultimate Maoist-SPA talks. He had visited countries like Norway, Finland, and Switzerland as potential destinations for the peace talks. He also recalled a long conversation he had with Erik Solheim, a Norwegian politician, about exploring the organisation of Norway-mediated talks.¹⁰⁷ In the end, Mr Nepal explained why holding talks in a third country proved to be difficult as far as the Maoists' participation was concerned:

To find a suitable location for the talks, I also met and spoke in the Netherlands with the chairman of the Philippines Communist Party, the Speaker of the Philippine parliament, and the Deputy Prime Minister of Thailand. But the problem was that travelling to those places was difficult. Not for me, of course, but for Prachanda. Because of that, we started talking with the CPIM [the Communist Party of India (Marxist)] to arrange a meeting place in India.¹⁰⁸

Travelling to a third country would have been difficult for the Maoist leaders. The Maoists had been labelled as a 'terrorist organisation' by the government of Nepal and several other countries, including the United States. Most of the senior Maoist leaders, including Pushpa Kamal Dahal 'Prachanda' and Baburam Bhattarai, had a

¹⁰⁴ Interview with Sekhar Koirala (22.08.2017).

¹⁰⁵ Interview with Sujata Koirala (18.08.2017), Shekhar Koirala (22.08.2017), and Pampha Bhusal (03.08.2017).

¹⁰⁶ Interview with Sujata Koirala (18.08.2017) and Shekhar Koirala (22.08.2017).

¹⁰⁷ Mr Solheim had earlier been involved in the Norwegian effort to mediate talks between the Liberation Tigers of Tamil Eelam and the Sri Lankan government.

¹⁰⁸ Interview with Madhav Kumar Nepal (11.07.2017).

Red Corner Notice issued against them by the International Criminal Police Organisation (INTERPOL). This meant that if they appeared at an airport for international travel, they would be immediately arrested.

Out of the few options available, India seemed to be the best choice. The open borders between Nepal and India allowed Maoist leaders to travel easily back and forth. For the SPA leaders, travelling to India would not be difficult either.

5.7 The 12-Point Understanding and the India Factor

While Nepali political actors, especially the SPA leaders, worked actively to resolve the armed conflict and end the King's autocratic rule, India also played a significant role during that time. India's attitude to the Maoist insurgency slowly began to change in the later years of the conflict. As discussed in the previous chapter, India initially exhibited contradictory behaviour by supporting both sides of the conflict. For instance, although it was clear that most prominent Maoist leaders lived in and operated from India, it turned a blind eye to their presence. For years, the Maoists used India not only as a shelter but also as a destination for training and weapons. Nepali security forces fighting against the Maoists also received substantial military, financial, and logistical support from India.

However, when the US-led 'War on Terror' intensified in the wake of the September 11 attacks, India demonstrated its loyalty to the US by declaring the Nepali Maoists a terrorist organisation. In fact, India declared the CPN(M) a terrorist organisation even before Nepal did. India then began to heavily support Nepali security forces in their fight against the Maoists. As the political equilibrium in Nepal began to change rapidly in the wake of King Gyanendra's coup, India gradually abandoned its paradoxical approach and started lobbying for an inclusive political framework that would include not only the parliamentary parties and monarchy, but also the Maoists.

For instance, as early as September 2004, Sitaram Yechury, a veteran leader of the Communist Party of India (Marxist), was approached by Indian Prime Minister Manmohan Singh and asked whether he could use his connections from the Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU) to talk to the Maoists and help bring them to mainstream politics (Whitfield 2008: 23). Yechury had met with a group of Maoist representatives in early 2005, and meetings continued as he, with DP Tripathi, in the wake of the 2005 royal coup, formed the Nepal Democracy Solidarity Committee. By mid-2005, senior Maoist leaders, such as Baburam Bhattarai and Krishna Bahadur Mahara, had meetings with officials at India's Ministry of External Affairs (Whitfield 2008, Adhikari 2014: 208–209).

A key informant, who used to accompany G.P. Koirala during his meetings with senior Indian leaders, including the Minister of External Affairs of that time Pranab Mukherjee, noted that India did not appear interested in getting rid of the monarchy and building a republic Nepal, but their concern was that the Maoist insurgency should be addressed and that the Maoists should be included within the political mainstream.¹⁰⁹

While there have been accusations that India's earlier indifference, as well as post-2004 proactive interest and action, were both strategic, India's tacit recognition of the Maoists as a political force was nonetheless a significant move as far as the peaceful resolution of the Maoist armed insurgency was concerned. By ultimately engaging with the Maoists as a political force and not as a terrorist group,

¹⁰⁹ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

India helped create a conducive environment in New Delhi where the Maoists and the SPA leaders could engage in dialogue and sketch out a new roadmap for peace and democracy in Nepal.

India did so at a time when the Maoists were likened to extremist organisations such as *Al-Qaeda* and the *Taliban*. For instance, after the Maoist-UML Six-Point Agreement was signed in Rolpa, the US embassy in Kathmandu issued a statement calling the agreement 'alarming' and urging that there should be no cooperation between the parliamentary parties and the Maoists until the Maoists shunned arms (Khanal 2005). India, on the other hand, not only allowed the Maoists and SPA leaders unhindered access to New Delhi, but its informal facilitation and moral support it extended through high-level private meetings gave Nepali actors fighting against the King's autocratic rule a psychological boost.

However, India was also vigilant about the activities of other third-party actors in Nepal and actively worked to minimise their impact or even chase them away from the field. After all, it was not the only third-party actor that had sought engagement in settling the armed conflict in Nepal. The UN, for instance, had started its work in Nepal as early as 2003. Among others, Tamrat Samuel, the UN's Senior Political Affairs Officer responsible for the South Asia region, made repeated visits to Nepal in an attempt to find possible UN-assisted avenues for resolving the conflict. In July 2005, UN Secretary-General's Special Adviser, Lakhdar Brahimi, visited Nepal and assured that 'the UN would remain available to provide its assistance in whatever form it may be needed' to solve Nepal's deteriorating political crisis. In the same year, the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) was able to persuade the government of Nepal to let OHCHR establish a monitoring mission that would observe, report, and work on preventing cases of serious human rights violations in the country (UN News 2005).

When visits from the UN officials began to become too frequent, India began to see that as a threat to its manoeuvring space. It interpreted the UN's increasing involvement as an act of encroachment into its area of influence.¹¹⁰ While the Maoists appeared to be in favour of inviting a relatively neutral third party, such as the UN, India was clearly against any third-party involvement in Nepal (Whitfield 2008: 9). Through various channels, India not only made its message clear that it opposed a third-party involvement in Nepal, but also systematically blocked other players—such as the Carter Centre and the Humanitarian Dialogue—and their activities in Nepal (Whitfield 2008: 13–17).

Nepali actors, who had initially targeted the UN as a potential mediator, slowly realised that the role that the UN system could play was mainly formal, which would be a limitation in solving the Nepal crisis since it required plenty of informal engagements as well.¹¹¹ Against this backdrop, India emerged as a strong candidate for the role of an external engager or a facilitator that could not only run a plethora of informal engagements, but also provide—as a powerful and influential neighbour—credible backing for any agreement that the SPA and the Maoists reached.

Furthermore, following the royal takeover in 2005, the conditions were highly favourable for an alliance between the Maoists and the SPA. The Six-Point Agreement was a remarkable achievement in itself. However, as past rivals, the sprouting relationship between the Maoists and the SPA also suffered from trust

¹¹⁰ Interview with an expert key informant (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹¹¹ Interview with Sudheer Sharma (02.08.2017).

issues. In such circumstances, even a slight involvement of a powerful third-party encouraged them to continue engagement even in the face of adversity and trust deficit. With India's indirect facilitation and support, this eventually resulted in the 12-Point Understanding and the resolution of a decade-long armed insurgency in Nepal.

5.7.1 The Making of the 12-Point Consensus

As I have highlighted throughout this chapter, the 12-Point Understanding has great importance in contemporary Nepali politics. Given that many of the key informants I interviewed played a direct role in its creation, I was keen to explore and gain insights about the discussions and developments that occurred on the days the Understanding was finalised. So, I often asked the key informants to describe the atmosphere in the room and share their memories from those days.

Shekhar Koirala vividly remembered the day the 12-Point Understanding was drafted and named the people who were present in the room. 'There is a lot of confusion about it', he emphasised, 'researchers like you should clear the confusion that there was no direct involvement of India in the 12-Point Understanding'. Mr Koirala, nonetheless, accepted that the Indian establishment, however, knew that the SPA and the Maoists were reaching an 'understanding', and that before the 12-Point Understanding was finalised, the leaders of the Nepali Congress and the CPN(M) had separately met with Pranab Mukherjee, the leader of the Indian Congress and India's External Affairs Minister at the time.¹¹²

Rajan Bhattarai, who had been assigned by his party, CPN (UML), to coordinate pre-agreement activities in New Delhi, also elaborated on how the Understanding had come about:

The claims that the 12-Point Understanding was drafted by India or originally written in Hindi are completely baseless. I was myself in New Delhi and was coordinating as per my party's instructions. Baburam Bhattarai and KP Oli drafted the text, and it was typed at the place we were staying. However, there is no need to debate the facilitative role of the Indian establishment. It let us use its land and helped create a conducive environment for dialogue. However, the argument that India was involved in the agenda-setting of the Understanding is wrong.¹¹³

Other participants shared similar stories. A key informant, for instance, shared accounts of his journey to New Delhi, explaining how he and his colleagues used the excuse of 'medical treatment' to travel to India while largely avoiding media and intelligence agency attention in Kathmandu.¹¹⁴ Bam Dev Gautam recalled similar events and explained how the 12-Point Understanding was drafted, redrafted, and finalised in a room where there were only Nepali leaders. He, too, however, accepted that even though the deal was possible because of the persistent action and effort of Nepali leaders, the Indian establishment was aware of what was going on there.¹¹⁵

As it is evident in multiple accounts of the political leaders who were directly involved in forging the Maoist-SPA alliance, it is apparent that the 12-Point Understanding was a result of a continuous effort that Nepali political actors made

¹¹² Interview with Shekhar Koirala (22.08.2017).

¹¹³ Interview with Rajan Bhattarai (13.07.2017).

¹¹⁴ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹¹⁵ Interview with Bamdev Gautam (15.07.2017).

in the wake of King Gyanendra's February 2005 coup. The first major milestone in that process was the Six-Point Agreement signed between the Maoists and the CPN (UML) in Rolpa. However, the 12-Point Understanding reached in New Delhi is the most significant and visible cornerstone of the Nepali peace process.

As Bishnu Poudel put it, the 12-Point Understanding was an outcome or an achievement that contained the collective consciousness, organisation, and values of Nepali political actors. However, since that outcome happened to be achieved in a foreign land, a wide variety of suspicions and interpretations have emerged.¹¹⁶

No matter how small India's contribution may have been, it must be properly acknowledged, and India deserves the credit that is due. However, India's role does not seem to be as significant and decisive as claimed by Pranab Mukherjee or S. Jaishankar. Moreover, the affinity between the Maoists and the SPA had been so close that, sooner or later, an alliance would have been formed, even if they had not been able to gather in New Delhi. Therefore, arguments—such as that of S Jaishankar—that the Maoists would still be in the jungle if India had not helped appear implausible and largely baseless. As Pradeep Gyawali put it:

If India's role had not been positive, it would have been a little difficult, but the process would have gone ahead. The Maoists had realised that they should come to a peace process, and the SPA had also realised that it was time to take the Maoists along and fight against the autocratic monarchy. The common midpoint was that the Maoists should be ready to shun arms, come to a peace process, and accept democracy, while other political parties should be ready to accept Constituent Assembly elections and make Nepal a republic. So, if India's role had not been positive, it would have been a little complicated, but it was not impossible.¹¹⁷

Altogether, the 12-Point Understanding came into fruition not because India used a whip of coercive diplomacy or because it performed the magic of a skilled mediator, but at that particular juncture in history, political developments in Nepal necessitated such a solution. In other words, the balance of power in Nepal's politics had moved from a trilateral into a bilateral one, and alliance-building between the Maoists and the SPA was quite obvious, given that both were suffering from the King's suppression.

The SPA recognised that its collaboration with the Maoists was crucial in the struggle against King Gyanendra's direct rule, and that this partnership would ultimately help to end the armed conflict. Similarly, the Maoists were also facing a crisis and a critical juncture. In a way, the insurgency was not in a position to move forward. Gradually, they had realised that even if they captured the state, they would not be able to sustain it/run it all by themselves. They were, indeed, searching for a way out.¹¹⁸

I will explore the theoretical linkages of these occurrences in detail in later chapters. However, in brief, from a theoretical standpoint, I argue that during the 2001 and 2003 peace talks, the Maoist armed conflict was not yet 'ripe'¹¹⁹ for resolution. By late 2005, when the 12-Point Understanding had been signed, a mutually hurting stalemate (MHS)¹²⁰ was developing between the Maoists and the

¹¹⁶ Interview with Bishnu Poudel (13.07.2017).

¹¹⁷ Interview with Pradeep Gyawali (10.07.2017).

¹¹⁸ Interview with Beduram Bhusal (14.07.2017).

¹¹⁹ For an in-depth understanding of conflict ripeness, see Chapter 3, or, for instance, Zartman & Touval (1985), Zartman (1989, 2000, 2001).

¹²⁰ See, for instance, Zartman (2002).

SPA. The Maoists had expanded and reached a certain level, but progressing further from there was proving to be extremely difficult for them. In the case of the SPA, they could neither dethrone the King nor surrender to the Maoists. Amidst this stagnation, they were able to convert a mutually hurting stalemate (MHS) into a mutually enticing opportunity (MEO) (see, for instance, Crocker 1992, Mitchell 1995, Pruitt 1997, Ohlson 1998, Pruitt & Olczak 1995). This was the case with India, too. India, which had been concerned about the spillover effect of the Maoist insurgency and the security threats that it would cause, had an 'enticing opportunity' to be an informal mediator or a facilitator. By doing so, it could not only help solve a protracted conflict in its immediate neighbourhood, but also claim credit for it and increase its leverage over political actors in Nepal.¹²¹

5.7.2 An Uneasy Aftermath

Interpreting India's role in the formation of the 12-Point Understanding and the overall peace process has been difficult. While there is no denying the moral and practical support that India provided, its exaggerated interpretation of its involvement created unease, confusion, and even resistance in Nepal (see Chapters 6 & 7). Baburam Bhattarai, one of the main protagonists of the Maoist armed insurgency as well as of the peace process, called the selection of New Delhi as a venue for the 12-Point Understanding a 'blunder':

The foundation of the 12-Point Understanding had already begun in Nepal. We had already reached an understanding in Rolpa, where CPN (UML)'s Acting General Secretary, Bamdev Gautam, and Yuba Raj Gyawali were present. We contacted Girija Prasad Koirala from there, but he said he was unable to come because he was sick and that reaching Rolpa on horseback would be difficult for him. As per his request, we agreed to meet in Delhi. That, however, has turned out to be a blunder...Slowly, India was able to enter our internal conflicts, and the situation escalated to the point that an economic blockade was imposed on us (Bhattarai 2016).

In the aftermath of the 12-Point Understanding, India's engagement in Nepal rapidly increased. India began micromanaging Nepali politics, often bluntly undermining Nepal's national sovereignty. India should have been celebrated for its facilitative role in ensuring the safe landing of an armed insurgency and restoring peace and democracy in Nepal. However, because of the unusual approach it adopted in the wake of the conflict settlement, anti-Indian protests were common in Nepal. A key informant described how India attempted to misuse the trust capital it had garnered by facilitating the Maoist-SPA talks in New Delhi:

The 12-Point Understanding was basically the result of the efforts of Nepali political actors. That was the Nepali agenda. But there was an attempt to misuse that agenda. In the pretext of helping the Nepali peace process, India tried to dictate or micromanage Nepal's internal affairs, on issues such as the content of Nepal's new constitution, the structure of the federal state and the type of political economy that we were adopting.¹²²

In the aftermath of a successful peace deal, India–Nepal relations should have been stronger than ever. Instead, in the years following the CPA, they took a nosedive. Although I will discuss these post-peace deal issues in detail in the next chapter, it is evident that India's desire for influence and its fixation on controlling Nepali politics have resulted in more losses than gains. In the next chapter, I explore how

¹²¹ Interview with an expert key informant (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹²² Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

India's influence in Nepal grew following the 12-Point Understanding. I will detail how India aggressively engaged in political engineering and micromanagement by leveraging its role as a 'peacemaker' and by trying to fill the institutional void left after the monarchy's departure.

5.8 Chapter Summary: India and the 12-Point Understanding

My aim in this chapter was to assess India's involvement in the formation of the 12-Point Understanding, signed in November 2005 in New Delhi, India, between the Maoists and the Seven Party Alliance. The 12-Point Understanding was instrumental in ending Nepal's 10-year-long armed conflict and in transforming Nepal into a federal democratic republic. I began the chapter by addressing a few crucial issues regarding the 12-Point Understanding and discussing why it is important to assess India's involvement. This is especially relevant as the significant processes that led to the signing of the 12-Point Understanding have received little attention despite their importance. I also dedicated a short section to explain how India attempted to take more credit than it deserved, while its role was primarily that of a facilitator or an informal mediator. In addition, I analysed political events dating back to the 2001 peace talks to highlight how Nepali political actors actively engaged and utilised their agency to resolve the armed conflict and restore democracy and the rule of law that had been snatched by an authoritarian king.

Despite the criticisms, India also played a constructive role. For instance, when the Maoists were tagged as terrorists by countries like the United States, India viewed the insurgency as a political issue. It engaged with Nepali political figures and facilitated a safe environment for dialogue. However, India's actions, such as its continuous attempt to take credit for the success of the Nepali peace process, and its recurring tendency to seek a 'stake' in political processes in Nepal, not only severed post-conflict India–Nepal relations, but also contributed little to India's pursuit of projecting itself as a regional peacebuilder. Furthermore, it belittled the active role Nepali political actors played and the agency they exercised in resolving the armed conflict.

6. Mission Micromanagement: An Analysis of India's Engagement in Post-Conflict Nepal

In the previous chapter, I discussed how, in the wake of King Gyanendra's 2005 coup and the repressive approach he adopted to silence his critics, a coalition was built between the Maoists and the Seven Party Alliance (SPA). The Maoist-SPA coalition was formed through the 6-Point Agreement signed in Gharti Gaun in Nepal's Rolpa District and culminated in the 12-Point Understanding signed in New Delhi in November 2005. The 12-Point Understanding, I argued, was primarily a result of the extensive work and concerted effort of Nepali political actors. It was a response to the political crisis and stalemate created by King Gyanendra's authoritarian rule and the prolonged armed struggle of the Maoists. In its aftermath, the Maoists and the SPA fought what was touted as the 'last fight' against the King's autocratic regime. I argued in the previous chapter that while India's tacit support facilitated the transition from the 6-Point Agreement to the 12-Point Understanding, its role was not as decisive and crucial as it was often projected.

In this chapter, I will concentrate on the years following the 12-Point Understanding and discuss how India strengthened its presence in post-conflict Nepal by employing a combination of soft power and hard power instruments. I begin the chapter by discussing the immediate aftermath of the 12-Point Understanding and by examining how it inspired a series of unprecedented nationwide mass protests in Nepal. I show how, despite international pressure to negotiate midway with the King, the people's movement continued until the King gave in, and the parliament, which was dissolved in May 2002, was reinstated. After that, I analyse India's increased engagement in post-conflict Nepal. When the monarchy was abolished in 2008, and as the camaraderie that shaped the Maoist-SPA relationship—and the relationship between the parties within the SPA camp—began to shift gradually from companionship into that of competition and rivalry, India consolidated its presence in Nepal as a major and largely uncontested international player. India tactfully took advantage of the absence of a strong, established institution created after the monarchy's departure. Ultimately, this led to a situation in which the Indian embassy in Kathmandu and operatives of the Research and Analysis Wing (R&AW)—the foreign intelligence agency of India—became de facto dealmakers and informal mediators in crucial political negotiations in Nepal. This also led to a scenario in which Nepal started becoming increasingly dependent on India for solving its 'peacetime' crises.

My primary focus in this chapter is on the strategies that India used in its engagement in post-conflict Nepal. In the initial years of the peace process and political transition, India resorted to micromanagement, whereas in the later years, it relied more on hard power policy instruments. When the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) came to power in India in 2014, the BJP leadership crafted its own 'vision' of Nepal, which was heavily guided by the BJP's Hindutva preoccupation, expressed in the ideology of Hindu nationalism. As a result, one of India's top priorities in

later years became to keep Nepal, at least constitutionally, a Hindu nation. When India's earlier strategies, such as micromanagement and power diplomacy, were gradually ignored or avoided by Nepali political actors, the BJP-led Indian establishment resorted to more aggressive pursuits, such as coercive diplomacy and the imposition of an economic blockade. India also attempted to put pressure on Nepal by ostracising and isolating it in international forums. Even seemingly benign instruments, such as development assistance, were used as a tool for deepening its influence in Nepal.

I conclude the chapter with a brief theoretical discussion on soft power, hard power, and their combination, known as smart power. I argue that in its engagements in post-conflict Nepal, India used both soft power and hard power and a combination of the two. The major takeaway from this discussion is that India's focus was not on the means per se, but on the ends (i.e., its foreign policy goals). Finally, I contest the claims that India's foreign policy choices are increasingly guided by soft power policy instruments and argue that India's over-reliance on hard power instruments, such as coercive diplomacy and an economic blockade, was counterproductive, as it faced strong resistance and defiance in Nepal.

6.1 Jana Andolan II and the Dream of a 'New Nepal'

In the previous chapter, I elaborated on how the 12-Point Understanding between the Maoists and the SPA was reached in New Delhi. The 12-Point Understanding, which was essentially a culmination of political negotiations carried out both in Nepal and India, created a sense of enthusiasm and hope among ordinary Nepalis. The 12-Point consensus sketched a roadmap for a new Nepal where King Gyanendra's repressive rule would be replaced by 'full democracy' (see Appendix 4). In addition, in contrast to the King's plan of suppressing the rebels by force, the 12-Point pact made it clear that the Maoist armed conflict was a political issue and that it should be solved through dialogue and a negotiated settlement. It also called for 'creating a storm of nation-wide democratic movement' to bring down the autocratic monarchy and urged people from all walks of life, including civil society and professional organisations, to participate actively in the democratic movement. Furthermore, it emphasised that the core of the Understanding included matters like 'democracy, peace, prosperity, progressive social transformation, independence, sovereignty, and the dignity of the nation'.

The parliamentary political parties in the SPA had been protesting the King's direct rule since his October 2002 proclamation, through which he had sacked the elected prime minister and became the country's de facto ruler. However, the protests organised to challenge the King's undemocratic move and for the restoration of democracy attracted little public support. These pro-democracy protests were mainly concentrated in big cities and heavily depended on the participation of active party cadres. The political impact of these protests was limited, as many Nepalis remained largely indifferent.

There were a few reasons behind people's apathy towards these protests. First, although the Nepali people valued political freedom and democracy, they were not satisfied with the performance of the parliamentary parties in the post-1990 era. Ordinary Nepalis had harboured elevated expectations of governments formed after the 1990s democratic transformation. The parliamentary parties, too, had promised development and prosperity under their leadership. However, this did not materialise. Rather than concentrating on socio-economic transformation, the parties frequently became embroiled in seemingly perpetual power struggles,

spending their time establishing and dismantling governments every few months. As a result, not a single government formed after 1990 completed the five-year term stipulated in the country's constitution. Political instability, widespread corruption, and the onset and proliferation of a violent conflict all occurred when the parliamentary parties were in power. The poor performance of the parliamentary parties was one strong reason why ordinary people did not show up in the early pro-democracy protests.

Second, the parliamentary parties protesting against the King's direct rule demanded the restoration of democracy, but they had no firm proposals to address the ongoing armed insurgency. At that point, for ordinary Nepalis, resolving the armed conflict and restoring peace and safety were more important than reinstating a derailed democracy. Third, since the King had promised to restore order and ultimately hand over power to the people's representatives, people appeared reluctant to oppose the King's move right after his October 2002 move.

The 12-Point Understanding, however, drastically changed the dynamics of Nepali politics. It was reached at a time when Nepalis had been desperate for peace after experiencing a decade-long armed conflict. After all, it was ordinary Nepalis who suffered the most because of the armed conflict. By the time the 12-Point Understanding was reached, King Gyanendra's authoritarian rule had been in full swing, and the people had slowly realised that under the King's leadership, there would be neither peace nor democracy. The 12-Point Understanding not only offered a clear roadmap for peace but also made the promise of full democracy and incorporated several agendas of socio-economic transformation. In other words, when Nepal was caught in violent political chaos, the 12-Point Understanding promised a new Nepal that would be peaceful, democratic, inclusive, and ultimately prosperous.

After signing the 12-Point Understanding in New Delhi, the Maoist-SPA coalition started preparing for a large-scale mass movement in Nepal. However, there were many uncertainties and obstacles ahead. Madhav Kumar Nepal, who played an instrumental role in accelerating *Jana Andolan II* or the 2006 'people's movement', recalled how foreign actors had been sceptical of the success of the planned mass movement and the popularity of Nepali political parties in general. For instance, Matthew Kahane, the United Nations Resident Representative in Nepal, approached Mr Nepal and advised him to compromise with the King. Mr Kahane believed there was little hope for a successful mass movement in Nepal. Similarly, Pranab Mukherjee, the Minister for External Affairs of India at the time, and James F. Moriarty, the US Ambassador to Nepal, both expressed similar doubts. They argued that the parliamentary parties lacked popularity in Nepal, and a successful mass movement under their leadership was unlikely.¹²³

These assessments turned out to be inaccurate. A few days after the 12-Point Understanding was signed, the CPN (UML) organised a mass rally in Butwal, a city in western Nepal. Over fifty thousand people showed up at that rally.¹²⁴ Considering that the previous efforts by the parliamentary parties to organise large street protests had failed, the show of strength by the CPN (UML) in Butwal was notable. The success of the Butwal rally clearly signalled that the Nepali people had approved the agenda of peace and democracy that the 12-Point Understanding proposed.

In the following months, several protest rallies and pro-democracy mass gatherings were organised in other big cities, including Kathmandu, Pokhara,

¹²³ Interview with Madhav Kumar Nepal (11.07.2017).

¹²⁴ Interview with Madhav Kumar Nepal (11.07.2017).

Biratnagar, and Birgunj. These rallies, often led by the SPA leaders, created a foundation for a peaceful revolution that Nepal would witness in April 2006.

As pro-democracy demonstrations were gaining momentum, the SPA announced a three-day general strike for 6–8 April 2006.¹²⁵ The King-led government attempted to foil the general strike and suppress the protests by declaring ‘no protest’ zones and introducing curfew orders. Arrests, detention, and the use of physical force were also used as protest-suppressing strategies. These strategies, however, were of little use. Instead of serving as a deterrent, they acted as a catalyst, encouraging people to join the street protests.

As repression continued and people's participation grew significantly, the three-day general strike turned into an indefinite one. Protests were not limited to big cities but were organised even in smaller cities and villages. As days went by, the pro-democracy movement—called *Jana Andolan II*¹²⁶ in Nepali—grew increasingly spontaneous and gripped the entire country. I was one of millions of Nepalese who participated in these protests. At that time, I was a college student in Kathmandu, the capital city, and like many other Nepalis, fed up with the chaos, the armed conflict and the prolonged political instability in the country. My family had been internally displaced because of the armed conflict, and everyday life under King Gyanendra's rule was equally unsettling. We witnessed and experienced Nepal being increasingly militarised, and civilian liberties, such as the freedom of movement, were curtailed and compromised. Security checks were part of our daily lives, and one could be interrogated or even arrested for possessing political books or magazines. While bigger cities, such as Kathmandu, were relatively safer and under government control, people in rural areas lived with a different reality. They had no other choice but to cooperate with both the Maoists and the state security forces. People in the cities were compelled to pay donations to the Maoists, whereas people in villages were often forced to provide food and shelter to them. The state security forces often harassed and tortured people who would ‘shelter’ the Maoists and provided them with any form of support.

Through the 12-Point Understanding, the Maoists shunned their agenda of one-party communist rule and expressed their commitment to peace and multi-party democracy. This shift in the Maoist policy offered a prospect for peace and helped *Jana Andolan II* become what it ultimately became. The Maoists also participated in the nationwide protests—informally but actively and mostly peacefully. The last episode of *Jana Andolan II*, which began on 6 April, continued for 19 days until the King agreed to read out a declaration presented by the SPA.

Jana Andolan II began with small protests concentrated mainly in cities. However, it proliferated throughout the country and became an example of massively successful civil disobedience (see Picture 2). For 19 days, it appeared that Nepal had come to a complete standstill. Hundreds of thousands of people flooded the streets, calling for peace, democracy, and the end of King Gyanendra's oppressive rule.

As the movement gained significant momentum, a diverse array of professional and non-political groups also became involved. In schools, teachers stopped

¹²⁵ The selection of this time frame, April 6–8, had symbolic significance. The democratic movement of 1990 reached its peak between April 6–8. With the ban on political parties lifted on 8 April 1990, democracy was reintroduced in Nepal after three decades of Panchayat/monarchical rule. Therefore, the time between 6 and 8 April was considered auspicious or the time of people's victory.

teaching, and in hospitals, healthcare professionals offered only emergency medical care, refusing to provide any other services.

Picture 2: Street Protests During Jana Andolan II in Kathmandu, April 2006. Photos: Author.

The media, non-profit organisations, women, and indigenous groups were all part of the movement. Those who worked in the essential service sector also protested by tying black bandages around their wrists. In some instances, even police officers and soldiers deployed to crack down on the protesters began neglecting orders to use force. The movement got so much support that when it was at its peak, officials at Nepal's national bank closed the treasury and stopped releasing funds to the government (Poudel 2006: 25).

There can be an exhaustive analysis of the potential reasons behind people's unusual participation in *Jana Andolan II*. Key reasons for the massive turnout included people's frustration with the armed conflict, King Gyanendra's oppressive direct rule, and the shrinking democratic space in the country. After more than ten years of violent conflict, the people of Nepal were yearning for peace. They longed to return to the ordinary lives they had known before the armed insurgency and the King's authoritarian rule. They saw a glimmer of hope in the 12-Point Understanding, which not only promised to end the armed insurgency and the King's direct rule but also envisioned a more prosperous and equitable Nepal.

6.1.1 Jana Andolan II and a Confused International Community

On 21 April 2006, day 16 of the general strike, Indian Prime Minister Manmohan Singh sent a special envoy, Mr Karan Singh, to Nepal. Mr Singh, an Indian politician, diplomat and former Prince Regent of Jammu and Kashmir, also happened to be a relative of the Nepali royal family. He came to Nepal with the mandate of settling the political crisis created by *Jana Andolan II*. Moreover, saving

India's long-held two-pillar Nepal policy, i.e., constitutional monarchy and multi-party democracy, was his top priority. Mr Singh held talks with the King and senior Nepali politicians and unsuccessfully attempted to strike a compromise (Hindustan Times 2006).

However, Mr Singh's visit to Nepal at the peak of a peaceful revolution did more harm than good. In Nepal, his visit was perceived as an Indian intervention to save a decaying monarchy. In hasty meetings he conducted in Kathmandu, his focus was on preserving the monarchy in at least some form and persuading the King to compromise with the SPA.¹²⁷

Mr Singh had reportedly attempted to persuade the King to renounce executive power and reach a compromise with the SPA. In return, India would ensure that the King would be saved from being disgraced and that the institution of monarchy would not be abolished (Muni 2012: 329). India was aware of King Gyanendra and his son Paras Shah's notoriety in Nepal. Therefore, it had proposed that Paras's son, Hridayendra, who was just four at the time, should be declared king to help save the monarchy. A senior political leader recalled receiving the 'baby king' proposal when *Jana Andolan II* was at its peak:

INC's [Indian National Congress's] Karan Singh was Sonia Gandhi's political and foreign affairs advisor. He had come to meet me in [place redacted] and pitched the idea of a baby king. I told him it was already too late for something like that. If a similar proposal had come a few months earlier, then we could have thought a bit, maybe. But in the situation we were in, I rejected his baby king proposal.¹²⁸

Mr Singh's engagements in Kathmandu reflected India's inability to read the changed political climate that was sweeping across Nepal. India wanted to maintain the status quo in a country that was preparing for an unprecedented political leap. It is no secret that the Indian establishment was worried about the rise of the Maoist movement in Nepal and feared that the eradication of the monarchy would further strengthen the communists in Nepal. Therefore, India believed that maintaining the status quo in Nepal would be in its best interest. India's intervention, however, came at a time when the general strike had completely 'stopped' the country, and most of the state machinery was no longer cooperating with the King's administration. The protests had been so massive that the King had no option but to give in and fulfil the protesters' demands.

On 21 April 2006, after meeting with Mr Singh, the King addressed the nation. In the televised address, he announced that the executive power of the Kingdom of Nepal, which he had kept to himself through a royal proclamation (i.e., the 1 February 2005 coup d'état), was being returned to the people. In the same address, the King called on the protesting parties to recommend a new Prime Minister. The wording of the King's announcement was meticulously crafted to give the impression that he had indeed renounced absolute power and that democracy was being restored. However, by simply seeking a name for a new Prime Minister, the King had quietly retained the executive power for himself. Appointing a new Prime Minister, therefore, would not have made much difference as far as solving Nepal's ongoing political crisis was concerned. The King's address, for instance, did not mention the Maoist armed conflict or how it should be resolved in the new political

¹²⁷ This was confirmed by several political leaders I interviewed, including the ones who had met Mr Singh.

¹²⁸ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

context. The primary demand of the SPA was the restoration of the dissolved parliament. The King's speech did not address that either.

The SPA leaders had understood that in the absence of a legislative body, a Prime Minister appointed by the King would be just another Prime Minister appointed by the King. They were clear that such an appointee would be just a representative of the King with no authentic executive power. A sovereign parliament, on the other hand, would not only pass new laws and policies, but would also provide political legitimacy and legal backing to decisions with broader and far-reaching consequences. The parliament was needed to address other serious political issues, such as finding a negotiated settlement to the armed conflict and determining the future of the monarchy.

For those who had occupied the streets and virtually 'halted' the country for over two weeks, the King's announcement was something that had come too late and offered too little. The general strike had gained so much momentum and reached such a level that simply appointing a new Prime Minister from the SPA would hardly make any difference. The people had come to the streets for peace, for the restoration of democracy, and for an assurance of a better future. In other words, millions of Nepalis were on the streets not because they wanted a new Prime Minister or a new set of ministers. They occupied the streets because armed conflict had paralysed their lives. The King's authoritarian rule had restricted their freedom and aspirations. They were tired of the old structures and institutions, which were mostly oblivious to their woes.

The announcement made by the King on April 21 was filled with eloquent language, but it failed to offer any real solutions to the country's political stalemate. It also failed to address the anger in the streets. The international community welcomed the King's move hastily, without consulting the SPA leaders or carefully reading the mood on the streets. India's Ministry of External Affairs quickly issued a statement welcoming the King's announcement (see MEA India 2006a). Other influential international actors with residential representation in Kathmandu, such as the US and the EU, quickly followed India's lead. The international community not only welcomed the King's move, but it was actively engaged in putting pressure on the SPA leaders to compromise with the King. Madhav Kumar Nepal recalled how, on 21 April, he had received unusual phone calls from foreign ambassadors requesting him to call off the general strike and compromise with the King:

That day, four ambassadors called me: the Indian, British, Norwegian, and the US ambassador [to Nepal]. They all said that it was an initial success and a perfect opportunity to compromise with the King. They said that we must grab the chance. I told them we couldn't call off the strike or the movement and that it would continue until the King completely surrendered. The fight was for sovereignty, and the movement would not stop until that sovereignty came to where it belonged, i.e., to the people.¹²⁹

Shekhar Koirala also recalled how the next morning, after the King's announcement, a troop of foreign ambassadors crowded the residence of NC President G.P. Koirala. Mr Koirala was the most prominent leader of the SPA and a de facto leader of *Jana Andolan II*. With Koirala, the ambassadors made the same request: call off the strike, compromise with the King, and propose a new Prime Minister's name.¹³⁰ However, the SPA leaders had already recognised that the King's announcement was a trap in disguise. It did not address their main demand

¹²⁹ Interview with Madhav Kumar Nepal (11.07.2017).

¹³⁰ Interview with Shekhar Koirala (22.08.2017).

and overlooked the people's aspirations for peace, the restoration of democracy, and a promise of political stability. Through a statement, the Maoists also rejected the King's announcement and warned the parliamentary parties not to backtrack from the 12-Point Understanding.

In emphasising a compromise between the SPA and the King, the international actors, led by India, were excluding the Maoists from the political process that was developing and were indirectly playing down the role of the Maoists in *Jana Andolan II*. A peaceful people's movement of a massive scale was an agenda of the 12-Point Understanding, and while the Maoists were not officially part of *Jana Andolan II*, their cadres actively took part in the street protests. Similarly, throughout the movement, the SPA leaders, including G.P. Koirala and Madhav Kumar Nepal, were regularly in touch with senior Maoist leaders such as Pushpa Kamal Dahal and Baburam Bhattarai.¹³¹

Despite the foreign pressure for a compromise, the SPA leaders made it clear that the King's announcement was nothing but a sham, and the street protests would continue. Some of the biggest street protests of *Jana Andolan II* were organised in the following days. As I witnessed myself, major roads and pavements in Kathmandu were filled with protesters shouting for peace and democracy, demanding that the King step down and leave the country.

As shocking images from the streets of Kathmandu circulated around the world, the King had fewer and fewer options at his disposal. The international community, which had enthusiastically welcomed the King's earlier move, swiftly revised their statements, saying that ultimately it was the will of the Nepali people that would prevail. In India, the Foreign Secretary, Shyam Sharan, who had earlier been India's ambassador to Nepal, affirmed at a press conference that the will of the Nepali people must be respected and that India would support democracy in Nepal. He added:

We, of course, support the view of the [Seven Party] Alliance that restoration of peace and multi-party democracy in Nepal is the need of the hour. The Alliance of course has been in the forefront, as I said, of the peaceful movement for the restoration of multi-party democracy in Nepal. They have given expression to the aspirations of the people of Nepal for democratic values and freedom and we believe that the sentiments of the people of Nepal need to be respected (MEA India 2006b).

Shyam Sharan's statement that day gave two messages. First, it indicated that India had abandoned its traditional two-pillar Nepal policy (i.e., parliamentary democracy and constitutional monarchy). Second, India also refrained from its usual recommendation that the constitutional forces in Nepal should cooperate, which clearly referred to a coalition between the King and the parliamentary parties while excluding the Maoists. This time, India emphasised peace and multi-party democracy and gave no clear statement on safeguarding the monarchy's future. In other words, India had sensed from the latest political developments, particularly the street protests, that the King and his administration had been hugely unpopular, and the institution of monarchy was becoming obsolete in Nepal. India also appeared to have realised that to secure its national interests, it needed to engage with and recognise the new actors strengthening their grounds in Nepal, i.e., the SPA and the Maoists.

On 24 April, three days after seeking a name for a new Prime Minister, the King once again addressed the nation. This time, he fulfilled the SPA's demand of

¹³¹ Interview with Shekhar Koirala (22.08.2017) & Madhav Kumar Nepal (11.07.2017).

reinstating the dissolved parliament and called the first meeting of the House of Representatives.¹³² The King had reportedly simply ‘read out’ the statement drafted by the SPA leaders, into which some ‘Indian input’ was also received.¹³³ In addition, it has also been argued that the King had agreed to yield power once the Chief of Staff of the Royal Nepali Army, Pyar Jung Thapa, receiving persuasion from India, had pleaded to the King that ‘there was no military solution to either the *Jana Andolan II* or the Maoist insurgency’ (Muni 2012: 329). As a powerful neighbour of Nepal, India might have certainly provided such advice to the army general. However, *Jana Andolan II* had gained significant momentum and reached such a peak that the King had very limited options.

The success of *Jana Andolan II* ended King Gyanendra’s direct rule. Without the participation of millions of Nepalis, achieving such a feat would have been impossible. With the proposal of a baby king, or by emphasising the unity between ‘constitutional forces’, India was actively engaged in moulding, altering, and manipulating the political course. However, as soon as it sensed that saving the monarchy was going to be impossible in the new political context, it swiftly changed sides by ditching its stance on the monarchy and extending hands to the reemerging and rising political forces: the SPA and the Maoists.

6.2 India’s Entry as a Meddler and a Micromanager in Post-Conflict Nepal

The success of *Jana Andolan II* was a significant political victory both for the SPA and the Maoists. In other words, the movement had approved the 12-Point Understanding and its message that the Maoist insurgency was a political issue and that it demanded a political solution. The way ahead was to be a tumultuous one. The countless negotiations and compromises that followed *Jana Andolan II* were often complicated. As a result, post-*Jana Andolan II*, everyday politics in Nepal became riddled with political impasses and prolonged stalemates. On one hand, the success of *Jana Andolan II* offered the SPA and the Maoists an unprecedented opportunity and a foundation from which a ‘new Nepal’ could be built. On the other hand, navigating a long and complex political transition was equally challenging. The power vacuum created in the wake of *Jana Andolan II* also seemed to overwhelm the political actors of the ‘new Nepal’. This was the point at which India’s presence in Nepal as an ‘unofficial mediator’, ‘dispute settler’, or even as a ‘micromanager’ intensified, and India’s political engineering in Nepal became pervasive.

India’s extensive involvement in post-conflict Nepal is often linked to the 12-Point Understanding. The most common argument is that since this agreement was signed in New Delhi with India’s tacit support, India’s presence in post-conflict Nepal became inevitable (see, for instance, Shrestha 2006, Jha 2012, Muni 2012, Sharma 2013). However, the tendency to see India’s extensive post-conflict engagement in Nepal as a continuation of the 12-Point Understanding is largely flawed and exaggerated. While India played a supportive role in bringing the SPA and the Maoists together, its contribution was not as decisive as later portrayed. As I showed in the previous chapter, the foundation for the Maoist-SPA coalition had

¹³² See King Gyanendra’s Proclamation, April 24, 2006, https://www.satp.org/satporgtp/countries/nepal/document/papers/King_Gyanendra%20Proclamation_Apr_24.htm

¹³³ Interview with Shekhar Koirala (22.08.2017).

already been laid out in the 6-Point Agreement signed in Nepal's Rolpa district. In fact, India's engagement in post-conflict Nepal increased unprecedentedly, not necessarily because it had facilitated the 12-Point Understanding, but because it was successful in getting the credit for 'mediating' the deal. In addition, India quickly recognised the power vacuum created by the departure of the 240-year-old monarchy and stepped up its presence in Nepali politics as a power figure, a status traditionally enjoyed by the monarchy.

Nepal's modern history is full of political struggles, shaped mainly by continuous altercations between forces supporting multiparty democracy and those advocating for a monarchical authoritarian regime. Thus, coups d'états, democratic movements, and sudden regime changes have moulded the country's modern political history. However, this pattern of political interplay underwent an abrupt change following *Jana Andolan II*. Although already weakened after the success of *Jana Andolan II*, the first meeting of the Constitutional Assembly on 28 May 2008 abolished the monarchy and declared Nepal a federal democratic republic. This declaration removed the monarchy, a major player, from the political battleground and brought in the Maoists as new players into the political mainstream.

The departure of a long-established institution with 240 years of history coincided with the rise of a new political force that had gained its legitimacy through radical communist ideology and acts of violence. This fateful swap had significant political and social repercussions. In other words, it was more than a simple change of guards at Nepal's political powerhouses. The Maoist insurgency and *Jana Andolan II* had thrived on the promise of creating a new Nepal, and on the new Nepal menu were several seemingly radical as well as contentious issues, such as state restructuring, promulgation of a constitution through a people-elected Constituent Assembly, settlement of Maoist combatants, and several other issues related to broader socioeconomic transformation.

As Nepal experienced unprecedented political upheavals and a massive socio-political transformation, this was naturally an issue of deep interest for Nepal's two immediate neighbours, India and China. At least in the initial years of the political transition, China took a somewhat cautious and distant approach, limiting itself to the role of an observer or somewhat of a passive player. India's involvement, however, was active and pervasive. In political processes and negotiations that followed *Jana Andolan II*, such as drafting the Peace Accord, preparing and finalising the interim constitution, and forming the interim legislature and the interim government, India was massively involved (Jha 2012: 337).

Ultimately, India became the sole international player exerting substantial influence in Nepal's peace process and political transition. India achieved this monopoly in three phases. First, it successfully took mediation credit by pointing out that the 12-Point Understanding had been signed in India and was done so under its active facilitation. No political actor in Nepal challenged this narrative, at least initially, as the tendency not to anger India was common. Second, India was successful in ousting potential competitors from the field (see, for instance, Destradi 2010, 2012). It was also successful in timing the departure of other actors that it thought might hinder its actions in Nepal. For instance, among others, India actively facilitated an early departure of the UN Special Mission in Nepal and the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (Bhandari 2016).

Third, India successfully convinced the West, particularly the US, the UK, and the EU, that its leadership was essential and undeniable for managing Nepal's peace process. Particularly following the 2005 royal coup, Western powers, confused by

Nepal's intricate tripolar conflict between the monarchy, the Maoists, and the parliamentary parties, began to accept India's leadership in dealing with Nepal's armed conflict and the peace process (Upreti 2009: 225). As a result, India's presence rapidly grew in Nepal. While New Delhi appeared reluctant to maintain a high-level political engagement with Nepal, Indian bureaucrats and foreign intelligence agencies, particularly the Research & Analysis Wing, ran whimsical operations in Nepal (see, for instance, Sharma 2013). Especially in the later years, Nepal became heavily dependent on India as far as managing its peace process was concerned (Upreti 2009: 234).

India consistently used a narrative—the responsibility narrative—to justify its post-conflict engagement in Nepal. As evident in the interviews I carried out, Indian government representatives in Kathmandu or the people working for Indian intelligence services often claimed that since India was the one that brokered the 12-Point Maoist-SPA deal, it had the moral responsibility to ensure that the peace process went smoothly, and the political transition was managed successfully till the end. As India's action later demonstrated, the moral responsibility narrative was merely a tactic devised to ensure that the peace process and post-conflict political arrangements were directed at India's will. Since India was the only international player with a substantial presence in post-conflict Nepal, its influence was profound, among others, in dictating the terms of the interim constitution, during both the first and second Constituent Assembly elections, and in forming new governments and toppling them every few months (Jha 2012: 337).

At one point, India's meddling in Nepal's internal affairs became so intense that even senior Nepali politicians, who were both accomplices and victims of India's engagement in Nepal, started being publicly vocal against it (PTI 2013). The India–Nepal relationship should have reached new heights during the peace process—a process which India claimed it had facilitated and strongly supported. On the ground, however, that was not the case. Within a few years after the peace process began, anti-India sentiment in Nepal skyrocketed, mainly due to India's micromanagement and interference. This was also visible in the streets of Nepali cities. As India's micromanagement of Nepali politics deepened, protests in front of the Indian embassy in Kathmandu started becoming increasingly common. Nepali media, civil society groups, and the academic community began to openly criticise India's micromanagement approach in Nepal. This was a big blow to the already delicate India–Nepal relations. The anti-Indian sentiment had grown so much so that in October 2010, the Indian Ambassador was attacked and shown black flags in Nepal (Nayak 2012: 137, Das 2010). Such an incident had never occurred before in the history of relations between the two countries.

6.3 Different Shades of Indian Micromanagement

India's entry, or rather its identity as a micromanager of post-conflict Nepal, became a subject of extensive discussion in Nepal. For several years, the term 'micromanagement' became a staple of Nepali media and political actors. However, despite its widespread use and notoriety, there has been limited scholarly examination of the actual practices and mechanisms associated with this alleged micromanagement. Indian micromanagement remains mysterious, in the sense that there is little information on what it meant in everyday political and administrative affairs. How were these micromanagement actions performed, and by whom? What type of actions were carried out, and what was the ultimate motive behind these actions? Amidst this confusion, the issue of Indian micromanagement

continues to remain primarily an abstract and elusive concept. It is more of a collective term, or a standard nomenclature, used for a variety of India's actions in Nepal.

There are a few underlying issues for this continued confusion. First, there has been a tendency to understand Indian micromanagement within a limited scope, i.e., equating India's micromanagement merely as an issue prevalent in the political domain. While Nepali politics suffered probably the worst pain of India's meddling and micromanagement, it was not the only area that put up with India's interference. Nepal's security sector—especially the Nepal Army and Nepal Police—as well as the civil bureaucracy, were also heavily affected by India's interference. Therefore, any attempt to investigate India's micromanagement in post-conflict Nepal must consider India's engagement not only in the political domain but also in other areas, including the security sector and the bureaucracy. My attempt in this section is just that—to look at India's micromanagement from three different domains (security, bureaucratic, and political) and shed light on the widely talked about, but poorly understood mechanisms of Indian micromanagement of post-conflict Nepal.

6.3.1 Meddling in the Security Sector

As India entered Nepal with its micromanagement armour, one of its most critical engagements was in the country's security sector. To strengthen its presence and influence in Nepal's security apparatus, it consistently tried to bypass civilian governments in Kathmandu and establish direct contact with the Nepali security forces. Whenever needed, India not only lobbied on their behalf but also stepped in to assist and offer them patronage. In other words, India's actions were directed towards ensuring that the de facto masters of Nepali security forces were in India and that the ultimate loyalty of Nepali security forces rested on New Delhi.

While India engaged with Nepal's entire state security organs¹³⁴, its primary focus was nonetheless on the two largest security agencies: the Nepal Army and the Nepal Police. Among the two, India's focus on the Nepal Army was even more intense. The national army had traditionally been a bulwark of the monarchy, and the monarchy had protected its special privileges. The monarchy had been a staunch protector of the army and vice versa. First, the weakening and eventual end of the monarchy following *Jana Andolan II* created a transitional power vacuum, which also affected the national army. Particularly after the first CA elections, the conservative army leadership was reluctant to cooperate with the Maoist-led post-conflict government. Moreover, the newly established institution of the presidency did not yield as effective an influence over the army as the monarchy. Consequently, India shrewdly stepped in to fill the power vacuum created by the monarchy's departure and began to act as the de facto protector of the army (see, for instance, Adhikari 2012, Adhikari 2014).

One significant incident of India's micromanagement that gained widespread media attention and public outcry also involved the national army. When the first Constituent Assembly elections were held in 2008, the Maoists emerged as the biggest political party. Since they could not secure a single majority, they were compelled to form a coalition government. When the Maoist leaders filled in top ministerial posts in the government, Rookmangud Katawal, a fierce critic of the

¹³⁴ Nepal Army, Nepal Police, Armed Police Force, and the state intelligence agency National Investigation Bureau.

Maoists and a staunch supporter of the outgoing monarchy, led the Nepal Army. Known for his disdain for democracy, Katawal openly opposed the CPA provision for merging the Maoist combatants into the national army (Adhikari 2014: 245). As later developments revealed, this was also something India wished for and desired.

Additionally, Mr Katawal opposed the government's proposal to make the national armed force more inclusive by recruiting Madheshi minorities. Under Mr Katawal's initiative, the Nepal Army also made several political recommendations to be included in the post-conflict interim constitution. These recommendations included that issues such as secularism, state restructuring and adopting an inclusive political framework should be decided not by the people-elected Constituent Assembly, but through a national referendum (Adhikari 2014: 245).

The relationship between the army and the Maoist-led leftist government further soured when, in April 2009, the government rejected Mr Katawal's proposal of extending the tenures of eight brigadier generals preparing for retirement. Instead of admonishing the generals to comply with the government's decision, Mr Katawal asked them to ignore the government's order and continue in office (Adhikari 2016).

Moreover, under Mr Katawal's leadership, the Nepal Army began recruiting soldiers—an act that bluntly violated the terms of the 2006 Comprehensive Peace Accord. As Mr Katawal's indifference towards Nepal's new political reality and his disobedience of the elected government grew, Defence Minister Ram Bahadur Thapa, a senior Maoist figure, demanded an explanation from Katawal for his seemingly reckless actions. Instead of answering the minister, Mr Katawal started 'lobbying with the other parties and diplomatic missions against the Maoists' (Adhikari 2014: 246).

Amid growing pressure for disciplinary action against Mr Katawal, particularly from within the Maoist party, on 3 May 2009, the Maoist-led government decided to dismiss him from his position as Chief of Army Staff of the Nepal Army. Even though Mr Katawal's dismissal was within the government's jurisdiction, it quickly became a controversial political issue. Instead of waiting for the government's decision to mature and then to challenge it in a court, Mr Katawal began making phone calls to 'international allies'.¹³⁵ India was particularly active in foiling the government's plan to oust Mr Katawal. Rakesh Sood, the Indian ambassador to Nepal at the time, met with Nepal's president, Ram Baran Yadav, twice over the course of two days. Mr Sood reportedly warned that if the government's decision to sack Mr Katawal was approved by the president, a serious mishap would follow. Mr Sood had given a similar warning to Prime Minister Pushpa Kamal Dahal 'Prachanda' (see Nepal Magazine 2009).

The Indian ambassador was not the only one who aggressively lobbied to keep Mr Katawal in his position. The Indian government in New Delhi also intervened actively. For instance, Pranab Mukherjee, India's Minister for External Affairs, made phone calls to Nepal's president and reportedly warned that the sacked army chief would not leave the army headquarters even if the president refused to give him a stay order (Jha 2012, Adhikari 2014, Nepal Aaja 2017). In a 2017 interview with Ratopati, a Nepali online news portal, President Yadav accepted that he had received foreign pressure in the Katawal case:

¹³⁵ Katawal revealed this himself in his 2018 autobiography (see Katawal 2018).

A foreign power, which I do not want to name, wanted me to give General Katawal a stay order and declare a state of emergency in the country. I, however, refused to declare an emergency (Yadav 2017).

The foreign power that Mr Yadav referred to was apparently India. Western diplomatic missions in Kathmandu, particularly those of the US and the UK, appeared to be in Mr Katawal's favour too. However, their lobbying and influence did not compare to that of India's. President Yadav ultimately succumbed to India's pressure and refused to approve the government's decision to sack Mr Katawal. This was an unprecedented and unexpected outcome, since Nepal's 2007 interim constitution granted no executive power to the president. The president's decision was also humiliating to the Maoists, since they had secured the highest number of votes in the 2008 CA elections and had led the coalition government as the biggest party in the Constituent Assembly.

A day after the president's stay order for Mr Katawal, Prime Minister Pushpa Kamal Dahal 'Prachanda' resigned from his position. The CPN (UML), a coalition partner in the government, was reportedly persuaded by India to withdraw from the government after having initially given a green signal for Mr Katawal's dismissal. This way, the first elected government of post-conflict Nepal collapsed within less than a year. In his resignation speech, Prachanda stated that regressive elements had hatched a conspiracy against the fledgling republic and that he would not give in to foreign powers. He further stated:

I would also like to draw the attention of all patriotic Nepali brothers and sisters towards the visible and invisible role of some international power centres in the Army chief issue...We are not willing to bow our heads in front of foreign masters and ignore the blood sacrifice of tens of thousands of patriotic individuals (Cited in Poudyal 2016).

Disenchanted by India's behaviour, which he perceived as a betrayal, Prachanda initiated what he called a campaign for 'national independence'. The obscure and short-lived campaign emphasised that the unequal relationship with India and India's engagement in Nepali politics had to be adapted to the 'new realities' (Jha 2012: 342).

The Katawal case stands as one of the earliest and most striking examples of India's successful micromanagement of a high-profile domestic issue in Nepal. By supporting General Katawal, India contributed to maintaining the status quo in Nepal. At the same time, it was also successful in vilifying the Maoists as would-be totalitarians. Ultimately, the Katawal case also broke the left alliance and crumbled the coalition government.

The attempt to sack the army chief proved costly to the Maoists. They not only lost control over the government but also became victims of a narrative that claimed that they were not serious about the peace process and were secretly working to establish a communist dictatorship. According to this narrative, the Maoists' motive for replacing Mr Katawal was to replace him with a pliable army chief who would ultimately help the Maoists seize state power. Whether the Maoists would go that way is a matter of mere speculation. The republican system in the country was the outcome of a long struggle against monarchical dictatorship. It was made possible through the joint efforts of the SPA, the Maoists, and civil society. While the argument that the Maoists wanted a more cooperative army chief is plausible, the accusation of plotting a communist dictatorship appears to be largely exaggerated. The Maoists were undoubtedly aware that the people who had vehemently rejected

King Gyanendra's authoritarian rule would do the same to any new dictatorial regime.

Even though the narrative of a communist dictatorship was used to vilify and ostracise the Maoists, the real motive for keeping General Katawal was to ensure that the Maoists had little to no representation in the national army when the army integration process began. A key informant familiar with Nepal's security sector recalled how the Indian establishment wished to prevent the Maoist combatants from integrating into the Nepal Army:

In my interactions with senior Indian leaders and ministers, their wish was that the Maoist combatants should not be integrated into the Nepal Army...They [India] facilitated the 12-Point Understanding, accepted the provision of a Special Committee [for army integration] and its mandate that the Maoist combatants should be integrated into the state security forces. However, they also kept saying that the Maoists should not be integrated into the national army. They took quite a contradictory approach.¹³⁶

A key informant, who interacted with Indian leaders regularly, recalled similar conversations he had. He argued that in the name of 'containing' the Maoists, India preferred the status quo to be maintained and resorted to using various propaganda tools, often running reckless intelligence agency operations in Nepal.¹³⁷

The Katawal case was a high-profile incident that visibly showed India's deep interest and engagement in Nepali security agencies in the post-conflict context. India has always tried to maintain a direct relationship with Nepali security forces—among other things, by funding their infrastructure and providing them with training and ammunition. However, the intensity of its engagement to the level of micromanagement was seen mainly in the post-conflict context.

India's interest and influence extended beyond the national army. Over the years of political transition, it was also deeply involved in the internal affairs of the Nepal Police. Ranjit Rae, who served as Head of the Northern Division at India's Ministry of External Affairs between 2002 and 2006, is one of the few former Indian government officials who has publicly claimed India's involvement in forging the 12-Point Understanding between the Maoists and the SPA. Mr Rae later served in Nepal as India's Ambassador between 2013 and 2017. During these four crucial years of the peace process and political transition, Mr Rae became a 'poster child' of Indian micromanagement in Nepal. In 2021, Mr Rae published a book acknowledging that anti-Indian sentiment in Nepal had been widespread. He also claimed that the so-called Indian micromanagement in Nepal was an invited one. In the book, he detailed two incidents of high-profile government appointments where he was indirectly invited to intervene. Both incidents relate to the appointment of heads of Nepal Police from two different government administrations:

A new Inspector-General of Police (IGP) for Nepal had to be selected since the incumbent was retiring. The home minister asked me for views about the candidates. I checked with my colleagues since it was important to have an IGP who was cooperative with his Indian counterparts and received the advice that the senior-most candidate on the list was the most suited. I conveyed to the home minister my opinion that it would be appropriate to follow the criteria of seniority and merit (Rae 2021: 17).

¹³⁶ Interview with an expert key-informant (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹³⁷ Interview with an expert key informant (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

On the next occasion, when another new IGP was to be selected, there was a list of four. Each of the four candidates visited me at India House conveying their keenness to strengthen cooperation with their Indian counterparts. I had not invited them to visit me (Rae 2021: 18).

Mr Rae mentions instances like these to claim that it was Nepali actors who sought India's intervention and not the other way around. An obvious shortcoming inherent in such arguments is that they rely on cherry-picked examples and tend to blame the victims. Mr Rae discusses the instances when he was allegedly invited to intervene, but he does not address how and why India reached that position in the first place. It is important to acknowledge that the situations Mr Rae referenced arose from a meticulous, pervasive, and prolonged Indian involvement in post-conflict Nepal. The IGP candidates lined up at the Indian embassy not because they welcomed India's intervention, but because they believed that securing the top job that they were aiming for was nearly impossible without India's blessing.

While only a few high-profile cases received ample publicity—such as the ones I mentioned above—India's interference and micromanagement in Nepal's security sector were often subtle and far from the media spotlight. There were several reasons why India kept the security sector under its micromanagement radar. First, as was visible in the Katawal case, India supported a conservative and pro-royalist army leadership that upheld the status quo and fiercely opposed the progressive leap Nepal wanted to take in the post-conflict context. For instance, by supporting Mr Katawal, India gave a clear message that it also favoured keeping the status quo in Nepal and disdained the structural and institutional shake-ups that the Maoist-led government wanted to execute. As Adhikari (2014: 243) has noted:

[India's] goal was to see the Maoists transform into another Nepali Congress or UML: demilitarized, socialized into the old political culture and responsive to the same incentives. The Maoist agenda of state reform was considered secondary. Like a number of parliamentary party leaders, Indian diplomats thought the Maoists' agenda hindered their transformation into a mainstream political party that operated according to the familiar rules of the parliamentary game.

Through similar incidents, such as supporting General Katawal, India demonstrated that it kept ties with Nepal's conservative and pro-royalist forces even though *Jana Andolan II* had made them virtually obsolete in post-conflict Nepali politics. A quick look at India–Nepal relations over the last seven decades reveals that India frequently objected to Nepal's progressive advancements. For instance, in the 1950s, India helped the autocratic Ranas secure political space even though the anti-Rana struggle swept across Nepal. Similarly, when its needs were met, India had no problem cooperating with the *Panchayat* dictatorship for nearly three decades. As far as settling conflicts or offering solutions to Nepal's domestic problems is concerned, India has often sought to maintain the status quo in one form or another or to advance the so-called middle-ground solutions.

Intervening in high-profile appointments and micromanaging the internal affairs of Nepal's established institutions, like the army and the police, was India's strategy to counter China, a clear competitor. In a way, through meddling and micromanagement, India could show that Nepal continued to be under its sphere of influence. India has always been anxious and paranoid about China's growing influence in Nepal, and its actions in Nepal are often targeted at preventing and checking any form of Chinese influence (see, for instance, Kumar 2016, Chapagain 2018).

Over the years, India has also mastered the art of dividing Nepali institutions and power entities by engaging them one-on-one. Apart from the usual government-to-government relations, India also maintains close contacts with other state structures and non-state forces and factions in Nepal. This includes security agencies, the judiciary, opposition parties, as well as dissidents and rebel groups. Those considered to be India's 'assets' or 'allies' in Nepal are often provided with financial and lobbying support. Those who are not pliable or are perceived as antagonistic are targeted and punished. These parallel one-on-one engagements have usually been used to practise the classic 'divide and rule' strategy and to secure India's self-interests.

Nepal's security forces heavily depend on India to import both lethal and non-lethal military equipment. The supply of arms and ammunition to Nepali security forces is a lucrative business for India. However, business aside, the information on Nepal's military strength is equally important. India is well aware of the total destructive power of Nepali security forces because most of the weapons that are used in Nepal come from India.¹³⁸ Similarly, India has always been wary of countries like China and Pakistan's potential affinity with Nepal's security forces and the repercussions that could have on its own security. As a result, keeping Nepali security agencies under close observation and control has always been India's priority. The post-conflict transition and fragile political environment provided an ideal opportunity for India to enhance its engagement in Nepal's security sector.

6.3.2 Nepali Bureaucracy and Politics as Hostages of Indian Micromanagement

As I argued before, India's post-conflict involvement in Nepal was complex and multifaceted. Besides the security sector, India's micromanagement and manipulation were also rife in Nepali politics and bureaucracy. It can be argued that India's influence began at the very beginning of the peace process, as the Indian establishment informally supported and facilitated the 12-Point Understanding signed between the SPA and the Maoists. India also influenced the Comprehensive Peace Accord signed in 2006 (Jha 2012: 337). In the years that followed, India strengthened its presence as the most dominant foreign power in Nepal.

As India consolidated its presence in post-conflict Nepal, its interest in Nepal's internal affairs also expanded. The areas of interest were broad, from major and minor political issues to seemingly trivial administrative issues, such as job appointments in Nepal's ministries and government institutions. Because of India's extensive engagement and pervasive micromanagement, it appeared as if India had been running a parallel government in Nepal. As a key informant explained, the loyalties of Nepali officials also seemed divided. Some appeared to be loyal to Singha Durbar (i.e., Nepal government's headquarters), while others seemed to have their loyalties to Lainchaur (i.e., the Indian embassy in Kathmandu).¹³⁹

During the years of political transition, a common trend was for the Indian embassy in Kathmandu to invite influential Nepali political leaders for 'dinner' to share their opinions, concerns, and demands, even regarding minor political issues.¹⁴⁰ This seemingly benign 'dinner diplomacy' was aimed at influencing and

¹³⁸ Interview with Balananda Sharma (16.08.2017)

¹³⁹ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹⁴⁰ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

micromanaging political processes in Nepal. One key informant, requesting anonymity, recalled that he, too, had been repeatedly invited by the Indian embassy in Kathmandu for dinner meetings and that he had ignored such invitations after attending once.

India also made use of other soft power instruments to exert its influence. India's government-sponsored scholarships are one such example. During the later years of political transition, when Indian micromanagement in Nepal peaked, India increased the number of scholarships it provided to Nepali students. By 2014, under nearly a dozen scholarship schemes, more than 3,000 Nepali students were sponsored by India (Tang 2021: 6). India prioritised children of influential leaders and bureaucrats for such scholarships, and when needed, these scholarships were used as political bargaining tools.

In 2010, it was reported that one of the Indian intelligence operatives in the Indian embassy in Kathmandu threatened a member of the Nepali Constituent Assembly to vote in a certain way else the provisional admission of his daughter in the embassy-run Kendriya Vidyalaya—a prestigious Indian High School in Kathmandu—would be revoked (Varadarajan 2010). India was also accused of paying Nepali leaders hefty sums as monthly allowances and providing them with a range of logistical and financial support (Bajgain 2017). Medical diplomacy was another tactic that India widely used. Under it, Nepali leaders facing various health issues would receive free treatment in India.¹⁴¹ In addition, since 2007, i.e., from the early days of the post-conflict transition, India has sponsored and trained senior Nepali government officials in several parts of India (EOI Kathmandu 2022). This also serves as a soft power tool for strengthening its influence in Nepal.

With these instruments in place, it is clear that India's interests in Nepal run deep. In the post-conflict transition, India was focused not only on policy and structural issues but was also heavily invested in setting up pliable people in important institutions. From changing senior police officers to selecting the national bank's governor and even deciding who would be appointed as Nepal's ambassador to India, its influence was felt in nearly every area.¹⁴² The Indian embassy in Kathmandu showed interest in appointments of government secretaries, the chief secretary, and even relatively junior positions, such as district-level Chief District Officers.¹⁴³ As a key informant put it:

Who should be appointed Vice-Chairperson of the National Planning Commission, or who should work as Kathmandu Valley Police Chief, who should run which ministry, and who should be at which section of the Ministry of Home Affairs. India's influence was extensive and everywhere.¹⁴⁴

Above all, India's top priority was forming and keeping a pliable government in Kathmandu. Whenever political coalitions were formed or dissolved in Nepal, India's involvement was inherent. For the most part, it seemed that forming a government in Kathmandu would be nearly impossible without a green signal from New Delhi. India ensured that political factions severed from New Delhi, those perceived as pro-China, or those hesitant to comply with India's wishes, were prevented from forming or maintaining a government or coalition. For instance, in

¹⁴¹ Interview with an expert key informant (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹⁴² Interview with a journalist (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹⁴³ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹⁴⁴ Interview with an expert key informant (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

March 2013, after the collapse of the first Constituent Assembly, the government led by Baburam Bhattarai was dissolved. An attempt was made to form a new government under the leadership of Nepali Congress Party leader Sushil Koirala. However, since India was reluctant to accept him as a Prime Minister, the new government was formed under the leadership of Chief Justice Khil Raj Regmi, a practice that had never been exercised in Nepal before.¹⁴⁵ Mr Koirala did not maintain special ties with India and was not considered to be an Indian asset. Nepal's interim constitution had no provision for forming a government under the Chief Justice's leadership under any circumstances.

Khadka Prasad Oli, who had boldly stood against India's 2015 economic blockade on Nepal, faced similar obstacles. Once considered India's close confidant, Mr Oli had later severed ties with New Delhi. India's discontent with him was reflected when he attempted to form a government on several occasions. A key informant, who was Mr Oli's colleague at that time, explained how India was active in preventing Mr Oli's ascension to power:

India played a role in preventing KP Oli from becoming Prime Minister. India played a role in removing him from the government. For this, various Indian agencies came forward. They worked underground but were visible from one side or the other.¹⁴⁶

During the years of political transition, New Delhi's role was crucial whenever a government was formed or collapsed in Kathmandu. Furthermore, whenever a political crisis or a stalemate gripped Nepal, agents of Indian intelligence agencies often flocked to Kathmandu and nested in five-star hotels, hatching and executing conspiracy ploys (see, for instance, Sharma 2013, Adhikari 2014, P. Jha 2014). This level of Indian involvement in post-conflict Nepal raises an obvious question: Why was the Nepali political leadership so submissive? Amid massive interference, did they make any attempts to challenge and break free from it?

Nepal's political parties and their leaders are certainly not immune to weaknesses, and they face serious domestic criticism for their 'incompetencies'. However, despite these shortcomings, they have occasionally challenged India's actions. I will discuss this partly in the upcoming section and partly in the next chapter. A careful analysis of Nepal's modern history shows that Nepali political actors attempted, on several occasions, to end India's interference and break free from Nepal's chronic and nearly exclusive dependency on India. However, the Nepali actors were relatively unsuccessful, as far as meddling and micromanagement in the post-conflict context were concerned.

India's meddling and micromanagement in the post-conflict context elevated and succeeded primarily due to three reasons. First, one of the main reasons was the weakness of the Nepali actors. There was a tendency for neither political leaders nor senior bureaucrats to 'anger' India.¹⁴⁷ For many, India was a necessary evil—a force too large to ignore and avoid altogether, but also useful at times. For some, India's favour meant high-profile political positions, lucrative jobs, donations, and all sorts of assistance for winning elections. Though Nepali politicians deny it, the benefits of receiving New Delhi's patronage are significant. In Shah's (2004: 211) words:

¹⁴⁵ Interview with a journalist (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹⁴⁶ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹⁴⁷ Interview with Bimal Gautam (12.08.2017).

The paradox of receiving Delhi's patronage is that while it invariably leads to power and privilege in Kathmandu, the tie itself is a great drain on moral legitimacy. That is why the Nepali elites and counter-elites continue to marshal much intellectual and political labour to deny, mystify and glorify their Indian connections, deploying the circular logic of cultural kinship, geographical proximity, and historical inevitability.

Ignoring India is not an option that many Nepali politicians can consider. Nepal's heavy dependence on India—from transit routes to development and budgetary assistance—means that running a government in Nepal without pleasing or at least satisfying India is extremely challenging.

Second, India's influence, up to the level of micromanagement, was facilitated by the power vacuum created by the monarchy's departure. When the monarchy was abolished, many traditional institutions and centres of power also fell apart. The process of creating new institutions and adapting them to a new political environment took considerable time. That fragile political transition, marked by post-conflict chaos and uncertainties, created an ideal environment for foreign manipulation. As a key informant put it:

India had a role in deciding who became a CDO [Chief District Officer] to who got the Prime Minister's post. They took advantage of our political transition and the lack of a unifying leader. We had multiple centres of power, which made it easier for them to meddle.¹⁴⁸

Third, India consistently used the responsibility narrative to justify and consolidate its actions in Nepal. Whenever challenged about its actions in Nepal, India justified its actions by claiming that it had played a positive role in initiating the peace process. India asserted that any critical decisions made afterwards should only occur after consulting with them. Moreover, if, for any reason, India was unable to influence decision-making processes in Nepal, it made sure that no other international actor got to do so.¹⁴⁹

6.4 The Shift from Micromanagement to Coercive Diplomacy

After years of meddling and micromanagement, India began to face resistance in Nepal. Among ordinary Nepalis, the anti-India sentiment started to become an established phenomenon. Nepali political actors faced immense public pressure as they were increasingly perceived as evolving into mere puppets of India. For Nepali politicians, particularly after the failure of the first Constituent Assembly, taking a public stance against India's micromanagement and defying New Delhi's orders became a matter of political survival. When faced with resistance, defiance, and avoidance of its mostly uninvited involvement, India also shifted its engagement strategy. From covert meddling and micromanagement, it adopted a more aggressive variant: coercive diplomacy. The transfer of power in India in 2014—from the Indian National Congress (INC) to the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP)—also impacted India's foreign policy choices. However, as far as India's Nepal strategy was concerned, it was moulded largely by the rapidly changing ground realities in Nepal.

The peace process and political transition in Nepal, which began in 2005–2006, made slow progress until 2015. However, a natural disaster that struck Nepal in

¹⁴⁸ Interview with an expert key informant (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹⁴⁹ Interview with a journalist (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

2015 drastically changed the country's political climate. In April and May 2015, two devastating earthquakes hit Nepal, killing more than 10,000 people. The tragedy and the loss left by the disaster engendered a sense of national unity in Nepal. Nepalis affected by the natural calamity began to pressure political parties, which have been drifting in a prolonged political transition, to come together, complete the peace process, address unfinished tasks of the transition, and provide the country with a new constitution.

Since the first Constituent Assembly was dissolved in May 2012 without drafting a constitution, people's dismay and frustration with political parties had already been mounting. The post-earthquake scenario demanded quick and concerted action from the major political parties. Moreover, in the wake of the devastating quakes, Nepal needed not just a new constitution, but also humanitarian relief and reconstruction work on a massive scale. Against this backdrop, it seemed that the only option available to Nepali political parties was unity and cooperation.

On 9 June 2015, less than a month after the second devastating quake, Nepal's four major political parties—Nepali Congress, CPN-UML, UCPN-Maoist, and Madheshi Janaadhikar Forum (Democratic)—reached a 16-Point Agreement and made a joint commitment to promulgate the long-awaited constitution. The 16-Point Agreement was made possible when the parties reached an agreement on the basic issues of the constitution and a framework for state restructuring. The parties also reached an informal agreement on how a new government would be formed and led, and how key political positions would be shared once the constitution was promulgated (Bhattarai 2015).

The four parties had shrewdly excluded India when they reached the 16-Point Agreement. Accustomed to choreographing every significant political move in Kathmandu, the 16-Point Agreement was a big blow to the Indian establishment. There were primarily two reasons behind this new development and the exclusion of India. First, in the wake of the devastating earthquake, when Nepal was still in ruins, the political parties were forced to reach a consensus, sort out pending issues, and begin the much-needed post-disaster reconstruction work. As I already mentioned, the political parties had no option but to unite and work together.

Second, there was a shared understanding among the main political parties that if the second Constituent Assembly also failed to promulgate a new constitution, Nepal would likely face another period of uncertainty and political stalemate. This meant that the dream of having a constitution written by the people's representatives might never come true. By the time the 16-Point Agreement was reached, the four political parties had been convinced that India's involvement in the process would overcomplicate the constitution-making process and that, as a result, the constitution might never be promulgated.¹⁵⁰ It was an open secret that India had heavily influenced the constitution-making process during the tenure of the first Constituent Assembly. When it realised that the overtly confident Maoists and the overall composition of the first CA were unfavourable for the agendas that it wanted to project, its hostility towards the CA increased. India's antagonism was one reason the first CA faced an abrupt dissolution.¹⁵¹

Nepal's main political parties that had more or less put up with India's meddling and micromanagement throughout the post-conflict period had been aware by 2015

¹⁵⁰ Several Nepali political leaders, including the Constituent Assembly Chairman Subhash Chandra Nembang, have said that they had decided to promulgate the constitution in September 2015 because missing that opportunity would have meant that the next chance would never come again (see Nembang 2017).

¹⁵¹ Interview with a journalist (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

that if a constitution was to be promulgated, it was essential to avoid consulting with India. They had been aware that India would not agree to a constitution without imposing its own terms and that if the second Constituent Assembly fell into confusion and stagnation like the first, the seven-decade-long aspiration of the Nepali people to promulgate a constitution through a people-elected assembly would be lost.

The exclusion of India during the 16-Point Agreement infuriated the Indian establishment. It quickly expressed its dissatisfaction by inviting former Prime Ministers Pushpa Kamal Dahal and Sher Bahadur Deuba to New Delhi. On 25 August 2015, Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi made a phone call to his Nepali counterpart, Sushil Koirala, and expressed his concerns over Nepal's constitution-making process (Roy 2015). Reportedly, the Indian Ministry of External Affairs and the Indian embassy in Kathmandu sought informal clarification from several senior leaders of the ruling parties about how the 16-Point Agreement was reached without India's knowledge (Bohara 2015a).

In the wake of the 16-Point Agreement, the constitution-making process gained momentum. Meanwhile, India, feeling neglected by Nepal's major political parties, intensified its lobbying efforts in both Kathmandu and New Delhi. The extensive lobbying was aimed at halting the constitution promulgation process. Even if the constitution was promulgated, India wanted to make sure that the new constitution addressed the issues of its interests. During this time, Indian ambassador to Nepal Ranjeet Rae 'did several trips between Kathmandu and New Delhi for consultation with his government on how to best engage with the Nepali leadership' (Roy 2015). By halting the constitution promulgation process, India wanted to break the unity between the major political parties and challenge the independence that the Nepali political actors had exercised through the 16-Point Agreement.

Three days before the scheduled constitutional promulgation date, on 17 September 2015, Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi sent a special envoy to Kathmandu. The envoy, Indian Foreign Secretary Subrahmanyam Jaishankar, had a clear goal: to prevent the draft constitution from being promulgated on the scheduled date. Mr Jaishankar, who was accompanied by the Indian Ambassador to Nepal, Ranjeet Rae, held talks with senior political leaders in Nepal and warned that neglecting India's advice would have severe consequences. A key informant, who closely followed Jaishankar's Kathmandu visit, recalled the mood of the Indian establishment:

Their mindset was that nothing could be achieved in Nepal without India's consent. The level of confidence that the Indian Prime Minister's envoy had was such that no matter how sovereign Nepal was, or no matter how sovereign Nepal's parliament or the Constituent Assembly were, if India requested something to be stopped, it would be stopped...even when it had already been passed by Nepal's parliament or the Constituent Assembly.¹⁵²

Regarding the constitution-making process, India's public stance was that all political stakeholders, including the Madhesh-based regional parties, should be taken aboard. While there was nothing sinister in having such a wish, ensuring a total consensus of all 601 CA members was practically impossible. Nearly 92% of the CA members were in favour of the drafted constitution, and only a small group of regional parties wanted to make further amendments. While the Nepali leadership was open to accommodating any genuine concerns that India had, the

¹⁵² Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

coercive approach that India took was not received well. As a key informant explained:

India, of course, could have told us about their concerns, but just before the constitution was being promulgated, the special envoy of the Indian prime minister came and asked to stop the entire process, and it was as if he was commanding us to do so.¹⁵³

Contrary to its official public stance of an inclusive constitution-making process, India had a list of changes it wanted to make in the draft constitution. It later emerged that India wanted seven amendments to be included in the draft constitution and had conveyed its message to the Nepali leadership through 'official channels' (Rawat 2015). The changes that India reportedly wanted were:

1) the crafting of electoral constituencies in proportion to the population 2) the right to participate in state structures on the basis of principles of proportional inclusion, 3) enabling citizens by descent or naturalisation to run for and hold all key political offices including President, Vice-President, and Prime Minister 4) representation in National Assembly to be based on population of the Provinces, 5) delineation of federal states, 6) delineation of electoral constituencies every 10 years, and 7) acquisition of naturalised citizenship to be automatic on application (Roy 2015).

In addition, India also consistently lobbied to remove secularism from the draft constitution and, through various channels, insisted that Nepal should keep its identity as a Hindu nation. Out of all these concerns, India's main preoccupation was with two issues. First, India wanted a maximum of two federal provinces in the plains bordering India, and those provinces would be run by autonomous governments.¹⁵⁴ In addition, India also wanted to make sure that the Madheshis and the population of Indian origin had greater representation in Nepali state organs and key political positions.¹⁵⁵ Interestingly, while India advocated for the inclusion of certain groups, it refrained from advocating an all-inclusive framework that would have ensured a fair representation of *dalits*, *janajits*, women and other marginalised groups. In contrast, its emphasis was on promoting representative democracy only for groups that had regional and cultural proximity to India.

India's 'order' to halt the constitution promulgation process was ignored, as the political parties were determined to continue with their previous plan. Subhash Nembang, the President of the Constituent Assembly, revealed in an interview that he had felt the effects of Nepali leaders' visit to India in the constitution-making process (see Nembang 2017). In addition, without disclosing the source, Nembang claimed that he had been asked to defer the constitution promulgation process and was promised the post of Nepal's President as a reward. When he had reportedly declined to stop the process, the undisclosed foreign source had threatened to retaliate by entangling him in false corruption charges. Ram Baran Yadav, who was Nepal's President at the time, also revealed later in an interview that some domestic and international forces had pressured him to halt the constitution-making process by declaring a state of emergency (see Yadav 2017). Mr Nembang and Mr Yadav did not specifically name India as the foreign force in question. However, there are good reasons to believe that the foreign force they were indicating was none other than India, given developments in Nepal during that period and the way India had been involved.

¹⁵³ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹⁵⁴ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹⁵⁵ Interview with an expert key informant (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

6.5 The Cost of a New Constitution: An Enraged India and an Economic Blockade

Despite India's pressure to halt the constitution promulgation process and reservations from some domestic groups, Nepal's Constituent Assembly promulgated the long-anticipated constitution on 20 September 2015. The new constitution was welcomed and celebrated in most parts of the country, even though it did not cause jubilation everywhere. Madhesh-based political parties and some ethnic minorities from the hills were unhappy because they argued that their grievances were inadequately addressed. Even bigger political parties and their leaders had their own reservations about various provisions of the constitution.

The constitution was not perfect and did not satisfy everyone, as it was ultimately a document of compromise. It emerged out of more than eight years of protracted negotiations and was promulgated as a 'good enough' document that would save Nepal from plunging into yet another episode of uncertainty and political chaos. A substantial majority of the Constituent Assembly (92%) voted in favour of the constitution, and though India had warned of bloodshed in the wake of the constitution's promulgation (N.K. Shrestha 2017a), no such incidents were reported in the country.

Nepal's development and strategic partners, such as the US, the UK, the EU, and China, swiftly welcomed the new constitution. India, however, was not pleased. India's Ministry of External Affairs released a statement saying that it had noted the promulgation of a constitution in Nepal and that it was concerned about the situation in several parts of the country (see MEA India 2015).

India not only refused to welcome the new constitution, but it also actively supported Madhesh-based groups, among others, that demanded a single province covering the entire plains of the Terai region, bordering India. Since the new constitution lacked such an arrangement, a group of Madhesh-based parties demanded an amendment to the constitution and began street protests. Interestingly, their protests were centred not in the capital city or any other major cities, but at some of the busiest transit checkpoints at the India–Nepal border (Ojha 2015). Kathmandu quickly interpreted that the protests were devised under New Delhi's guidance and that Madhesh-based parties had become victims of India's plan to punish the Nepali government and major political parties, for they had defied New Delhi's orders.

When most of Nepal was still celebrating the new constitution, the enraged Indian establishment, citing security concerns, halted the transit passage to Nepal. In practice, this meant that the supply of fuel and other necessary items to Nepal was completely stopped. Even though India accused the border protests as the real trigger behind its decision, Nepali authorities clearly understood that it was yet another economic blockade imposed by India.

The 5-month-long blockade crippled Nepal's economy and paralysed the everyday lives of millions of Nepalis. Being a landlocked country, Nepal heavily depends on India for sea passage and almost all its imports. Instead of providing Nepal unconditional access to international transit points as per international law, India has repeatedly used border and transit issues as political and strategic weapons to put pressure on Nepal. India's 'blockade tactic', thus, is an old one. It

resorted to the same tactic in the past on different pretexts in 1970 and 1989–90, respectively.¹⁵⁶

While previous economic blockades had been tragic, the 2015 blockade was particularly devastating and took a heavy toll on Nepal. Nepal was hit by a massive earthquake in April and May of the same year, and India's blockade not only hampered imports of fuel and consumer goods but also severely compromised the transport of essential medicines and earthquake relief material. Since almost all petroleum products enter Nepal through India, the blockade entirely paralysed vehicular movement and the public transportation system in Nepal, leading to an economic and humanitarian crisis in the country.

Moreover, India largely remained apathetic to an unfolding humanitarian crisis in its neighbourhood and showed no interest in loosening the blockade or controlling the protests at border checkpoints. Months earlier, when Nepal was struck by two devastating earthquakes, India had displayed a completely different face. Its logistical support and involvement in post-quake relief and rescue operations in Nepal were phenomenal. A few months later, however, when Nepal was reluctant to incorporate its 'issues' into the country's new constitution, India not only remained indifferent to an escalating humanitarian crisis, but it helped orchestrate it.

Despite increasing domestic and international criticism, along with mounting evidence suggesting the involvement of the Indian establishment in orchestrating the blockade, India consistently maintained in public and official statements that the closure of transit points was a result of protests by Madhesh-based parties in the border regions. However, there are at least four reasons that show the insincerity inherent in India's official statements and denial of its involvement in the economic blockade. First, this was not the first economic blockade India had used to put pressure on Nepal. As already mentioned, India used the same strategy in 1970 and 1989–90. On both occasions, India had been successful in getting the outcomes it had desired.¹⁵⁷ So, the Indian establishment understood that since Nepal was almost entirely dependent on India for sea passage, economic blockades worked well to put pressure on Nepal. In the past, India used economic blockades as a last resort, and it did the same in 2015. Thus, despite India's denial, it was apparent that the 2015 blockade was merely a new version of India's old 'blockade' strategy.

Second, how the Nepal blockade was discussed in India's political, media, and civil society circles also showed that the blockade was not a logistical issue caused by protests at border checkpoints. Rather, it was a foreign policy tool designed and implemented by the Indian establishment. Discussions in India's parliament and the response of External Affairs Minister Sushma Swaraj to Indian MPs further indicated that India was behind the blockade plan.¹⁵⁸ In addition, the Modi government was criticised within India for using a heinous strategy, such as an economic blockade, with supposedly the closest neighbour of India. Especially in the later months, many Indian journalists and civil society activists actively wrote and campaigned against the blockade, and there was a common understanding

¹⁵⁶ For a brief overview of the impact that India's previous economic blockades had on Nepal, see, for instance, Crossette (1989) and Shrestha (2015).

¹⁵⁷ In 1970, Nepal was largely an agrarian and self-sufficient economy, and the blockade's impact was minimal. The blockade ended on 13 August 1971 after Nepal and India signed a trade and transit protocol. In 1989, India used the blockade as a political tool to exhaust the Panchayat regime. The blockade was lifted once the Panchayat system was abolished.

¹⁵⁸ Interview with Beduram Bhusal (14.07.2017).

developing inside India that the blockade symbolised India's ugly neighbourhood diplomacy (Menon 2021). Gradually, Indian politicians also began to accept that the blockade was a policy mishap and that India should be ready for course correction (Adhikari & Bhattarai 2017).

Third, India kept blaming the Madheshi protesters for the blockade, but these protests were relatively small and concentrated only around a handful of border points. India and Nepal share a 1,751-kilometre-long border and have dozens of transit points and many border crossings. While the Madheshi protesters were focused mostly on Birgunj and other major border entry points, there were other transit points with no obstacle whatsoever. Had India wanted to ensure Nepal's right to sea passage, it could have easily done so by opening those points. However, it was reluctant to do so. Dip Kumar Upadhyay, Nepal's ambassador to India at the time, shared his frustration in a media interview over India's double standards during the blockade:

India did not accept that there was a blockade, but people were suffering. India kept saying that it was not behind the blockade and that the problem in the border areas was caused by our own Madheshi people. Okay, there were protests in Birgunj, but why weren't goods coming from the Bhairahawa checkpoint? India would not provide answers to such questions. At that time, I felt like I was fighting alone. People were angry at me on social media. It was not uncommon for the aggrieved masses to be so outraged. I was in an early stage of diplomacy. What happens in diplomacy—which I later learnt—is that no matter how bitter the relationship, you use sweet words. India did not tell us it was going to impose an economic blockade, but it kept giving us pain and suffering (Upadhyay 2018).

Fourth, India lifted the blockade after five months when it finally realised that the blockade strategy had backfired this time. In the two earlier blockades, India had successfully pressured Nepali rulers to concede and had attained favourable results. This time, India encountered strong opposition from the Nepali people, faced criticism at home, and was on the brink of international condemnation.¹⁵⁹ As Devendra Raj Pandey explained, India's assumption must have been that if the blockade lasted for a week or two, ordinary Nepalis would come to the streets to oppose the government and that Kathmandu would ultimately surrender before New Delhi. But that is not what happened.¹⁶⁰ People did come to the streets, but the protests were targeted not against the Nepali government, but against the blockade and India (see Picture 3). When India finally decided to lift the blockade, the border passage was immediately opened, even though the Madheshi protesters had not called off the strike. This also clearly shows that the blockade was a coercive political instrument designed to weaken the 'unruly' Nepali political forces.

The Madheshi political parties had the constitutional right to protest and demand an amendment to the newly promulgated constitution so that it became fair and inclusive for every minority group in the country. However, their overt reliance on India proved to be counterproductive, as they were first used and then shunned by India, as mere political pawns.¹⁶¹ In private conversations, senior Madheshi leaders often vented their frustration that they had been badly used by India.¹⁶²

¹⁵⁹ Interview with Bimal Gautam (12.08.2017).

¹⁶⁰ Interview with Devendra Raj Pandey (02.08.2017).

¹⁶¹ Interview with two journalists (interview year 2017, names and interview dates redacted).

¹⁶² Interview with Sudheer Sharma (02.08.2017).

Picture 3: Nepali Protesters Demonstrating Against the Indian Economic Blockade in Front of the Indian Embassy, Kathmandu, October 2015. Photo Credit: Gopen Rai

There were several reasons why India became impatient during the fifth month of the blockade and ultimately lifted it. I have already explained some of these reasons. There was yet another issue that had particularly bothered India, and it was Nepal's growing proximity to China. As Nepal was dealing with severe shortages of fuel, essential goods and medicines, China responded with assistance packages. Among others, China supplied 1.3 million litres of petrol to Nepal (Tiezzi 2015). It was largely a symbolic move, but useful in mitigating the dire fuel shortage caused by the blockade.

Furthermore, as the blockade continued, Chinese and Nepali officials started drafting a transit and transportation agreement between the two countries. First of this kind, the Agreement would end Nepal's sole dependence on India for international trade. Even though Nepal endured the effects of India's economic blockades in the past, there had been no serious attempt to find an alternative trade route through the northern border, i.e., through China. This was mainly because no Nepali government had been audacious enough to challenge Nepal's perpetual dependency on India as far as international trade and transit were concerned. In addition, the Indian establishment had always been active in thwarting a close relationship between China and Nepal, a strategy designed to keep Nepal dependent on India and within its sphere of influence.

In 2015, the Nepali government, the major political parties of Nepal, and most of the Nepali people united to oppose the economic blockade. As Bishnu Poudel put it:

Nepal faced three economic blockades imposed by India, in 1970, in 1989–90 and in 2015. We were unable to stand properly in the 1970 blockade; we were unable to stand properly

in the 1989–90 blockade, but in 2015, it was different. We stood firm against it, and India backed off.¹⁶³

Factors such as Nepal's growing proximity to China and the domestic pressure that the Indian establishment faced within India were important in lifting the blockade, but the resilience and unity that the Nepali people demonstrated were equally crucial.

6.6 From Coercion to Cornering: India's Attempt to Vilify and Isolate Nepal in International Forums

As I previously explained, India's attempt to stop the constitution promulgation process in Nepal was overlooked by the country's major political parties, and the constitution was promulgated on the scheduled date. The new constitution was warmly welcomed by most of Nepal's international allies, but an infuriated India ended up imposing an economic blockade on Nepal. The undeclared economic blockade disrupted the everyday lives of millions of Nepalis and paralysed Nepal's economy. As Nepalis stood united against the blockade, and when Nepal began strengthening its trade ties with China, India played yet another card at its disposal: ostracising and isolating Nepal at international forums. Some scholars have also termed this practice as 'international advocacy and coalition building' against Nepal (see, for instance, Bhattacharjee 2018). This was an unusual step from India because any bilateral issues between the two countries had rarely been internationalised in such a manner before.

Before it decided to end the economic blockade, India actively used international forums to denounce Nepal's new constitution and the process through which it had been promulgated. In an attempt to exert international pressure and isolate what it likely viewed as an 'unruly' neighbour, India essentially conducted a smear campaign against Nepal and its major political forces. For instance, amidst India's economic blockade, in November 2015, at the UN Human Rights Council's Session of the Universal Period Review in Geneva, the Indian delegation raised the issue of the constitution and how it was promulgated despite some groups' reservations. Nepal's Foreign Minister, Kamal Thapa, responded to the Indian delegation, saying that Nepal had every right to promulgate its constitution on its own and that restricting the supply of goods from the border was unacceptable (TKP 2015). Minister Thapa also made it clear that the Nepal government was aware of some factions' dissatisfaction over the constitution and that Nepal possessed the capacity to solve its internal issues itself. Furthermore, he emphasised that the new constitution was drafted and promulgated in a fully democratic manner (see TKP 2015).

A week after the Geneva incident, during Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi's visit to the UK, India and the UK issued a joint press statement where concern for Nepal's constitutional settlement was raised (Myrepublica 2015). Since the UK had already welcomed Nepal's new constitution, the new twist had developed after India had been successful in persuading the UK to include the Nepal issue in the joint press statement. A similar joint press statement was issued by India and the EU on 30 March 2016 in the wake of the 13th EU–India Summit.¹⁶⁴

¹⁶³ Interview with Bishnu Poudel (13.07.2017).

¹⁶⁴ See, Joint Statement 13 EU–India Summit.

India attempted to do the same during Narendra Modi's visits to the United States and Japan.¹⁶⁵

Nepal's Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MOFA) issued counterstatements to challenge these claims. Through MOFA statements, Nepal argued that constitution-making was Nepal's internal issue and that Nepal was fully capable of handling its internal affairs on its own. Responding to the EU-India joint press statement, MOFA Nepal requested India and the EU to 'fully respect the sovereign and democratic rights of the people of Nepal and refrain from making uncalled-for statements' (Myrepublica 2016).

As close neighbours, bashing each other in international forums was something unusual for both India and Nepal. Nepal endured the impact of three economic blockades imposed by India, yet it chose not to internationalise the issue. Whenever there were issues between Nepal and India, solutions were often found in dialogue and compromises between the two nations, though this usually required Nepali leaders to make concessions to India. However, in 2015, when Nepal's political forces rejected India's recommendations for the new constitution, India quickly opted to internationalise the issue.

In this case, the China factor also played a role. India's paranoia was fuelled by its belief that it was losing its traditional control over Nepal and that China was increasingly influencing Nepali politics. While the proximity between China and Nepal increased during the Indian blockade, and senior Nepali political leaders visited China frequently, there were no credible signs that China was interfering in Nepal's internal politics or that it had any demands regarding the new constitution.

While India attempted to put pressure on Nepal by internationalising the constitution issue, Nepal has historically remained neutral and silent on the internal issues of both India and China. For instance, in 1983, when the Gurkha Land movement¹⁶⁶ was at its peak in India, its leader, Subhash Ghisingh, came to Kathmandu seeking support. Even though the movement aimed to establish a separate provincial state within India for Nepali-speaking Gorkha people, Nepal refused any kind of support for it. Afraid of India, senior Nepali leaders did not even meet Mr Ghisingh.¹⁶⁷

For years, both India and China have been facing significant issues related to human rights violations. Among others, China has been accused of repressing the Uyghur ethnic minorities as well as those associated with the Free Tibet Movement. Similarly, human rights violations in the Indian states of Kashmir and Manipur, and the treatment of minorities in BJP-ruled India, are issues that have raised international concern and condemnation. However, Nepal has preferred to remain silent on such issues.

After the democratic movement of 1990, notwithstanding a short stint of King Gyanendra's direct rule, Nepal has attempted to build its image as a democratic country where issues of human rights, the rule of law, press freedom, and protection of minorities have been cherished and gradually institutionalised. Nepal has been vocal in international forums against human rights violations in other parts of the world. However, when it comes to speaking against similar issues in its neighbourhood, Nepal has continuously chosen to remain silent. While regional powers such as India and China are quick to assert their take on any issue in the

¹⁶⁵ Interview with Sudheer Sharma (02.08.2017).

¹⁶⁶ The Gorkhaland movement is a campaign to create a separate province in India, in the Gorkhaland region of West Bengal, for the Nepali-speaking Gorkha people.

¹⁶⁷ Interview with Mumaram Khanal (24.07.2017).

region, small countries such as Nepal are forced to remain silent just because they cannot afford to ‘anger’ their powerful neighbours.

However, India’s international advocacy and coalition-building against Nepal’s new constitution had little impact. There were press statements that called on Nepal to revise its constitutional course. However, soon, the international community also realised that the economic blockade was unjust and inhumane, and that India was a perpetrator in the plot.

6.7 India’s Direct Development Grants: A Device for Deepening Dependency

In previous sections, I discussed how India used strategies such as micromanagement, power diplomacy, and coercive foreign policy to expand its influence in Nepal. These strategies reflect only a part of the full picture. Whenever necessary, India has resorted to an extensive use of soft power as well. So, the influence has been expanded not only through coercion but also through seemingly benign means, such as humanitarian relief, grants, loans, and development assistance programmes.

When Nepal was hit by two devastating earthquakes in 2015, India was one of the first countries to reach Nepal with a rescue and relief package. India’s extensive humanitarian relief work, which was termed *Operation Maitri*, had at least two strings attached to it: to counter China’s disaster diplomacy and, by doing so, increase its own influence in Nepal (Chand 2017).

Besides humanitarian relief operations, India continues to be one of Nepal’s largest bilateral donors. For decades, Indian assistance to Nepal has poured in all shapes and sizes, including grants, loans, logistical support, and the transfer of technical knowledge. After the 2015 earthquakes, the total relief assistance that India provided was estimated to be over USD 67 million (EOI Kathmandu 2020). In its 2019–20 budget, India allocated INR 1200 crore (approx. 147 million EUR) as ‘aid to Nepal’. India also loaned over USD 1.65 billion for infrastructure and post-earthquake reconstruction projects (EOI Kathmandu 2020). In addition, India provided financial and logistical support to activities that facilitated Nepal’s political transformation. For instance, it provided more than 1,300 vehicles, voting machines, and other equipment during Nepal’s first and second Constituent Assembly elections (Sarwar & Malik 2018: 81).

India’s continuous assistance has significantly shaped Nepal’s social and economic development. The Indian establishment is aware of the importance of India’s assistance to Nepal and its chronic and perpetual dependency on Indian aid. There are clear indications that Nepal’s ongoing dependency on Indian aid has intensified the unequal relationship between the two countries. Particularly in the post-conflict context, India used development aid and other assistance programmes to further its influence in Nepal. One such example is the Small Development Projects (SDP), which India runs through its embassy in Kathmandu.

In 2003, when Nepal was overwhelmed by the Maoist armed insurgency and nearly on the brink of becoming a failed state, India successfully convinced the Nepali government to sign an agreement granting India unrestricted access to design and implement development projects in Nepal. The SDP programme initially allowed India to run individual development projects of up to 30 million Nepali Rupees.¹⁶⁸ In August 2008, amidst India’s extensive involvement in post-

¹⁶⁸ Approx. 2,10,000 Euros as of November 2024.

conflict Nepal, the SDP was renewed, and the spending limit was increased to 50 million Nepali Rupees¹⁶⁹ per project. In 2017, when Nepal was reluctant to renew the SDP agreement, arguing that the programme's structure did not align well with Nepal's new federal system and that there were no sufficient legal provisions for accepting such programmes, Indian officials reportedly pressured Nepal (Onlinekhabar 2017).

Under the SDP scheme, India designed and implemented more than 500 infrastructure and community development projects in various parts of Nepal within just over a decade. These projects included building schools, health centres, rural roads, community centres, and libraries. Under the SDP umbrella, India also funded several cultural, religious, and capacity-building training programmes. The SDP projects have been implemented in all of Nepal's 77 districts, and India has spent billions of rupees on them (see EOI Kathmandu 2022).

While India's assistance in development and infrastructure projects has been helpful in certain areas, it has had political implications. The way SDP projects are implemented, as well as India's continuous lobbying and insistence on renewing the programme, has created both suspicion and controversy. First, since the SDP projects are selected by the Indian embassy, Nepali officials have virtually no influence over the projects that are selected. This has created a situation in which Nepali politicians have to visit the Indian embassy and request that development projects be directed at their constituencies. Second, the SDP projects are not reflected in Nepal's budgetary system and do not necessarily align with the country's development plans, needs, and priorities. As a result, the SDP programmes contribute little to the development path that Nepal aims to pursue.

Third, since the SDP projects require no separate approval from Nepali officials, the Indian embassy is free to choose programmes according to its own strategic interests. As a result, SDP projects are often used to influence Nepali politicians and achieve specific political goals. The level of freedom that India has in the SDP is so extensive that, according to a former Nepali foreign minister, it has 'put a question mark over Nepal's national sovereignty' (N.K. Shrestha 2017b).

Despite ongoing controversies and Nepal's efforts to discontinue or regulate it, the SDP continues in the country. Although the programme started in the final years of the armed conflict, it expanded rapidly in the post-conflict context. As already mentioned, India has funded hundreds of programmes under the SDP and continues to do so. As a result, the Indian embassy in Kathmandu has seemed less like a diplomatic mission and more like a foreign strategic powerhouse, where Nepali politicians line up to request development projects. This way, the SDP has deepened Nepal's dependency on India, and India has effectively used it as a tool for expanding its influence in Nepal.

6.8 Religion to the Rescue: Hatching Hindutva in Nepal

As I have mentioned throughout this thesis, the post-conflict political transition in Nepal was prolonged for years, and India's various conflicting interests in Nepal contributed to exacerbating the situation. When the 12-Point Understanding was signed, the Indian National Congress (INC) party was in power in India. As the INC had built its image as a liberal and secular political force in India, it had no objection that, through the political mandate of *Jana Andolan II*, Nepal, too, was creating a similar secular image for itself. When the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) came to

¹⁶⁹ approx. 3,51,000 Euros as of November 2024.

power in India in 2014, there was a shift in the mood of the Indian establishment. The BJP-run government became increasingly influenced by a Hindutva ideology and was shaped by strong Hindu nationalist undertones.

Senior BJP politicians, such as Rajnath Singh, who led the BJP twice from 2005 to 2009 and from 2013 to 2014, had already become vocal since the early 2000s that Nepal should keep its identity as a Hindu nation (Outlook India 2006). This unsolicited advice did not reflect the aspirations of most Nepali people. It also did not align with the growing political consciousness sweeping across Nepal. Whether in opposition or in government, BJP leaders consistently maintained their unofficial yet firm stance that Nepal should avoid becoming a secular state. A key informant, who had accompanied Nepal's then Prime Minister and NCP President, G.P. Koirala, during one of his visits to India, recalled how the BJP leadership was concerned about the secular road that the Nepali leadership had taken:

I was with Girijababu [i.e., G.P. Koirala] when he met BJP leader Rajnath Singh. Rajnath raised the Hindu nation issue. His dissatisfaction was that we had adopted secularism in the [2007] Interim Constitution.¹⁷⁰

While the BJP leadership was committed to their vision of a Hindu Nepal, their influence in Nepal was limited because their party was in opposition in India until 2014. When the peace process and political transition began in Nepal, the Indian National Congress (INC) was in power in India. The INC-led government had its own interests in Nepal, but whether Nepal kept or ditched Hinduism as a state religion was not a priority. The INC, as a political party, has established a secular and relatively liberal image in India. By supporting the 12-Point roadmap, it can be argued that the INC-led Indian government effectively approved and endorsed secularism in Nepal.

The BJP's own rise was closely tied to its pro-Hindu ideology. The party achieved a remarkable victory in the 2014 Indian general elections in the lower house of India's Parliament, the Lok Sabha. It emerged victorious in 228 out of 563 seats and received 31.34% of the total votes (Election Commission of India 2015). This was the most significant election success the BJP had achieved since its founding in 1980. Two factors had been crucial for this unprecedented feat. First, the party presented Narendra Modi as the future Prime Minister. Though controversial for his attitude towards minorities, Mr Modi was widely seen as a visionary and successful Chief Minister of Gujarat. Mr Modi spent more than 12 years, from 2001 to 2014, as Gujarat's Chief Minister and was often portrayed as a pro-development leader. By initiating massive infrastructure and development projects, he received credit for transforming the impoverished state of Gujarat. By the time the BJP presented him as the Prime Minister candidate, he was already a widely popular figure in India.

Second, Mr Modi was not the sole factor that contributed to the BJP's massive success in the 2014 election. In addition to Mr Modi's charisma and a carefully crafted image of a pro-development visionary, the BJP also relied heavily on the party's rebranded Hindu nationalist image. The BJP leaders' proximity to Hindu right-wing extremist organisations such as Rastriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS) was no longer a secret. Hindutva—a political ideology rooted in Hindu nationalism and conservatism that aims to establish India as a Hindu state—became the de facto political ideology that the BJP sought to advance.

¹⁷⁰ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

The rise of the BJP in India naturally had an impact on Nepal. As Nepal prepared to promulgate a new constitution in 2015, the BJP-led government in India pressured Nepali politicians to reinstate Nepal's constitutional identity as a Hindu nation. By reinstating Nepal as a Hindu nation, the BJP also sought to plant the seeds of the Hindutva ideology in Nepal.

India's desire to preserve Nepal's Hindu identity was evident, especially during the final months of the constitution-making process in Nepal. In autumn 2015, when Nepal's Constituent Assembly started finalising the new constitution, senior leaders of Nepal's three major political parties were invited to India. It is now clear from multiple sources that the leaders were made aware of the BJP-led India's concern about Nepal's new constitution. One of the wishes of the Modi government was that Nepal would reinstate its identity as a Hindu nation, a provision abrogated in the 2007 Interim Constitution. In response, the leaders had reportedly assured India that the policy of secularism adopted in the 2007 Interim Constitution would be replaced, at least by an alternative term that would indicate Nepal to be a non-secular Hindu nation.¹⁷¹

Saying no to India is something that many Nepali leaders are unaccustomed to. That was probably the reason the Nepali leaders felt compelled to make a false promise to India. The leaders were aware that the political realities at home were unfavourable for such a regressive move. Reinstating Nepal's Hindu identity would contradict the mandate of *Jana Andolan II* and the Maoist armed struggle. It would also disrupt the progressive political climate of post-conflict Nepal. In addition, arguing for a Hindu nation would also mean advocating indirectly for the revival of the abolished monarchy (A. Wagle 2016).

In India, some leaders of the ruling BJP party actively and openly campaigned against a secular Nepal. Mahant Adityanath, an Indian MP and BJP leader, wrote a letter to Nepal's Prime Minister Sushil Koirala and demanded that Nepal reinstate its Hindu identity. Mr Adityanath also delivered speeches at events and rallies that sought to further similar religious agendas (Srivastava 2015). Reportedly, there were also covert Indian delegations that attempted to persuade Nepali leaders to reinstate Nepal's Hindu identity. Recent claims also suggest that financial assistance from India has been contributing to the protests and mobilisation in Nepal that are calling for a Hindu and monarchical state (see Ramachandran 2024).

On 20 September 2015, Nepal's Constituent Assembly promulgated the new constitution. Contrary to India's wishes, the new constitution ditched the Hindu-nation agenda and adopted secularism. However, in an attempt to appease New Delhi and some dissatisfied groups at home, an additional clarification on secularism was added. It was said that, in Nepal's context, secular meant 'religious, cultural freedoms, including protection of religion, culture handed down from time immemorial' (Constitution of Nepal 2015: 8).

This obscure clarification was not enough for India. Reinstating Nepal's identity as a Hindu nation had gradually turned into a matter of prestige for the BJP-led government. The Hindu nation agenda did not emanate entirely from the BJP's love for Hindutva. By making Nepal a Hindu nation, the BJP-led government aimed to demonstrate its ability to manipulate and control political affairs in its immediate neighbourhood and show that countries like Nepal remained within its sphere of influence. In other words, this was an opportunity for the Modi government to

¹⁷¹ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted). See also, Bhattarai (2017), Nembang (2017), Shrestha N.K. (2017a), Verma (2017).

challenge the growing narrative that India was losing its influence in South Asia to China.

In New Delhi, Nepal's decision to adopt secularism was perceived as a sign of disobedience. A few days after the 'secular' constitution was promulgated in Nepal, India responded by imposing an economic blockade, which I have already discussed in detail. While secularism was not the only issue behind India's displeasure, it was arguably one of the most significant. Baburam Bhattarai, a senior Maoist leader who was Nepal's Prime Minister during the first Constituent Assembly, asserted in an article published on *Lokaantar*, a Nepali-language news portal:

There is no unanimous understanding of why India acted the way it did. Some think that India's emphasis was on federalism, but my understanding is different. The main interest of the Indian leadership was not in federalism or republicanism in Nepal, but in keeping Nepal a Hindu nation (Bhattarai 2017).

At a time when the BJP, a party that had gained power through Hindu nationalism, was in office in India, Nepal chose to abandon its Hindu identity and became a secular state. In the view of the BJP-led Indian administration, this could have been the perfect opportunity for Nepal to reclaim its Hindu identity and promote the Hindutva agenda. However, dismissing the Hindu nation agenda was not a decision made to upset the BJP-led India. Nor was it a plot devised by China or Western Christian missionaries, as is often claimed by its critics. Secularism was a longstanding political demand in Nepal for many decades. The CPN (UML), one of the biggest political parties in Nepal, had already demanded secularism to be ensured in the country's 1990 constitution. Similarly, when the Maoists launched their armed insurgency in 1994, one of their demands was for Nepal to abandon its Hindu identity and adopt secularism.¹⁷²

For over two centuries, the Shah Kings used Hinduism to strengthen their hold on power and justify their hereditary rule. When the Shah dynasty ruled Nepal, they often relied on anecdotes and narratives that presented them as reincarnations or representatives of Hindu gods or that they were ordained by higher powers to rule. However, three major political events, 1. The democratic movement of 1990, 2. The Maoist armed struggle (1994–2006), and 3. The royal massacre of 2001 altered the fate of both the monarchy and Nepal's identity as a Hindu nation.

With the end of the monarchy in 2008, the political influence that Hinduism had over Nepal's state affairs was further weakened. The Maoists, who promoted the Marxist notion that religion is the opium of the people, emerged as a powerful political force. As the country's political climate began to change, the CPN (UML), a moderate communist party, also began branding itself as a strong supporter of secularism. Ideas of republicanism and secularism also received strong support within the Nepali Congress Party, a relatively conservative force that had historically been a bulwark of both the monarchy and Nepal's Hindu identity.

Against this backdrop, for Nepal's major political parties, declaring Nepal a Hindu nation in 2015 would have been a vastly regressive move. Secularism was already adopted in the country's 2007 Interim Constitution, and backtracking to the Hindu identity was a politically tricky task, if not an impossible one. Moreover, the monarchy that fostered the idea of a Hindu Kingdom for its own survival had already been abolished. In the aftermath of a decade-long armed insurgency, the increased political awareness of ordinary Nepalis sought a new Nepal with at least some degree of ideological, political, and cultural transformation. All these

¹⁷² See Appendix 5, demand no. 18 of the Maoists' 40-point demand.

aspirations would not fit well with the agenda of a Hindu nation. In addition, unlike in India, the concept of Hindutva has not flourished in Nepal, and Hindu nationalist and ultra-nationalist groups, such as the RSS in India, have never garnered much public support in Nepal. As Sharma (2017) put it:

Nepal is a Hindu-majority nation, and so is India. However, there is Hindutva in India, and not in Nepal. Since Hindutva is a political concept, it implies that the Hindu religion should have a role in dictating state affairs.

Even though Nepal's major political parties successfully enshrined secularism in the country's 2015 constitution, the road ahead has been challenging. Riding high on Hindutva, the BJP remains in power in India, and its prominent leaders and sister organisations continue to campaign, mostly covertly, for a Hindu Nepal. Some leaders of the BJP or its parent organisation, the RSS, still believe that even though India is a secular country, Nepal should reinstate its identity as a Hindu state and become a role model to religious campaigns aspiring to attain similar goals. Some Indian pro-Hindutva activists advocate that, after declaring itself a Hindu nation, Nepal should restore the overthrown monarchy.¹⁷³ Moreover, India has been accused of intensifying its Hindu-nation lobbying and secretly funding pro-Hindu campaigns and demonstrations in Nepal in recent years (see Ramachandran 2024).

Under the BJP leadership, India itself suffers from the radical Hindutva ideology. In India, numerous groups continue to campaign to make the country a Hindu nation. Similarly, under the BJP rule and with a shrinking inclusive space, the hardships faced by minorities and non-Hindu religious groups have significantly increased in recent years (see, for instance, Komireddi 2019, Jaffrelot 2021). The Hindutva fixation of the BJP has fuelled hatred and intolerance in India and its neighbouring countries. As a result, the world's largest democracy now increasingly resembles an authoritarian regime, and it permeates the entire South Asian region with an atmosphere of systemic oppression and pervasive intolerance.

Secularism in Nepal has been systematically attacked by domestic conservative and pro-monarchy groups, with support from Indian Hindutva organisations. Although Nepal is constitutionally a secular country, there is a risk that this provision could be flipped at any moment in the future. The protagonists of post-2006 Nepal, along with advocates of secularism and inclusivity, continue their fight for a truly secular Nepal.

6.9 Hard Power, Soft Power, and India's Nepal Policy Mishap

Notions of hard power and soft power are based on neo-realist and liberal institutional theories of international relations. Foreign policy approaches such as coercive diplomacy, economic sanctions, and military interventions are usually considered to be hard power strategies (see, for instance, Keohane & Nye 1989). In contrast, soft power strategies are more subtle and less confrontational. These might include economic cooperation, promotion of common political values, conflict management, diplomacy (Kurlantzick 2007), philanthropy (Jenkins 2007), the use of information (Armistead 2004), and even elements such as rhetoric, persuasion, and agenda setting (Rothman 2011: 50). Furthermore, Nye (2009: 162) lists public diplomacy, broadcasting, exchange programmes, development

¹⁷³ Interview with Sudheer Sharma (02.08.2017).

assistance, disaster relief, and military-to-military contacts as soft power instruments.

It is common to view hard and soft power as two opposite ends of a continuum. In foreign policy practice, this dichotomy is rarely visible. As Rothman (2011: 60) argues, 'rather than defining power based on the two types of power typology, different forms of power maintain places on a continuum from the softest forms of attraction to the hardest form of physical control over another'. Similarly, there is a growing realisation that contemporary foreign policy strategies employ a mix of both hard and soft power instruments—a practice that Nye (2009, 2013) has termed a 'smart power' strategy. The practice of using all available tools, whether hard or soft, is becoming more common due to 'long-term structural changes in international conditions' (Wilson III 2008: 110). There is also a growing realisation among key international players that combining both strategies is more effective and efficient in pursuing and advancing their foreign policy agendas (Wilson III 2008).

In its post-conflict engagement in Nepal, India employed both hard power and soft power, which, for simplicity, can be referred to as smart power. Though India has always exerted a degree of influence in Nepal, the extent and intensity of this influence have fluctuated over time. As this thesis has documented, India's engagement in post-conflict Nepal represents a period of extensive involvement in its southern neighbour. While some of India's actions could be categorically labelled as either soft power or hard power, there were also many grey areas. For instance, the 2015 economic blockade and the Indian Foreign Secretary's aggressive power diplomacy before Nepal's constitution was promulgated are clear examples of India's use of hard power. Whereas micromanagement, which was primarily India's *modus operandi* in post-conflict Nepal, had ingredients of both hard and soft powers. Micromanagement as a practice heavily relied on both direct and indirect threats, meddling, manipulation, and financial incentives. However, seemingly softer strategies, such as direct development grants, were also part of it.

The use of pure soft power was also common. India's massive humanitarian assistance following the 2015 earthquakes, its involvement in cultural and community development initiatives, and its annual scholarships for hundreds of Nepali students are notable examples of India's soft power in Nepal.

Agenda setting has often been argued as an instrument of soft power (Rothman 2011). Nye (2009: 160), for instance, argued that 'hard power is the use of coercion and payment. Soft power is the ability to obtain preferred outcomes through attraction. If a state can set the agenda for others or shape their preferences, it can save a lot.'

As India began its engagement in post-conflict Nepal, one of its priorities was, indeed, agenda-setting. When *Jana Andolan II* was at its peak, it could be sensed that the monarchy's future was at stake in Nepal. In response, India sent a special envoy to Kathmandu, who extensively lobbied in favour of the monarchy. Although it is unclear who originated the idea, India supported the concept of a baby king and lobbied relentlessly to persuade Nepal's major political parties to accept it. India's interest in agenda-setting was evident when it sought specific provisions in Nepal's 2015 constitution, as well as previously in the 2007 interim constitution and the 2006 Comprehensive Peace Accord. When the Hindu-nationalist BJP came to power in India in 2014, restoring Nepal as a Hindu nation became another agenda for India in Nepal.

These agenda-setting episodes did not depend solely on soft power instruments. For instance, to compel Nepal to include certain provisions in the country's 2015

constitution, India imposed an economic blockade. The Indian embassy in Kathmandu and Indian diplomats visiting Nepal, typically as special envoys, often employed subtle carrot-and-stick tactics. Some even resorted to threatening and intimidating Nepali politicians (see, for instance, N.K. Shrestha 2017a). Actions like these certainly do not represent a foreign policy regimen based on soft power instruments. One takeaway from this is that India's focus in Nepal was on the ends rather than the means. If India saw certain instruments as being helpful in achieving certain foreign policy goals or for serving its self-interests, it was rarely hesitant to use them.

Then, there is an obvious follow-up question: Was India's cocktail power policy (or the so-called smart power) a success in Nepal? Overall, India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition was largely unsuccessful. While India did exert its influence over Nepal, it was unable to control major political events the way it inherently desired. In addition, India's extensive engagement in Nepal to the level of micromanagement and its coercive foreign policy choices—such as an economic blockade—tarnished India's image in Nepal and took a toll on the so-called special relationship between the two countries.

First, particularly after the 2015 blockade, India and its reckless actions were widely criticised in Nepal. India's criticism was no longer confined to academic debate or the manifestos of a few political parties; the public in Nepal was unprecedentedly vocal against India's actions. Second, despite its ample attempts, India failed to steer Nepali politics as it desired. Despite India's strong reservations, Nepal promulgated the 2015 constitution, faced an economic blockade, successfully created a sense of national unity, and strengthened its relationship with China. Similarly, actions such as abolishing the monarchy, integrating Maoist combatants into the national army, and dividing federal Nepal into seven provinces were completed despite India's discontent and ongoing reservations.

Third, the Indian establishment suffered a domestic backlash for its poor neighbourhood policy. The post-2014 BJP government faced strong criticism within India for imposing an economic blockade on a close neighbour like Nepal. In other words, India's overreliance on hard power strategies, such as economic blockade and other forms of coercive diplomacy, was counterproductive. As a key informant explained:

They [India] also divided the political leadership [in Nepal]. But this impacted India negatively. India could have fulfilled its national interests in Nepal with a softer approach. The hard approach has backfired, and it seems that they are going to lose what they could have gotten from Nepal. Now, pro-Indian and anti-Indian sentiments seem to be established phenomena.¹⁷⁴

During the political transition, many of India's actions in Nepal were guided by the perception that if India were absent from the scene, that place would be occupied by China. Preventing, shrinking, or eliminating potential Chinese influence was unquestionably at the crux of India's Nepal policy. However, that strategy did not work well. India's aggressive approach became the very reason that compelled Nepal to reach out to China. As a key informant explained:

India attempted to prevent the transport and transit agreement that Nepal wanted to sign with China. India also attempted to prevent the BRI [Belt and Road Initiative] agreement between China and Nepal. Furthermore, India continuously showed interest in changing the

¹⁷⁴ Interview with an expert key informant (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

government in Nepal. However, the more it got engaged, the more policy failures it experienced in Nepal.¹⁷⁵

Despite the impediment imposed by India, Nepal signed the transport and transit agreement with China. India also pressured Nepal to reject the Chinese invitation to join the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), but Nepal managed to join it. Besides the BRI and a new transport and transit agreement, Nepal and China signed an additional ten contracts related to Nepal's infrastructure and economic development plans (Adhikari & Ma 2022: 2). While India has been accused of being proactive in blocking the implementation of these agreements, for Nepal, being able to sign these agreements with China was an achievement in itself.

India's excessive reliance on coercive strategies—such as an economic blockade, pervasive meddling, micromanagement, and power diplomacy—was the primary reason India suffered a backlash in Nepal. As I explained above, India's assistance to Nepal, whether through development cooperation, humanitarian relief, or budgetary support, has been substantial. India also facilitated the 12-Point Understanding reached between the Maoists and the SPA in New Delhi in November 2005. In the wake of *Jana Andolan II*, the Indian establishment did try to save the monarchy. However, when it became clear that Nepal and Nepali people were heading towards a federal democratic republic, India supported the process and refrained from being an obstacle.

However, problems began when India started to see its assistance as an investment and wanted a return or an output on that investment.¹⁷⁶ To secure that return, India deepened its engagement and, as shown throughout this chapter, used coercive policy instruments that undermined Nepal's sovereignty and the will of the Nepali people. Consequently, India failed to instil in the hearts and minds of ordinary Nepalis a sense that its involvement in Nepal was an act of benevolent support from a close neighbour. Instead, India was increasingly seen in Nepal as a malevolent actor and a reckless regional bully. As Nye (2009: 162–163) puts it, 'in today's information age, success is the result not merely of whose army wins but also of whose story wins'. From this perspective, India's story miserably failed in Nepal.

Against this backdrop, India's engagement in Nepal's post-conflict political transition offers a few critical insights. First, India's actions in Nepal refute the overtly romanticised claims of India as a rising giant on the back of soft power instruments (see, for instance, Tharoor 2011, Malone 2011), or what Wagner (2005) termed India's transition from a 'malign' hegemon into a 'benign' hegemon. In Nepal, India used soft power as well as hard power, and its over-reliance on hard power instruments was particularly intense in the later years of the political transition.

Second, when the BJP's Narendra Modi became Prime Minister in 2014, he promised better ties with neighbouring countries and unveiled the Neighbourhood First Policy. In the early days of his premiership, his administration did attempt to mend soured ties in the immediate neighbourhood. In the case of Nepal, Mr Modi became the first Indian Prime Minister to visit the country in 17 years. While in Nepal, Mr Modi delivered an impassioned speech in the Constituent Assembly and promised various assistance packages. However, as the years went by, the Neighbourhood First Policy proved to be little more than a gimmick and rhetoric.

¹⁷⁵ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹⁷⁶ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

In addition, it also became increasingly clear that the BJP-led India was unwilling to engage in serious introspection and make necessary course corrections.

Third, India relied heavily on its intelligence agencies and bureaucrats to handle its engagements in Nepal. However, that choice was inefficient and mostly counterproductive. While Kathmandu craved a high-level political engagement from New Delhi, the foreign intelligence agency of India, the Research and Analysis Wing, was busy running reckless intelligence operations in Nepal—toppling governments and making new ones every few months. Despite the Modi administration’s rhetoric on having meaningful political engagements, the helm of India’s Nepal policy was left at the mercy of detectives, bureaucrats, and technocrats who lacked a serious understanding and sensitivity involved in the relationship between the two countries. The lack of direct political engagement between the two countries caused frustration, suspicion, and anger in Nepal. This further damaged the already-strained relationship between the two countries.

Fourth, as I discussed in the previous sections, the Nepali political leadership did put up with India’s meddling and micromanagement to a certain extent for years. However, when they realised that India’s interventions did not coincide well with their own vision and aspirations for the country, they also began challenging and defying India’s actions. During the peace process and political transition years, Nepal witnessed incidents of reckless micromanagement, a pervasive feeling of powerlessness, and a sense of deepening dependency. However, there were also instances of unprecedented national unity, resistance, and collective defiance. The more coercive and hard power instruments India used, the greater the resistance and defiance it encountered. A lesson can be learnt from this experience: Foreign policy practices that rely heavily on hard power instruments, like coercive diplomacy, often eventually prove to be ineffective and counterproductive, as demonstrated in this example.

6.10 Chapter Summary: India in Nepal’s Peace Process and Political Transition

In this chapter, I elaborated on India’s engagement in post-conflict Nepal and showed how India’s influence in Nepal intensified after the 12-Point Understanding was signed in New Delhi in November 2005. I began the chapter by discussing the importance of the 12-Point Understanding in inspiring a series of street protests in Nepal in 2006. These protests, termed collectively as *Jana Andolan II*, were instrumental in initiating a peace process to end the Maoist armed insurgency and in steering Nepal toward a new political course. I then moved on to analyse India’s entry into post-conflict Nepal as a meddler and a micromanager. India’s interference took various forms and was widespread across Nepal’s security, political, and bureaucratic sectors. In the later years of political transition, India resorted to more ‘malign’ instruments, such as coercive diplomacy, an economic blockade, and the vilification and isolation of Nepal in international forums. Along the way, it also consistently used soft power instruments, such as development and humanitarian assistance. A change of regime in India in 2014 also had an impact on India’s Nepal policy. After 2014, the government led by Narendra Modi and the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) pressured Nepal to restore its Hindu identity.

Among other things, India was able to engage aggressively in political engineering and micromanagement by capitalising on its role as a ‘mediator’ and by attempting to fill the institutional void created in the absence of the monarchy. However, its excessive reliance on hard power and an aggressive engagement style

began to backfire as Nepali political actors started to resist and defy New Delhi's orders and undue demands.

The analysis I offered in this chapter is useful for understanding India's engagement in post-conflict Nepal. However, analysis of these cases alone is insufficient for fully grasping India's true motivation for meddling in Nepal. In essence, the issues discussed in this chapter are merely symptoms of a deeper, underlying structural problem. As I will argue in the next chapter, at the core of India's meddling and micromanagement lies a desire to keep Nepal tightly under its sphere of influence and run it as a client state. For India, Nepal is a sub-imperialist destination, an entity it can utilise to strengthen its position as a regional hegemon and gain the support it needs to achieve its ambition of becoming a global superpower.

7. India's Engagement in Post-Conflict Nepal: Neo-Dependency, Sub-Imperialism, or a 'Grand Design' for a Nepali Client State?

In the previous chapter, I conducted a detailed and mainly descriptive analysis of India's involvement in post-conflict Nepal. I showed that India's interference and micromanagement affected Nepal's state structures and institutions, severely impacting post-conflict peacebuilding and constitution-making processes. In this chapter, I examine the historical and broader issues between India and Nepal. I also set the stage for building the case of sub-imperialism in the next chapter.

I begin this chapter by discussing India–Nepal relations as a case of long-standing historical dependency and demonstrate how India's actions in Nepal already since the 1950s were aimed at reducing Nepal into a pliable client state. I argue that several unequal treaties between India and Nepal demonstrate the asymmetry inherent in the so-called special relationship between the two countries. I then discuss how the India–Nepal relationship characterises a long history of cooperation and co-dependency, as well as coercion and conflict. After examining some of India's major strategic interests in Nepal, I argue that though there have been slight shifts in India's short-term and medium-term interests, as far as India's long-term interest in Nepal is concerned, it has always remained the same.

I conclude the chapter by arguing that India's pervasive post-conflict engagement in Nepal was aimed at deepening Nepal's dependency and, in line with its long-term Nepal policy, i.e., converting Nepal into one of its sub-imperialist projects. The pattern, I argue, appeared largely similar to other sub-imperialist cases seen in different parts of the world (see, for instance, Çağlı 2009, Christensen 2013, Bond 2015). As is typical in other sub-imperialist projects, in Nepal's case, too, India's aim appears to be gaining control over natural resources and raw materials from weaker regions and reproducing a world system based on neoliberal capitalism and military and other forms of aggression. Nepal's geostrategic location, its natural resources—especially water—and India's goal to strengthen its status as a regional power while aiming for global superpower status seem to be the primary reasons for its actions in Nepal.

7.1 India–Nepal Relations and the Case of Historical Dependency

India's involvement in Nepal's post-2005 peace process and political transition requires a broader evaluation. This evaluation should extend beyond the specific time frame of the peace process and the domain of peace and mediation research. In other words, a historical analysis of India's involvement in Nepal is essential for a clearer understanding of India's motives behind its meddling and micromanagement in Nepal, which I elaborated on in the previous chapter.

As I mentioned in previous chapters, India's involvement in post-conflict Nepal was not an isolated event in the long and tumultuous coexistence between the two countries. India's presence and influence have always been felt in Nepal, even

though the degree of such influence has varied over time. At certain points in history, such as the early 1950s and 1990s, as well as during and after the Maoist armed insurgency, India had a stronger presence and influence in Nepal. In short, Nepal has sometimes been heavily dependent on and vulnerable to India's political and economic interference, but it has also made repeated attempts to break free from this trap.

Historically, India's treatment of Nepal has been primarily shaped by its own national—particularly security, geopolitical, and economic—interests. For instance, China's rise as a communist state and its military occupation of Tibet in 1951 played a significant role in shaping India's post-independent Nepal policy. In the wake of the Chinese occupation, India's presence in Tibet quickly withered away. Its security concerns and perceptions were also significantly altered. In the new scenario, any threat to Nepal was also considered to be a threat to India (Muni 2015: 3). This was also reflected in a speech delivered by India's first Prime Minister, Jawaharlal Nehru, in India's Parliament on 6 December 1950:

From time immemorial, the Himalayas have provided us with a magnificent frontier...We cannot allow that barrier to be penetrated because it is also the principal barrier to India. Therefore, much as we appreciate the independence of Nepal, we cannot allow anything to go wrong in Nepal or permit that barrier to be crossed or weakened, because that would be a risk to our own security (Jawaharlal Nehru's speeches volume II 1954: 257).

The 1962 war between China and India further consolidated India's perception of Nepal as a 'buffer state'.¹⁷⁷ The idea that the Himalayas were India's ultimate frontier began to be known as the Nehru doctrine and was firmly encoded at the core of India's foreign and neighbourhood policy. Still today, the 'Nehru doctrine' remains dominant in the psyche of the Indian establishment and continues to shape India's contemporary dealings in South Asia.

After Tibet was annexed by China in 1951 and India was defeated in the 1962 Sino-India War, India grew increasingly concerned about potential national security threats from its northern border. As a result, three small states in its northern frontier—Sikkim, Bhutan, and Nepal—became strategically even more critical for India. For New Delhi, the independent existence of these small states was a threat since India's perception was that they could be subjected to Chinese influence and used for anti-India activities. Consequently, stepping up its influence over these three countries and controlling their internal politics became India's routine approach. Sikkim was finally annexed to India in 1975. Bhutan's sovereignty remained significantly compromised as India was reluctant to abandon the British-era agreements regarding Bhutan's defence and foreign affairs.¹⁷⁸ In the case of Nepal, too, the Indian establishment had a hard time accepting it as an independent state with its own foreign policy choices and domestic political preferences. However, as Bhatnagar & Ahmed (2021: 3) put it, 'while Sikkim and Bhutan succumbed to Indian influence, Nepal has continued to resist'.

A former Indian Foreign Secretary, Jagat Mehta, wrote in his 2010 memoir that Nehru's 'overlordship' hindered India-Nepal relations, which could have otherwise been a unique and remarkable example of a co-dependent and cordial partnership

¹⁷⁷ A buffer state is a country that lies between two rival or potentially hostile countries. Because of their geographical positioning, buffer states can sometimes be thought to prevent conflict between hostile neighbouring countries.

¹⁷⁸ The 1949 India-Bhutan Friendship Treaty, which gave India the right to oversee Bhutan's defence and foreign affairs, was renewed in 2007 with some modifications. However, that did not significantly change Bhutan's heavy dependence on India.

(cited in Kumar 2016). Already during the Nehru era, India's actions in its neighbourhood were increasingly at odds with the global image it projected or the rhetoric it used in international forums. As Shah (2004: 196–197) argued:

Nehru and his generation of Indians claimed the moral leadership of the Third World in a discourse of de-colonisation and Afro-Asian solidarity. This was projected in moral opposition to the Western powers, which were seen as tainted by colonialism and slavery. Paradoxically, however, within South Asia, the Indian nationalists mimicked and consolidated the British colonial worldview and practices.

India was a leader of the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM) and a strong supporter of the New International Economic Order (NIEO). Both NAM and NIEO were emancipatory agendas proposed by developing countries to end a bipolar global order, elaborate economic colonialism, and the perpetual dependency of developing countries on the West.

While India confidently carried that emancipatory emblem at international platforms, such as the UN, its actions in South Asia suffered from the hangover of the British Raj. As Gordon (1992) put it, quarantining the subcontinent from what it would regard as outside interference became India's fundamental foreign policy objective after its independence in 1947. Similarly, Ziring (1978: vii) argued that Indian hegemony over the South Asian subcontinent had 'modulated in a number of phases that involved the integration of the princely states, the forcible absorption of Hyderabad, Kashmir, and Goa, the annexation of Sikkim, an imposed protectorate over Bhutan, a dominant presence in Nepal and Bangladesh, and finally the humbling of Pakistan'. India's main goal in the wake of its independence from the British Raj was to obtain regional and external acceptance of its hegemonic status in South Asia (Rose 1978: 60). In Nepal, that meant moulding its political evolution and converting the country effectively into a 'de-facto protectorate' (Myrdal 1968: 195).

It was already during Nehru's premiership that India termed the India–Nepal relationship as a 'special' one (Muni 2015). Despite the positive connotation of the term, for Nepal, the 'special' relationship with India resulted in greater dependency and a gradual loss of national sovereignty. As I mentioned earlier, particularly after the 1962 Sino–India war, India stepped up its engagement in Nepal and attempted to mould Nepali politics in its favour. Initially, India was in a rather 'subdued mood' (Subedi 1998: 168). To prevent Nepal from forming closer ties with China, it closely cooperated with King Mahendra and his repressive *Panchayat* regime. In the post-war scenario, India's interest was in strengthening Nepal's border security arrangements, improving Nepal's defence capabilities, and shaping Nepal's foreign policy (Muni 2015). By 1965, India even succeeded in persuading King Mahendra to purchase military equipment only from India (Whelpton 2005: 102). When the Sino–India war was over, in the name of border security, Indian troops entered and stayed in western Nepal's Kalapani region. While some troops were withdrawn from Kalapani after Nepal's repeated protests, some Indian troops continue to remain in Kalapani, an area touted to be ideal for observing Tibet (Risal 2019).

As years went by, it became increasingly clear that India was unable to maintain an exclusive grip over Nepal. Despite its heavy reliance on India for several issues, including international trade, the Nepali leadership had global aspirations and sought to engage with the outside world. Long before India gained independence from the British, Nepal established diplomatic ties with powerful Western countries, including the US, the UK, and France. Though not as strong as its relationship with India, Nepal's ties with China were also in good shape. This

situation resulted in Nepali leadership refusing to passively comply with India's attempts to reduce Nepal to a pliable de facto protectorate. Ultimately, this led to a repetitive pattern where India would try to subjugate Nepal and its leadership through various means, while Nepal and its leadership would seek to break free from that. To this day, that pattern persists in one form or another and continues to influence contemporary India–Nepal relations.

7.1.1 A 'Grand Design' for a Client State?

What does India really want from Nepal? This question is likely the most contemplated by both Nepali international relations experts and the general public in Nepal. As various incidents covered in this thesis also demonstrate, Nepal and its people have endured much suffering due to India's actions in the country. Even after more than seven decades of India's independence and several regime changes in both countries, the ground on which the relationship between these two countries is based has not changed much. As a result, Nepal remains in a state of perpetual political, economic, and cultural subordination to India. In the *durbars* of New Delhi, the reluctance to recognise Nepal as a sovereign and independent nation-state remains prevalent. This reluctance has persisted even when Nepal has tried its best to address many of India's authentic interests and genuine security concerns. As a key informant elaborated:

In fact, Nepal has addressed India's interests. However, it [India] has not let Nepal function as a free and sovereign nation and run its state affairs accordingly. Yes, Nepali politicians have their own weaknesses, but those who look at Nepal from New Delhi or those who frame India's Nepal policy see Nepal not as a separate nation, but as if it were one of India's provinces. That mindset, obviously, is problematic.¹⁷⁹

As I argued above, India's wish to see Nepal as a pliable and submissive state is not new. Throughout history, it has been clear that India's particular focus is on taking control of Nepal's defence and foreign affairs. In a 2017 interview, Baburam Bhattarai, a former Nepali Prime Minister, explained how India's contemporary neighbourhood policy was still guided by desire and the Nehru-era hangover:

India's former foreign secretary, Shiva Shankar Mukherjee, advised us during his recent visit to Nepal to change our approach. He said that we [Nepal] should focus on economic development and India would take care of our defence concerns...It is apparent that Indian leadership is not interested in addressing outstanding issues between the two countries...Their only interest is their own national security and the idea that the Himalayas serve as their ultimate security frontiers (Cited in Pant 2017).

In this context, it is clear that India's actions in post-conflict Nepal were largely driven by its long-term strategy to transform Nepal into a weak and submissive client state.¹⁸⁰ As a rising economic and political powerhouse, India has not shied away from showing off its intentions for regional hegemony. As far as its intention regarding Nepal is concerned, India wants Nepal's internal and foreign affairs to be conducted according to its guidance. It wishes that in international forums like the

¹⁷⁹ Interview with a journalist (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹⁸⁰ In international relations, a client state is a state that is economically, politically, and/or militarily subordinate to another bigger or more powerful state. Sometimes, a client state is alternatively referred to as a satellite state, dominion, neo-colony, protectorate, or vassal state.

UN, Nepal should act along India's lines.¹⁸¹

As political events, particularly of the last two decades, have demonstrated, Nepal has the opposite aspirations. As far as its relationship with India is concerned, Nepal wants to break, or at least weaken, its traditional dependence on India and aspires to diversify its foreign relations. Domestically, it wants to run its affairs as a sovereign nation, and internationally, it seeks to build an independent global image and a unique identity. However, Nepal's aspirations to exist as an independent and sovereign nation have clashed with India's desire to keep Nepal as a powerless and pliable entity. In other words, India aims to limit Nepal's aspirations and available choices. Whereas Nepal seeks to escape the dependency trap and strives to create a new reality for itself. This discrepancy in aspirations is at the core of much of the friction between the two countries.

Historically, India's actions in Nepal have often exhibited inconsistent and contradictory patterns. As discussed in previous chapters, India has a history of cooperating with authoritarian administrations while also supporting democratic movements in Nepal. It also has the habit of running parallel engagements in Nepal. For instance, during the Maoist armed insurgency, it provided unofficial shelter and a safe haven to senior Maoist leaders. However, it also supplied military assistance to Nepali security forces and assisted them in their fight against the Maoists.

Similarly, India supported the democratic movements in Nepal in 1950, 1990, and 2006. However, in the wake of such movements, it was reluctant to promote the rule of law and democratic institution-building processes in Nepal. As I will show later in this chapter, it has also been largely hesitant to support Nepal's aspiration for development and economic prosperity. In contrast, India's actions in Nepal primarily appear to be targeted at keeping Nepal both unstable and underdeveloped. As a key informant explained, the Indian establishment has recognised that maintaining mild instability in Nepal serves its interests, and this practice has persisted. As he further explained:

A stable and prosperous Nepal is good for India, too, and that's what they say. However, in practice, India cannot stand a stable and independent Nepal. And they do not want to see complete chaos or the demolition of Nepal either. Some say it's 'controlled instability'. India applied the strategy of controlled instability for many years, and later, it started micromanaging as well.¹⁸²

There is a widely shared and growing belief in Nepal that India's actions and inactions in some contexts can be explained in terms of its ulterior motive of keeping Nepal mildly unstable and relatively weak. As a key informant elaborated, India employs a variety of strategies for that. These include dividing influential Nepali politicians by supporting them interchangeably, as well as capturing big development projects and keeping them in limbo for years.¹⁸³ This would ultimately thwart Nepal's potential for prosperity and economic independence.¹⁸⁴ Arguably, behind these actions is a fear ingrained in the psyche of the Indian establishment that a prosperous and economically stable Nepal may not always be submissive to India. Economically prosperous and politically stable Nepal could manage its

¹⁸¹ Interview with Sudheer Sharma (02.08.2017).

¹⁸² Interview with an expert key informant (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

¹⁸³ He, for instance, gave the example of the 1792 km long Hulaki Highway, which India and Indian companies held for years but never managed to finish and, in the end, virtually abandoned.

¹⁸⁴ Interview with an expert key informant (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

natural resources independently and might not always support India in multilateral global forums like the UN, BIMSTEC, or SAARC.

Thus, India's Nepal policy in recent decades has been increasingly influenced by a concern that a fully independent Nepal would establish its own international identity. In this scenario, Nepal might not be willing to be a part of India's regional strength showcase. In other words, India remains hesitant to abandon its belief that its interests are best served when Nepal is dependent, weak, and unstable rather than when Nepal is politically independent, stable, and economically prosperous.

Though India often justifies its actions with a moral framing of defending democracy and the rule of law, its democratic motives in Nepal and elsewhere, too, have been repeatedly questioned. Its support for democratic movements in Nepal has often been conditional and strategically calculated. When its interests are served, it has tolerated dictatorial regimes for decades. When it has supported democratic movements, particularly successful ones, it often seeks to gain a stake in the aftermath. As a key informant explained, New Delhi sees its support for Nepal's democratic movements as an investment, eagerly awaiting the returns.¹⁸⁵ As the largest democracy in the world, promoting democracy in its neighbourhood should have been its moral obligation. However, even when supporting democratic movements, India has taken its vested interests into account before extending such support. As I explain in the next section, this has been particularly evident in the unequal treaties and agreements that have accompanied significant political changes in Nepal, where India's involvement was instrumental, if not decisive.

7.2 Unequal Treaties and an Unwillingness for Revision and Retrospection

As noted earlier, India has historically offered conditional support to Nepali political actors. However, Nepal has often had to pay back when it received such support. The idea of maintaining mild instability in Nepal, or a state of controlled instability, can be connected to agreements and treaties finalised either before or after major political upheavals in Nepal, in which India played a direct role. In other words, during times of internal turmoil or political instability in Nepal, India has historically taken advantage of the situation to pursue its own interests. As Shah (2004: 204) argued:

All of the controversial Indo-Nepal treaties on the exploitation of Nepal's natural resources were enacted immediately after a change of regime in Nepal: the Gandak and Koshi treaties after the ousting of the Ranas in 1950, and the Tanakpur and Mahakali treaties after the overthrow of the Panchayat in 1990. Indeed, Mohan Shamsheer signed the Treaty of Peace and Friendship of 1950 at his weakest moment, when his regime was already beginning to crumble.

With its parallel and multiple engagements with Nepali political actors, India has, over the years, mastered the art of 'divide and rule' in Nepal. Weak political institutions, insecure political leadership, and a long-standing dependency on India have often meant India getting its way in Nepal. On one hand, India has used Nepal's political transitions and vulnerable position to compel it to sign treaties and agreements that disproportionately favour India. On the other hand, when the Nepali side has lobbied and requested a re-evaluation and rectification of unequal issues inherent in past treaties and agreements, India has often chosen to neglect

¹⁸⁵ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

such requests.

While the Indian establishment demands that Nepal address India's security and other concerns, it has rarely shown interest in responding to Nepal's desire to review past treaties—which Nepal views as unequal—and in resetting ties between the two countries. India has maintained its policy of indifference regarding Nepal's requests for revisions and retrospection. In addition, it has employed counteraccusations as a tactic to evade Nepal's requests. For instance, for years, Nepal has clearly expressed its desire to revise Articles 5, 6, and 7 of the 1950 Treaty of Peace and Friendship between the two countries. However, India has not only ignored Nepal's request but has also criticised Nepal for not being clear and specific about its wishes (Ghimire 2017).

In 2014, when Narendra Modi began his first tenure as India's Prime Minister, he initially showed some willingness to mend soured relations with India's neighbours. In Nepal's case, it was reflected in his first visit to Nepal as India's Prime Minister. Mr Modi visited Nepal less than three months after being sworn in as India's 14th Prime Minister in May 2014. As the first Indian Prime Minister to visit Nepal in over seventeen years, he was received with the utmost warmth. Ordinary Nepalis lined up on the streets to welcome him and cheer for him, and he delivered a warm and lengthy speech in Nepal's parliament.

During that visit, an agreement was reached to form a high-level task force to identify key bilateral issues and seek recommendations for enhancing the relationship between the two countries. An initial proposal for such a mechanism was proposed by Nepal in 2011 during Prime Minister Dr Baburam Bhattarai's visit to India (Baral 2019). However, it was only in January 2016, after the 2015 blockade, when ties between the two countries had reached a new low, that a bilateral mechanism was formed to study the underlying 'irritants' affecting the relationship between the two countries. The task force was called the Eminent Persons' Group (EPG) and included eight members, with four from each country. It comprised veteran diplomats and foreign policy experts from both countries. As I mentioned earlier, the EPG's main mandate was to study the underlying issues between the two countries and provide recommendations for improving India–Nepal relations.

As per its mandate, the EPG thoroughly studied underlying issues between the two countries for nearly three years. In July 2018, the group finalised a joint report with a wide range of recommendations. Among other recommendations, there was reportedly a suggestion to re-evaluate past unequal treaties, including Articles 5, 6, and 7 of the 1950 Treaty of Peace and Friendship. The report also included several suggestions for enhancing trade, commerce, natural resource management, and cultural ties (Giri 2021).

Since 2019, the EPG has made several attempts to submit the joint final report to the Prime Ministers of India and Nepal. While Nepal was prepared to receive the report, India has avoided doing so. When the final meeting of the EPG took place in 2018, it was decided, for reasons unknown, that the joint report would be submitted first to the Indian Prime Minister and then only to his Nepali counterpart. India's unwillingness to receive the report has meant that even after more than four years, the report's actual content remains unknown, and the EPG is losing the relevance and the legitimacy that it once enjoyed (Giri 2021).

Moreover, India has not been open and specific about why it is uninterested in receiving the joint report. After all, half of the members in the EPG were Indian nationals and appointed by the Indian government. In press briefings, when asked about India's reluctance to receive the report, Indian officials have often tended to

avoid the question by answering that the Prime Minister was very busy and that his office had been unable to find a suitable time slot for receiving the report (Neupane 2018). This excuse, however, is highly implausible. Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi has visited Nepal twice, in August 2018 and May 2022, after the EPG finalised its joint report, but he has continued to be reluctant to allocate the few minutes required for receiving the report. Most recently, in September 2024, Nepal's Prime Minister KP Sharma Oli is reported to have requested the receipt of the EPG report during his meeting with Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi in New York. According to media reports, this request was met with disapproval from the Indian side, which contributed to a somewhat tense atmosphere during the meeting (see Dhakal 2024).

India's unwillingness to receive the EPG report demonstrates its whimsical and casual approach in its dealings with Nepal. It is apparent that Prime Minister Modi's busy schedule is just an excuse, and the Indian establishment seems to be avoiding the EPG report primarily for two reasons. First, India is reluctant to implement the recommendations included in the report. Accepting the EPG report and not implementing its recommendations would be morally and diplomatically a difficult choice for India because it had co-commissioned the EPG, and its appointees were part of the high-level group. Second, it is also likely that the EPG might have been commissioned as a distraction strategy when anti-Indian sentiment in Nepal peaked in the wake of the 2015 economic blockade.

India's continuous indifference to the EPG report reflects its lack of interest in addressing the underlying issues that have consistently strained the relationship between the two countries. In other words, the EPG debacle illustrates that India does not give Nepal, an independent and sovereign nation-state, the attention it seeks and desires from its closest neighbour. Nepal has interpreted India's apathy and unresponsiveness in the EPG as arrogance and carelessness (Poudyal 2022). However, it has also opted out of receiving and publishing the report unilaterally. While this may be seen as Nepal's cautious approach or mature diplomacy in dealing with its powerful neighbour, it also reflects Nepal's fears and a longstanding inferiority complex embedded in the Nepali establishment's mindset when addressing issues related to India. After all, provoking the Indian establishment is an option that the political elites in Kathmandu rarely consider.

7.3 A History of Cooperation, Co-dependency, Coercion, and Conflict

As I mentioned in the previous chapters, the relationship between India and Nepal has not always been troublesome. This is not a relationship representing continuous conflict or coercion. While there have been many episodes of coercion and conflict, there have also been periods of friendship and cooperation. On one hand, India has played a significant role in Nepal's political, social, and economic development. On the other hand, it has also actively sought to maintain its influence over Nepal, reducing it to a weak, submissive, and perpetually dependent state. Whether through hard power measures—such as meddling, micromanagement, and economic sanctions—or relatively softer means—such as financial assistance, development aid, and defence cooperation—India's goal has remained unchanged: to extend its sub-imperialist influence into Nepal and gain political, economic, and geo-strategic advantages.

India's assistance and cooperation with Nepal began shortly after its independence from British rule. India played a crucial role in Nepal's institution-

building and modernisation processes, which started right after its independence in 1947. India's own process of rebuilding and rebranding itself as a new decolonised democracy had also influenced its relationship with Nepal. Independent India received assistance from and looked up to Western countries for its post-independence social and economic development. The colonial past and Western influence, particularly British, hugely affected and shaped India's post-colonial political, economic, and social structures (Carey 2012, Griffiths 2019).

As India began to modernise itself in the image of the West, it also dragged Nepal along the way. However, the difference was that Nepal's movement towards development or modernisation was heavily controlled and guided by India. For independent India and its ambitious leadership, Nepal and other neighbouring countries were more than simply neighbouring countries. They provided cheap labour and raw materials, served as investment destinations, and offered promising markets for selling goods and services to generate surplus. In that sense, India's assistance to Nepal was also an effort to accelerate the development of a neoliberal market economy and a political establishment impeccably loyal to India.

In the late 1940s, India supported Nepal's first democratic movement and, in 1951, facilitated a tripartite political deal between the Ranas, the Nepali Congress and King Tribhuvan that replaced the 104-year-old autocratic Rana rule with democracy. India also helped Nepal form its police force and reorganise and reform the national army (Chhetry 2021). Until 1959, Nepal did not have a university, and colleges in Nepal ran under affiliation to India's Patna University. Nepal did not have a modern currency until 1932 and a national bank until 1956. Even Nepal's foreign reserves were kept at the Reserve Bank of India. On matters such as these, Nepal remained dependent on India for years.¹⁸⁶ While Nepal is no longer as dependent as it once was, it still relies on India for a number of issues. Still today, Nepal is almost entirely dependent on India for sea passage and international trade.¹⁸⁷ The Nepali rupee, Nepal's official currency, is pegged to the Indian rupee. In practice, this means that the Nepali currency lacks independent value in international markets, and its worth is mainly determined by the performance of the Indian rupee.

It has always been India's top priority to keep Nepal under its sphere of influence or ensure that a pliant regime sits in Kathmandu. That is also because Nepal is one of the most lucrative markets and export destinations for India. For instance, in the fiscal year 2018–19 alone, India's exports to Nepal were a whopping 7.7 billion USD. In the same period, Nepal's exports to India were merely 508 million USD (EOI Kathmandu, 2020). Between 1995 and 2020, India's exports to Nepal increased annually by 15.5%, from USD 159 million in 1995 to USD 5.85 billion in 2020 (OECD 2022). In 2023, India's exports to Nepal stood at USD 7.25 billion, as reported by the United Nations COMTRADE database on international trade. The highest figure recorded was USD 9.19 billion in 2021.¹⁸⁸

Indian firms remain the largest and the most influential foreign investors in Nepal, as their share of foreign direct investment (FDI) in Nepal is estimated to be between 35–40% (G.S. Wagle 2016, Khanal 2024). India exports more than 665 products to Nepali markets, making Nepal's economy practically India-dependent and India-oriented. It is no surprise that the vast trade deficit between the two

¹⁸⁶ Interview with Rajan Bhattarai (13.07.2017).

¹⁸⁷ Even though Nepal has opened transit links through China, most of Nepal's international trade continues to happen through Indian ports.

¹⁸⁸ Statistics available at <https://comtradeplus.un.org>

countries has had a serious impact on the Nepali economy. While India exports petroleum products, automobiles, machinery, pharmaceutical products and a range of other high-end consumer items, Nepal's main exports to India remain cheap labour, raw materials, and petty consumer and agricultural items, such as edible oil, coffee, tea, and spices (Shrestha 2023).

For India, Nepal has been a source of cheap labour for a long time. It is estimated that as many as eight million Nepali citizens live and work in various Indian cities (Mishra 2023). Unsurprisingly, most of these labour migrants are engaged in low-skilled, low-wage menial jobs, working mostly as security guards, cooks, cleaners, and taxi drivers. The number of Nepali women trafficked to Indian cities for prostitution and sex slavery is also staggering. Each year, it is estimated that as many as 7,000 Nepali women and girls are trafficked to India, with the majority forced to work as prostitutes in Indian brothels (Sanghera & Kapur 2000, Dhungel 2021). India also has a long history of recruiting Nepali youths into its national army. As of 2022, about 32,000 Nepali Gurkha soldiers were serving in the Indian army (Shrestha A. 2022). Whether to crack down on domestic mutinies or fight foreign wars with neighbouring countries such as Pakistan or China, it is Gurkha soldiers that India has frequently deployed on the frontlines.¹⁸⁹ As a result, in over 70 years of service to the Indian Army, countless Nepali youths have lost their lives fighting for India—defending its borders, sovereignty, and territorial integrity.

In essence, Nepal has been a source of cheap labour and brave mercenaries for India. From fighting its foreign wars to patrolling the streets of New Delhi, Mumbai, and Hyderabad, Nepali cheap labour has been extensively used in India for decades. In addition, geographically, Nepal acts as a buffer state against China, and economically, it is a lucrative and burgeoning market for India's exports. Though Nepal could be considered a relatively small economy, for India, it is one of the biggest export destinations. For instance, in 2022, Nepal was India's eleventh largest export destination, right after Belgium and Germany (Indian Trade Portal 2022).

As previously stated, India played a supportive role in Nepal's pursuit of democracy and modernisation. Particularly after the end of the repressive Rana regime in 1951, India helped Nepal set up political, legal, and financial institutions. While India took a more assertive approach in dealing with the two smaller states in the region, Sikkim and Bhutan, with Nepal, its role was more complex and contradictory. On one hand, India accepted Nepal's status as an independent nation-state. It also accepted, at least in theory, Nepal's sovereignty and national integrity without any hesitation. India had no objection when Nepal sought to join various international organisations. It even accepted Nepal's bid for UN Security Council membership in 1968. When India itself was a poor and developing economy and a recipient of international development aid, it did not hesitate to provide its own development assistance to Nepal already since the 1950s (see, for instance, Khanal 1964). On the other hand, however, when Nepal attempted to exercise an independent foreign policy or challenged India's dominance, Nepal faced backlashes and fierce opposition from New Delhi. One example is Nepal's effort to free itself from military and non-military alliances and gain the status of a Zone of Peace (ZoP), and India's persistent and coordinated opposition to it.

During his 1975 coronation ceremony, King Birendra proposed that Nepal be named a Zone of Peace (ZoP) by the United Nations. The King argued that this would give Nepalese non-alignment a new dimension. He had reportedly drawn

¹⁸⁹ Interview with Hari Bahadur Thapa (20.07.2017).

inspiration from ‘Swiss neutrality’. He believed the ZoP model would accelerate Nepal’s economic development and promote an independent global image. The proposal was endorsed by more than 115 countries, including the US, the UK, the Soviet Union, France, China, and almost all South Asian countries except India (Thapa 2015c).

The ambitious ZoP proposal was not only unappealing to India, but it also actively worked to sabotage its progress and implementation. It extensively lobbied with other countries, such as France and the Soviet Union, to renounce their support for the proposal (Thapa 2015c). As Nepal's closest neighbour, India should have been the first country to endorse it. However, India interpreted that doing so would mean losing its traditional grip on Nepal (Duquesne 2022). It had also probably assumed that an economically prosperous and independent Nepal would not be ideal for its geopolitical and economic interests in the region.

Nepal's ZoP proposal gradually fizzled out primarily due to India's opposition and extensive lobbying against it. However, India's contradictory approach towards Nepal persisted. On one hand, it continued providing Nepal with development and military assistance and supported three democratic movements in Nepal—in the 1950s, 1990s, and late 2000s. On the other hand, when rulers in Kathmandu did not act the way New Delhi wanted, it suppressed Nepal’s political autonomy and sovereignty. It also repeatedly disregarded and compromised the agency of Nepali political actors.

India remains one of Nepal’s biggest bilateral donors, and as I have already explained, India’s assistance comes in all shapes and sizes. Whether through development cooperation assistance, humanitarian relief, budgetary support, or scholarships, India’s assistance to Nepal has been significant. For instance, in its 2024/25 budget alone, India allocated a grant of INR 7 billion (NPR 11.20 billion) to Nepal (Onlinekhabar 2024).

As already mentioned, when two devastating earthquakes hit Nepal in April and May 2015, India’s efforts in rescue and relief operations in Nepali towns and villages won the hearts and minds of millions of Nepalis. Nonetheless, only a few months later, when the Indian establishment was livid at Nepal’s unwillingness to include India’s issues in Nepal’s new constitution, it responded by imposing an economic blockade that created a humanitarian catastrophe in Nepal. To achieve its goals in Nepal, India employed the blockade strategy also in 1970 and 1989–90.

India’s engagement in Nepal and its interactions with Nepali political actors are guided by specific objectives and adhere to a consistent pattern. India’s aid to Nepal is also inherently conditional. Eventually, Nepal often faces significant consequences for the support it receives from New Delhi. Historical evidence shows that Indian assistance typically comes with plenty of strings attached, and when New Delhi is upset, measures such as an economic blockade become imminent. Aid and assistance have essentially worked to keep a pliant regime in Kathmandu and perpetuate Nepal’s economic and political subordination and dependency on India. As I will explore later in this chapter, in exchange for the aid and assistance provided, India seeks pro-Indian economic, political, and defence policies in return. In addition, India wants access to lucrative natural resources, the sharing of intelligence information with its security agencies, and support on multilateral international platforms.

7.4 India's Strategic Interests in Nepal

The Indian establishment tends to justify its actions in Nepal with the perpetual and habitual excuse that India has strategic interests in Nepal. Nepal as a part of India's security and strategic sphere is a notion proposed long ago by India's first prime minister, Jawaharlal Nehru. As I already argued, over the years, there has been no significant shift in that perception. India still views Nepal as a subordinate part of its security and strategic sphere and acts accordingly. As an established South Asian regional power and an emerging global power, India does have stakes and interests in Nepal. Still, the strategic interest narrative has often been used to deepen its influence in Nepal.

As I previously discussed, the two countries have signed several treaties and agreements in the past and continue to do so. Such agreements are often related to trade, investment, free movement of Indian and Nepali nationals, and management of natural resources. In addition, India has repeatedly expressed its concerns over the potential use of Nepali soil—primarily by third-country nationals—to carry out anti-Indian, terrorist, and criminal activities targeted at India. Although there have been a few isolated incidents,¹⁹⁰ there have been no major terrorist or criminal attacks against India originating from Nepali territory.

India's other concern has been the suspected activities of the Inter-Services Intelligence, Pakistan's intelligence agency, as well as the smuggling of counterfeit Indian currency through Nepal.¹⁹¹ India and Nepal share an open border that extends over 1,751 kilometres. This means that countries are naturally concerned about events occurring across the border. Furthermore, they have mutual expectations and are interested in whether these concerns are taken seriously. As Bishnu Poudel explained, Nepal has always been ready to address India's legitimate concerns. Whether it involved controlling the smuggling of fake Indian currency through Nepal or ensuring that no terrorist groups find refuge within its borders, Nepal has always been serious.¹⁹²

The Nepali side strongly feels that it is India that has not taken Nepal's concerns and requests seriously. India, for instance, turned a blind eye to the presence of senior Maoist leaders sheltering in its cities during the Maoist armed insurgency. Nepal had declared the Maoists a terrorist organisation, and so had India. However, in contrast to its official stance, the Indian government took barely any action to arrest and extradite senior Maoist leaders to Nepal, despite repeated requests from the Nepal government.

India and Indian companies are involved in various infrastructure and natural resource management projects in Nepal. However, they have shown little interest in carrying out the mega infrastructure projects for which they were awarded contracts.¹⁹³ For instance, even more than 26 years after the signing of the ambitious Mahakali Treaty, India has yet to start the project, which should have been completed years ago, according to the treaty agreement. In 2022, Nepal's new international airport in the southern city of Bhairahawa faced severe limitations in its activities because India refused to provide more than one air route for planes

¹⁹⁰ One notable example is the hijacking of Indian Airlines Flight 814 en route from Kathmandu to New Delhi in 1999 by Pakistani militants.

¹⁹¹ Interview with Mumaram Khanal (24.07.2017).

¹⁹² Interview with Bishnu Poudel (13.07.2017).

¹⁹³ Interview with Mumaram Khanal (24.07.2017).

entering Nepal. Reportedly, the route that India provided was not the shortest or the one that Nepal had requested (Shrestha H.P. 2022).

Similarly, India has built 21 dams and embankments along its border with Nepal in manners that obstruct the natural course of downstream rivers. Every rainy season, Indian authorities close the barrage outlets unilaterally, causing flooding and inundation in Nepali towns and villages in the border area (Ghimire & Giri 2021). As numerous reports indicate, Indian authorities have shown little interest in finding long-term solutions to these issues (see, for instance, Pyakurel & Anupam 2020, Bagale 2020).

It is also worth noting that India's interests in Nepal have often tended to shift when there is a regime change in India. For instance, as I discussed in Chapter 6, the BJP-led Indian establishment pressured Nepal to restore its identity as a Hindu nation in the 2015 constitution. The Hindu-state agenda was not a priority for the previous government led by the Indian National Congress. Nevertheless, despite regime changes and occasional minor adjustments, India's long-term Nepal policy—centred around its security and economic interests—has remained largely the same.¹⁹⁴

Over time, India's economic and security interests in Nepal have somewhat evolved. However, a key aspect of India's Nepal policy has remained the prevention of third countries' influence to safeguard its interests. India has been particularly concerned about the potential and actual presence of countries such as China, Pakistan, and even the United States (Muni 2012: 317). Already in the 1950s, India was successful in prevailing in Nepal through the controversial 1950 Treaty of Friendship that gave India special privileges over other countries for the 'development of natural resources' and 'industrial project' in Nepal (Muni 1973: 191).

China's increasing influence in Nepal has been an issue of serious concern for India (Arora 2015a). Given the long-standing rivalry between the two countries, India's desire for China to limit its involvement in Nepal is partly understandable. However, India's concerns about China's presence in Nepal are largely exaggerated and unjustified. First, they are largely based on India's reluctance to acknowledge Nepal as a fully sovereign nation with the right to establish its own relationships with other countries, including China. In other words, Nepal cannot be expected to limit its engagement with China simply to assuage India's insecurities. Second, China's involvement in Nepal is not an inherent threat to India's security. China has increased its presence in South Asia in recent years with its Belt and Road Initiative, which seeks to expand China's economic and geopolitical influence across Asia and beyond. While Nepal has joined the BRI, no real progress has been made regarding its implementation. In addition to the BRI, China has invested in a few mega-infrastructure projects in Nepal in recent years. However, India has always been the frontrunner when it comes to influencing Nepal's internal politics. While Nepal has valid reasons to be cautious about the BRI and the potential debt trap it could create, the initiative could also benefit the country by providing essential infrastructure.

Third, China and India are not rivals or competitors, as they are often portrayed. On many fronts, they are allies. Whether it is their participation in the BRICS forums or the vast bilateral trade and investment activities they share, there is

¹⁹⁴ A notable exception was I.K. Gujral's short stint as India's Prime Minister between April 1997 and March 1998, during which he prioritised proactive soft-power policies as a means of mending and improving relations with India's neighbours.

ample evidence to suggest that India's accusations of Chinese involvement in Nepal and the perceived threat to India are largely unfounded. India's concerns about China's presence in Nepal might have been partly driven by historical grievances, particularly India's defeat in the 1962 China–India war. The main reason, however, appears to be India's fear of losing Nepal to China as one of its sub-imperialist destinations, which I will discuss in detail in the next chapter.

A senior Nepali politician I interviewed shared with me a list of issues that had emerged as India's concerns in Nepal over the years. The list included potential issues such as the use of Nepali territory by Pakistan-based terrorist organisations, lapses in the surveillance and management of the open border, and the rise of Chinese cultural centres near the Indo–Nepal border in northern Nepal. India has also been increasingly concerned about Saudi and Pakistan-funded madrassas near the Indo–Nepal border in the south, illegal trade, leakage of transit goods, drug and arms smuggling, and human trafficking.¹⁹⁵ The shared feeling of the Nepali leadership—also reflected during my interviews—is that India's genuine concerns should be addressed and that Nepal should understand the sensitivity of the open border.¹⁹⁶

There have been no major incidents that would suggest that there had been lapses from the Nepali side as far as cooperating with Indian authorities on transborder issues, such as tackling fake currency or cracking down on individuals involved in criminal and terrorist activities. In Nepal, however, the prevailing sentiment is that the core issue lies not in isolated border or security concerns but in India's reluctance to fully recognise Nepal as an independent and sovereign state capable of making its own important decisions. As Bishnu Poudel explained:

We are ready to address India's legitimate concerns. Whether it is the issue of fake currency or the wish that terrorists or criminals should not be able to take shelter in Nepal. We can work together on these and many other issues, too. However, we should be clear that we are two independent countries and that, as sovereign countries, we have equal status.¹⁹⁷

Furthermore, as I mentioned earlier, India's interests in Nepal extend beyond mere geopolitics and security and include economic and resource issues. While Nepal may appear to be a small market, it continues to be an attractive market destination for India. Nepal's proximity to India, with its emerging economy and growing middle class, makes it a lucrative market for Indian businesses. More than 30% of Nepal's foreign direct investment comes from India (G.S. Wagle 2016, Khanal 2024), and as I previously mentioned, India's exports to Nepal have rapidly increased in recent years (see, for instance, OEC 2022).

India has long been focused on securing its grip on the Nepali market and has sought to maintain a dominant position in key sectors such as energy, transportation, and telecommunications. Nepal's reliance on India for key imports such as petroleum products, pharmaceuticals, and machinery has enabled India to use its economic power to maintain influence in the country. Along with strengthening its hold on the Nepali market, India is also keen on ensuring unrestricted access to Nepal's natural resources. In the next section, I will discuss how India's actions in Nepal are partly driven by its desire to access Nepal's natural resources, particularly water.

¹⁹⁵ Interview with Shekhar Koirala (22.08.2017).

¹⁹⁶ This feeling was shared by several key informants I interviewed for this study.

¹⁹⁷ Interview with Bishnu Poudel (13.07.2017).

7.5 A Sub-Imperialist Search for Nepali Resources: India's Engagement in Nepal's Water and Hydroelectricity Sectors

As I proposed in Chapter 3, a suitable theoretical vantage point to look at contemporary India–Nepal relations is sub-imperialism. As I will discuss in detail in the next chapter, Nepal is both a case of Indian sub-imperialism and an example of resistance against it. Studies on contemporary sub-imperialism have shown that the appropriation of natural resources is a common aspect of sub-imperialist projects (see, for instance, Çağlı 2009, Bond 2015, Bond et al. 2021). The appropriation and exploitation of resources is a way for sub-imperialist powers to gain an advantage over other countries and assert their dominance in the global system. It is well-known that dominant powers use natural resource appropriation as a strategy to consolidate their economic and geopolitical influence. They achieve these goals often by establishing economic dependencies, controlling supply chains, manipulating global markets, and reinforcing the subordination of resource-dependent economies.

As I argued in the previous section, two long-term strategies primarily guide India's Nepal policy. First, intending to reduce Nepal into a pliable client state, India aims to minimise the influence of other countries in Nepal while strengthening its own. This can be labelled as the political aspect of India's domination of Nepal. The second one is economic and resource-oriented. India's sub-imperialist project in Nepal includes the appropriation of both natural and human resources. For example, India's ongoing and contentious involvement in Nepal's water resources sector is a key element of its sub-imperialist efforts, which requires further clarification.

Nepal has abundant water resources in the form of snow cover, rivers, springs, lakes, and groundwater. Among these, the country's 6,000+ rivers and rivulets are particularly crucial as they provide a dependable water source for various uses and present favourable conditions for generating hydropower (Rauniar 2022). Nepal's potential for economically viable hydroelectricity production is estimated to be between 42,000 and 83,000 megawatts (MW) (Gunatilake et al. 2020: 3). Currently, very little of this potential has been harnessed. It is estimated that Nepal can generate an estimated USD 8 billion per year by exporting electricity to power-hungry India, which needs as much as 12,000 MW of electricity merely for its rapid industrialisation schemes (Mandal 2019).

However, despite ample attempts, Nepal has been able to reap only limited benefits. The way India has engaged in Nepal's water and hydroelectricity sector illustrates why Nepal has not fully capitalised on its water resources. It is well-known that Nepal's water resources have attracted India's attention for a long time. As a close neighbour, Nepal has historically relied on India to harness its water resources, too. The two countries have signed several water treaties and agreements, one common component of these agreements being that India harnesses Nepal's water resources for water and hydroelectric power generation, and the two countries mutually benefit from that.

However, the water agreements between Nepal and India—which dictate how the two countries share and use water resources—have been characterised by significant inequalities that have persisted over time. As a larger and more powerful player, India has wielded considerable influence over these agreements, and the resulting terms have largely favoured India's interests over those of Nepal. All major water agreements between the two countries, including the Sharada Dam (1927), the Koshi Agreement (1954), the Gandak Agreement (1959), the Tanakpur

Agreement (1991) and the Mahakali Treaty (1996), suffer from two major issues. First, these treaties and agreements have heavily favoured India (see, for instance, Gaudel 2013: 16–17, Chandra & Prasad 2020, Bagale 2020) or were signed in haste or under duress, particularly when Nepal had characteristically unstable and short-term governments (Gyawali & Dixit 1999, 2000, 2001). Second, India has never been interested in following the terms and conditions of these agreements and compensating Nepal with agreed-upon benefits. It has been consistently clear that India's motive behind these agreements has been signing agreements with Nepal, completing the DPR (Detailed Project Report) process, and then holding the projects in limbo. As Muma Ram Khanal noted, India neither completes these projects nor allows other potential actors to step in and take over.¹⁹⁸

Nepal's longstanding distrust and resentment towards India regarding water cooperation can be traced back to the Koshi and Gandak treaties of the 1950s. Looking back, it is apparent that both treaties were flawed in their lack of foresight and vision. The projects included in these treaties were plagued by poor design and ineffective implementation. Despite attempts to amend the treaties, such as in the case of the Koshi treaty in 1966 and the Gandak treaty in 1954, the level of trust and confidence necessary to foster future cooperation was never achieved (Muni 2015: 402). As a result, the legacy of these treaties has left a lasting impression on the Nepali psyche, fuelling a deep-seated mistrust of India's intentions in Nepal's water sector.

In fact, the lack of progress in implementing past treaties and agreements appears deliberate. According to Thapa (2015a), India's strategy has essentially been to sell Nepal and Nepalis the dream of hydroelectricity development and economic prosperity and keep using Nepal's water resources without any resistance or restriction. He further argues that if Nepal prospers economically by selling electricity, it could build sophisticated dams in its rivers and harness its water resources without India's assistance—a situation India wants to prevent. Thus, India's actions in Nepal underlie a component that thwarts Nepal's economic progress and perpetuates Nepal's dependency.

As a strategy to maintain and deepen its economic domination of Nepal, India has actively discouraged and thwarted foreign investments in Nepal's hydroelectricity sector. The 750-1,200 MW West Seti Hydroelectric Project is an ideal example of how Nepal's hydroelectricity sector has suffered from Indian manipulation. An Australian company, Snowy Mountain Engineering Corporation, attempted to construct the West Seti Hydroelectric Project but could not begin construction for more than seventeen years. After that, the Government of Nepal awarded the construction contract to a Chinese company called the China Three Gorges International Corporation (CTGI). The CTGI held the project for over 3 years but was unable to start the project. In both cases, the India factor worked as an indirect inhibitor (Giri & Prasain 2022).

The dispute over the sale of the electricity generated was the main reason the West Seti Hydroelectric Project remained stalled for nearly three decades. India's refusal to buy electricity produced by other countries in Nepal was one of the main reasons for the project's failure (Ghimire 2022). Despite numerous attempts, neither company could secure a power purchase agreement with India. In June 2022, after years of delays and stagnation, the Government of Nepal had no option but to give the project to the National Hydroelectric Power Corporation (NHPC), a company owned and operated by the Indian government (Prasain 2022).

¹⁹⁸ Interview with Mumaram Khanal (24.07.2017).

The 1,200MW ambitious West Seti project got stuck in a state of uncertainty for more than 29 years, whereas Nepal faced severe energy scarcity and began importing electricity from India. Hydroelectricity has been touted for years as one of the avenues for Nepal's economic prosperity. In fact, Nepal does have the potential to earn a significant amount of revenue by exporting its surplus electricity to India and other neighbouring countries. According to a 2017 study, if the country can harness its hydropower potential and start exporting 13 gigawatts of electricity to India by 2030, it could earn up to Rs 310 billion per year (Parikh et al. 2017: 2). Furthermore, if the capacity is doubled to 26 gigawatts by 2045, Nepal could earn as much as Rs 1,069 billion (approx. 7.6 billion USD) per year (Prasain 2022).

However, India's policy of rejecting the purchase of electricity produced by third countries has had a detrimental impact on the potential benefits that Nepal could have derived from hydroelectricity. In 2016, India introduced a new policy that mandated purchasing electricity exclusively from companies that are either fully Indian-owned or have a majority stake held by Indian companies (Thapa 2017). This policy stance by India has significantly hampered Nepal's efforts to harness its abundant hydroelectric resources and capitalise on its potential as a major exporter of clean, renewable energy.

Following complaints and lobbying from Nepal, India slightly revised that policy in 2018 and removed the 51% ownership requirement (Bhushal 2022). Despite this change, there are still certain conditions that must be met. The revised policy still maintains that India can import electricity only if the generating company is not owned by any individual or legal entity that is a resident or citizen of a third country that shares a land border with India and does not have a bilateral agreement on power sector cooperation with India. This was an indirect attempt by India to restrict foreign investments, especially from China, in Nepal's hydroelectricity sector.

As a result of India's exclusionary policy, the West Seti project, which was being developed first by an Australian company and then by a Chinese company, was unable to strike a power purchase agreement with India. As mentioned above, in 2022, the NHPC, an Indian state-owned company, received the contract for the project. However, there is no guarantee that the company will begin and complete construction on time, as the issue of Indian companies holding projects for years, if not decades, has been a persistent concern in Nepal. Moreover, since water-sharing issues were excluded in the West Seti deal, there are concerns that India's intrinsic interest in the project might be for water and not necessarily for hydroelectricity (Bhushal 2022).

In diplomatic dealings with their Nepali counterparts, Indian authorities have been clear about refusing to purchase electricity produced by other countries, particularly by China (Malhotra 2018). However, India's reluctance to purchase electricity generated by Chinese investments in Nepal is clearly an implausible excuse and a double standard. It is no secret that India itself has been welcoming Chinese investment, and the two countries have had a long history of bilateral trade and economic cooperation. While the exact reasons behind India's refusal to buy electricity from China-backed projects in Nepal are unclear, India's insecurity regarding China's potential political influence in Nepal is unquestionably a major factor. Furthermore, India also has an economic interest in this decision.

The Indian establishment is aware that by denying the purchase of electricity generated by Chinese investments, India can ultimately get construction contracts for mega hydropower projects in Nepal. Indian developers have already replaced Chinese contractors on some of Nepal's largest hydroelectric projects, including the

West Seti project discussed above (Bhushal 2022). Indian companies also hold Arun III and Upper Karnali, with a capacity of 900 MW each. In June 2023, during Nepali Prime Minister Pushpa Kamal Dahal's visit to India, two major hydropower projects were awarded to Indian companies: the 679-MW Lower Arun and the 480-MW Phukot Karnali (Dhital 2023). This addition further strengthened India's significant presence in Nepal's hydropower sector.

It remains to be seen whether Indian companies will complete these mega-projects. However, one thing is clear: India's monopoly over Nepal's water resources has been steadily expanding. Since India has adopted the policy of purchasing electricity from Nepal only when it is produced by Indian companies, Nepal is left with little choice but to comply with India's terms. This will also mean that Nepal will be compelled to sell its electricity to India at a lower price. Thus, by discouraging or thwarting foreign investment in Nepal's hydropower development and by stunting Nepal's progress in the hydropower sector, India continues to limit Nepal's potential for economic progress and perpetuates Nepal's dependence on India.

7.5.1 India's Long-standing Thirst for Nepali Rivers

There is growing evidence that India's interest in Nepal's water resources expands beyond just hydroelectricity. It also includes a plan to secure access to water for its own consumption and to meet the growing demand for water in the future. As already mentioned, Nepal has abundant water resources, including several rivers and lakes originating from the Himalayas. These water resources are essential not only for hydroelectricity generation but also for Nepal's survival, as they supply drinking water and support other needs, such as agriculture. India, however, is a water-scarce country with a large population that is heavily dependent on agriculture for their livelihoods.

With growing urbanisation, India already faces water scarcity, and a water scarcity crisis is projected to be imminent in some parts of India (see, for instance, Gupta 2008, Gulati & Banerjee 2016). Water, therefore, is a scarce commodity in India. Against this backdrop, ensuring unrestricted access to Nepal's water resources is part of India's strategy to secure future water supply for its water-scarce regions. For that, India not only wants a pro-India government in Kathmandu but also has a keen interest in bureaucratic appointments in the Ministry of Water Resources and the Irrigation Department.¹⁹⁹

India's interest in Nepal's water resources is driven by its need to secure water for consumption and to meet the growing demand for water in the future. In this context, Nepal's water resources are an important strategic asset for India. Unsurprisingly, India has pushed for several bilateral water resource agreements with Nepal. These include constructing dams and irrigation channels, and developing hydropower projects. Most of these agreements, however, have been contentious. India has been accused of attempting to control Nepal's water resources and failing to take Nepal's needs into account (see, for instance, Thapa 2017, Tandan 2021). The problem lies in how the agreements were signed, mostly during fragile and transitional political periods in Nepal, as well as the way these agreements were implemented—or not implemented. Historically, Nepal has advocated for a more equitable distribution of these resources, although it has seen little success.

¹⁹⁹ Interview with a journalist (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

Over the years, it appears India has mastered the art of entrapping Nepal into political transitions and then fulfilling its resource interests. India used Nepal's unstable political situation to construct dams in Nepal's Koshi and Gandaki rivers and irrigate its two states, Bihar and Uttar Pradesh (Thapa 2015a). Nepali water experts argue that India wants to build new high dams in the Koshi and Karnali rivers to guarantee a long-term water supply for the two provinces. In fact, the construction of the Koshi High Dam is a long-standing wish of India, which the Nepali side has successfully thwarted for decades (see Thapa 2015a).

India's interest in Nepal's water resources has been long, extensive, and well-documented. As with West Seti, Upper Karnali, Arun III and many others, Indian companies have invested in some of Nepal's biggest hydropower projects. However, especially in recent years, India has become increasingly interested in Nepali rivers as reliable sources of drinking water and irrigation. As a key informant put it, unlike electricity—which can be generated from various sources, including coal, natural gas, and renewable energy—water is a scarce and essential resource with no real alternative or substitute, and India knows that well. He further added:

In a way, one might think that Nepal's rivers ultimately reach India, and nobody can prevent India from benefiting from this natural flow. The natural flow of rivers, however, is unregulated. India wants a regulated and controlled flow of water. For that, India intends to construct dams in Nepal's mountains, which will, among other things, cause inundation in Nepal.²⁰⁰

As explained by the above-mentioned key informant, Nepal's major rivers, such as the Koshi, Gandaki, and Karnali, flow downstream and eventually reach India. While India benefits from the water resources provided by these rivers, it also seeks to maintain tight control over them, particularly in terms of their access and use. Therefore, building dams and barrages in Nepal's mountains allows India to secure access to controlled water flow.²⁰¹

India's focus on controlled access to these rivers is driven by its need to ensure a reliable and secure water supply for its own use and limit any potential downstream impacts, such as flooding or water shortages. The water agreements signed between Nepal and India aim to manage and control the water flow from these rivers. These agreements have, however, become a source of tension between the two countries. Nepal feels that its sovereignty over its water resources is being compromised and that it is not receiving a fair share of the benefits from the joint management of these rivers. As such, the question of controlled access to Nepal's rivers remains one of the critical issues in the bilateral relationship between the two countries.

India's first water-harnessing projects were on the Koshi and Gandak Rivers in 1954 and 1959, respectively. From the very beginning, these projects were controversial as they heavily favoured India (Bagale 2020). In response to Nepali grievances, the agreements were revised in 1964 for the Gandak and in 1966 for the Koshi; however, there was a deep distrust between the two countries in water harnessing. In 1996, an ambitious new treaty, the Mahakali Treaty, was signed. The treaty envisioned an integrated development of barrages, dams, and hydropower in Western Nepal's Mahakali River (Gyawali & Dixit 1999). More than two decades after the treaty's ratification, there has been barely any progress in implementing the Mahakali treaty.

²⁰⁰ Interview with a journalist (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

²⁰¹ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

As with hydroelectricity, India has shown a similar attitude towards Nepal's large-scale water and irrigation projects and has actively worked to block foreign investments in these sectors. According to Thapa (2015a):

If one looks at the background and India's attitude, it is clear that India's main motive is to use Nepal's water the way it wants. A large part of Nepal is dry due to a lack of irrigation, and India has created a situation where Nepal cannot use its own water resources properly. India has repeatedly foiled Nepal's plans to secure loans and foreign investment for irrigation projects. Loans approved for the Sikta and Babai projects stalled due to Indian pressure. Big projects such as the Koshi Diversion, Kankai Irrigation Project, and Bheri Diversion Irrigation Project, which were studied with colossal investment, got stalled due to a lack of loan support. In the 1980s, the Saudi Development Fund showed interest in issuing a loan of 1 billion rupees to Babai, and a draft of the agreement was also prepared. But later, the Fund pulled out from the project, arguing that it had received an objection from India and that the loan would be processed only if Nepal could secure India's consent.

There are growing concerns that Nepal's water resources are increasingly becoming a priority for India due to the potential for generating green hydrogen from water. Experts predict a shift from petroleum to electricity and hydrogen as the main energy sources within a decade, and Nepal has the potential to excel in both energy sectors. According to a 2021 study, Nepal could produce as much as 3,153,360 tons of green hydrogen by 2030, using surplus hydroelectricity (see Thapa et al. 2021). Nepali green hydrogen has been touted as one of the cheapest to produce. According to research conducted by GHLab, the cost of hydrogen production in Nepal is as low as USD 1.17 per kg, which is significantly lower than the global average of USD 3 per kilogram (Subedi 2021).

Aware of Nepal's potential in this sector, the Indian government and Indian firms have started lobbying for the right to extract green hydrogen from Nepali rivers. In June 2023, during Nepali Prime Minister Pushpa Kamal Dahal's visit to India, green hydrogen was reportedly one of the top agendas that Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi raised in discussion with his Nepali counterpart (Dhungana 2023a). India has clearly understood that Nepali green hydrogen is not only lucrative but also an excellent source of renewable energy that can be exploited to reach its goal of becoming carbon neutral by 2070. Among others, Gautam Adani, an Indian billionaire who aims to become the leading green energy industrialist by investing USD 70 billion by 2030, is accused of eyeing Nepal's hydropower resources for green hydrogen production. Reportedly, the Adani Group has been trying to invest in the 10,000 MW Karnali Chisapani hydro project, and the group's aim apparently is not hydroelectricity generation, but green hydrogen (Dhungana 2023b).

Against this backdrop, India's deep interest in Nepal's resources is evident in the political orchestrations that New Delhi periodically performs in Kathmandu. India, for instance, is keenly interested in the appointments of key positions in the ministries and departments that deal with Nepal's natural resources. In addition, India also actively mobilises its apparatuses to ensure that any policy or structural reforms in Nepal align with its resource and political interests. For instance, when Nepal's major political parties decided to adopt federalism as part of the state restructuring process in the post-conflict context, India actively attempted to mould the federal setup—particularly the demarcation of new provinces—in its favour. Notably, Nepal's largest rivers, such as Koshi and Karnali, were the subject of India's deep interest in the entire saga (Thapa 2015b).

7.6 Chapter Summary: Navigating India's Political and Economic Motives in Post-Conflict Nepal

This chapter examined India–Nepal relations as a case of long-standing historical dependency. In other words, it traced India's efforts since the 1950s to reduce Nepal to a pliable client state. The analysis highlighted the asymmetry in the 'special relationship' between the two countries, which is evident, among others, in the numerous unequal treaties between them. This chapter also demonstrated how India–Nepal relations continue to be characterised by a complex interplay of cooperation, co-dependency, coercion, and conflict. After examining India's strategic interests in Nepal, I argued that while its short- and medium-term interests have shifted slightly, its long-term interests have remained largely the same.

I interpreted India's extensive post-conflict engagement in Nepal as an effort to reinforce Nepal's dependency and establish it as one of India's sub-imperialist destinations. In other words, India's actions in post-conflict Nepal were consistent with its long-term Nepal policy. In essence, India's actions in Nepal were driven by Nepal's geostrategic location, abundant natural resources—particularly water—and India's broader ambition to strengthen regional dominance as part of its pursuit of global superpower status. The chapter also highlighted how India's interference hindered Nepal's economic advancement, particularly in harnessing its natural resources. In addition, it demonstrated a historical pattern of India exploiting Nepal's political transitions and instability to secure favourable agreements.

In the next chapter, I will tackle the theoretical dilemma surrounding contemporary India–Nepal relations, arguing that sub-imperialism provides a more accurate theoretical framework for understanding this complex coexistence. I will demonstrate that India's relationship with Nepal reflects key elements of sub-imperialism: India's use of economic power to shape Nepal's political and economic landscape, its role as a regional hegemon with a tendency to dominate neighbouring countries, and its exploitation of Nepal's natural resources and labour.

8. The Face of Indian Sub-imperialism in Nepal: An Aspiring Hegemon and a Resource-Greedy Neighbour?

In the previous chapters, it became clear that India's actions in post-conflict Nepal were reckless, its presence emphatic, and its motives questionable. Through several examples, I demonstrated that the two countries engaged in an unequal relationship, characterising a dominant and influential player and a subordinate and dependent partner. In this chapter, my orientation is more theoretical. Specifically, my goal in this chapter is to develop a theoretical perspective for examining the relationship between India and Nepal. In doing so, I also try to identify plausible theoretical strands that help 'deconstruct' their relationship. I begin the chapter by exploring how India's long-term engagement in Nepal can be seen as a manifestation of its sub-imperialistic tendencies. I discuss how India has strategically deployed its power to secure its grip on Nepali politics, Nepal's domestic markets, and its natural resources. For India, I argue, Nepal remains one of its sub-imperialist destinations and an important 'asset' for maintaining its regional dominance and enhancing its standing on the global stage.

As I show in the latter part of this chapter, India's sub-imperialist aggression has been repeatedly defied and challenged by Nepal. Nepal has asserted its sovereignty on multiple occasions and has sought to break free from India's domination. Interestingly, India's sub-imperialism in South Asia is intertwined with its internal colonialism at home. This has benefitted neoliberal corporate capitalism and pro-Hindutva political elites, but it has also caused irreparable harm to India's democratic and secular values.

The chapter concludes with a brief discussion on the rising powers of the Global South, particularly the BRICS, and how their economic and political rise has failed to challenge the neoliberal economic path laid out by Western hegemonic powers. Instead of challenging global hegemonic powers, I argue that the so-called rising powers of the Global South have resorted to extractivist and often oppressive foreign and economic policies and have actively contributed to the maintenance of neoliberal regimes. Theoretically, this chapter offers insights into rising power behaviour and new forms of dependencies in the Global South. It also offers a unique insight into contemporary sub-imperialism and how it works.

As a concluding thought, I argue that the so-called rising powers of the Global South offer little hope as far as the developing countries' long-cherished dream and aspiration of creating the New International Economic Order is concerned. Similarly, the rising powers' hegemonic and sub-imperialist aspirations jeopardise the true potential of South-South Cooperation. Nonetheless, a ray of hope can be found in the anti-sub-imperialist and anti-hegemonic resistance, as well as the collective action and solidarity among social and grassroots movements in the Global South.

8.1 Nepal as India's Sub-Imperialist Destination

As I discussed in detail in the theoretical framework chapter of this thesis (see Chapter 3), sub-imperialism refers to a situation in which a country or group of countries, while not being imperialist powers themselves, act as intermediaries for imperialist powers. In sub-imperialism, dominant actors use their power to extract resources, control markets, and influence politics in other countries, often in collaboration with the dominant global powers. As I argued in the same chapter, there is growing evidence that the so-called rising powers of the Global South, such as the BRICS, have exhibited sub-imperialist tendencies and have contributed to neoliberal regime maintenance. In practice, this could involve facilitating capital accumulation, resource extraction, and expansion of their markets in ways that reinforce prevailing power relations rather than challenging them.

Ruy Mauro Marini introduced the concept of sub-imperialism in the 1960s to explain Brazil's expansionist policies in Latin America and Africa. Scholars like Elif Çağlı, Adrián Sotelo Valencia, Patrick Bond, and Ana Garcia have made significant contributions to the contemporary literature on sub-imperialism (see Chapter 3). Bond, for instance, argues that BRICS countries follow colonial and neo-colonial models of sub-imperialism, which include different modes of accumulation, exploitation, and super-exploitation (see Bond 2015). He identifies three additional roles of sub-imperialist regimes: ensuring regional stability, advancing globalised neoliberalism, and continuing exploitative practices in their hinterlands.

Sub-imperialism is a feature of the dominant international system, representing an intermediate stage between the centre and the periphery. Sub-imperialist actors act as intermediaries, being both dominant and subordinate units that exert military, economic, and political control over a specific region. Economic exploitation is central to sub-imperialism. It involves the super-exploitation of labour, monopolisation of the economy, and appropriation of natural resources, all of which provide the foundation for this practice. Unlike neocolonialism, which operates on a global scale, sub-imperialism is territorially specific, with the influence of sub-imperialist agents restricted to a particular region (see, for instance, Väyrynen & Herrera 1975, Çağlı 2009, Bond 2015, Bond et al. 2021).

Sub-imperialism increasingly seems to be a key element in the modern dependency puzzle. As I argued in Chapter 3, contemporary dependency relations differ significantly from those of the past. As Strange (1994: 215) argues, in today's world, opting out of the global market economy is no longer a viable option due to the proliferation of multinational corporations and pervasive corporate capitalism, and that is what today's dependency looks like. Despite claims made by proponents of globalisation, the benefits of globalisation have not been evenly distributed and have created polarisation. In today's so-called globalised context, dependency relations persist through trade deals, foreign direct investment, and even development aid (Farny 2016). Similarly, rather than ending the practice, the rise of a select few countries in the Global South to the 'core' has established new dependency relations within their dominant regions.

The argument advanced here is that India's actions in Nepal, which I have discussed throughout this thesis, can be regarded as sub-imperialist in nature. This chapter's objective, therefore, is to comprehensively examine the available evidence that substantiates this claim. In the previous chapters, I mostly discussed India's historical political domination of Nepal, as well as the increased control in the post-conflict context. However, to understand the full picture of Indian sub-imperialism in Nepal, it is essential to focus more on economic dominance and resource issues,

as well as how these factors affect the underlying mechanisms of sub-imperialism at work.

As I partially explained in the previous chapter, India's economic domination of Nepal is long and extensive. First, Indian firms continue to hold the top position as the biggest and most influential foreign investors in Nepal, and their contribution to the country's foreign direct investments is estimated to be above 35% (Khanal 2024). With more than 665 commodities exported to Nepal by India, the Nepali economy is highly reliant and focused on India. Consequently, the substantial trade deficit between the two countries has negatively impacted Nepal's economy (G.S. Wagle 2016). While India exports various manufactured goods such as machinery, processed petroleum products, pharmaceuticals, and other consumer goods, Nepal's primary exports to India include unskilled labour, raw materials, and small-scale consumer and agricultural products. This is typical of a sub-imperialist relationship, in which the dominant power extracts resources and labour from the weaker state while selling back manufactured goods at a profit.

Furthermore, India's trade policies have been detrimental to Nepal's economy, and the trade deficit between the two countries has skyrocketed, particularly in recent years. For instance, in the first six months of the fiscal year 2022/23 (mid-July 2022 to mid-January 2023), Nepal exported goods worth just Rs 57.84 billion to India while it imported goods worth Rs 486.33 billion from India, resulting in a trade deficit of a whopping Rs 428.33 billion for Nepal (Republica 2023).

Second, international financial institutions such as the World Bank, Asian Development Bank, and the IMF are the biggest creditors of both Nepal and India. While India is itself indebted to these global financial giants, for Nepal, in addition to these neoliberal financial institutions, India is also one of the biggest creditors (see Rijal 2022). India's role both as a lender and a creditor in the global financial ecosystem also signifies its position as a sub-imperialist agent.

Third, India has effectively dominated and controlled Nepali markets through various strategies. For instance, as Shrestha (2018) argues, India has hurt Nepal's small industries, particularly agriculture, by heavily subsidising its own small industries. As a result, Nepali markets are flooded with government-subsidised, mass-produced, cheap Indian products. This has led to a decline in Nepal's small industries, which cannot compete with subsidised Indian industries. India has also negotiated with Nepal to safeguard Indian investments in Nepal.²⁰² Unequal treaties between the two countries force Nepal to seek India's clearance and approval for purchasing arms. This means that Nepal is largely compelled to buy weapons from India, as long as such weapons are available. Although Nepal's arms imports from India are declining, India remains one of the largest suppliers of arms, ammunition, and military equipment to Nepal (Bishoyi 2024). Large-scale arms and military equipment deals represent another form of economic exploitation and surplus extraction that Indian defence companies are involved in within Nepal. In short, India's political domination of Nepal has enabled it to exert greater influence over Nepal's economic policies, leading to further subjugation of Nepal's economic sovereignty.

Natural resource appropriation, central to sub-imperialist relationships, is also evident in India–Nepal relations. As discussed in the previous chapter, India has actively sought unhindered access to Nepal's water resources for years. India already faces water scarcity, and water and energy have been recognised as two

²⁰² For instance, the Bilateral Investment Promotion and Protection Agreement signed in 2011 guaranteed investment protection for Indian companies in Nepal.

major constraints to the rapid economic progress that India aims to achieve (see Kumar & Furlong 2012). Domestically, hydroelectricity production has been challenging for India, among others, due to civil society's resistance to dam construction projects (Bharadwaj et al. 2006).

India's approach to appropriating water from its neighbouring countries has been labelled as 'water hegemony' (Hanasz 2014, Bagale 2020, Tandan 2021). In practice, India's water hegemony means controlling the rivers that flow through the region to gain political and economic leverage over its neighbours. Furthermore, India has also been accused of using its control over the rivers to manipulate water flows to its own advantage while depriving downstream countries of their fair share of water resources (see Bagale 2020). As I demonstrated in the previous chapter, India's thirst for Nepali rivers has been sustained, and an act carefully orchestrated. As a result, India's water and hydroelectric projects in Nepal have not been in Nepal's best interests, with India or Indian companies extracting large profits from these projects or leaving them in limbo for years.

India's military involvement in Nepal can also be seen as one of the indicators of its sub-imperialist position. India has not militarily invaded Nepal as such, but over the past decades, there have been several incidents of military domination and encroachments. In the wake of the 1962 Sino-Indian war, India stationed 18 military barracks and checkpoints in Western Nepal, near the Nepal-China border. While India withdrew most of these barracks, it still has a military presence in Nepal's Kalapani area (see, for instance, Cowan 2015). Similarly, for more than two decades, India has placed military commandos equipped with sophisticated weapons as 'sky marshals' in its Kathmandu-bound planes. In recent years, the number of such commandos has increased without Nepal's consent, and even though the practice has been justified as an anti-terrorism precaution, the lack of consent from Nepal and the extent of surveillance being carried out in Nepal have raised concerns. India has, in fact, lobbied for years to station such commandos at Kathmandu Airport (see The Kathmandu Post 2018, Baral 2021: 45). In addition, Indian security forces have repeatedly killed and harassed Nepali citizens at the India-Nepal border. Their actions, marked by excessive force and unwarranted aggression, have led to the unjust killings and harassment of innocent Nepali citizens in the region (see Chhatyal 2017, Pokharel 2021).

Moreover, India not only sells arms and military equipment to Nepal, but it also supports and trains Nepali security forces. The US military is engaged in a similar relationship with the Indian army, a strong indicator of India's sub-imperialist position. As mentioned earlier, India has long been a major supplier of arms to Nepal. India has not only provided military assistance to Nepal, but the Indian Army also played a vital role in establishing the former Royal Nepal Army. It continues to provide reorganisation and modernisation support to the Nepal Army and has trained Nepali military personnel for decades, both in India and Nepal (Cheetry 2021). India's active involvement in Nepal's security sector indicates that it is positioning itself as a major defence player in the region, which is typical of countries in a sub-imperialist position.

As I mentioned earlier, while India equips, supports, and trains Nepali security forces, its own military receives similar support from the United States, which strongly reinforces its status as a sub-imperialist power. The United States has been a major supplier of arms to India for decades. Since 2008, India has contracted for nearly USD 20 billion worth of US-origin defence articles (Congressional Research Service 2024). Similarly, in 2022, it was reported that the US planned to send a USD 500 million military aid package to India, making India one of the biggest

military aid recipients from the United States, along with Israel and Egypt (Sen & Martin 2022). Between 2018 and 2024 alone, India acquired more than USD 15 billion in arms and military equipment from the United States (Patel 2024). Historically, India has also been a major recipient of US economic aid. Between 1946 and 2012, it received approximately USD 65.1 billion in economic assistance, positioning it as the largest beneficiary of US aid during that period—exceeding even key allies such as Israel and Egypt (see Rajghatta 2015). Moreover, the United States is India's largest military exercise partner, with regular joint exercises across all services. Notable joint exercises include Yudh Abhyas (Army), Vajra Prahar (Special Forces), and various naval exercises (Congressional Research Service 2024). In fact, the US has been training and assisting the Indian military for decades. India's receipt of military aid and training from the US is also seen as a way of strengthening its ties with the US, a hegemon with whose guidance and footsteps India has preferred to operate.

Furthermore, India's participation in regional strategic and military alliances, such as BIMSTEC, and its role in the US-led Indo-Pacific strategy offer strong evidence for its sub-imperialist position in the South Asian region. BIMSTEC, the Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation, is a regional grouping of seven countries: Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar, Nepal, Sri Lanka, and Thailand. It was formed in 1997 to promote economic and technical cooperation among its members. However, largely due to India's wish, BIMSTEC has, in recent years, redirected its focus from economic and technical cooperation to security issues. In 2018, the group held its first joint military exercise, in which all BIMSTEC members except Nepal participated (Mohan 2018). India is the largest and most powerful member of BIMSTEC, and it has used its position within the group to promote its own interests in the region. It has been pushing for BIMSTEC to take a more active role in countering China's influence in the region. India has also used BIMSTEC to promote its own security interests. For instance, it has used the group to build closer ties with Myanmar, a key strategic partner in India's efforts to counter China (Roy 2022). BIMSTEC's maritime security cooperation framework also serves India's security and geostrategic interests.

The gradual 'securitisation' of BIMSTEC reflects India's growing adaptation as a sub-imperialist power in South Asia. India has long sought to be the dominant power in the region and has increasingly attempted to use BIMSTEC to achieve this goal. India's indifference towards the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC)—a regional bloc that includes Pakistan as a member and has China as an observer—indicates that India views BIMSTEC as a strategic platform. Unlike SAARC, it can leverage BIMSTEC to counter China's increasing regional influence and to bolster India's own sub-imperialist position.

While India actively forms and maintains its prominent position in regional political and military alliances, such as SAARC and BIMSTEC, it also participates in similar mechanisms created by Western powers, especially the United States. India's participation in the US-led Indo-Pacific strategy is one such example. The Indo-Pacific strategy is a US-led initiative aimed at countering China's increasing regional influence and preventing the possible decline of the US as a global hegemon. India has been a key partner in this strategy, and one of the openly declared aims of the Indo-Pacific strategy has been to support 'India's continued rise and regional leadership' (The White House 2022). This essentially means strengthening India's role as the US's junior partner in the region or consolidating its position as what sub-imperialist scholars often refer to as a regional 'deputy

sheriff' (see Bond 2015).

In short, India's ongoing involvement in Nepal's security sector, military presence on Nepali soil, long-standing efforts to oversee Nepal's defence and foreign relations, the use of sky marshals on Kathmandu-bound flights, large-scale arms deals, and active participation in regional military alliances all show its desire to maintain control and exert influence over Nepal. Similarly, its role as the US's 'deputy sheriff' in the South Asian subcontinent and its political and military subordination to the US indicate its sub-imperialist position in the region.

Given the evidence of economic dominance, political interference, and extractive practices in the country, it is evident that India's actions in Nepal clearly demonstrate a typical sub-imperialist relationship. The trade deficit between the two countries, coupled with the typical pattern in which Nepal sends mainly raw materials and cheap labour while India sends manufactured goods, shows a clear dependency pattern at play. India's actions of indebting Nepal, undermining its small industries by subsidising its own, and dominating Nepal's internal market only worsen the long-standing dependency. Furthermore, India's attempt to appropriate Nepali resources, especially water, also demonstrates the face of Indian sub-imperialism.

As mentioned earlier, India's sub-imperialist position is evident in its relationship with the United States. While India is the dominant power in South Asia, it remains subject to US influence and domination. Several factors contribute to the US domination of India. First, India is heavily dependent on the US for trade and investment. India is the 10th largest trading partner of the US, and the US is India's largest trading partner (US Census Bureau 2017). The US also invests heavily in India. For instance, in 2021 alone, US investments in India stood at approximately 45.45 billion USD, whereas foreign direct investment from India in the United States was merely 2.95 billion USD (Statista 2021a, Statista 2021b). This unquestionably has made India vulnerable to US pressure on trade and economic issues.

As India exploits Nepali cheap labour mostly in the informal economic sectors, US companies are engaged in a similar practice in India. By setting up their own operations in the country, more than 1,000 American multinational companies have taken advantage of the lower labour costs. These companies employ approximately 1 million people in a variety of roles, including back-office IT and call centres (Moschella 2021).

In addition, as I mentioned above, India's reliance on the US for security is extensive. India is a member of the US-led QUAD alliance and actively participates in the US-led Indo-Pacific strategy. It relies heavily on the US for security assistance, including access to intelligence and military equipment, and has a history of assisting US military operations. For instance, India allowed the US to use military bases on its soil in 2001 to conduct offensive operations in Afghanistan. This was despite ordinary Indians protesting the US invasion by participating in some of the largest anti-war demonstrations the country had ever seen (Kennedy & Palmer 2001).

India and the US have signed several defence agreements in recent years, including the Logistics Exchange Memorandum of Agreement, the Communications Compatibility and Security Agreement, and the Basic Exchange and Cooperation Agreement, which enable greater military interoperability and information-sharing (Sneesh 2020). The share of US weapons in the Indian Army has gradually increased over the years (Congressional Research Service 2024). The Indian military has purchased high-end defence equipment from the United States,

including C-130J transport aircraft, P-8I maritime surveillance aircraft, and Apache attack helicopters (Singh 2020). India is not only a lucrative arms trade destination for the US but has also been providing training to the Indian military, particularly through joint exercises such as the Malabar naval exercise (Rajagopalan 2022). The US-India relationship is often presented as a strategic partnership—a term that aptly conceals the underlying elements of domination and dependency. As Roy (2014: 44) put it:

Being a “strategic partner” of the United States does not mean that the heads of state make friendly phone calls to each other every now and then. It means collaboration (interference) at every level. It means hosting US Special Forces on Indian soil (a Pentagon commander recently confirmed this to the BBC). It means sharing Intelligence, altering agriculture and energy policies, opening up the health and education sectors to global investment. It means opening up retail. It means an unequal partnership in which India is being held close in a bear hug and waltzed around the floor by a partner who will incinerate her the moment she refuses to dance.

India has been obliged to cooperate with the US on various issues, including trade, security, and the act of countering China. India’s increasing dependence on the US for its security gives the US leverage over India’s foreign policy, too, creating a dynamic in which decisions made in New Delhi are often influenced by the considerations of Washington. In essence, in the contemporary international system, India continues to act as the US’s junior partner, overseeing and extending the US-led hegemonic world order in South Asia.

8.1.1 Means, Ends, and Methods of Indian Sub-imperialism

The sub-imperialist relationship between India and Nepal does offer some insights into how sub-imperialism operates—particularly at the state level—in the contemporary Global South. The India–Nepal case illustrates that sub-imperialism is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon and is intricately linked to the historical contexts of the countries involved. This example, along with other similar cases observed globally, shows that sub-imperialism does not emerge as a spontaneous occurrence; rather, it is the result of prolonged historical processes and interactions. It appears to stem from decades, if not centuries, of dependency, subjugation, and political and economic domination.

India’s sub-imperialism in Nepal, for instance, is deeply rooted in India’s legacy of historical and cultural domination of Nepal. As Nepal’s close and powerful neighbour, India has historically played a dominant role in Nepal’s political affairs, even before India’s own independence. India’s assertive influence in Nepal can be traced back to the Treaty of Sugauli signed between the East India Company and Nepal in 1816, which allowed the East India Company ruling in India to control matters related to Nepal’s internal and foreign affairs.

A few theoretical insights can be drawn from the India–Nepal sub-imperialist framework. While the concept of sub-imperialism has been useful in understanding how larger powers dominate smaller states, it has somehow also suffered from the limitations of being too simplistic and deterministic. For instance, it has often overlooked the agency of smaller states and how they resist imperial and sub-imperial domination. The role of non-state actors, such as social movements and civil society organisations, in challenging dominant power structures has also received little attention. At times, the scholarship on sub-imperialism is fixated on reinforcing a binary view of the world in which there are only two categories: imperial/sub-imperial powers and subordinated states. However, this kind of

attitude or worldview needs further investigation and elaboration to gain a more realistic understanding of contemporary sub-imperialism.

As I have already discussed, the political and economic ramifications of Indian sub-imperialism in Nepal have been immense. Several key features, including unequal exchange, financial domination, and political subordination, characterise the sub-imperialist relationship between the two countries. Even though unequal exchange and loans alone do not inherently imply sub-imperialism, they seem to be strongly linked to the practice. Unequal exchange refers to the fact that Nepal is forced to sell its goods and services at lower prices than it would receive in a fair market. It is estimated that as many as 8 million Nepali citizens are working in India, mostly providing a source of cheap labour. As previous research studies have highlighted, Nepali migrants in India are often employed in the informal economic sectors, such as agriculture, security, construction, and domestic work, and are typically paid lower wages than their Indian counterparts (see, for instance, Saraswati et al. 2015, Shrestha M. 2017, Regmi et al. 2019). In addition, India employs more than 32,000 Nepalis in its national army, virtually compelling Nepali citizens to fight lethal wars to protect its borders and its national interests (Shrestha A. 2022).

India's financial domination involves using debt and credit, but also development aid, to expand its control over Nepali politics and the economy. Political subordination, as I detailed in the previous chapters, refers to how India uses micromanagerial manipulation, power diplomacy, and other harsh measures, such as economic blockades, to influence and engineer Nepali political terrains.

Multinational corporations, which often operate across national borders as surplus-collecting and transferring agents, are central in establishing, maintaining, and perpetuating sub-imperialism. They possess and exercise significant economic and political power, too. They often take advantage of differences in labour and environmental regulations between countries, engaging in practices such as outsourcing, tax evasion, and a reckless pursuit of profit. Already a decade ago, around 525 Indian firms, many of them multinational, were operating in various sectors across Nepal, including construction, energy, minerals, and manufacturing (IANS 2014). They primarily have a twofold motive: first, to make a profit and transfer that into their headquarters in New Delhi, and in some cases, to Western capitals, such as New York or London, supposedly the ultimate imperialist locations. Second, they are also engaged in exploring and exploiting Nepali resources to maximise profit.

In addition to grabbing large hydropower projects and other construction deals, Indian firms have also been involved in extracting Nepal's diverse natural resources, such as medicinal herbs. Nepal's abundant biodiversity includes around 700 flowering plant species with medicinal properties (Pokharel & Ghimire 2017). However, despite the potential for utilising these plants to benefit Nepal's economy, many are sold or smuggled to Indian firms (Basnet 2019). Once processed and packaged as consumer goods, they are sold back to Nepali markets and elsewhere at a significantly higher price, generating a hefty surplus. Furthermore, Indian firms are also involved in extracting and transporting stone, gravel, and sand from Nepal's mountains (Ghimire 2021).

The exploitation of Nepal's natural resources and the domination of Nepali markets are not limited to Indian private corporations. As I explained earlier in the case of the West Seti Hydropower project and the involvement of NHPC Limited, the Indian state itself operates 277 industrial and business entities, known as central public sector undertakings (PSUs). These state-owned entities are engaged

in exploiting natural resources both at home and abroad. The NHPC Limited, for instance, has developed itself as an energy giant and has numerous projects in India and neighbouring countries, including Nepal and Bhutan. Over the past 30 years, India's central PSUs have contributed roughly 20% to the country's gross domestic product (GDP) and have particularly dominated key industries such as oil and gas, utilities, mining, heavy engineering, and banking (Chandra & Walton 2020: 191). The primary aim of PSUs has been to accumulate profit, bolster Indian state capitalism, and ultimately strengthen India's position as a regional hegemon. To achieve this goal, it is essential to uphold a robust state capitalism, which plays a crucial role in supporting India's sub-imperialist activities.

The influence of multinational corporations in sustaining sub-imperialism is widely acknowledged. However, little attention has been given to the role of state capitalism as a strong subsidiary of sub-imperialism. As with Indian sub-imperialism, it is becoming increasingly clear that strong state capitalism can also play a significant dual role—maintaining sub-imperialism and benefiting from it. In such instances, the state's control over the economy and its resources is crucial in exerting its influence in other countries and regions. Equally, sub-imperialist practices could be principally used to enrich and embolden state capitalism. Thus, there is a need to broaden our understanding of sub-imperialism to include the role of state capitalism in perpetuating and benefiting from it.

Traditionally, the study of sub-imperialism also appears to have suffered from economic determinism. As a result, scholars have primarily focused on the economic aims of sub-imperialist agents, often neglecting inherent political and geopolitical motives. Sub-imperialism, however, has both economic and political goals. As demonstrated in this case study, India's sub-imperialist engagement in Nepal is not solely motivated by the desire to exploit Nepal's resources for economic gains. While this remains one of the main motives, Nepal's strategic location and its position in the international system—regardless of how weak it might be—also play a critical role in India's actions in Nepal. In other words, Nepal is not merely a hinterland for fulfilling India's economic interests; it is also an independent nation-state with geopolitical significance. Thus, a comprehensive understanding of sub-imperialism should entail factors beyond just economic interests.

Finally, it is worth highlighting how Indian sub-imperialism in Nepal is neither new nor unique. India has exerted similar economic and political pressure on several other South Asian countries, particularly Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Bhutan, and the Maldives. This pattern adds another layer of depth to understanding India's sub-imperialism in the South Asian region. India is clearly guided by the perception that it can only establish and maintain an unequal relationship with its neighbouring countries if it succeeds in establishing and consolidating its hegemonic power over them. For that, the recognition of India's hegemony by the major world powers is essential, and so far, India has been successful in receiving that recognition.

In an attempt to expand its dominance in the region, India has been increasingly displaying hostility towards Pakistan, with its threats escalating in recent years. India's aim seems to coerce Pakistan into accepting a subordinate position, thereby further expanding its regional dominance. While it is unlikely, a potential submission of Pakistan will create a challenge for other South Asian countries to resist India's drive for regional hegemony. It is worth noting that India's actions in this regard are not limited to the regional sphere. The United States has become involved as part of the price for securing India's full cooperation in encircling China. While India, with the help of the United States, intends to expand its global

influence and simultaneously consolidate its regional power, China has its own hegemonic vision for South Asia. With initiatives like the BRI and associated dependency and debt, less powerful countries in South Asia are caught in a double trap from both India and China. As both compete for influence and dominance in the region, an intensified hegemonic confrontation between China and India in South Asia is highly probable.

8.2 Defying Dependency and Sub-imperialist Aggression

One important aspect to note about the India–Nepal sub-imperialist structure is how it has been consistently defied and challenged. The narrative of contemporary sub-imperialism remains incomplete without incorporating the stories of defiance and resistance. On one hand, grassroots movements, civil society organisations, and international advocacy networks have emerged to challenge the exploitative practices associated with resource appropriation and advocate for more equitable and sustainable resource management. On the other hand, political entities bearing the burden of sub-imperialist aggression have resorted to defiance and resistance whenever such options are available.

As is apparent from this, as well as previous chapters, the relationship between Nepali political actors and the Indian establishment has been historically marked by both cooperation and conflict, as well as obedience and defiance. Nepali political actors have, at times, quietly complied with Indian micromanagement. However, they have also resisted the interference and asserted their agency. This has involved utilising various political tools at their disposal, such as leveraging popular sentiment against India, engaging in diplomatic manoeuvring, and even resorting to confrontational tactics. In other words, contemporary India–Nepal relations, or India’s sub-imperialism in Nepal, not only reflect dependency and domination but also defiance, efforts to form alternative alliances, and an aspiration to break free from the deep-rooted domination.

As documented throughout this thesis, Nepal has managed to successfully push back against Indian pressure in several cases. Even though the large power asymmetry between the two countries and Nepal’s vast economic dependence on India have limited Nepal’s ability to challenge India’s influence and control fully, Nepal has still made efforts to assert its sovereignty. For a long time, Nepal has relied on resisting Indian pressure as a strategy for survival and a means of coping with external influence. Nepal’s assertion of agency demonstrates the significance of both agency and autonomy in its bilateral relations with India. Regime changes and domestic political dynamics in both countries have also influenced the relationship between Nepal and India. At times, Nepal has garnered support from various Indian domestic actors—including the media, civil society, opposition parties, and non-profit organisations—while manoeuvring some of its most challenging confrontations with its powerful southern neighbour.²⁰³

Nepal’s resistance to Indian interference is not a new phenomenon. Nepal has long sought to break free from India’s domination. Despite being a relatively small

²⁰³ As societies, India and Nepal share religious, cultural, and linguistic similarities. The people-to-people relationship is also strong and largely cordial. Indian and Nepali civil society and non-governmental organisations maintain close ties, work jointly on many social and environmental issues, and share a long history of cooperation. Social and political movements in both countries also maintain cooperation and draw inspiration from each other. Therefore, the India that is being referred to in the sub-imperialist context is predominantly the Indian political and bureaucratic establishments. This encompasses the various branches of government, political parties, and the civil service that hold power and decision-making authority within India.

country, Nepal has demonstrated a remarkable determination to assert its sovereignty and pursue its own interests at various historical junctures. One early example of Nepal's effort to release itself from India's grip came in the 1970s when it successfully sent back 17 out of the 18 Indian military camps from its northern border. This move was seen as a major victory for Nepal and a sign that it was willing to stand up to India and defend its sovereignty.²⁰⁴

Even before that, in 1962, when war erupted between India and China, Nepal chose to remain neutral and did not take sides (Acharya 2019). For India, Nepal's neutrality was a difficult pill to swallow. India has long viewed Nepal as part of its sphere of influence and anticipated that Nepal would support it in the conflict. Nepal's decision to remain neutral signalled a clear challenge to India's regional dominance. Despite India's disappointment, Nepali leadership at the time had understood that taking sides in a conflict between the two powerful neighbours could have had disastrous consequences for Nepal. By remaining neutral, Nepal protected its sovereignty and avoided getting caught up in a conflict in which it had no direct stakes. Nepal's decision to stay neutral in the 1962 China–India war was a clear message that while Nepal was willing to maintain close relations with both China and India, it was nonetheless determined to chart its own course as an independent nation and pursue its own interests, even when that meant challenging dominant powers in the region.

In the previous chapters, I discussed how Nepali political actors, at times, resisted India's pressure, particularly its meddling and micromanagement in the political domain. For instance, Nepal's 2015 constitution was promulgated, even though India sent its top diplomat to Kathmandu, who threatened Nepali leaders not to promulgate the new constitution without India's consent (see Chapter 6). When Nepali political actors defied New Delhi's orders, India imposed an economic blockade on Nepal. Instead of giving in to India's pressure, as it had often done in the past, in 2015, the Nepali leadership refused to bow down and endured the mass suffering caused by the blockade. In addition, both as a symbolic move and as an attempt to find an alternative trade route, Nepal reached out to China and signed several trade and transit agreements. These agreements were meant to end Nepal's sole and perpetual trade dependency on India. For the Nepali political class, who had been lulled by India for decades, knotting new ties with China was tantamount to an act of rebellion.

Another major example of defiance from Nepali political actors was demonstrated during the 2006 political upheavals. As *Jana Andolan II* was at its peak, the political climate in Nepal was rapidly turning against the monarchy. Street protestors had begun to demand the abolition of the monarchy and the restoration of full democracy in Nepal as a democratic republic. Despite this, India actively lobbied in favour of the monarchy and sought to preserve it, at least in some form (see Chapter 6). India stood by the crumbling monarchy until the last minute (Shrestha 2012). India did so even when it was clear that the monarchy in Nepal had become obsolete and was beyond redemption, primarily due to its repeated authoritarian ambitions. However, despite India's active lobbying and pressure to save the monarchy, Nepali political forces were adamant about getting rid of it. Ultimately, Nepal became a federal democratic republic, and despite India's interference, Nepali political forces were successful in abolishing the 240-year-old monarchy.

²⁰⁴ Interview with Sudheer Sharma (02.08.2017).

Similarly, after years of protracted negotiations, Nepal's major political parties came together and reached a consensus to promulgate a new constitution in 2015. As I discussed in Chapter 6, India used several strategies to shape Nepal's new constitution in its favour. Among others, restoring Nepal's constitutional identity as a Hindu nation was one of its top priorities. India also took a keen interest in the state restructuring process and the demarcation of Nepal's new provinces. In September 2015, as Nepal's Constituent Assembly was about to declare the new constitution, India dispatched a special envoy to Kathmandu. The envoy threatened senior Nepali leaders to stop the constitution promulgation process. Once again, Nepal's major political parties defied India's interference in Nepal's internal politics and continued with the scheduled constitution promulgation plan. In many respects, for Nepali political forces, promulgating the new constitution without receiving a green signal from New Delhi was an unusual and defiant act.

Dismayed by Nepal's defiance, India imposed an economic blockade on Nepal. An economic blockade was a proven strategy that India also used in the past to achieve its goals in Nepal. Whenever New Delhi was under the impression that its grip on Nepal was loosening or that Nepali rulers were independently exercising their domestic and foreign affairs, economic sanctions were used as 'taming' strategies. However, Nepal responded differently to the 2015 blockade. Instead of giving in to India's pressure, Nepali political forces showed unprecedented unity and resisted the blockade.

As two key informants argued, India had believed that the blockade would lead to a rise in anti-government sentiment in Nepal, prompting disillusioned Nepalis to take to the streets to overthrow the government. In the chaos that would follow, the new constitution issued without New Delhi's consent would also become irrelevant. Ultimately, Nepal would take a new political course, and India would be invited to facilitate the new political transition.²⁰⁵ This, however, did not happen. People came to the streets in Nepal, but their target this time was not their government, but India.

Furthermore, instead of negotiating with India and complying with New Delhi's terms, Nepal reached out to China for an alternative route of transit passage. As a result, Nepal and China signed several trade and transit agreements, and goods began to enter Nepal through the northern border. These new agreements with China were not only symbolic but also signalled a paradigm shift in Nepal's foreign policy. These agreements also ended the perception that India was Nepal's only option as a transit route and trade and investment partner.²⁰⁶ An increasing trade between China and Nepal also made India more anxious and insecure about its neighbours joining hands with China (Sharma 2019: 97).

Traditionally, India was not accustomed to receiving this degree of resistance from Nepal. Its dissipating influence on Nepal, particularly in the later years of the post-conflict political transition, was interpreted by some sections of the Indian intelligentsia as India's foreign policy failure in the region. As a key informant put it:

India considers Nepal—South Asia in general, but particularly Nepal—within its traditional domain. But now, their understanding is that Nepal is slowly slipping out of their hands, and they want to increase that grip in every possible way.²⁰⁷

²⁰⁵ Interview with an expert key informant and a senior political leader (interview year 2017, names and interview dates redacted).

²⁰⁶ Interview with Rajan Bhattarai (13.07.2017).

²⁰⁷ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

As I mentioned earlier, China has its own economic and strategic interests in Nepal, although its influence has not been as colossal as India's. Nonetheless, Chinese influence has steadily increased in recent years. For instance, despite India's extensive lobbying against it, China persuaded Nepal to join the BRI. In 2018, a Chinese company was awarded the contract to build Nepal's largest hydroelectricity project without a tender process.²⁰⁸

Supporting Nepal during crises or when ties with India have soured has been a Chinese strategy to extend its influence in Nepal. Nepal has also used its increased affinity with China to diversify its foreign relations and end its deep-rooted dependency on India. In contrast to India's more aggressive approach, China has taken a relatively cautious and observant stance. However, the effects of China's growing engagement in Nepal are yet to be seen.

8.2.1 Strategies to Minimise India's Interference: Advocacy of Sovereign Equality and Diversification of Foreign Relations

Particularly after India's increased interference in the post-conflict years, Nepal has sought to assert its sovereignty in its relationship with India by advocating for the principle of equal sovereignty (PTI 2021). The concept of equal sovereignty asserts that, despite differences in size, population, or economic power, all countries are equal in terms of their sovereign status and the right to self-determination. The concept of 'equal sovereignty' that Nepal has advocated shares similarities with the principle of sovereign equality enshrined in the UN Charter of 1945, which maintains that all states are equal before international law, no matter the size of their territory, population, economy or military. Bishnu Poudel elaborated on what the principle of equal sovereignty meant in the context of India and Nepal:

The relationship between Nepal and India is a relationship between two neighbouring countries. Geographically, our sizes differ, and so does our population. Our capacities might also be different. However, we are two independent sovereign nations of equal status. As independent sovereign nations, the relationship between our two countries should be based on mutual benefit and equality.²⁰⁹

Particularly during the peak of Indian interference and micromanagement, Nepali political actors increased their calls for equal sovereignty in international forums, public interviews, and diplomatic engagements with India. This period saw a concerted effort by Nepali political actors to assert Nepal's autonomy and sovereign rights. Nepal's approach to sovereign equality emphasised fostering a relationship with India grounded in mutual respect and adherence to international norms and bilateral agreements. Though not always successful, by doing this, Nepal sought to ensure that both nations interacted as equal partners.

In addition, diversification of foreign relations became one of Nepal's strategies to minimise Indian influence and interference. Nepal maintains diplomatic relations with 183 countries worldwide (TKP 2024) and is an old and active member of the United Nations. Despite its limited size and power and being sandwiched between two global powers, India and China, the country sees itself as a significant participant in the international community. Intending to build relationships

²⁰⁸ The Budhi Gandaki hydropower project, with an estimated capacity of 1200 MW, was awarded to the China state-owned Gezhouba Group Corporation in 2018. However, the contract was scrapped in 2022 after the Chinese company failed to make any progress on the project (see Lamsal 2022).

²⁰⁹ Interview with Bishnu Poudel (13.07.2017).

beyond its immediate neighbours, Nepal, for instance, actively engages in multilateral platforms such as the United Nations, Non-Aligned Movement (NAM), and the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC).

In recent years, Nepal has made further efforts to diversify foreign relations, partly as a strategy to reduce India's influence and its dependency on India. In 2016, Nepal, for instance, signed a Trade and Transit Agreement with China, which offered access to Chinese ports as an alternative to Indian routes. The proposed Nepal–China railway under the BRI is another significant step aimed at reducing Nepal's 'India-lockedness' (Poudel 2022). While the full impact of the BRI is yet to be seen, the act of joining the pact itself was, in a sense, an act of defiance for Nepal. Similarly, Nepal's participation in initiatives such as the South Asian Free Trade Agreement and collaboration with the BIMSTEC have also aimed at diversifying trade and lessening its dependency on India.

Nepal has been selective in its participation in these international platforms. For instance, in 2018, Nepal declined to participate in the India-led BIMSTEC Field Training Military Exercise, a joint military exercise of BIMSTEC member states. By declining to participate in the joint military exercise, Nepal signalled that it was not interested in becoming part of any military alliances in the region. In response, India's Army Chief Bipin Rawat said that countries like Nepal could not de-link themselves from India and that any affinity with China was temporary (Kulkarni 2018). New Delhi's interpretation was that Beijing guided Nepal in its decision not to participate in the joint military exercises. However, Nepal has also avoided forming any military alliances with China.

Particularly during the years of political transition, when India's interference in Nepal was extensive and its actions harsh and ruthless, ordinary Nepalis, too, resisted that vehemently. During these years, there were several anti-India protests in Nepal. At times, Indian diplomats faced black flag displays or were even physically assaulted (Nayak 2012: 137). In 2009, Nepal's then Prime Minister Pushpa Kamal Dahal 'Prachanda' resigned from his position after failing to dismiss the Nepal Army chief, who was strongly backed by India. In the aftermath, he called for a campaign for 'national independence'. He insisted that the unequal bilateral relationship between the two countries, the trade deficit, border disputes, and India's engagement in Nepal's internal politics had to be challenged (Jha 2012: 342). Prachanda's so-called campaign did not gain momentum as he soon kept himself busy in the usual power politics, but the message he delivered underlined Nepal's unwillingness to readily accept India's interference and its dominant position in the region.

In summary, Nepal has strongly resisted India's sub-imperialist domination, and this resistance continues. As already discussed, Nepal's efforts to break free from India's domination are ongoing and multifaceted. While India is an important neighbour for Nepal in many respects, its sub-imperialist and hegemonic tendencies have been actively challenged and resisted in Nepal. Despite the hurdles and failures, Nepal and its people have remained steadfast in asserting their sovereignty and pursuing their national interests, even if it has meant challenging India's dominance in the region. Thus, Nepal is not only a case of India's sub-imperialism but also a strong example of resistance against it.

8.3 India's Domestic Woes: Suppression of Dissent and Internal Colonialism

The literature on Indian foreign policy reveals a complex and often contradictory portrait of the Indian state, a state that is simultaneously constrained by its internal and regional conflicts and increasingly assertive in its global engagements. As Happymon Jacob has often portrayed in his works, India's unresolved conflict with Pakistan, and its inherent nature as a reactive and internally conflicted state, has produced a 'no war, no peace' scenario that has exacted a heavy institutional and human toll (see Jacob 2018a, 2018b).

In his view, this persistent state of tension limits India's strategic flexibility and fosters a securitised environment that shapes both domestic and foreign policy. Furthermore, Jacob critiques the centralised nature of foreign policy decisionmaking in New Delhi, which often marginalises the perspectives and security concerns of India's border states.

However, the tendency to paint a rosy image of a rising India is also common. Some scholars, such as Raja Mohan and Sreeram Chaulia, depict an India that is recalibrating its traditional non-alignment into a flexible and pragmatic engagement with multiple major powers (see Mohan 2012a, 2012b, Chaulia 2011). In contemporary India, these scholars see a state that is becoming more ambitious and confident, shedding past hesitations, and increasingly willing to act as a responsible stakeholder in global governance. The dominant framing of India's foreign policy as one of 'strategic autonomy'—often interpreted as challenging Western hegemony—has gained currency in such accounts. However, for those of us who take a more critical perspective, this so-called strategic autonomy appears to be little more than what Marini described decades ago as *antagonistic cooperation*: a relationship between a dominant imperialist power and a subordinate or sub-imperialist state, in which collaboration is shaped by underlying tensions and asymmetrical power dynamics (see Marini 1972).

Rather than representing a clear defiance of the West, India's foreign policy, in this reading, reflects a strategic alignment where both parties pursue their interests—often in ways that reinforce existing hierarchies. The argument that India is fundamentally challenging the West is, therefore, unconvincing.

Examining how contemporary India functions within its borders is equally crucial for understanding its sub-imperialist engagement in the neighbourhood. This examination should also explore the Indian establishment's interactions with its own people, particularly its treatment of religious and linguistic minority groups, indigenous populations distant from the urban centres, and those who dissent from the dominant Hindutva rhetoric. While doing so, one can see that the challenges Nepal faces in its interactions with the Indian establishment have significant parallels to the issues different Indian demographics encounter with their government. In other words, understanding how the Indian establishment interacts with specific segments of its domestic population can provide valuable insights into comprehending its malevolent involvement in Nepal.

Contemporary India is deeply divided and has largely abandoned values such as openness, religious tolerance, and secularism, which it once held dear. In its ambitious pursuit to counter China's political and economic influence and establish itself as a dominant regional and global power, India has adopted strategies that have tarnished its previous image. Under the Bharatiya Janata Party's leadership, India has sought to redefine its identity through Hindutva fundamentalist ideology

while also promoting extractivist corporate capitalism. The face of today's India is also marked by inherent confusion and contradictions. As Deepak Prakash Bhatta explained:

In recent years, India's own democratic space has been shrinking, the developmental space is narrow, and technologically, they are not as sound as the Chinese. They look confused. Now, especially under Narendra Modi's leadership, it seems that all they are seeking is to be America's junior partner.²¹⁰

As mentioned earlier, the challenges faced by Nepal at the hands of the Indian political class bear similarities to the challenges that many ordinary Indians encounter in contemporary India. For years, activists and scholars like Arundhati Roy, Ashutosh Varshney, and Siddharth Varadarajan have analysed and critiqued the problems facing India under the BJP rule. The Indian ruling class faces accusations of repression, exploitation, marginalisation, and worsening economic inequality. Indian governments have been accused of formulating policies and actions that are often biased against certain groups, which has often led to discrimination and exclusion from opportunities and resources. The moral decay of the Indian establishment is evident in its mistreatment of minorities, including Muslims, Dalits, and other marginalised groups, who have been subjected to systemic discrimination and violence for years.

It is also increasingly evident that the Indian state structure or the Indian 'development model' is designed to serve a particular corporate interest (Bhalerao 2021) and to largely cater to its sub-imperialist motives. Those who voice dissent have even accused the Indian establishment of engaging in oppressive practices and perpetuating a form of internal colonisation. For instance, writing in 2011, Arundhati Roy, a prominent Indian activist, argued:

Almost from the moment India became a sovereign nation it turned into a colonial power, annexing territory, waging war. It has never hesitated to use military interventions to address political problems—Kashmir, Hyderabad, Goa, Nagaland, Manipur, Telangana, Assam, Punjab, the Naxalite uprising in West Bengal, Bihar, Andhra Pradesh and now across the tribal areas of central India. Tens of thousands have been killed with impunity, hundreds of thousands tortured. All of this behind the benign mask of democracy.

Who have these wars been waged against? Muslims, Christians, Sikhs, Communists, Tribals and, most of all, against the poor, for the most part Dalits, who dare to question their lot instead of accepting the crumbs that are flung at them. It's hard not to see the Indian State as an essentially upper-caste Hindu State (regardless of which party is in power) which harbours a reflexive hostility towards the 'other'. One that in true colonial fashion sends the Nagas and Mizos to fight in Chhattisgarh, Sikhs to Kashmir, Kashmiris to Orissa, Tamilians to Assam and so on (Roy 2011: 123–124).

Over the years, the BJP-led Indian establishment has crafted and aggressively canvassed the narrative of an economically robust and politically relentless India. As scholars such as Roy and others have argued, behind the carefully crafted image of a rising India—with impressive growth and a rejuvenated sense of Indian glory—lies a harsh reality: a country that exploits its own people, commodifies natural resources, suppresses dissenting voices and minorities, and practices internal colonialism. Dey (2019), for instance, argues that India's internal colonialism is visible in three different forms: the subordination of ethno-racial and non-Hindu religious groups, the subordination of areas not dominated by the descendants of

²¹⁰ Interview with Deepak Prakash Bhatta (17.08.2017).

Ancestral North Indians of the North and West Indian states and the subordination of rural populations by the urban elites and Anglicised India.

Indian governments have consistently promoted extractivist economic practices despite the suffering they have caused the people of India. According to a 2011 study, around 21 million people have been displaced in India due to extractivist projects, and of these, more than 40% of displacements have happened in rural indigenous communities (Singh Negi & Ganguly 2011). Similarly, large-scale land grabs and plundering of natural resources have been increasingly common in contemporary India (see, for instance, Levien 2018, Chettri 2020).

In short, India's domestic and regional policies—which are largely shaped by a sub-imperialist motive—characterise a systemic exploitation of its own marginalised groups and hinterlands. A similar approach is reflected in its engagements with neighbouring countries like Nepal. This duality—internal marginalisation paired with external dominance—defines the behaviours and policy choices of the Indian ruling class.

8.4 Unpredictable Rising Powers and the End of Emancipatory South–South Cooperation?

India's sub-imperialist engagement in Nepal and its internal colonial practices can be analysed and theoretically linked to the broader context of South–South relations and the behaviour of the so-called rising powers of the Global South. The economic and political rise of a handful of countries of the Global South has been apparent and indisputable. BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa), for instance, have emerged as a significant global group of rising powers. The formation of the New Development Bank and the Contingent Reserve Arrangement by BRICS has created alternative channels for funding and lending. In this way, they have challenged the dominance of Western financial institutions such as the IMF and the World Bank. BRICS' collective voice has also grown stronger in international forums, such as the UN and the World Bank, where they have been advocating for reforms to transform existing global institutions and governance structures into more inclusive and representative platforms that address the concerns of the Global South. The BRICS are also reportedly working on unveiling their own currency and challenging the dominance of the US Dollar (Sullivan 2023).

However, as I discussed in Chapter 3, despite their growing influence and some effort to create alternative avenues for cooperation and development, the BRICS countries still largely adhere to the neoliberal path laid out by Western hegemonic powers. Like the Western powers, BRICS prioritise economic growth and market-oriented policies over social welfare programs and redistribution of wealth. This neoliberal model, focused on free markets and trade liberalisation, has often exacerbated societal inequalities and contributed to environmental degradation. It has caused harm to communities and ecosystems. Moreover, the BRICS have not yet openly challenged the Western domination of the global governance and decision-making system. Rather, they have sought to complement the existing global governance structures by ensuring their representation. In other words, the BRICS still adhere largely to the Western neoliberal model and have not yet challenged the prevailing hegemonic structures that shape global politics and the global economy.

As scholars studying contemporary sub-imperialism have noted (see, for instance, Çağlı 2009, Bond 2015, Valencia 2017, Bond et al. 2021), rising powers of the Global South have demonstrated a clear tendency to exercise sub-imperialism

in their regions. As I examined throughout this and previous chapters, India's actions in Nepal clearly appear to confirm that proposition. Sub-imperialism seems to help emerging countries like India accelerate their political and economic rise. Once this rise is achieved, it appears that the practice nonetheless continues with the aim of consolidating the sub-imperialist status, expanding the scope and outreach, and potentially moving towards global hegemony.

In India's sub-imperialism in Nepal, a rising power mentality is also visible. That mentality shatters the hopes and dreams of an emancipatory world order once expected to be led by and begin from the developing world. Rising powers' sub-imperialist aspirations also shatter the hopes held by the optimists who saw ample promise and continued to have faith in South–South Cooperation as an emancipatory and noble practice (see, for instance, Mawdsley 2012, Carmody 2013, Cheru 2016, Muhr 2016). This raises two key questions in contemporary international relations: first, how do these rising powers behave in the international system? Second, how do they interact with their weaker neighbours? As is the case with India and Nepal, the asymmetrical relationship between a large, emerging power and a smaller, economically dependent state, in which the former's influence shapes a range of issues in the latter's affairs, is a pertinent issue in contemporary international relations with ample geopolitical and economic implications.

Furthermore, the India–Nepal case also demonstrates that both the concept and practice of South–South Cooperation demand a more critical and thorough examination. As shown in this and previous chapters, India's actions in Nepal do not reflect typical South–South Cooperation. In fact, the two countries could have been a remarkable example of such cooperation. However, India's clear intent to establish Nepal as one of its client states or sub-imperialist destinations has hindered that possibility. As a result, the relationship between the two countries is one of sub-imperialist dependency. In other words, India benefits from Nepal's resources and controls Nepali markets to accumulate surplus. Similarly, Nepal relies on India for multiple critical issues. As this thesis has demonstrated, political stability in Nepal is largely affected by India's actions and inactions. Economically, Nepal depends on India and receives financial assistance in the form of aid and loans. In addition, India is Nepal's main supplier of manufactured goods and the primary route for international trade and transit.

Unsurprisingly, there is an alarming trade deficit between the two countries, and India also benefits from Nepali cheap labour, including more than 32,000 Nepali men serving in the Indian Army. In short, the contemporary India–Nepal relationship is marked by deep dependency, ongoing economic and political dominance, and significant power asymmetry and inequality. As sceptics have rightly argued, the rhetoric of South–South Cooperation adopted by the rising powers in the Global South has proven to be mere rhetoric. It appears to be aimed at not challenging, but securing a stronger position within the US-centred world order (see, for instance, Vanaik 2013, Bond & Garcia 2015, Bond et al., 2021).

The India–Nepal case serves as a reminder that while the concept of South–South Cooperation is not sinister in itself, it is necessary to recognise that it is not a one-size-fits-all concept either. In other words, it requires an understanding of each participating country's specific contexts. This includes considering the unique social, political, economic, and historical factors that shape the relationship between countries. It is equally essential to understand its complexities and limitations, especially when there is a power asymmetry between participating countries, as has been the case between Nepal and India.

Along with the necessity for a deeper and more nuanced understanding of South–South Cooperation, it is also important to focus on South–South conflicts. Although South–South Cooperation has received significant academic and policy interest, conflicts and tensions between developing countries in the Global South have received little attention, especially within the domain of global development studies. As the tumultuous co-existence between Nepal and India has shown, South–South conflicts can arise from various issues, including power asymmetry, territorial disputes, resource interests, ideological differences, and geopolitical tensions.

As I discussed in the previous section with the example of Nepal challenging India’s dominance, there is a glimmer of optimism in the defiance and resistance to sub-imperialism and regional hegemony from within the Global South. In the long run, this could pave the way for an alternative, anti-imperialist future. As countries and people bearing the burden of chronic dependency, sub-imperialism, and internal colonialism voice their concerns and demand change, a transformative movement may emerge. This movement could change existing relations by challenging prevailing power structures and promoting a more equitable and just regional and global landscape. However, this would require extensive collaboration and solidarity among the developing countries caught in sub-imperialist traps, as well as among social and grassroots movements aiming for greater empowerment and self-determination for the Global South.

8.5 Chapter Summary: Sub-Imperialist Framework for Understanding Rising Power Behaviour

This chapter focused on the theoretical underpinnings that help explain contemporary India–Nepal relations. The chapter began with a discussion of India’s historical and strategic engagement with Nepal and moved on to frame the relationship within the framework of sub-imperialism. I argued that India wielded influence over Nepali politics, markets, and natural resources, essentially treating Nepal as one of its sub-imperialist domains. The exploitation and control of Nepal aligned with India’s goals of enhancing its regional dominance and elevating its global status. With numerous examples, I also showed that while India entrapped Nepal in a chronic dependency, it was itself tangled in a somewhat similar relationship with the United States. As discussed in this chapter, American companies have invested heavily in India, where they benefit from the country’s low labour costs. There is a substantial trade deficit between the two countries, and India depends heavily on the US, among others, for security and defence. In addition, India is part of the US-led Indo-Pacific strategy, which aims to strengthen India’s role as the US’s junior partner in South Asia.

The chapter also highlighted instances of Nepal resisting India’s sub-imperialist manoeuvres—asserting its sovereignty and challenging India’s dominance. I linked India’s sub-imperialism in South Asia to its internal colonial practices, which favoured neoliberal corporate capitalism and pro-Hindutva politics at the expense of democratic and secular values. The chapter concluded with a discussion on the role of rising powers in the Global South, particularly the BRICS, in shaping the international political and economic orders. I emphasised that instead of challenging Western hegemony, the rising powers have embraced extractive and oppressive foreign policies, contributing to the maintenance of the neoliberal regime that thrives on a reckless expansion of extractivist corporate capitalism. This clearly undermined the aspirations of developing countries for a New International

Economic Order and posed a formidable challenge to inclusive and emancipatory South–South Cooperation. However, the prospects for a more equitable international order may ultimately arise from anti-sub-imperialist and anti-hegemonic resistance led by social and grassroots movements in the Global South.

9. Mediation, Micromanagement, and an Era of Peace Dependency?

In the previous chapter, I adopted a broader perspective to examine India's involvement in Nepal. I positioned contemporary India–Nepal relations within the sub-imperialist framework and argued that India's extensive presence and interference in Nepal could be explained in terms of its two primary sub-imperialist motives: first, keeping Nepal under its sphere of influence by perpetuating economic and political subjugation, and second, securing its access to Nepal's valuable natural resources and Nepali markets by micromanaging Nepali politics and weeding out other international players from the field.

In this chapter, my focus is somewhat narrower and more specific. As I discussed in the previous chapters, there is considerable confusion regarding India's role as a mediator in Nepal's peace process, as well as its emerging identity as a self-proclaimed mediator and regional 'peacemaker'. My goal in this chapter is to address that issue. In other words, I adopt a peace research perspective to address two critical questions: 1. How can we interpret India's role as a peace mediator, and where do its actions fit within a 'mediation spectrum'?, 2. How can we interpret its engagements in Nepal's peace process and political transition through the lens of peace and mediation research?

I begin the chapter by examining India's role as an informal mediator or facilitator of the Nepali peace process. Next, drawing from the mediation literature, I analyse whether India contributed to making the Maoist armed insurgency 'ripe' for resolution. I argue that the Nepali peace process began and accelerated not because of external influence or coercion from India or any other third party, but because of a combination of two scenarios: a mutually hurting stalemate (MHS) and a mutually enticing opportunity (MEO) for the Maoists and the SPA, and to some extent, for India as well.

To construct a plausible theoretical explanation, this chapter builds on the arguments presented in the earlier chapters and introduces the concept of 'peace dependency.' Peace dependency, I argue, is a state of perpetual reliance on former peace mediators/facilitators for resolving any subsequent conflicts. This reliance enables the former mediator (or the states they represent) to strengthen their influence, serve vested interests, or interfere in the internal political affairs of mediation recipients. I used the Nepali peace process as a case study to illustrate how Nepal became dependent on India for post-conflict peace and how India gained influence in subsequent political negotiations in Nepal. Theoretically, the concept of 'peace dependency' enriches the mediation literature and is particularly helpful for analysing and evaluating the complexities of post-conflict situations. I conclude the chapter by briefly discussing three key lessons from the Nepali peace process, which could offer valuable insights for practitioners in mediation and peacebuilding.

9.1 India as an Informal Mediator of the Nepali Peace Process

As I discussed in Chapter 4, the dubious role that India played during the Maoist armed insurgency (1996–2006) is well-known (see, for instance, Shah 2004, Mishra 2004, Bhattarai 2005, Whelpton 2005, Whitfield 2008, Upreti 2009, Destradi 2010, Sharma 2013, Adhikari 2017, Dhungel 2019). Throughout the armed insurgency, India maintained parallel engagements with both the Nepali state and the Maoists. On one hand, India declared the Maoists to be a terrorist organisation, supplied arms and ammunition to Nepali security forces, and trained them to crush the rebels by force. On the other hand, it also provided tacit support to the Maoists by letting them operate freely from India and providing unofficial shelter to prominent Maoist leaders in various Indian cities²¹¹.

Against this backdrop, in this study, I explored India's role in the background negotiations that led to the 12-Point Understanding (Chapter 5) and analysed India's influence in the events before and after the 12-Point Understanding as well as the CPA (Chapters 6 and 7). In Chapter 5, I discussed how the Maoists and parliamentary political parties came together to defeat their common enemy—the autocratic monarchy—in the wake of King Gyanendra's autocratic move in February 2005. In the same chapter, I detailed how the Six-Point Agreement signed in Nepal's Rolpa district created the foundation for the 12-Point Understanding and, ultimately, for *Jana Andolan II* and the peace process.

Throughout these processes, locating India's role has been challenging, primarily for two reasons. First, India had multiple engagements in Nepal on several levels. For instance, there were high-level political engagements, including leaders' visits and the dispatch of envoys and diplomats. However, Indian bureaucracy, security, and intelligence operations were also typical and regular. Second, India's engagement, whether political or non-political, was largely opaque and covert. As a result, evaluating how these engagements influenced political processes has proved to be a challenging task.

India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition has been described in various ways, including as 'unclear and questionable' (Subedi & Bhattarai 2017: 95), a facilitative one (Destradi 2010: 17, Shrestha 2012: 211, Ghimire 2018a: 6), and as an example of tacit support (Whitfield 2008: 6). Some scholars have also designated India the title of a mediator—a mediator that took on the job intending to persuade the rebels to shun arms and to join mainstream politics (see, for instance, Poudel 2018: 7). It has also been argued that the Nepali peace process and post-conflict political transformation would not have been possible without the Indian support (Whitfield 2008: 6).

India's eventual involvement in a future peace process in Nepal was predicted during the armed conflict and the early years of the peace process (see, for instance, Mishra 2004, Janjua 2007). While India's role as a facilitator and informal peace mediator has generally been accepted, its self-projected image as a promoter of democracy has been bluntly rejected (see, for instance, Destradi 2010, Anderson 2014, H.B. Jha 2014, Bhattarai 2018: 13). Destradi (2010), for instance, argued that India's actions in pre-mediation and post-mediation scenarios in Nepal were guided mainly by its desire to become a benevolent hegemon in the region. Similarly, Musachhio (2018: 40) claimed that India was using democracy and development narratives merely as soft-power tactics to perpetuate its hegemony

²¹¹ India did arrest some mid-level Maoist leaders and handed a few of them over to Nepali authorities. However, these incidents were sparse and largely symbolic.

over Nepal.

Thus, as I already indicated, particularly from the perspective of peace and mediation research, there are two major dilemmas: first, where to place India's actions in the mediation spectrum, and second, how to interpret its engagements in the post-CPA years. Before addressing these questions, it is essential to determine the point of departure for the Nepali peace process. As I have already argued in previous chapters, the 12-Point Understanding signed in New Delhi on 5 November 2005 between the Maoists and the alliance of seven Nepali political parties, known as the Seven Party Alliance, was the actual beginning of the Nepali peace process. A remarkable characteristic of this peace process was that it began with an agreement or an understanding between two oppositional forces fighting to end King Gyanendra's direct rule in the country. The formal peace accord, the CPA, was signed a year later in November 2006 in Kathmandu. However, the 12-Point Understanding was essentially the *de facto* peace agreement that effectively ended the Maoist armed insurgency. Therefore, when examining India's role as a mediator in the Nepali peace process, it is important to first consider India's involvement in the 12-Point Understanding before exploring the subsequent political negotiations that followed.

As not all engagements are inherently focused on mediation, determining what qualifies as a mediation activity versus what should be excluded is also crucial. As I discussed in Chapter 3, a wide range of activities have been covered under the umbrella of mediation. For instance, Zartman & Touval (2007: 438) argue that mediators aim to help 'the parties to find a solution that they cannot find by themselves'. Similarly, Fisher (2001: 4) outlines mediation as a peaceful, non-binding, and non-coercive approach. Nevertheless, not all third-party interventions in the form of mediation are as benign as these statements.

Scholars who have looked at mediation practice from a foreign policy perspective have often noted that conflict mediation can very well be used as a foreign policy tool to serve foreign policy interests (see, for instance, Touval 1975, 1987, 1992) and that while some mediators could be considered 'pure mediators', a lot of today's conflicts are mediated by 'power mediators' as well. Great powers, colonial powers, and neighbouring states are typical examples of power mediators (Svensson 2007: 230). As this thesis has also documented, the manoeuvring space of power mediators is particularly broader, and to persuade the parties to obey, they can exercise a range of strategies and options, such as incentives and punishments, and even put pressure on them to accept a compromise (see Harris & Reilly 1998: 109).

In the eyes of powerful states, mediation as a foreign policy tool is arguably a prudent choice because they can use it to serve their own interests without causing too much suspicion and opposition (Touval 1992). Strategies that such mediators use could be both coercive as well as non-coercive (George 1991, Jakobsen 2016), and also hybrid in nature (Mac Ginty 2011, Mac Ginty & Richmond 2016). While mediation itself is construed to be a benign instrument, big powers can use it to serve their defensive and expansionist interests (Touval 1992: 232-33).

Given these theoretical propositions, India appears to be a strong candidate for the role of a 'power mediator' in Nepal. When the 12-Point Understanding was signed in New Delhi, Nepal was on the brink of becoming a failed state. The ongoing armed conflict and the authoritarian rule of the King had severely weakened the country. The spread of armed conflict and political instability in Nepal had started to impact India's interests as well. Against this backdrop, the 12-Point Understanding was virtually a rescue package that ended the protracted armed

conflict as well as the King's authoritarian rule. This raises an important question: Was India, as a power mediator, the mastermind behind the 12-Point Understanding that pushed Nepali political forces to come to the negotiating table and start a peace process?

As I discussed in Chapter 5, Indian politicians and diplomats have publicly claimed that they had a role in the safe landing of the armed insurgency in Nepal. There was indeed a strong need for India to resolve Nepal's armed conflict. As the strength of the Nepali Maoists grew and their connections with Indian Maoist groups and other Communist movements strengthened, the Indian establishment increasingly craved a solution. India was aware of the consequences of a potential 'spillage' of the Maoist armed insurgency and the challenges it would face once Nepal practically turned into a failed state. This motivation of India is of theoretical interest. In other words, was it with this motivation that India used informal mediation or facilitation as a foreign intervention tool that scholars such as Touval (1975, 1987, 1992) have argued?

It is also important to note that India's facilitation of the 12-Point Understanding and subsequent processes began when its relationship with Nepal's monarchy had deteriorated. When King Gyanendra assumed absolute power by staging a coup d'état on 1 February 2005, India appeared convinced that the King had done so under China's backing. Since many democracies, including the US, the UK, and India, condemned the King's move, King Gyanendra leaned on authoritarian regimes, such as China, for support. In the wake of the February 2005 move, the relationship between the Indian establishment and the Nepali monarchy soured not only because India was worried about a totalitarian regime in Nepal, but also because India perceived that if the monarchy was left untamed, China's influence in Nepal would be manifold.

In addition to the China factor, as the Maoist insurgency became more and more lethal during the King's direct rule, the mood in New Delhi gradually began to shift. The Indian establishment slowly recognised that the Maoist insurgency in Nepal was a political issue requiring a political solution to prevent further destabilisation of Nepal and the region. In the early years, India had labelled the Maoists as terrorists and supported Nepali forces in combating them. Under the King's command, when Nepali security forces stepped up their offensives against the rebels, senior Maoist leaders reached out to New Delhi seeking support. Already in 2002, the Maoists had sent a letter to Indian Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee, arguing that they were not a terrorist group but a political force and that they would not go against India's interests²¹² (Muni 2012: 320–21).

New Delhi's change in perspective on the Maoist insurgency is one thing, but its role as a mediator in uniting the Maoists and the SPA is something else entirely. As I showed in Chapter 5, while India did play a facilitative role in the background negotiations preceding the 12-Point Understanding, there is no credible evidence or indication that it played the role of a power mediator or that it used a coercive whip to compel the Maoists to renounce violence and the SPA to accept the political legitimacy of the Maoists. In fact, it was the polarisation of Nepal's politics in the wake of King Gyanendra's 2005 coup that had compelled the Maoists and the SPA to join hands and craft a new political roadmap.

²¹² Senior Maoist leader Dr Baburam Bhattarai later claimed that similar letters were sent to the UN, the US, China, and the UK. The purpose of such letters reportedly was to improve the Maoists' image, who were then internationally defamed as terrorists (see Khadka 2012). Dr Bhattarai completed a doctorate from an Indian university and maintained close ties with the Indian intelligentsia and members of various political factions.

However, this does not mean that India was totally absent from the scene. Senior Maoist leaders were in close contact with Indian leftist and communist parties that were part of the coalition government at the time. Similarly, the Nepali Congress party leaders who were in New Delhi for the talks with the Maoists were in close communication with senior leaders of the Indian National Congress Party, which was leading the Indian government at the time. As Sekhar Koirala recalled, the Indian establishment was well aware of the development brewing in the background and had seen drafts of the 12-Point Understanding.²¹³ Madhav Kumar Nepal also recalled how India had provided diplomatic and logistical arrangements for their visit to New Delhi at a time when travelling abroad was difficult for senior political leaders because of the King's direct rule.²¹⁴ Maoist Chairman Pushpa Kamal Dahal 'Prachanda' has also accepted that on numerous occasions, India played a facilitative role in the formation of the 12-Point Understanding and that without India's goodwill and facilitation, such an achievement would have been difficult to achieve (see, for instance, Pandey 2016). Since it was difficult for the Maoist leaders to travel to a third country because of an international travel ban, New Delhi was an ideal location to hold talks with the SPA leaders.

In short, India's facilitative role in the 12-Point Understanding process was largely constructive and useful as far as restoring peace and democracy in Nepal was concerned. India did not use the whip of power diplomacy to unite the Nepali opposition forces. Still, it facilitated an initiative for peace and democracy in Nepal that had begun in the form of the Six-Point Agreement in Nepal's Rolpa district in October 2005. Nevertheless, as I elaborated in previous chapters, India attempted to take undue ownership of the Nepali peace process and used it as an excuse to micromanage Nepal's internal politics. Goodwill aside, from a foreign policy perspective, facilitating the peace process in Nepal was one of the many ways for India to ensure that Nepal continued to be under its sphere of influence and that Nepali political actors operated under New Delhi's political guidance. This ultimately meant that the so-called special relationship between the two countries continued to exist, and the chains of dependency and power asymmetries further strengthened.

9.2 What Made the Maoist Insurgency 'Ripe' for Resolution?

Ripeness was another theoretical issue that I raised in Chapter 3. While I do not intend to question the concept of ripeness, in the case of Nepal's Maoist armed insurgency, I am interested in whether India played a role in making the conflict 'ripe' for resolution. How external actors, such as powerful neighbouring states, make conflicts ripe and ready for resolution or contribute to escalating or protracting them is a relevant topic in peace and mediation research as well as in international relations. The concept of 'ripeness' or ripeness theory (see, for instance, Zartman & Touval 1985, Zartman 1989, 2000, 2001) remains highly influential in peace and mediation research. In its simplest form, it advances the argument that conflicts are resolved only when they are 'ripe' for resolution. The so-called 'ripe moment' is often called a psychological state of conflicting parties that motivates them to engage in a mediated negotiation (see, for instance, Haass 1988, Rubin 1991, Stedman 1996, Pruitt 2005). Therefore, conflict management and resolution strategies should depend on the perception, creation, and use of such

²¹³ Interview with Sekhar Koirala (22.08.2017).

²¹⁴ Interview with Madhav Kumar Nepal (11.07.2017).

ripe moments (Zartman 1989).

In the aftermath of *Jana Andolan II*, as India's influence in Nepal increased significantly, both pro-India and India-sceptic views became increasingly noticeable in the country. It was common to see India involved in all significant political events, both past and present. As a result, India was portrayed as a 'grand designer' that united the Maoists and the SPA to resolve the armed conflict, and to abolish the increasingly unruly monarchy that was leaning more and more towards China. In other words, considering this narrative, by encouraging or pressuring the Maoists and the SPA to unite, India was attempting to make the Maoist insurgency 'ripe' for resolution.

The argument that India united the Maoists and the parliamentary parties to abolish the monarchy appears highly plausible on the surface. However, as I explained in previous chapters, this argument is flawed for several reasons. As my discussion in the previous chapters has also shown, India did facilitate the 12-Point Understanding, but its primary motivation for involvement in the post-2005 Nepali peace process and political transition was not for ending the monarchy or bringing democracy, peace, or stability to Nepal.

It is clear from India's post-conflict engagement in Nepal that India wanted the Maoist insurgency resolved for three main reasons. First, as already mentioned, India was experiencing the spillover effects of the Maoist insurgency, and it had begun interfering with its domestic security interests. India was concerned about the influence of Nepal's Maoist insurgency on its own Maoist movements, such as the Naxalites, particularly in the central and eastern parts of India. Nepal's Maoists demonstrated organisational success and a revolutionary narrative that inspired similar groups in India. Second, India was worried that the political and social chaos that the Maoist insurgency had brought to Nepal was slowly converting the country into a failed state. While India has traditionally sought to keep Nepal 'mildly unstable', it has a history of increasing its involvement and finding solutions when major crises arise. It did so in the 1950s, the 1990s, and also in the late 2000s. The historical pattern of India's engagement in Nepal strongly indicates that it prefers unstable states in its neighbourhood but not failed states.

Third, India quickly sensed that when the Maoists and the SPA were joining hands to fight against the King's direct rule, a peace process was imminent in Nepal and that it was already brewing along the way. While India did attempt to save the monarchy—at least in some form and until the last minute—it also supported the sprouting peace process in Nepal. As I explained in Chapters 5 and 6, India was increasingly interested in maintaining the status quo, with the Maoists joining peaceful politics and functioning like other parliamentary parties. Likewise, the monarchy would also be given a dignified role in post-conflict Nepal.

However, as the political climate rapidly escalated in Nepal in the mid-2000s, India began to realise that if the Maoist insurgency was not settled on time, its reverberating effects would damage its national security interests. That realisation marked a turning point in India's stance on the Nepali Maoists. In the new context, India viewed the Maoists not as a terrorist group to be eradicated through force, but as a political entity advocating for their rights and seeking to establish their place in the political landscape.

In addition to India's security and strategic interests, the presence of Indian communist parties in the coalition government and the connections that Nepali Maoists had cultivated within the Indian establishment influenced India's shift in its approach to the Nepali Maoists. Similarly, the Maoists and the SPA, aware of India's formidable presence in the region, had sought India's 'goodwill' for their

new roadmap for peace and democracy in Nepal.²¹⁵ Senior Maoist and SPA leaders had met with high-profile Indian politicians and briefed them about the political course they were taking. Even though Nepali politicians have often denied Indian involvement in the content of the 12-Point Understanding, there are some indications that India reviewed and influenced certain aspects of it (see, for instance, Muni 2012: 314–17). Nonetheless, India's role in the entire process was not that of a power mediator, but rather of an active and shrewd facilitator. In other words, there is no clear and credible evidence to suggest that India played a role in making the Maoist insurgency 'ripe' for resolution by exerting pressure on the Maoists and the SPA.

India's facilitation of the 12-Point Understanding was largely a tactical move. As I mentioned earlier, by late 2005, India had recognised that the Maoist-SPA coalition would shake up the political landscape in Nepal and that the end of the Maoist insurgency and the emergence of a peace process were inevitable. India tactfully saw an opportunity in this. By facilitating the road to an imminent peace process in Nepal, it could portray itself as a regional peace broker and an emerging South Asian peacemaker—an ideal credential for a rising and ambitious regional power like India. In addition, the Indian establishment of the time understood that by being involved in Nepal's peace process, India could increase its influence in Nepal and simultaneously chase off potential competitors. In other words, it could deliver a message to global superpowers, particularly the United States and China, that Nepal was firmly under India's influence, and whether it was a matter of war or peace, India prevailed in Nepal. This motivation aligns with the argument of some scholars that when nation-states seek to mediate a conflict, one reason is to 'prevent rival powers from intervening and expanding their influence' (Zartman & Touval 1996: 446).

To sum up, the idea that third parties, particularly influential foreign powers, can compel conflicting parties to join a peace process is not new. Mediation scholars, such as Aggestam (2002a, 2002b, 2005: 280) and Bercovitch (2002), for instance, have argued that third parties can influence and strengthen the conflicting parties' perception of a ripe moment, often by using power or communication. As a matter of fact, Nepal appears to be an ideal candidate for such an influence. However, as I discussed above, it was not India's, China's or any other third party's influence or coercion that triggered the peace process in Nepal. From the theoretical perspective of conflict resolution, the Nepali peace process was the outcome of a combination of two scenarios: a mutually hurting stalemate (MHS) and a mutually enticing opportunity (MEO) for the Maoists and the SPA, and to some extent, to India as well. In the next section, I will discuss how the MHS and MEO were instrumental in triggering the Nepali peace process.

9.3 Mutually Hurting Stalemate (MHS) and Mutually Enticing Opportunity (MEO) as Triggers of the Nepali Peace Process

Before King Gyanendra assumed direct rule in February 2005, the Maoists and parties in the SPA were rivals. The main parties of the SPA, such as the Nepali Congress and the CPN (UML), were often in government and had allowed lethal combative operations to suppress the Maoists. The Maoists, too, had mobilised their offensives against the parliamentary parties. The Maoists killed, abducted,

²¹⁵ Many of the leaders I talked to accepted that India's 'goodwill' was present in the 12-Point Understanding and the peace process that followed in its aftermath.

tortured, and displaced the parliamentary parties' party cadres in massive numbers. Ironically, the Maoists declared in their political documents that they were fighting to end the monarchy and make Nepal a people's republic; however, in practice, their main targets during much of the armed insurgency were the parliamentary parties and their cadres. In fact, until the 2005 Chunbang meeting, the Maoists' strategy was to build a 'patriotic' coalition with the monarchy and replace the parliamentary parties from the political scene. Senior Maoist leaders have accepted in interviews that they had been in touch with people from the royal palace for talks with the King and that they had also mulled over the possibility of a 'patriotic' power-sharing deal with the monarchy (see, for instance, Adhikari 2011).

As I also discussed in the previous chapters, King Gyanendra was not receptive to the Maoists' proposal for talks. The idea of a so-called 'patriotic coalition' with a communist rebel group did not appeal to him. Instead, the King devised an authoritarian plan to sideline and suppress both the Maoists and the parliamentary political parties. With the aim of becoming the sole ruler, in February 2005, he staged a coup, concentrated all power in himself, and placed parliamentary party leaders under arrest.

When the King adopted the policy of repression, the Maoists and the parliamentary political parties entered a mutually hurting stalemate (MHS). In the new scenario, opposing each other as they had done before would only hurt their political goals. Similarly, India also reached a point at which playing contradictory cards or using armed insurgency in Nepal as a 'bargaining tool' or a way to keep Nepal 'mildly unstable' was no longer viable. Doing so would inherently hurt its strategic and security interests. As a result, India reached the point at which it either had to support a democratic and peaceful political transition in Nepal or take the side of the King's repressive regime, hurt its national interests, and face international defamation.

In addition to the triangular mutually hurting stalemate (MHS), there were also components of mutually enticing opportunities (MEO). Some scholars have presented MEO as a counter possibility to MHS (see, for instance, Crocker 1992, Mitchell 1995). The tendency to take MEO as a complementary element to MHS is also common (see, for instance, Pruitt & Olczak 1995, Pruitt 1997, Ohlson 1998). Unlike MHS, MEO focuses on enticing possibilities and opportunities that can be achieved if the conflict in question is resolved.

When the Maoists and the SPA formed an anti-King coalition in 2005, it represented both MHS and MEO. This was an enticing opportunity because their unity would make them the most potent political force in Nepal, and eventually, their victory was inevitable. Once they defeated the King, they could reshape the Nepali political landscape as they desired, which they ultimately did. In addition, once peace and democracy were restored under their leadership, they would not only get the credit for their 'struggle', but their ascendancy to power would also be straightforward.

Interestingly, helping solve the Maoist armed insurgency through a negotiated settlement also became an enticing opportunity for India. It was one of the reasons why India took up the role of an informal facilitator of the 12-Point Understanding process and later as an informal mediator of a range of political negotiations. As an alternative, India could have also supported the King's repressive regime. When favourable for serving its interests, India has supported authoritarian regimes in the region, including in Nepal in the past, but also in Bhutan, the Maldives, and Myanmar. This time, however, India's choice was also guided by the enticing opportunity it saw on the horizon. As I mentioned earlier, the enticing opportunity

was that facilitating conflict resolution in Nepal would not only align with its security interests but could also enhance its image as a peacemaker and strengthen its position as a dominant regional power in South Asia.

A noteworthy point to consider in relation to the Nepali peace process is that MHS and MEO were present in parties directly involved in the conflict (i.e. the Maoists and the SPA). However, the third party that took on the role of facilitator, India, also recognised elements of MHS and MEO. While mediation research mainly focuses on MHS and MEO in belligerents, it is also important to expand it to include third-party stakeholders. This can help explain why some conflicts attract mediators and facilitators (see, for instance, Svensson & Onken 2015), while others receive no mediation interest and are allowed to deteriorate.

9.4 The Pain of 'Peace Dependency' in Post-Conflict Nepal

The motive 'behind' mediation and the motive 'beyond' mediation are the two central themes I have attempted to address throughout this thesis. When analysing third-party involvement, the motives and behaviour of mediators and facilitators in mediation processes have been widely studied. Still, we know little about how mediators or facilitators engage after a successful peace agreement.

As I elaborated in the previous chapters, India was successful in portraying itself as the *de facto* dealmaker of the 12-Point Understanding, which provided the foundation for the Nepali peace process. Although India's role was not as significant as it has often been portrayed, the Indian narrative prevailed mainly due to its longstanding, strong, and traditional influence in Nepal. In the previous chapters, I demonstrated how India skilfully crafted and utilised the peace broker identity along with a peacebuilding narrative to strengthen its presence and influence in post-conflict Nepal. While India's role in the 12-Point Understanding was primarily that of a facilitator, the inflated narrative of its success as a peace broker helped strengthen its presence in the post-conflict scenario. As I presented in Chapter 6, India used a micromanagement strategy during the early years of the peace process. However, in the later years, it increasingly relied on hard power policy instruments, such as aggressive power diplomacy and economic sanctions.

Throughout the years of the peace process, a particular pattern of Indian involvement was consistently evident. Whenever a political crisis or stalemate hit Kathmandu, representatives from the Indian establishment—mainly Indian embassy officials or operatives from Indian intelligence agencies—presented themselves as 'mediators' or 'deal makers'. As a result, in the years after the CPA, India became increasingly influential in shaping Nepal's post-conflict political landscape. Meanwhile, Nepal gradually turned to India for assistance in managing and resolving its post-conflict political crises. Emboldened by the recognition it received for facilitating the 12-Point Understanding, India began to intervene and seek a stake in all significant political negotiations in post-conflict Nepal. As I have discussed in previous chapters, India influenced the 2006 CPA, the provisions of the Interim Constitution, the disarmament and management of Maoist combatants, and the departure of UNMIN, the UN mission in Nepal.

Over time, India's involvement extended beyond matters related to the peace process. As I mentioned earlier and discussed in detail in Chapters 6 and 7, in the years following the 12-Point Understanding, India became a *de facto* mediator and a powerful deal-breaker in Nepal. This led to a situation in which Nepal started becoming dependent on India to ensure post-conflict stability in the country. When it came to addressing post-conflict grievances or the concerns of dissatisfied groups,

India acted as a de facto powerhouse, capable of influencing power centres in Kathmandu and significantly altering political developments and outcomes. For instance, India mediated the negotiations between the government of Nepal and dissatisfied Madhesi groups on various occasions (Jha 2012: 347). In August 2007, India facilitated an agreement between the Madhesi Janaadhikar Forum and the government of Nepal. Similarly, in February 2008, India actively and visibly mediated an Eight-Point Agreement between the government and the United Democratic Madhesi Front (Jha 2012).

As India's voice began to prevail in some of the major political decisions taken in Kathmandu, Nepal gradually lost control over its internal affairs. As a result, decisions that were taken in Kathmandu were heavily guided, influenced, instructed, or even directed by India (see Chapter 6). While India–Nepal relations are complex and cannot be simplified to just a peace mediator and a mediation recipient, the post-conflict relationship between the two countries does provide valuable insights into post-peace agreement situations in a post-conflict context.

What Nepal experienced in the post-conflict context regarding India is something I refer to as 'peace dependency'. While India's role in initiating or mediating Nepal's peace process was limited, it effectively positioned itself as an informal mediator and a key planner in the Nepali peace process. Subsequently, it strengthened its presence in Nepal and began to influence political developments to an unprecedented extent. As I mentioned earlier, Nepal became significantly reliant on India to maintain post-conflict peace and stability. Recognising and understanding these dependencies in post-mediation and post-conflict situations is crucial, yet it is not a common practice. Therefore, my intention in this section is to explore this theoretical area and highlight these post-conflict 'dependencies'.

There were several drawbacks of the peace dependency that Nepal was subjected to as the peace process progressed over the years. First, after the 12-Point Understanding, India emerged as the uncontested and nearly exclusive foreign influence in Nepal's internal affairs. Its role as a mediator or a dealbreaker was controversial but rarely contested. The carefully crafted credentials of a successful peace broker influenced successive negotiations and the post-conflict political restructuring process. As a result, as I discussed in Chapter 6, there were instances of 'mundane mediations' during which India's presence was strong and pervasive. At times, it seemed that the Indian embassy in Kathmandu and India's intelligence agencies pressured Nepali politicians into their 'mediation' traps. This led to a situation in which Indian agencies covertly 'mediated' political dealings when there was no such need. In other words, the so-called Indian 'mediation' often took place through informal, covert meetings, even in seemingly ordinary situations like resolving inter-party conflicts or addressing grievances of a dissatisfied minority. In essence, mediation evolved into a loosely defined tool that allowed India to micromanage Nepal's internal affairs, often to inject and promote its own political, economic, and strategic interests. As I have described in previous chapters, India's 'mediation' was not limited to conflict management but included a wide range of other issues, including government formation, post-conflict political restructuring, constitution-making, and high-profile political appointments.

Second, particularly in the later years of the peace process and political transition, India's influence and interference virtually plagued Nepal's peacebuilding and constitution-making processes. For instance, India's attempt to inject its interests into Nepal's new constitution, its fixation with the state-restructuring process, and its undue attempt to reinstate Nepal's identity as a Hindu nation unnecessarily prolonged the post-conflict peacebuilding and constitution-

making process and severely compromised the political autonomy and agency of Nepali political actors. Furthermore, during the initial years of the peace process, India's focus on preserving the monarchy and its efforts to isolate and demonise the Maoists proved to be equally harmful and counterproductive to Nepal's efforts to achieve a smooth transition to peace and democracy after the conflict.

Third, India's prolonged, controversial, and often unnecessary engagement in post-conflict Nepal as a 'perpetual mediator' was particularly detrimental to the relationship between the two countries. As India's engagement in post-conflict Nepal deepened, anti-India sentiment also increased. Anti-India demonstrations on the streets of Kathmandu started to become increasingly common, and on one occasion, the Indian ambassador to Nepal was even physically attacked (Das 2010, Nayak 2012: 137).

9.5 Lessons for Peace and Mediation Practitioners

I will discuss the overall lessons from the Nepali peace process in Chapter 10, in which it will be demonstrated that despite some significant successes, the Nepali peace process fell short in ensuring social justice, achieving the long-awaited socio-economic transformation, and incorporating gender equity into the peacebuilding framework. In this section, I will reflect on mediation and negotiation scenarios from the Nepali peace process and highlight three important lessons specifically aimed at peace and mediation practitioners.

First, the peace process in Nepal began long before negotiations for a formal peace agreement, or the CPA, were initiated. The Comprehensive Peace Accord, signed in 2006, is officially recognised as the peace agreement. However, it was the 12-Point Understanding between the Maoists and the SPA that outlined the roadmap for a negotiated settlement of the Maoist armed insurgency and a more democratic and inclusive future for the country. While the CPA was a formal peace agreement, the 12-Point Understanding can be regarded as a *de facto* peace agreement that effectively ended the armed insurgency.

Second, the Nepali peace process began when two forces—the Maoists and the SPA—united against the King's direct rule and formed a pact for peace and democracy. They planned to defeat the King's direct rule and convert Nepal into a federal democratic republic, which would get a new constitution written by people's representatives and have a reformed, more equitable state structure. The plan to defeat the King's administration was executed within months. Other processes took time, but they were ultimately completed. In that sense, it was an unorthodox peace process because it began not with negotiations between a government party and a rebel group, but with a pact between two oppositional forces working to topple a repressive regime. This example serves as a reminder for practitioners that peace processes might emanate from diverse origins and circumstances and that there is an obvious need to think outside the box when aiming for peace.

Third, and perhaps the most important lesson from the Nepali peace process, is that practitioners should aim to identify patterns of peace 'dependency' and work to eliminate them. As I discussed in this and previous chapters, India entered the Nepali peace process as an informal facilitator, but over time, India's influence expanded considerably, and Nepal became heavily reliant on India to address even minor political stalemates. The self-proclaimed mediator quickly became a micromanager that attempted to reshape several political and policy outcomes in Nepal—sometimes successfully and sometimes unsuccessfully. Nepali political actors significantly lost control over their internal matters during this process.

Nepal's national sovereignty was also heavily compromised. The Nepali peace process serves as a reminder that those helping to bring peace might be interested in more than just peace. In Nepal's case, it was clear that mediation assistance and peacebuilding support were used as political and tactical tools for micromanaging internal politics, deepening dependency, and advancing the external engager's own interests.

India's prolonged involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition raises questions about mediators' mandates. For instance, should there be clear entry and exit strategies, as well as timelines, if external mediation, mediation assistance, or facilitation is used? While any external contribution to conflict resolution is beneficial, what measures can be taken to prevent 'peace dependencies' in post-conflict situations? Should it not be an established notion that helping to end one conflict does not guarantee automatic and unlimited access to future engagements?

The Nepali peace process also shows that identifying and tackling the hidden intentions of external parties in mediation and post-conflict situations is immensely important. As previous research has also shown (see, for instance, Touval 1992, Zartman & Touval 1996, Cunningham 2010, Bercovitch 2011), the awareness that external parties, whether mediators or facilitators, often enter peace processes with their own baggage of agendas is equally essential. As seen in Nepal's case, this 'baggage' can be reflected in biases, preferences, and elaborate covert plans. In other words, the uplifting stories and celebrated songs that promote peace and democracy may not always align with the reality of what occurs behind closed doors and in practice.

As I showed in the previous chapters, India, which entered the Nepali peace process as a facilitator of the 12-Point Understanding, changed its face over time. In the later years of the peace process and political transition, India was no longer the facilitator or the mediator it claimed to be. It deliberately and consistently used its minutely crafted 'peace-broker' image to manipulate, micromanage, and influence political outcomes in Nepal (see Chapter 6). In addition, it also began taking sides and was actively engaged in marginalising and weakening political actors that did not act according to its wishes. For instance, when it became clear that the Maoists had laid down their arms and joined the peace process, the Indian establishment secretly but actively worked to push them out of the political spotlight they had enjoyed as the largest political party in parliament after the 2008 Constituent Assembly elections. India's intervention in the Katawal case, which involved the dismissal of the chief of the Nepal army in 2009 by the Maoist-led government, is one example of how India sought to curb the ambitions of the radical transformation that the Maoist-led government aimed to implement in the post-conflict years.

Similarly, although India often claims to promote democracy and the rule of law in the South Asian subcontinent, its actions in Nepal contradict those claims. As I elaborated in Chapter 6, as a self-proclaimed mediator, India consistently worked to undermine the spirit of the Nepali peace process and the mandate of *Jana Andolan II*. Contrary to the spirit and demands of *Jana Andolan II*, India worked to preserve the monarchy until the very end, both overtly and covertly. It also undermined the agency of Nepali political institutions and the importance of a due political process in issues such as constitution-making and state restructuring. In other words, India's rampant and pervasive presence in post-conflict Nepal was largely detrimental to peace, democracy, and political stability in the country.

Above all, the most important lesson or reminder regarding mediation practice

and post-conflict peacebuilding is that mediation, negotiations, and post-conflict peace processes do not take place in a vacuum. They are influenced by a variety of internal and external factors, such as geopolitical realities, the military, economic and diplomatic interests of external parties, as well as the institutional capacities of those who are receiving external support.

In other words, as I also argued in the previous chapters, broader political, regional, and structural realities must be considered when analysing contemporary mediation practices and peace processes. The world order we live in, the political economy we have adopted, and the political ideologies that influence our national politics all affect the practice of conflict mediation and post-conflict peacebuilding. Therefore, to study today's conflict mediation practices and peace processes effectively, we need a broader analytical framework that seriously considers these issues.

9.6 Chapter Summary: Navigating Peace-Dependency in Post-Conflict Contexts

This chapter analysed India's role as an informal mediator and facilitator in the Nepali peace process, as well as its involvement in key negotiations during Nepal's post-conflict political transition. The focus was primarily theoretical. Borrowing the concept of 'ripeness' from the mediation literature, I assessed India's role in making the Maoist armed insurgency 'ripe' for resolution. I argued that it was not India-induced ripeness that made the Maoist armed insurgency ready for resolution. Instead, a combination of two scenarios—a mutually hurting stalemate (MHS) and a mutually enticing opportunity (MEO) between the Maoists and the SPA was instrumental in ultimately ending the armed conflict with a negotiated settlement. I then discussed the aftermath and repercussions of India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and post-conflict political transition. In an attempt to formulate a theoretical framework, I built on the arguments presented in the previous chapters and introduced the concept of 'peace dependency'. I suggested that peace dependency refers to a continuous reliance on former peace mediators or facilitators to resolve future conflicts. This reliance increases the influence of these mediators (and the states they represent), allowing them to pursue their own interests or interfere in the internal political affairs of the parties receiving mediation or facilitation. The concept of peace dependency enriches the mediation literature by offering nuanced perspectives that are essential for comprehending and assessing the complexities inherent in post-conflict contexts. The chapter wraps up by sharing three key lessons from the Nepali peace process. These insights offer valuable perspectives for practitioners involved in mediation and peacebuilding efforts.

10. Peace Without Justice and Socio-Economic Transformation: An Assessment of Nepal's Peace Process and Political Transition (2005–2017)

In recent years, it has become increasingly common to evaluate the success of a peace process using a wide range of parameters. While still important, classic indicators of a successful peace process—such as cessation of hostilities, peace agreements, and the DDR processes—seem inadequate for providing a comprehensive view of post-conflict societies. As a result, contemporary peace processes are evaluated from a broader perspective. A successful peace process or post-conflict peacebuilding includes several key components: a fair and comprehensive transitional justice system (Fletcher & Weinstein 2002), principles of social inclusion embedded within the peacebuilding framework (Paffenholz & Ross 2015, True & Riveros-Morales 2019), and the integration of human society or processes of life enhancement in the form of ‘positive’ peace (Galtung 1964: 2, Galtung 1996: 30, Galtung & Fisher 2013). In essence, a successful peace process addresses both conflict and security issues. It also tackles broader structural problems that ultimately improve human lives and enhance the freedom people enjoy. Peace processes also have an inherent mandate and responsibility for initiating the process of socioeconomic transformation and creating inclusive, just, fair, and thriving social and political realities.

Against this backdrop, my goal in this chapter is to critically examine Nepal’s peace process and assess its ‘utility’ in relation to some of these issues. In that sense, the aim of this chapter is rather pragmatic. As I examine the Nepali peace process for its promises and outcomes, I present some observations in the form of ‘lessons’.²¹⁶ This study was not specifically designed to identify or analyse the lessons from the Nepali peace process. Therefore, my approach here is somewhat general. Nonetheless, I believe this addition will provide valuable insights that mediation practitioners, negotiators, policymakers, political actors, and peace researchers will find useful in both conflict and post-conflict contexts.

I begin this chapter by exploring some of the key debates surrounding Nepal’s peace process, examining its development along with its political, military, and social dimensions. Despite its inherent defects and underlying dilemmas, the question of whether the Nepali peace process can be considered successful remains at the centre of discussion. This discussion is part of a broader inquiry: When should a peace process be deemed complete, and what implications do ‘complete’ and ‘incomplete’ peace processes carry? One of the most contested issues in Nepal’s peace process is transitional justice, and I will discuss that in this chapter with thorough consideration and depth. As I seek to understand the political motives

²¹⁶ These ‘lessons,’ however, mostly reflect my key informants’ perspectives and, naturally, my interpretation and analysis.

behind a languished transitional justice process and an abandoned national reconciliation program, I argue that a peace process that has failed to deliver on its promises of justice, post-conflict healing, and national reconciliation is far from successful.

I also analyse how women, despite their significant contributions to both the Maoist armed insurgency and the *Jana Andolan II*, were marginalised in the peace process. In addition, this chapter presents insights from the Nepali peace process that may provide valuable lessons for peace practitioners and post-conflict contexts elsewhere. Finally, I examine the extent to which post-conflict governments largely neglected the socio-economic dimensions of the peace process. I conclude the chapter by arguing that Nepal's peace process can be considered as technically and partially successful, marked by a peace agreement, a cessation of hostilities agreement, and the completion of the DDR process. However, the inability to implement a functional transitional justice mechanism and an inclusive peacebuilding framework, the absence of broader socio-economic transformation, and unmet expectations among the people create a breeding ground for social unrest and future conflicts.

10.1 Lessons from an Incomplete Peace Project?

Every peace process is unique and can offer unique lessons. One of the aims of peace research, after all, is to promote peace and a peaceful resolution of violent conflicts and find viable solutions. The practice of sharing peace process lessons, both by peace researchers and practitioners, is also common. Nevertheless, there has been a persistent dilemma regarding Nepal's peace process: despite its shortcomings, should it be considered a mission accomplished, or is it still a work in progress even after nearly nineteen years since the CPA? The confusion is further complicated when some elements of the peace process appear to have been deliberately protracted, if not languished altogether. Time and again, the political elites have used the unfinished peace process narrative as a weapon and a shield, using it as a convenient bargaining tool and a subtle threat in disguise. If that were not the case, after so many years since its inception, Nepali political leaders would not still be uttering the rhetoric of an ongoing peace process. They would not be warning that the peace process would derail or be in danger if a particular political course was not adopted.²¹⁷

Instances like these raise an obvious question: When can peace processes be considered complete? Or can they linger indefinitely? Why do some elements of a peace process receive immediate attention while others are dragged on for decades? What are the moral and political implications when a supposedly unfinished peace project is used to manipulate, threaten, gain public support, and advance a specific political agenda? While these are not easy questions, my analysis in this chapter revolves around these very issues.

As I mentioned earlier, in Nepal, the peace process evolved alongside the political ambitions of key actors in post-conflict politics. In the process, the term 'peace process' was both misused and abused. For instance, when the first Constituent Assembly (CA) elections were held in 2008, the Maoists said that if they failed to secure enough votes to ensure their decent representation in parliamentary politics, the peace process would be over. They often warned that if they lost the CA

²¹⁷ It is still common for political leaders in Nepal, especially the Maoist leaders, to use the 'peace process card' when a particular political development is unpalatable.

elections, they would return to ‘the jungle’, and a new violent conflict would erupt. In the same elections, other parties created a counter-narrative suggesting that if the former rebels were voted into power, they would eventually govern the country authoritatively. These narratives inherently contradicted the spirit of an open and peaceful political process guaranteed by the 12-Point Understanding and the CPA.

Over time, despite numerous challenges, both the Maoists and the parliamentary parties remained committed to the peace process. While they often leveraged the process strategically to serve their interests, they nonetheless upheld its primary principles and core mandates. The rhetoric of an incomplete and ongoing peace process continues to reverberate through the Nepali political landscape. Nevertheless, it is widely accepted that the primary objectives of the Nepali peace process have been largely achieved. The key informants interviewed for this study also widely shared this assessment. Most contended that, despite various challenges and inherent shortcomings, Nepal's peace process was, by and large, complete and successful.

Looking at it from a broader perspective, Nepal's peace process had three main components: political, military, and social. The most important was the political component. The political mandate of the peace process was to draft and declare a new constitution through a Constituent Assembly and to restructure the state for greater inclusivity and decentralisation. Despite numerous challenges (see Chapters 5 and 6), Nepal adopted a new constitution in 2015, through which the state was restructured from a centralised unitary state into a federal democratic republic. The new constitution has been gradually implemented through the establishment of new institutions and the election of representatives at the federal, provincial, and local levels.

The second component was the military, which involved the disarmament, demobilisation, and reintegration of the Maoist soldiers. In the wake of the 2006 CPA, an Agreement for Monitoring the Management of Arms and Armies was reached. The United Nations Mission in Nepal (UNMIN), a UN Security Council-mandated mission, monitored military cantonments and arms containers. Maoist combatants and an equal number of soldiers from the Nepali Army were kept in cantonments and barracks (Bogati 2015: 5). More than 31,000 personnel turned up as Maoist soldiers as the UNMIN began the verification process, out of which UNMIN verified 19,602 persons as eligible Maoist combatants (Martin 2010: 122). The Maoist combatants, known as the People's Liberation Army (PLA), were kept in 28 cantonment sites throughout the country. While 19,602 were verified as eligible combatants, 4,008 were categorised as underage or deemed ineligible because they had joined the PLA too late, that is, after the peace process had begun. The ineligible combatants were released from the camps and provided with various vocational skills training under the UN Inter-agency Rehabilitation Programme (Bogati 2015: 5).

The military component of the peace process, which involved arms and combatant management, was unquestionably a top priority, since the very foundation of the peace process depended on it. Still, this process progressed quite slowly as political disagreements and protracted negotiations in other areas of the peace process, such as constitution-making or state restructuring, affected the decisions about the future of the Maoist combatants. Addressing the issue of combatants required extensive consultations that demanded significant time and effort (Bleie & Shrestha 2012). The CPA offered the Maoist combatants two options. They could either join a state security force, such as the national army or the armed police, or accept an economic package and live independently. A vast majority of

the ex-combatants (i.e., 15,585) chose voluntary retirement and received, according to their rank in the PLA, anywhere between NPR 500,000 to 800,000²¹⁸ (Bogati 2015: 5).

While a small number of the ex-combatants did join state security forces, the disinterest of the vast majority in working as 'career soldiers' explains, at least partly, their ideological inclination in joining the Maoists' People's Liberation Army (PLA). This suggests that the arguments put forth by some scholars, such as Acharya (2009), who equate the recruitment and mobilisation of rebels solely with economic activities or compare the relationship between rebel soldiers and their leaders to that of an employee and an employer, appear implausible. The decision of the Maoists' PLA indicates that individuals who join a rebel movement have the capacity to make thoughtful choices and, whenever possible, exercise the agency available to them. Identifying the motives of individuals who join a rebel movement can be beneficial for post-conflict security management and other related contexts.

The military component of the peace process faced additional challenges as well. For instance, the Maoists were accused of recruiting new combatants and inflating their numbers after the peace process had begun. A leaked video of the Maoist Chairman, Pushpa Kamal Dahal 'Prachanda', appeared to support this claim.²¹⁹ Addressing his party cadres, Prachanda claimed that they had successfully deceived UNMIN into verifying more combatants than were actually eligible. According to Ian Martin, the UN Secretary-General's personal representative in Nepal from 2006 to 2007 and the Special Representative of the Secretary-General and Head of UNMIN from 2006 to 2009, the inflated numbers were potentially caused by the expansion of the PLA that had occurred during the early stage of the peace process (Martin 2010:122).

Although the number of combatants appeared to be inflated, the government chose to be flexible and accepted the higher figures. This was a politically and tactically important issue for the post-conflict government. As Nepal transitioned from a Hindu constitutional monarchy to a federal democratic republic, the presence of a greater number of rebel soldiers in cantonments created indirect pressure on the King to accept the Constituent Assembly's decision to abolish the monarchy and declare Nepal a federal democratic republic.

However, the process of integrating former Maoist combatants into the state security agencies was far from smooth. While most ex-combatants chose voluntary retirement, those who wanted to join the state security forces encountered various challenges. Army integration was a political issue deeply embedded in the peace process. An initial resistance from the top leadership of the Nepal Army complicated the integration process in its infancy (see, for instance, Adhikari 2014). This was further complicated by the fact that some saw Maoist combatants as ideologically indoctrinated and radicalised and thereby unfit to be integrated into the national army.

In addition, welcoming ideologically influenced Maoist combatants, or those who did not necessarily meet the basic entry requirements of the Nepal Army, became a matter of prestige for the army leadership. Furthermore, the Nepal Army had been mobilised to suppress the Maoists, and the relationship between the national army and the rebels had always been tense. Therefore, even when the political climate had changed in the country, welcoming their former enemies as their new counterparts was something the army leadership attempted to avoid. In

²¹⁸ As of December 2024, the amount is equivalent to approximately EUR 3,500 to 5,500.

²¹⁹ The leaked video is available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TcozIxx9F2I>

addition, India, which was actively involved in micromanaging Nepali politics in the post-conflict context, also preferred that Maoist combatants not be included in the national army.²²⁰

In the end, the army could not stay indifferent to the political consensus that had been formed about the entry of rebel combatants into the national army. While the army leadership under Rookmangud Katawal resisted army integration, the change in leadership eventually allowed the integration process to continue. As a result, more than 1,400 ex-combatants joined various ranks of the Nepal Army (Bohara 2015b). Despite initial concerns about combatants' ideological indoctrination and the potential impact it could cause, the integration process was largely successful. The ex-combatants not only graduated from the Nepal Military Academy but also later served in the United Nations' peacekeeping missions in various countries (Bohara 2015b).

Overall, the military aspect of the peace process was successful. Some have even termed it as 'unique and unorthodox' as well as 'effective' (Bhandari 2015). It largely adhered to international principles and practices while also featuring its own unique Nepali model (Wagle & Jackson 2015: 437). Even though the military integration of ex-combatants was relatively successful, research shows that their social integration was more challenging (see, for instance, Subedi 2014, Bhandari 2015, KC 2019). Those who could not get UNMIN's verification faced a difficult path ahead. Similarly, the issue of child soldiers was also largely overlooked throughout the peace process (Binadi & Binadi 2011).

The third component of the peace process was a social one. This primarily involved transitional justice and reconciliation processes, and this is where the Nepali peace process failed miserably. Nineteen years after the CPA was signed, issues of transitional justice and reconciliation processes are still in limbo. The continuous apathy towards addressing these issues has raised serious questions about the fate of the Nepali peace process. As I examine in the next section, the fact that transitional justice and reconciliation processes were never seriously considered makes the Nepali peace process deeply flawed.

10.2 Peace Without Justice? The Issue of Transitional Justice and National Reconciliation in Post-Conflict Nepal

As I discussed in Chapter 4, Nepal's ten-year-long armed conflict (1996–2006) was characterised by a wide range of serious human rights violations, including extra-judicial killings, torture, abductions, disappearances, rape, extortion, and even mass killings of innocent civilians. Committed by both the Maoist rebels and Nepali state security forces, these grave human rights violations continue to remain as indelible scars of the armed conflict. Aside from a few isolated cases, most crimes committed during the armed conflict have never been thoroughly investigated or subjected to a fair judicial process. As a result, the war victims have been left with an elusive hope for justice that has now been prolonged for years.

In post-conflict scenarios, it is common for serious human rights violations committed during a conflict to be addressed through transitional justice mechanisms. Transitional justice frameworks typically include judicial and non-judicial measures and can include 'criminal prosecutions, truth commissions, reparations programs, and various kinds of institutional reforms' (ICTJ 2021). In post-conflict societies, a transitional justice setup is essential because the normal

²²⁰ Interview with an expert key informant (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

justice system is often inadequate to address large-scale, systemic and serious human rights abuses. Furthermore, in the aftermath of a violent conflict, it is common for victims to demand the justice that is due and the reparation that is necessary for healing and moving forward. At the core of transitional justice is also the idea that there can be no peace without justice (Anderlini et al. 2004). Transitional justice is also based on the idea that 'in the aftermath of massive human rights abuses, victims have well-established rights to see the perpetrators punished, to know the truth, and to receive reparations' (ICTJ 2021). At the core of this again is the notion that 'systemic human rights violations affect not just the direct victims, but society as a whole...and states have duties to guarantee that the violations will not recur, and therefore, a special duty to reform institutions that were either involved in or incapable of preventing the abuses' (ICTJ 2021).

As a key component of transitional justice, reconciliation is also often part of healing and recuperation in post-conflict societies. Reconciliation can simply mean 'coexistence, dialogue, forgiveness and healing' and should not be construed as an 'attempt to restore things to how they were before the conflict, but rather about constructing relationships in a way that allows everyone to move forward together' (Anderlini et al. 2004: 2). As Anderlini et al. (2004: 3) elaborate, reconciliatory measures or a reconciliation process are crucial in a post-conflict scenario primarily because they help establish relations among parties and thereby reduce the risk of future violence.

In Nepal, the Comprehensive Peace Accord, signed between the CPN (Maoists) and the Government of Nepal in 2006, clearly recognised the need for a transitional justice process as the country prepared for a post-conflict future. In the CPA, the signatories, the CPN(Maoists) and the Government of Nepal, agreed to find out the whereabouts of people who disappeared or were killed during the conflict and to inform their families within 60 days of signing the peace agreement.²²¹ Nineteen years have passed since the CPA was signed, yet that promise remains unfulfilled. Similarly, the CPA also envisioned a National Peace and Rehabilitation Commission for providing relief and rehabilitation for war victims.²²² It also proposed a high-level truth and reconciliation commission to investigate and punish serious human rights violations and crimes against humanity committed during the armed conflict.²²³

Nepal's Interim Constitution 2007, promulgated after *Jana Andolan II* and subsequent peace talks, also recognised the need for transitional justice and reconciliation frameworks to be in place. However, amidst political wrangling over a new constitution and debates primarily focused on state restructuring, political parties continued to show apathy towards transitional justice, post-conflict truth-finding, and reconciliation issues. In the absence of a transitional justice mechanism, war victims and their relatives attempted to seek justice through the country's existing judicial system, but often with little success.

²²¹ CPA clause 5.2.3 mentioned: Both sides agree to make public within 60 days of [the] signing of the agreement information about the real name, caste and address of the people 'disappeared' or killed during [war] war and to inform the family about it. See an English translation of the CPA at: <https://ucdpged.uu.se/peaceagreements/fulltext/Nep%2020061121.pdf>

²²² CPA clause 5.2.4 mentioned: 5.2.4. Both sides agree to form a National Peace and Rehabilitation Commission to establish peace in the society by normalizing adverse situation generated by armed conflict and to carry out relief and rehabilitate people victimised and displaced by war, and to carry forward the tasks related to this through the Commission.

²²³ CPA clause 5.2.5 mentioned: Both sides agree to set up a High-level Truth and Reconciliation Commission through [a] mutual agreement in order to investigate [the] truth about people seriously violating human rights and involved in crimes against humanity, and to create an environment of reconciliations in the society.

Even though Nepal's courts did not have the mandate for handling wartime cases, the Supreme Court of Nepal gave verdicts on a few wartime cases. Without a transitional justice legal framework in place, the Court sentenced the 'guilty' based on the existing penal code. While issuing verdicts on a few cases it had entertained, the Supreme Court directed the government to address the legal framework for transitional justice issues and to provide justice and compensation to victims of the armed conflict (see, for instance, Wagle 2015, Billingsley 2016, Jeffery & Timilsina 2021).

The CPA included clear provisions for establishing a truth and reconciliation commission, as well as for conducting a thorough investigation into serious human rights violations that took place during the armed conflict. Nevertheless, the continuous apathy of major political forces towards these issues crippled Nepal's transitional justice process even before it properly began. The issue of transitional justice was not only overlooked, but on several occasions, individuals accused of committing serious human rights abuses and atrocities were given high-profile public positions and political appointments (OHCHR 2011).

The first attempt to establish a truth and reconciliation commission occurred in 2010 when the government sought to pass new legislation for this purpose. However, political parties disagreed on the amnesty provisions in the proposed bill. Eventually, the bill was rejected by the Constituent Assembly.²²⁴ Three years later, in 2013, a Maoist-led government came up with an ordinance that again included 'lax' amnesty provisions. This time, the Supreme Court dismissed the ordinance, arguing it was short of international standards (Mathieu 2014).

After the Supreme Court's repeated directives, international and domestic pressure from various human rights organisations, and consistent and concerted demand and push from the victims' organisations, in April 2014, a new Act called the Enforced Disappearances Enquiry, Truth and Reconciliation Commission Act (TRC Act) was passed.²²⁵ The Act was largely similar to the 2013 ordinance, which included controversial amnesty provisions. Unsurprisingly, this Act also faced widespread criticism for its provisions that granted flat amnesty, even to those involved in serious human rights violations. If implemented, it would effectively create systemic loopholes that would allow for the avoidance of investigating some of the most severe human rights abuses that occurred during the armed conflict. Pradeep Gyawali, a member of the task force that created the draft of the 2014 TRC Act, recalled leaving the task force for that reason:

After widespread pressure, we came up with the TRC bill. I was in the task force that drafted the bill, but later left because of a few reservations. When it was proposed that the incidents of serious human rights violations, too, could be covered under an amnesty framework, I disagreed. Later, the Supreme Court, too, rejected that, and so did the international community.²²⁶

In February 2015, the Supreme Court of Nepal ruled in response to a petition from a group of 234 war victims. The court argued that several provisions in the TRC Act did not align with Nepal's 2015 constitution and its international commitments to human rights protection. Subsequently, in April 2020, the Supreme Court refused the government's request to review the previous ruling (Bhetwal 2023).

²²⁴ The Constituent Assembly had the mandate to function as Nepal's legislative parliament as well.

²²⁵ The Act is available at: <https://www.satp.org/Docs/Document/839.pdf> [Accessed 8 February 2023].

²²⁶ Interview with Pradeep Gyawali (10.07.2017).

Nonetheless, as directed by the TRC Act, in February 2015, two commissions, the Commission of Investigation on Enforced Disappeared Persons Nepal and the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC), were formed. Amid widespread criticism and a lack of political consensus on addressing serious wartime atrocities, the two commissions began their work. By February 2018, the two commissions had reportedly received over 63,000 requests to investigate abuses and human rights violations that occurred during the decade-long conflict. Two years later, in February 2020, it was reported that the TRC had conducted a preliminary investigation into less than 10% of the requests, and out of more than 63,000 complaints, not a single case had been resolved (HRW & AF 2020).

Apart from the preliminary investigation into a few cases, no concrete action has been taken to ensure justice for war victims. In April 2023, the government filed an amendment to the TRC Act (2014) in Parliament. However, due to objections from the opposition parties, a special parliamentary committee was formed to discuss the bill's provisions (The Kathmandu Post 2023). Finally, on August 14, 2024, Nepal's House of Representatives passed an amendment to the Transitional Justice Act, officially called the Investigation, Truth and Reconciliation Commission (Third) Amendment Bill, 2024, with a majority (Bhusal 2024).

Despite the new legislation, significant uncertainty remains regarding its implementation and whether Nepal's war victims will receive the justice they eagerly await and deserve. While the new TRC Act aims to address the severe human rights violations committed during the decade-long armed insurgency, critics have raised concerns that its provisions may favour perpetrators over victims. Notably, the new legislation includes mechanisms for significant reductions (up to 75%) in sentencing for those who cooperate (Gupta 2024). This undermines the pursuit of accountability for serious crimes such as torture and enforced disappearances.

Eighteen years after the CPA, a new piece of legislation was finally passed, with near national consensus, to address the protracted transitional justice issues. However, it may take years to implement it thoroughly. While the two high-level commissions set up for transitional justice and national reconciliation continue to operate, their presence has been largely symbolic, serving mainly as 'showpieces'. In the absence of strong political backing, these commissions neither have enough resources nor a proper mandate for effectively investigating wartime atrocities.²²⁷ Without robust mechanisms to safeguard victims' rights and uphold international human rights standards, the prospects for achieving justice for conflict victims continue to remain bleak.

In short, the prolonged stagnation of the transitional justice process has not only delayed the delivery of long-overdue justice but has also tainted the reputation of the otherwise largely successful Nepali peace process. In addition, despite being a signatory to various international treaties and conventions, Nepal's inability to keep up with its commitments has tarnished its global image. Time and again, Nepal's commitment to investigating serious wartime abuses has been questioned at international forums. It has also been argued that Nepal's continuous disinterest in seriously investigating wartime atrocities would also encourage the international community to 'step up' so that serious human rights abusers were brought to trial (see, for instance, Khatry 2020). In fact, in 2016, Maoist Chairman Pushpa Kamal Dahal cancelled a visit to Australia at the last minute due to fears that he might be arrested there for war crimes (Koirala 2019). In 2013, a senior Nepal Army officer

²²⁷ Interview with Bishnu Raj Upreti (03.08.2017).

who worked as a military observer in the UN Mission in South Sudan, Colonel Kumar Lama, was arrested in the UK and tried in a British court for his suspected involvement in torture inflicted upon political dissidents in Nepal during the armed conflict.²²⁸ (Shrestha S. 2017, Massagé & Sharma 2018) Incidents like these ultimately compelled Nepali political parties to reach a consensus on the TRC bill. Nonetheless, concerns remain that it may simply be another political manoeuvre rather than a genuine commitment to finally address the beleaguered transitional justice process.

10.3 Transitional Justice Setbacks and Their Ripple Effects

Nepal's beleaguered transitional justice process primarily raises two serious questions. First, as previously mentioned, whether Nepal's peace process can still be seen as complete, even with transitional justice and national reconciliation programme continuing to remain in limbo. Second, why has Nepal failed to deliver on the promise of justice, even though comparatively complicated puzzles of the peace process, such as transforming the country from a Hindu monarchy into a secular federal republic, declaring a new constitution through a Constituent Assembly, or managing arms and combatants, have been completed successfully?

While interviewing the key informants, when I asked their opinion on whether Nepal's peace process should be considered complete, most described it as 'essentially complete' or 'nearly complete,' though they acknowledged that some 'minor issues' still needed to be addressed. As noted at the beginning of this chapter, narratives framing the peace process as either complete or incomplete were strategically employed for years to serve specific political agendas.

As examples from other countries also show, peace processes are typically long and complex. Due to their length and complexity, it is neither possible nor always necessary to subject them to a binary distinction and label them as complete or incomplete. Sometimes, this binary distinction seems to be used to further a political goal or specific rhetoric, which appears to be true in the case of Nepal.

The tendency to label Nepal's peace process as a 'mission accomplished' underlies the idea that transitional justice is only a minor supplementary puzzle of a broader peace process. Unsurprisingly, that notion, paired with some high-profile politicians' strategy to avoid trial for their involvement in wartime atrocities, is responsible for the delayed, or essentially denied, transitional justice process in Nepal. In other words, while transitional justice was included in the CPA for the sake of inclusion, it never received the careful attention it deserved. It seemed that the scope of the Nepali peace process was deliberately narrowed. The process was overshadowed by the flawed notion that peace is achieved once warring parties reach an agreement and resolve their disputes. This misconception proved to be both misleading and counterproductive.

The failure to include transitional justice issues at the heart of Nepal's peace process has led to several unintended consequences. These include a rising culture of impunity, protests and strikes from victims, and a declining trust in the country's justice and political systems, among others. In 2017, as soon as he became Nepal's Prime Minister for a second term, Pushpa Kamal Dahal 'Prachanda' went to the Nepal Army headquarters to address army generals, where he surprisingly assured that no action would be taken against army officers involved in wartime incidents

²²⁸ Colonel Lama was tried in a British court under a 1988 Act that grants British courts the authority to prosecute suspected war criminals and human rights violators, even if they are foreign nationals and their offenses occurred outside the UK. Colonel Lama was acquitted in 2016.

(Prasain 2017). Mr Dahal's action not only demonstrated a lack of political will in investigating and addressing serious wartime atrocities, but it was also an intervention in the jurisdiction of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission. Similarly, those who spoke out for victims have often faced threats and backlash. One notable example is that in 2016, a commissioner for the Truth and Reconciliation Commission, who opposed a blanket amnesty for perpetrators of wartime atrocities, reported facing a security threat because of her stance (Himalayan News Service 2016).

While the lack of political will is central to the failure of Nepal's transitional justice mechanism, there are also other contributing factors. First, when the 12-Point Understanding was signed in India in late 2005, the issue of transitional justice did not receive the attention it deserved. The negotiations that led initially to the 12-Point Understanding and later to the CPA were guided by the conviction that if the warring parties agreed on key issues, the peace process would proceed smoothly.

Even though the warring parties engaged in most of the fighting, civilians were the ones most affected by the conflict. Therefore, any peace pact or transitional justice mechanism that excludes or ignores the civilian victims of the conflict would be incomplete and destined to fail. In other words, the two major parties of the Nepali peace process, the Maoists and the SPA-led government, from the very beginning, failed to pay serious attention to this issue. Instead, they seemed to intentionally disrupt or destabilise the systems that would have ensured a reliable transitional justice mechanism and an effective post-conflict reconciliation process. Pradeep Gyawali, who was part of the 2006 peace talks as a member of the government negotiation team, acknowledged that focusing exclusively on conflict resolution while neglecting victims' issues was a significant shortcoming of the Nepali peace process from the outset. He added:

In many places, we see that only conflict issues dominate peace processes. In other words, conflicting parties' problems are prioritised, but victims' problems are covered up. It also happened in Nepal. When this happens, it could start another cycle of conflict. In order to prevent this, the victims first, the community first, and the people first approach should be adopted, and only then would a peace process be successful.²²⁹

Second, as I showed in previous chapters, India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition was significant in the years following the 12-Point Understanding. India's political and bureaucratic establishment in New Delhi—along with the Indian embassy in Kathmandu—was heavily involved in shaping and influencing political processes and outcomes in post-conflict Nepal. Through its active involvement in Nepal's peace process, India sought to carefully craft an image of a democracy promoter (Destradi 2010). As I have documented throughout this thesis, the image of a democracy promoter, or that of a regional peacemaker and peacebuilder, however, was not reflected in its actions in Nepal. From a broader perspective, India appeared to have two primary motives in Nepal. The first was enhancing its regional and international image through its involvement in Nepal's peace process. The second, and more central, was manipulating and micromanaging Nepal's decision-making processes to safeguard its national

²²⁹ Interview with Pradeep Gyawali (10.07.2017).

interests (see Chapters 6 and 7). These priorities overshadowed its claimed commitment to promoting democracy, human rights, and the rule of law.

If India truly upheld its claim as a promoter of democracy and the rule of law, it should have pushed and advocated for an effective transitional justice mechanism in Nepal. However, it never did so. Since India's concerns in Nepal's peace process were largely guided by its own vested interests, the issue of implementing an effective transitional justice process had never been India's priority. In short, India remained indifferent to these issues mainly because, as far as serving its national interests was concerned, these issues were of no relevance. Thus, India's indifference towards transitional justice and national reconciliation in Nepal contributed indirectly to the sidelining of the transitional justice agenda.

Finally, the lack of a detailed framework for transitional justice processes in the CPA meant a weak foundation for these mechanisms.²³⁰ Legislation and instruments created to address these issues were introduced years after the CPA was signed. They were the result of persistent pressure from war victims and human rights organisations. In other words, the fundamental flaw was in the very design and structure of the peace process, in which transitional justice was treated as a secondary concern and lacked a detailed implementation plan. As Prakash Bhattarai argued, Nepal's peace process followed a sequential model in which important issues were addressed one at a time. All actors concentrated on a specific problem, and once that step was completed, attention shifted to the next issue.²³¹ The heavily centralised decision-making practice, in which only a few prominent leaders made nearly all decisions, was one reason the peace process dragged on for so long and why issues of justice were overlooked.²³²

10.4 Forgotten and Invisible: Women at the Periphery of the Nepali Peace Process

While themes such as gender equity and women's social emancipation were strongly supported by the Maoists as well as the parliamentary parties, women were notably absent at the critical moments of the peace process.²³³ For instance, not a single female politician was present, neither as a signatory nor as a participant, when the 12-Point Understanding, the very foundation of the Nepali peace process, was created in New Delhi in November 2005. In 2006, as formal peace talks between the Maoists and the Government of Nepal commenced in Kathmandu, women were once again overlooked. Neither the Maoist nor the government negotiation teams cared about making the negotiation teams inclusive by including women negotiators in their teams. In addition, all five civil society representatives who served as observers in the peace talks were men.

This way, from the very beginning, Nepal's peace process virtually became an exclusive club of men, in which, despite repeated demands from various women's organisations, women's participation was continuously neglected. The exclusion of women from peace processes continues to remain a common practice globally (Aggestam & Svensson 2018). In 2018, the US Council on Foreign Relations found

²³⁰ Interview with Pradeep Gyawali (10.07.2017).

²³¹ Interview with Prakash Bhattarai (12.07.2017).

²³² Interview with Bishnu Raj Upreti (03.08.2017).

²³³ For instance, the Maoists' 40-point demand, submitted to the government just before launching the armed struggle in 1996, demanded that 'patriarchal exploitation and discrimination against women should be stopped' and that 'daughters should be allowed access to [the] paternal property.' (See Appendix 5)

that major peace processes that were undertaken between 1990 and 2017 had merely 8% women mediators and negotiators, respectively, and women's representation as witnesses and signatories in peace processes stood barely at 5% (Council on Foreign Relations 2018). The exclusion of women from key stages of the Nepali peace process reinforced the unfair global trend that diminishes the vital role women could play as architects of peace and a better future. By sidelining women from the peace process, Nepali political actors missed an opportunity to make the process gender-inclusive and to challenge a global trend that neglected and marginalised women.

While women were clearly overlooked in the peace process, their involvement in both the Maoist armed insurgency and *Jana Andolan II* was significant. Women's participation in the Maoist movement has been studied and written from different angles, and there are countless stories of the resilience, bravery, and sacrifice Nepali women demonstrated during the armed conflict (see, for instance, Onesto 2005, Lohani-Chase 2008, Dahal 2015, Kolås 2017). Even though most of the Maoist combatants were men, it has been estimated that the number of female combatants, nonetheless, stood somewhere between 30 to 50% (Tamang 2009: 73). Out of the 19,602 combatants verified by the UNMIN as qualified Maoist combatants, 3,846 (i.e., 19.6%) were female (Steenbergen 2020: 35). This number itself is significant because women had joined the insurgency as combatants at a time when even state security agencies, such as the Nepal Army, refrained from recruiting women to fight on battlefields. Women's involvement in the Maoist movement went beyond combat; they were also active as party cadres, mobilisers, and volunteers.

Most of the female cadres who joined the Maoist movement came from Nepal's remote and disadvantaged areas and represented the country's minority populations. For many of these women, the Maoist movement provided a unique revolutionary platform where they could assert their agency as agents of change and challenge the deep roots of patriarchy that thrived on suppressing, subjugating, and conditioning them to an endless cycle of exploitation. In addition, the Maoist manifestos that promised gender equality at all levels, including girls' rights to paternal property, encouraged women to join the Maoist movement. Manifestos aside, the Maoist movement created a tangible space where many Nepali women, historically confined to the boundaries of their homes, lost in their kitchens, in seemingly mundane chores such as raising children or pleasing men, could finally be part of something greater—a mission of a kind, that had the potential to permanently change their lives and alter the destiny of their country.

Nevertheless, there were darker aspects to what might be seen, in a somewhat romanticised manner, as the exceptional participation of women in the Maoist insurgency. Some women who participated in the rebel movement were not breaking free from the shackles of patriarchy or feudalism that had historically enchained them. They were entrapped and forced to join the rebel movement. In some cases, girls as young as 12 or 13 were found to be working for the Maoists (Thapa & Sijapati 2003: 180), a clear indication that some of the rebel recruitments were forced (Manchanda 2004: 243).

Apart from the ideological charm of the Maoists, some women joined the movement also because they wanted to seek revenge on the security forces who had abused and raped them during a suppression spree, in which innocent civilians were crushed as Maoist supporters. In addition, women who were left as social outcasts and could not be accepted back into society also joined the rebels (Gautam 2002). Some women also joined because their sons, husbands, or fathers were

killed by the state security forces. However, no matter how they had joined, women and girls were an essential part of the rebel movement. Without their participation, both voluntary and coerced, the Maoist movement would not have achieved the strength it did, especially in the later years of the conflict.

Furthermore, women were the primary victims of the armed conflict, which took a significant physical, emotional, and psychological toll on them. Rape, torture, and sexual abuse were used as tools of war, and women were victims of some of the most horrible wartime atrocities.²³⁴ The armed conflict also increased the likelihood of early marriages for girls (Valente 2011). When men left their villages—as fighters, as displaced persons escaping forced conscription and abuse, or as economic migrants seeking employment abroad—it was often women who took care of the ones left behind. As a result, women were forced to carry a significant psychological and emotional burden as well.

Nepali women also participated vehemently in *Jana Andolan II*, the 2006 democratic movement that ended King Gyanendra's direct rule as well as the decade-long armed conflict. However, as already noted above, when the season of political change was over, the promises of gender equality and the widely canvassed agenda of women's emancipation were virtually abandoned. While the 2015 constitution guarantees at least 33% of seats for women in all elected bodies, other far more critical issues that could have impacted the lives of grassroots women have been forgotten. For instance, legal provisions that ensure women's equal citizenship and property rights do not yet exist. While women's representation in elected bodies from top to bottom has increased their political participation, there are still concerns that their actual participation and influence in decision-making processes continue to remain marginal.

Similarly, when it came to the case of female ex-combatants, apathy prevailed. For these women, the post-war reintegration program had little to offer, and, as a result, many female ex-combatants were 'pushed back into traditional gender roles' (KC & Van Der Haar 2019, Steenbergen 2020). In the absence of a gender-inclusive framework in the DDR policy and the continuous indifference towards their voices, female ex-combatants experienced and endured various forms of marginalisation in the post-conflict context (Goswami 2015, KC 2019: 453).

This scenario in Nepal is similar to that of women who were forgotten in the aftermath of the Arab Spring in North Africa and the Middle East (see, for instance, Johansson-Nogiés 2013, Khalil 2014a, Khalil 2014b). The Arab Spring was a series of pro-democracy uprisings that began in 2010 across the Middle East and North Africa, challenging authoritarian regimes and addressing issues like corruption, unemployment, and political oppression. Women actively participated as protesters, organisers, and advocates, leveraging social media, leading demonstrations, and raising awareness despite facing significant societal and institutional barriers. Women were often at the forefront of the protests. However, in post-victory transitional processes, women's participation was significantly restricted. In countries such as Tunisia, Egypt and Libya, not only were women's rights under attack, but violence against women was found to be rising (Johansson-Nogiés 2013).

Nepal's persistent neglect of women's participation in the peace process and its disregard for women's rights issues is deeply unfortunate. It is an affront to the immense sacrifices made by Nepali women during the Maoist armed insurgency

²³⁴ Some notable examples include the murder of Maina Sunuwar and the torture and abuse inflicted upon women detainees at Nepal Army's Bhairabnath Battalion.

and *Jana Andolan II*. This serves as a crucial lesson for future peace processes globally that women must be meaningfully included in all stages of peacebuilding.

10.5 Peace Without Progress: Nepal's Struggle for Post-Conflict Socio-economic Transformation

As I mentioned at the beginning of this Chapter, the Nepali peace process had three major components: political, military, and social. While assessing each of these components can be valuable, there is a broader standard to evaluate the overall success of a peace process. That is, a peace process is truly successful when it upholds the promises it made in the first place and effectively addresses the socio-economic and structural issues that perpetuate conflict and foster a culture of violence. In other words, a successful peace process should create opportunities for freedom and foster positive changes in people's lives. This can be equated to what Galtung (1964) termed 'positive peace'. While negative peace could be achieved by ensuring the absence of violence or by promoting violence reduction, he argued, positive peace encompassed 'the integration of human society' or 'processes of life enhancement' (Galtung 1964: 2, Galtung 1996: 30).

Positive peace has an emancipatory agenda (Grewal 2003: 6). In this sense, peacebuilding involves more than just disarming weapons and reintegrating former combatants back into society. Above all, peacebuilding is about overcoming the contradiction at the root of conflict formation and involves 'defining a new formation; new structures, new institutions' (Galtung 1996:112). As Ahtisaari (2008: 13) put it, 'preventing reoccurrence of violence is not only about obliterating guns, but it is about developing a healthy state and society'. 'Peace agreements cannot solve all problems', he argued, 'at best, they can be institutional and political frameworks and arrangements that enable the parties to continue working together on the issues agreed upon'. Behind these statements lies a message for creative conflict transformation and a conviction that a peace process should carry an agenda for change and broader socio-political and economic transformation.

In Nepal's case, the Comprehensive Peace Accord was a lengthy and ambitious document that included a range of agendas for the country's socio-economic transformation. The CPA promised a better Nepal where citizens' rights to issues such as health and education would be duly protected. The inherent message was to guide Nepal towards a welfare state while ensuring that democracy and the rule of law also flourished. While political slogans such as '*prosperous Nepal, happy Nepalis*' or '*building a new Nepal*' flourished in the post-conflict years, when it came to genuinely materialising the message of the CPA or the spirit inherent in these slogans, Nepal's political leadership has miserably failed.

Building on the spirit of the CPA, Nepal's 2015 constitution aimed to create a society focused on democratic socialism and a flourishing welfare economy. However, the realities on the ground do not reflect these aspirations. Despite the colossal political changes in the country over the last two decades, Nepali youths continue to flock to India, the Middle East, and East Asian countries to sell cheap labour, as employment opportunities at home are almost non-existent. Before the armed conflict, the number of Nepali youths who went for foreign employment was in the thousands. However, in post-CPA years, the number skyrocketed. For instance, in the fiscal year 2013/14 alone, as many as half a million Nepalis sought

foreign employment permits.²³⁵ In 2023, the number exceeded 770,000 (Pokharel 2024). Had the agenda of social transformation promised by the CPA been implemented, this should not have been the case.

Promises made in the health and education sectors have proven to be equally futile. While a few symbolic initiatives have been taken, the post-CPA governments have virtually forgotten the agenda of comprehensive social transformation, which was at the core of the CPA. Similarly, the rhetoric of constructing a 'new Nepal' has also practically lost its meaning. Nineteen years after the signing of the CPA, ordinary Nepalis still cannot see the changes that were promised. A new Nepal, a new world, and a new future that they eagerly awaited is nowhere in sight. As a result, there appears to be deep frustration over how things have unfolded in the post-CPA years. Despite ample promises, the CPA and the political structures and institutions built upon its foundation have repeatedly failed to deliver. As a key informant put it:

The peace process solved the issues of 19,602 Maoist combatants, but this country is of more than 30 million people. We still have people who work the whole day and go to bed hungry at night.²³⁶

Promises of socio-economic transformation and change were sprinkled through every significant political document that emerged after the 12-Point Understanding. The CPA, the 2007 Interim Constitution, and the 2015 Constitution were all documents of hope that promised a better future for ordinary Nepalis. Since many of the promises outlined in these documents remain unfulfilled, it is essential to explore why Nepal's post-conflict aspirations for change and rapid socio-economic transformation continue to be elusive.

Post-conflict governments in Nepal have been led by the 'agents of change' themselves. Since the start of the peace process, the Maoists and the traditional parliamentary parties in the SPA have consistently held power. However, the transformative capacity they demonstrated in regime change did not translate into effective political management in the post-conflict scenario.²³⁷ In addition, new forms of conflict and contestation emerged among former allies that had jointly spearheaded the political transformation. As one key informant explained:

The Maoists thought that they could not win the war, but they could use the peace process and emerge as winners. Similarly, the opposing side seemed convinced that, since the Maoists had renounced violence and joined the peace process, they, rather than the Maoists, had actually won the game. Because of this mutual disillusion, things did not progress as they should have.²³⁸

Within a matter of years, the political agendas which had accelerated both the armed insurgency and *Jana Andolan II* were gradually pushed aside. Instead, they were replaced by regional, ethnic, and somewhat populist agendas.²³⁹ As elections became new battlefields both for the Maoists and for the traditional parliamentary parties, resorting to 'unhealthy' means just for the sake of winning elections became

²³⁵ In 1993/94, the number of labour approvals issued by Nepal's Department of Foreign Employment was a mere 3,605 (Nepal Labour Migration Report 2022). See the report for an in-depth understanding of historical trends in Nepal's labour migration and how post-conflict Nepal has emerged as a remittance economy.

²³⁶ Interview with Bala Nanda Sharma (16.08.2017).

²³⁷ Interview with Prakash Bhattarai (12.07.2017).

²³⁸ Interview with Devendra Raj Pandey (02.08.2017).

²³⁹ Interview with Rajan Bhattarai (13.07.2017).

a common practice. As a result, elections not only became expensive, but also rife with 'criminal candidates' (Chetri 2018: 119–120). The self-inflicted pressure to win elections at any cost led political parties to adopt slogans designed to make them instantly popular and secure more seats in elected bodies. The gradual decline of agenda-based politics and the rise of election-based politics endangered many of the 'pro-people' and 'pro-change' agendas of the struggle era.

The Maoists, once viewed as a breath of fresh air in Nepal's traditional dirty politics, became increasingly distracted and disoriented by the new realities of parliamentary politics. While their success as a rebel force and an agent of change was remarkable, as a governing party, their performance was mediocre at best. Contrary to people's expectations, they could not implement the agendas of change they had long cherished and advocated for. Similarly, the dismantling of old feudal structures, such as the monarchy and its affiliates, and the inability to establish new, functional democratic institutions, resulted in what one key informant described as a situation of 'political anarchy and chaos'.²⁴⁰ In the flurry of change, a lot of promises were made. For example, the 2015 constitution includes the right to employment among many other rights. However, no concrete steps were taken to ensure that people could exercise these rights. The necessary institutional structures for implementing these rights were consistently ignored.

Nineteen years after the CPA, Nepal's peace process still stands at a crossroads. The end of a decade-long armed conflict is, of course, an achievement in itself and should not be belittled. However, since post-conflict Nepal has not lived up to its promises, the protagonists of the peace process are likely to face tougher questions in the days ahead. They have repeatedly failed to fulfil their promises and meet people's expectations. In other words, the lack of broader socio-economic transformation, people's unmet expectations, and declining trust in the agents of change create a breeding ground for social unrest and future conflicts in Nepal.

10.6 Different Lessons for Different Stakeholders

Since very little has been written about the potential lessons the Nepali peace process could offer, my aim in writing this chapter is to compile a set of 'lessons' that other peace researchers and practitioners would find helpful. As already discussed, the neglected transitional justice and national reconciliation process, as well as the marginalisation of women in the peace process, emerged as two key issues. These issues offer valuable lessons for practitioners to draw upon. However, the Nepali peace process provides many other lessons as well. The key informants I interviewed—who were deeply involved in Nepal's peace process and political transition both before and after the conflict—shared insights from their practices, and that primarily serves as the foundation for these lessons.

One of the notable characteristics of the Nepali peace process was that, despite receiving significant international input, it was primarily a 'home-grown' initiative. As I explained in Chapter 5, India did play a facilitative role in bringing the Maoists and the SPA together and sketching a joint roadmap for peace. Other countries also provided logistical, financial, moral, and similar support. Nevertheless, the peace process itself was, by and large, domestically driven. As I explained in previous chapters, the peace plan had already started to take shape with the 6-Point Agreement between the Maoists and the CPN (UML) in Gharti Gaun, Rolpa. In other words, after King Gyanendra seized absolute power in February 2005, Nepal's

²⁴⁰ Interview with Muma Ram Khanal (24.07.2017).

political climate was such that, sooner or later, a coalition between the forces that opposed the King's rule was inevitable.

The Maoist-SPA alliance, the 12-Point Understanding, *Jana Andolan II*, the peace process that followed, and the political changes that took place in the post-conflict context were all primarily driven by Nepal's domestic political needs. They were also led by Nepali political actors. As already mentioned, Nepal received significant logistical and financial support from various international donors, but the peace process primarily remained in Nepali hands. Nepal did invite a UN mission, UNMIN, but its role was primarily that of an observer and facilitator. The homegrown aspect of the peace process can be regarded as an achievement in itself because military and other forms of more invasive international engagements in post-conflict scenarios have been protracted, unsuccessful, and often controversial (see Blanken & Sullivan 2017, Sullivan et al. 2020, Kavanagh & Frederick 2023). Nepali actors, however, were able to avoid that scenario. As Sudheer Sharma put it:

As we have seen in many countries, when there is an international engagement, the way out is very difficult. In our case, yes, it took time. Yes, the transition took time, but we were able to solve everything, and that's an achievement in itself. We did not bring a UN military-type mission here, nor did we directly involve other neighbours, including India or any other power. However, we were able to resolve a situation that had almost become like a civil war.²⁴¹

Another lesson from the Nepali peace process is that dismantling primary state organs is not a prerequisite for post-conflict settlement. In terms of political restructuring, Nepal was transformed from a centralised unitary monarchical state into a decentralised federal democratic republic. However, most of the previous state organs, such as the security agencies, as well as judicial and basic administrative units, were kept mostly intact. The long-term effects of this decision are yet to be seen; nevertheless, it demonstrates that even complex and prolonged conflicts, such as Nepal's Maoist insurgency, can be resolved without dismantling the state's existing structures.²⁴²

A quick historical review of armed conflicts and peace processes in other regions shows that dissatisfied factions that reject a peace process often abandon it and resort to violence again (see Fujikawa 2024). In the case of Nepal's Maoists, that did not happen. While a faction within the Maoist party, led by Mohan Baidhya 'Kiran', opposed the party's decision to give up arms and accept what they called a treacherous compromise, they kept their reservations within the party and did not leave the peace process.²⁴³ While the faction ultimately split from the mainstream Maoist party in 2012, i.e., six years after the CPA, they continued to engage in peaceful politics.

After accusing Mohan Baidhya 'Kiran' of being a weak leader, a faction within Kiran's group formed a new party in 2014. The party was led by Netra Bikram Chand 'Biplov'. Biplov's party tried rebranding itself as a radical leftist party, like that of war-era CPN(Maoists), but the attempt was unsuccessful. Even though the party's activities were banned in Nepal, it was not involved in any large-scale armed action. It was, nonetheless, engaged in small-scale violent attacks, extortion, and demolition of public and private properties. Unable to receive much support from

²⁴¹ Interview with Sudheer Sharma (02.08.2017).

²⁴² Interview with Rajan Bhattarai (13.07.2017).

²⁴³ Interview with Mumaram Khanal (24.07.2017).

the public, the group accepted the government's peace talks proposals and, in March 2021, resurfaced to peaceful politics from underground.

The ability to cultivate a 'home-grown' peace process and prevent a conflict relapse can be considered two significant achievements of the Nepali peace process. However, a few other nuisances and practices 'adulterated' the peace process and prevented it from becoming what it could have truly become. One of the few issues that has rarely been discussed is the decision-making structure established during the peace process and political transition. The decision-making structure was highly centralised during the entire peace process and political transition, which prevented the peace process from becoming truly inclusive. As Bishnu Raj Upreti put it:

Politicians say that Nepal's peace process is unique all the time. It is unique in the sense that they sidelined the whole mechanism, and the five top leaders took charge of everything.²⁴⁴

On one hand, the practice of overly centralised decision-making was an unhealthy practice in a nascent democracy. On the other hand, it prevented the possibility of cultivating a peace process that could have had much broader ownership. Since crucial decisions of the peace process and post-conflict political arrangements were taken by a tiny group of top leaders from major political parties, people's representatives, civil society, women, and marginal groups were consistently sidelined.²⁴⁵ At times, the Constitutional Assembly, too, appeared to be a mere showpiece where decisions taken elsewhere were presented just for the sake of procedural and legal validity.

Similarly, the widespread, albeit often superficial, presence of international organisations in the post-CPA years has been identified as one of the reasons that slowed down CPA implementation and the constitution-making process. Devendra Raj Pandey, one of the five civil society observers present in the 2006 peace talks, argued that at times, international organisations, especially donor agencies and INGOs, overshadowed Nepali actors and effectively hijacked the 'field'. This not only slowed the overall pace of the peace process but also hindered the development of a genuinely homegrown peace process. As Pandey explained, there were too many seminars and too much roaming around from Nepal to foreign countries and vice versa.²⁴⁶ As Whitefield (2008: 11) also noted, this 'roaming around' had begun as early as 2002, with numerous workshops and visits organised under the banner of the Nepali conflict, often taking place in the capital cities of Western countries.

An unprecedented level of donor engagement in Nepal's peace process diverted the attention of elected representatives and public officials, who should have been focused on implementing the CPA and drafting the new constitution. Instead, they frequently travelled abroad to attend workshops and seminars. Mumaram Khanal, a member of the first Constituent Assembly (CA), recalled that the Assembly was often nearly empty, as members—divided into various caucuses—were frequently absent due to international travel. Khanal argued that some donor agencies invested heavily in stoking Nepal's 'ethnic psychology', often funding and supporting ethnic caucuses in the CA. This made parliamentary caucuses more influential than the CA itself. As a result, the second CA did not allow caucuses at

²⁴⁴ Interview with Bishnu Raj Upreti (03.08.2017).

²⁴⁵ Interview with Bishnu Raj Upreti (03.08.2017).

²⁴⁶ Interview with Devendra Raj Pandey (02.08.2017).

all.²⁴⁷

International support and solidarity in peace processes can be instrumental and desirable. Nepal, too, received plenty of international support from international organisations as well as from bilateral and multilateral donor agencies. Support came in different forms, shapes, and sizes—grant and loan assistance, logistical support, training and technical knowledge, and plain solidarity and goodwill. While some of this support was extremely important and needed, international organisations' haphazard entry and programs designed just for the sake of doing something often cluttered the manoeuvring space of Nepali actors and slowed down processes that were essential for the smooth progress of the peace process. In addition, as Hari Bahadur Thapa explained, it appeared that some donor agencies had flocked to Nepal solely because it was a conflict-ravaged country on the path to a peace process, and they, too, wanted to be part of the success story.²⁴⁸ Therefore, goodwill aside, some INGOs landed in Nepal and started working without a genuine need identification and lacked coordination with other agencies already working in the field. In this regard, Nepal's peace process serves as an example from which, among others, international donor agencies can also learn a lesson or two.

10.7 Chapter Summary: Analysing the Gaps in Nepal's Peace Process

This chapter critically examined Nepal's peace process and assessed its practical implications and outcomes on various key issues. The aim was rather pragmatic—to offer observations in the form of 'lessons', which can be valuable for mediation practitioners, negotiators, policymakers, political actors, and peace researchers working in conflict and post-conflict contexts. The chapter started by examining the political, military, and social dimensions of the Nepali peace process. The subsequent analysis examined whether the Nepali peace process could be considered a 'mission accomplished,' notwithstanding its inherent flaws and underlying challenges. The broader issue of when a peace process should be considered complete, as well as the implications of labelling a peace process as either 'complete' or 'incomplete', were also discussed. A significant focus of the chapter was on the issue of transitional justice in the Nepali peace process. Potential political motivations that hindered the transitional justice process and led to the abandonment of a national reconciliation program were also analysed. Nepal's peace process did achieve significant milestones, including a peace agreement, a cessation of hostilities agreement, and the completion of the Disarmament, Demobilisation, and Reintegration process. It also achieved many of its political goals, including state restructuring and the introduction of a new constitution written by people's representatives for the first time in Nepal's history. However, the failure to implement a functional transitional justice mechanism and an inclusive peacebuilding framework, along with the inability to achieve broader socio-economic transformation, cast a shadow over an otherwise successful peace process. This partial success, coupled with people's unmet expectations, poses risks for social unrest and potential future conflicts.

²⁴⁷ Interview with Mumaram Khanal (24.07.2017).

²⁴⁸ Interview with Hari Bahadur Thapa (20.07.2017).

11. Conclusions

This study examined India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition in the post-conflict era. The examination period was primarily, but not exclusively, confined to the years between 2005 and 2017. This period was marked by a series of tumultuous events that shook Nepal, including the culmination of an armed insurgency led by the CPN (Maoists), the rise of authoritarian rule under King Gyanendra, and a massive movement for peace and the restoration of democracy. In 2006, following the success of the pro-democracy mass movement (*Jana Andolan II*), King Gyanendra shed his authoritarian armour and yielded to the pro-democracy protests. The Maoists also ended their armed struggle to engage in peaceful politics, and Nepal entered a lengthy post-conflict political transition that lasted for over a decade. As the nascent republic experienced a series of political avalanches in the post-conflict era, India—one of Nepal's closest neighbours—was heavily involved, often exhibiting a complex character, transmitting both assistance and assertion.

While India's influence was acknowledged as critical and emphatic in Nepal's peace process and political transition, the specifics of its engagement remained largely unexplored. Its facilitation of the 12-Point-Understanding in New Delhi in November 2005, its role as an unofficial mediator of the 2006 peace accord, and its involvement in various other negotiations that took place during the political transition of the post-conflict era remained largely unclear. Against this backdrop, this study examined India's role in the Nepali peace process and the post-2005 political transition. By doing so, this study offers a fresh perspective on the Nepali peace process, prompts a re-evaluation of India–Nepal relations, and provides a different perspective on how India has projected and asserted itself as a rising power in South Asia. In addition to its primary focus, this study also offers a few theoretical and practical insights from the Nepali peace process that can be helpful for practitioners engaged in peacebuilding and post-conflict reconstruction efforts elsewhere.

A three-layered framework was used to address the main research question. The first layer involved analysing India's engagement in Nepal before the 2006 peace deal (i.e., between 2005 and early 2006). The second layer focused on India's influence during the peace deal period, particularly throughout 2006. Finally, the third layer centred on the post-peace deal years, from 2006 to the 2017 post-transition parliamentary elections. In line with the main research question, the overall objectives of this study were to understand India's motivation for its involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition. The study aimed to demonstrate how peace mediation practices vary across different contexts and are influenced by a range of historical, economic, and geopolitical factors. In addition, it sought to contribute to the mediation literature by highlighting the opportunities and challenges in mediation and post-mediation practices. The research also aimed to provide a broader perspective on mediators' post-mediation engagement in a developing country context and to examine mediation, peace processes, and post-conflict political transition through the lens of multiple theoretical perspectives.

Theoretically, this study drew from three domains: peace and mediation

research, international relations, and global development studies. Since peace mediation and political processes are closely tied to global and regional power relations as well as broader political and economic factors, this combination of various theoretical strands was both essential and beneficial.

The first theoretical domain focused on peace mediation and its use as a foreign policy tool, both historically and in the contemporary context (see Chapter 3, and, for instance, Touval 2003, Bercovitch 2011). This involved a thorough analysis of concepts such as mediators' motives, 'power mediators' and 'pure mediators' (see, for instance, Harris & Reilly 1998, Svensson 2007). The second domain explored various strands of critical international relations theories and looked at the broader picture of the global system. The focus was particularly on rising power behaviour, South–South Cooperation (see, for instance, Muhr 2016; Bergamaschi et al. 2017), and sub-imperialism (see, for instance, Bond & Garcia 2015, Valencia 2017, Gray & Gills 2017, Katz 2021). The third domain, grounded in world-systems and dependency theories, served essentially as an extension of the second domain. The world-systems and dependency theories—which offer both a long-term historical perspective and an analysis of economic relationships as well as global labour divisions—provided an excellent analytical lens for analysing India–Nepal relations, both in the post-conflict context and more broadly.

Collectively, the three theoretical domains revolved around one central issue: how the so-called rising powers of the Global South engage with their less powerful neighbours and reproduce the unequal power relations they themselves often experience with global superpowers. Drawing on examples from other contexts as well as India's engagement in post-conflict Nepal, I argued that the way so-called rising powers of the Global South engaged within their spheres of influence not only shattered the long-held dream of establishing a new international economic and political order but also created unequal regional relationships marked by dependencies, exploitation, and various forms of instability and aggression.

Methodologically, this study adopted a critical realist approach and is a singular case study. Data were accumulated from four sources: 1. Semi-structured key informant interviews, 2. Opinion pieces and media interviews (mainly of key informants unavailable for an interview), 3. Video talks and speeches, 4. Articles collected from Nepali media archives. A total of 18 key informant interviews were conducted, totalling 982 minutes. These were supplemented by 12 videos (360 minutes) and 105 textual sources—including opinion pieces, interviews, news articles, and in-depth reports—amounting to 750 pages of data. The qualitative content analysis method was used for data analysis, adopting an inductive approach rooted in grounded theory. McCracken's (1988) guidelines for analysing long qualitative interviews were used to enhance the data analysis process.

11.1 Main Findings

This study examined India's extensive engagement in Nepal in the post-conflict context and demonstrated how peace processes can be affected by a range of external interests and geopolitical vulnerabilities. This study is also an exploration of how, in a regional and global supremacy row, seemingly benign instruments, such as peace mediation, can be used as a foreign policy tool for perpetuating and consolidating dependency, strengthening and imposing extractivist motives and sub-imperialist manoeuvres, and achieving a wide range of foreign policy goals. Overall, this study provides deeper insights into the complexities of contemporary

peace processes, which are increasingly shaped by geopolitical, security, economic, and resource interests.

As per the objectives of the study, Chapter 5 examined the origins of the Nepali peace process. Discussing and analysing a series of political events in Nepal from as early as 2001, the chapter offered a broader view of the Nepali peace process and its gradual evolution. It demonstrated that while India's facilitative role in the 12-Point Understanding process was helpful, it was internal political dynamics accompanied by the Six-Point Agreement, signed between the Maoists and the CPN (UML) in Nepal's Rolpa district in October 2005, that had triggered and steered the peace process in Nepal.

Nevertheless, India portrayed itself as a peace broker of the Nepali peace process and used that identity to consolidate its presence in post-conflict Nepal. As discussed in Chapter 6, India actively meddled and micromanaged various political processes during Nepal's post-conflict political transition. For over a decade, it used both soft power and hard power instruments to maintain and tighten its grip on Nepal's political, bureaucratic, and security institutions. However, in the later years of the political transition, India's haphazard use of hard power instruments—such as coercive diplomacy and an economic blockade—faced strong resistance from both Nepali political actors and the public. In addition, India's attempt to reinstate Nepal as a Hindu nation was also unsuccessful.

Chapter 7 offered a thorough analysis of India's motives behind its engagement in Nepal's peace process and political transition. It demonstrated that India's engagement in Nepal's peace process and the political transition was not sudden and was intricately linked to the long and volatile relationship between the two countries—a relationship historically characterised by episodes of cooperation and co-dependency as well as coercion and conflict. Since already the 1950s, India's undeclared Nepal policy has been to reduce Nepal to a meek and pliable client state and, in return, fulfil its geopolitical, security, economic, and resource interests. In other words, India's actions in Nepal have been directed towards converting Nepal into one of its sub-imperialist destinations, gaining control over its natural resources (particularly water), and reproducing a world system based on neoliberal capitalism and various forms of aggression.

Through its sub-imperialist actions, India tightened its control over Nepali politics, domestic markets, and natural resources. As detailed in Chapter 8, while India has historically and gradually drawn Nepal into a web of dependencies, its relationship with global financial institutions and Western powers, particularly the United States, has also shown dependency patterns. For instance, it has been heavily indebted to international financial institutions—such as the World Bank and the IMF—and massively relies on the US to fulfil its security and defence needs. Similarly, India has become a sought-after destination for US-based corporations looking for cheap labour, where as many as a million Indians work mainly in back-office IT and call centre jobs for over 1,000 US-based firms (Moschella 2021). Moreover, India's participation in strategic security mechanisms such as the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue and the US Indo-Pacific Strategy suggests that India continues to serve as the US's junior partner or acts as its 'deputy sheriff' in the South Asian subcontinent.

Furthermore, India's sub-imperialist manoeuvres in South Asia are intertwined with its tendency for internal colonialism at home. As discussed in Chapter 8, this practice has catered well to neoliberal corporate capitalism and the proliferation of the Hindu-nationalist Hindutva political ideology. The mindset of a so-called 'rising

India' is reflected in its reckless domestic actions and exploitative interactions with its less powerful neighbours, such as Nepal.

The way India has engaged with Nepal—particularly in the post-conflict context but also otherwise—demonstrates that the economic and political rise of the so-called rising powers in the Global South, such as the BRICS, has not truly challenged Western neoliberal hegemony but has rather reinforced it through extractivist and oppressive policies. This undermines the hopes and dreams of particularly smaller and less powerful developing countries aspiring to create a just and more equitable world order. This also highlights the necessity for a deeper, more critical examination of both South–South cooperation and South–South conflict.

This study reveals that India's influence and Nepal's reliance on India grew significantly in post-conflict Nepal. As detailed in Chapter 9, India consistently used a mediator narrative—that it had initiated the Nepali peace process by facilitating the 12-Point Understanding—to consolidate its presence in Nepal. As a result, the Indian embassy in Kathmandu and representatives of Indian intelligence agencies became increasingly influential in striking post-conflict political deals in Nepal. Thus, Nepal experienced a state of 'peace dependency' in which its political actors became heavily dependent on India to find solutions to post-conflict political crises and to ensure post-conflict stability and peace. The concept of 'peace dependency' contributes to the mediation literature and can help understand and assess the complexities of post-conflict scenarios.

Finally, while the primary focus of this study was not on an exhaustive elaboration of lessons learnt from the Nepali peace process, the data analysis revealed a wealth of insights that could be useful for practitioners and policymakers. To ensure that these valuable observations are highlighted, I dedicated a separate chapter to them. Thus, Chapter 10 critiqued Nepal's peace and political transition process, highlighting its accomplishments and significant shortcomings, and offered valuable lessons for other peace and political transition processes in similar contexts.

Nepal's peace process completed important milestones, including a cessation of hostilities, a peace agreement, and the Disarmament, Demobilisation, and Reintegration process. It also achieved political milestones, such as state restructuring and the promulgation of a new constitution through a constituent assembly. However, these achievements represent only partial success. As discussed in Chapter 10, nineteen years have passed since the CPA, and Nepal has yet to address wartime atrocities through a transitional justice framework. A broader socio-economic transformation process—expected to take off right after the 2006 CPA—remains largely abandoned. Despite the partial and technical success, the lack of a transitional justice framework and the absence of broader socio-economic transformation make the Nepali peace process incomplete, making Nepal susceptible to new forms of social unrest and future conflicts.

11.2 Nepal's Peace Process: A Home-Grown Initiative with an External Facilitation

Exploring the origins of the Nepali peace process was one of the main objectives of this study. The 12-Point Understanding signed between the NCP (Maoists) and the Seven Party Alliance on 22 November 2005 in New Delhi ushered in a new era in Nepali politics. The 12-Point Understanding was instrumental in ending the Maoist armed insurgency, guiding Nepal towards republicanism and federalism, and making the country secular and more inclusive. Although there was no official

mediator for the 12-Point Understanding, India acted as an unofficial facilitator and later inflated its contribution, portraying itself as a key peace broker. Critics of the 12-Point Understanding process have often tended to label it as a ploy or a 'grand design' of the Indian establishment to abolish the China-leaning monarchy and consolidate India's proxy rule in Nepal.

Contrary to claims of foreign involvement, this study demonstrates that the 12-Point Understanding was primarily driven and shaped by Nepal's internal political dynamics. In other words, it resulted from the persistent efforts of Nepali political actors in the wake of King Gyanendra's coup in February 2005. As detailed in Chapter 5, the first significant milestone for the peace process was the Six-Point Agreement signed between the Maoists and the CPN (UML) in Nepal's Rolpa district in late October 2005. The Six-Point Agreement was a precursor to the 12-Point Understanding and contained similar themes.

The 12-Point Understanding was reached in New Delhi under special circumstances. For instance, communication between the Maoists and the SPA became increasingly difficult as the King's administration intensified its surveillance and repressive measures. This prompted the selection of New Delhi as a venue for further negotiations. This choice was more pragmatic than strategic. Senior Maoist leaders were already based in India, and the SPA leaders could travel there under various pretexts without causing much suspicion.

Nevertheless, India facilitated the 12-Point Understanding informally and unofficially. Leaders, who had participated in the negotiations in New Delhi, admitted that India, for instance, provided logistical support and ensured the smooth travel and accommodation of the SPA leaders visiting for the talks. The Indian government's official stance at the time was that the Maoists were a terrorist organisation. Despite that, Indian security and intelligence agencies did not interfere in the talks. In contrast, the Indian leadership secretly but actively communicated with Nepali leaders. By engaging with the Maoists as a political force rather than viewing them as a terrorist group, India helped create a supportive environment for the talks. This allowed the Maoists and the SPA leaders to enter discussions and outline a new roadmap for peace and democracy in Nepal. Some sources even claim that Indian officials reviewed and contributed to the draft of the 12-Point Understanding (see Muni 2012). The key informants I interviewed, some of whom had participated in the New Delhi negotiations, frequently used phrases such as 'goodwill', 'tacit support', or 'facilitation' to describe India's role in the talks that resulted in the signing of the 12-Point Understanding.

Moreover, the 12-Point Understanding was not an outcome of India's coercive diplomacy or its excellent mediation/facilitation skills. The power dynamics in Nepali politics necessitated such a solution at that time. The balance of power in Nepali politics had shifted from a trilateral to a bilateral one, and an alliance between the Maoists and the SPA was imminent, as both had been marginalised and suppressed by the King.

As argued in Chapter 9, from a theoretical perspective of conflict resolution, the convergence of Mutually Hurting Stalemate (MHS) (see, for instance, Zartman 1989, 2002, 2022) and Mutually Enticing Opportunity (MEO) (see, for instance, Crocker 1992, Mitchell 1995, Pruitt & Olczak 1995, Pruitt 1997, Ohlson 1998) acted as the catalyst for the Maoists and the SPA to unite, oppose the King's direct rule, and resolve the armed conflict through a negotiated settlement. Before King Gyanendra's royal takeover in February 2005, parties in the Seven Party Alliance were in power and oversaw security forces involved in conflict with the Maoists. The Maoists also carried out killings and abductions targeting SPA party cadres.

However, the political landscape underwent a dramatic shift when the King seized power through a coup. In the new scenario, the SPA and the Maoists faced a common adversary, making their previous antagonism counterproductive and leading to a mutually hurting stalemate (MHS).

Similarly, the Maoist-SPA partnership presented a Mutually Enticing Opportunity (MEO) for both. They knew that if they united, they could become Nepal's most potent political force. Unity would bring them additional domestic and international support and virtually guarantee a decisive victory against the King. Forming a coalition would enable them to reshape Nepali politics based on their shared vision. In short, for them, restoring peace and democracy under their leadership would provide two distinct benefits: public recognition for their concerted efforts and an unhindered ascent to power.

India's informal facilitation of the 12-Point Understanding can also be seen as leveraging an enticing opportunity. The protracted Maoist insurgency in Nepal posed a significant security threat to India. By the mid-2000s, it had begun to realise that using the armed insurgency in Nepal as a 'bargaining tool' was no longer viable, and continuing support for the increasingly unpopular King Gyanendra meant increased domestic pressure and international condemnation. Presented with a potential tipping point where a unified opposition (SPA and the Maoists) could prevail, India strategically supported the peace process and a democratic transition in Nepal. In other words, it aligned itself with the winning side and successfully safeguarded its long-term strategic interests in Nepal.

Based on the observations in this study, there appears to be a need to expand the scope of Mutually Hurting Stalemate (MHS) and Mutually Enticing Opportunity (MEO) to encompass parties beyond the direct belligerents in armed conflicts. In Nepal's case, mainly in the later stages, the armed conflict involved the Maoist rebels and government security forces led by the King. Yet, the peace process began when MHS and MEO aligned between the Maoists and the SPA. India, the facilitating party, also acted upon recognising an enticing opportunity. Broadening the application of MHS and MEO to include non-combatant stakeholders would also help explain why some conflicts attract significant mediation and facilitation efforts (see, for instance, Svensson & Onken 2015) while others are neglected and allowed to deteriorate.

11.3 India's Meddling and Micromanagement in Post-Conflict Nepal

Amid a violent armed conflict and King Gyanendra's oppressive direct rule, the 12-Point Understanding emerged as a beacon of hope for the Nepali people. After all, it outlined a roadmap for a peaceful, democratic, inclusive, and prosperous Nepal. Within just five months of its signing, the new political roadmap outlined in the 12-Point Understanding was approved in April 2006 through *Jana Andolan II*—a massive people's movement in which millions of Nepalis participated.

As previous works have also shown (see, for instance, Whitfield 2008, Destradi 2010, Shrestha 2012, Adhikari 2012, Sharma 2013, P. Jha 2014, Ghimire 2018a, Poudel 2018), India exerted significant influence and established a strong presence in post-conflict Nepal. As discussed in Chapter 6, it mediated, meddled, and micromanaged Nepal's post-conflict political processes for years. India became the uncontested and virtually sole international player during the political transition. It achieved that status in three phases. First, it portrayed itself—informally but

emphatically—as the architect of the Nepali peace process, often referring to the fact that the 12-Point Understanding was signed in New Delhi and under its facilitation. As this study has also demonstrated, India’s facilitation or tacit support was indeed helpful in uniting the Maoists and the SPA and reaching the 12-Point Understanding. However, India’s role was not as decisive as it was later portrayed. Since the common tendency among Nepali politicians was to avoid upsetting India, they did not challenge the Indian narrative, at least initially.

Second, India actively and successfully ousted other potential competitors from the field. Whether it was constraining the roles of the Switzerland-based Centre for Humanitarian Dialogue and the US-based Carter Centre (Whitfield 2008: 35) or accelerating the early departure of the UN Mission in Nepal and the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, India played an active role (Bhandari 2016). Third, through lobbying and persuasion, India secured Western support, particularly from influential powers such as the US, the UK, and the EU, for its role as an indisputable player in managing Nepal’s post-conflict political affairs.

After the monarchy was abolished in 2008, the absence of a 240-year-old established institution created a transitional power vacuum in Nepal, which India tactfully used to strengthen its presence in the country.²⁴⁹ This ultimately resulted in Indian intelligence agencies and the Indian embassy in Kathmandu acting as *de facto* deal-makers and mediators, settling Nepal’s post-conflict disputes and extensively micromanaging Nepal’s post-conflict domestic politics.

As discussed in Chapter 6, Nepali domestic politics, security agencies, and the bureaucracy were subjected to India’s influence and heavy micromanagement in the peace process and political transition years. India’s influence was profound, for instance, in dictating the terms of the interim constitution, shaping the environment of both the first and second Constituent Assembly elections, and pulling the strings of post-conflict government formations and toppling them every few months (Jha 2012: 337). India also unofficially mediated post-conflict negotiations between the Nepali governments and dissatisfied minority groups. When it came to political appointments, whether it was a government minister, a prominent police officer, or a Chief District Officer, India took a deep interest.²⁵⁰

When analysing India’s actions in Nepal through the lens of global power relations and international affairs, India used both soft power and hard power, as well as a combination of the two. India’s soft power strategies included development and cultural grants, disaster relief assistance, loans, scholarships, medical treatments, and visits and training targeted at Nepali bureaucrats. India, for instance, provided over USD 67 million in aid following the 2015 earthquakes in Nepal. Its 2019–20 budget allocated INR 1200 crore (approx. 147 million EUR) as ‘aid to Nepal’. In its 2024/25 budget, it allocated a grant of INR 7 billion (approx. 74.5 million EUR) to Nepal (Onlinekhabar 2024). India also loaned over USD 1.65 billion for several infrastructure projects and post-earthquake reconstruction work (EOI Kathmandu 2020).

India’s assistance, however, came with numerous strings attached. As one of the key informants I interviewed noted, India sought dividends, in one form or another, for nearly all its aid and assistance to Nepal.²⁵¹ It has also become increasingly clear

²⁴⁹ Interview with a journalist (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

²⁵⁰ Interviews with an expert key-informant, a senior political leader, and a journalist (interview year 2017 names and interview dates redacted).

²⁵¹ Interview with a senior political leader (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

that India's assistance to Nepal is often aimed at maintaining a compliant regime in Kathmandu. The support that India provides in various forms serves as an incentive for Nepali leaders to adopt pro-Indian economic, political, and defence policies. For Nepal, accepting assistance from India or being chronically dependent on it has also involved signing unequal treaties, granting Indian companies access to valuable natural resources, sharing intelligence with Indian security agencies, and supporting India in multilateral international forums.

As this study has explored, in the early years of the peace process and political transition, India relied more on strategies such as micromanagement and power diplomacy. When those strategies were gradually defied and ignored by Nepali political actors, India resorted to harsher and more aggressive options, such as coercive diplomacy and an economic blockade. For example, despite India's reservations and coercive diplomacy, when Nepal's Constituent Assembly enacted a new constitution in 2015, India responded by imposing an economic blockade on Nepal. The blockade lasted for nearly five months, causing a humanitarian crisis. As Nepal faced the repercussions of the economic blockade, India continued to exert pressure by ostracising and isolating Nepal in international forums (see Chapter 6).

India's strategic interests in Nepal have also tended to fluctuate in response to shifts in political leadership in India. For instance, when the Bharatiya Janata Party came to power in India in 2014, restoring Nepal's identity as a Hindu nation appeared to be one of its top priorities. When Nepal was declared a secular republic in 2008, the Indian National Congress, a vocal supporter of secular principles, was in power in India and supported Nepal's transition to secularism. Nevertheless, despite variations such as these, India's long-term interests in Nepal—geopolitical, economic, and resource-related—have remained relatively consistent.

India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition reflects a broader trend in modern foreign policy practice, where powerful countries increasingly employ a combination of forceful (hard power) and persuasive (soft power) tactics to achieve their objectives. This approach, often referred to by scholars as 'smart power' (see Nye 2009, 2013), has become increasingly common because such combinations are viewed as effective for advancing and pursuing the actor's agendas (Wilson III 2008).

However, India's hard power faced significant resistance and proved to be largely counterproductive in Nepal. Despite its considerable influence, India was unable to shape major political developments as it desired. The abolition of the monarchy, Nepal's transition to secularism, and the provincial demarcations significantly diverged from India's preferences. It was also unable to influence the content of Nepal's 2015 constitution or prevent its promulgation. Moreover, despite India's efforts to prevent it, Nepal signed new transit agreements with China and joined the BRI.

Although India successfully engaged in minor power manoeuvres, its hard power strategies—such as coercive diplomacy and an economic blockade—led to a rise in anti-India sentiment and protests in Nepal. Evidence from India's involvement in post-conflict Nepal challenges the arguments previously advanced by some scholars that India's foreign policy is mainly driven by soft power strategies (see, for instance, Wagner 2005, Tharoor 2011, Malone 2011), and that it promotes democracy (Janjua 2007, Anderson 2014, H.B. Jha 2014), with the intention of positioning itself as a benevolent hegemon in South Asia (Destradi 2010).

11.4 India: A Benign Rising Power or a Sub-Imperialist Regional Hegemon?

India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition represented an intensified episode of its engagement. However, as Nepal's immediate neighbour and a key regional player, India has consistently exerted influence and pressure on Nepal. India's involvement has influenced and shaped Nepali politics and its modern history. As I noted in earlier chapters, this 'perennial presence' poses methodological challenges for analysing contemporary India–Nepal relations. Therefore, drawing on relevant historical references and establishing deeper and critical connections is essential to understanding India's actions and motives in Nepal.

As discussed in Chapter 7, the story of India–Nepal relations is one of a long-standing historical dependency. Historical evidence shows that India's actions in Nepal, dating back to the early 1950s, were aimed at transforming Nepal into a compliant client state. Thus, India's intensified engagement in Nepal's post-2005 peace process and political transition, too, was consistent with its long-term, unofficial Nepal policy. Through both its benevolent and ruthless engagements in Nepal, India sought to reinforce dependency and establish Nepal as one of its sub-imperialist domains.

Although India has both short and long-term strategic interests in Nepal, two issues are fundamental to India's long-term Nepal policy. First, India seeks to transform Nepal into a more compliant client state by minimising the influence of other countries while consolidating its own dominance. Second, it aims to fully leverage Nepal's economic and resource potential. In other words, as discussed in Chapters 7 and 8, in addition to the geopolitical motives for tightening its grip on Nepal, India also has significant economic and resource interests.

While analysing India–Nepal relations, it is common to emphasise India's security and geo-strategic interests. However, India's economic interests in Nepal are also substantial. For decades, Nepal has endured the weight of India's economic dominance. Nepal's economy is both highly reliant and focused on India, with India often, directly or indirectly, dictating the terms of the trade deals between the two countries. Indian companies remain the largest source of foreign direct investment in Nepal, accounting for over 35–40% of the total foreign direct investments in the country (G.S. Wagle 2016, Khanal 2024). India has also been accused of effectively 'killing' Nepal's small industries, especially agriculture, by inundating Nepali markets with government-subsidised and mass-produced products (Shrestha 2018).

India exports nearly 700 commodities to Nepal, mainly manufactured goods, such as machinery, pharmaceuticals, processed petroleum, and consumer goods (OEC 2022). Whereas Nepal's meagre exports to India consist of raw materials and small-scale consumer and agricultural products (see Shrestha 2023). The trade deficit between the two countries has skyrocketed over the years. For instance, in the first six months of the fiscal year 2022/23, Nepal exported goods worth only NPR 57.84 billion to India, while it imported goods worth NPR 486.33 billion from India, resulting in a substantial trade deficit of NPR 428.33 billion for Nepal (My Republica 2023).

Nepal also 'exports' cheap and mainly unskilled labour to India, where an estimated 8 million Nepalis work low-skilled, low-wage menial jobs, mostly as security guards, cooks, cleaners, and taxi drivers. It is estimated that as many as 7000 Nepali women are trafficked every year to India, where they are forced to work

as sex workers (Sanghera & Kapur 2000, Dhungel 2021). More than 32,000 Nepali men serve in the Indian army, fighting lethal wars and protecting India's borders and territorial integrity (Shrestha A. 2022).

For India, Nepal is an important and growing export market. Despite having a relatively smaller economy, Nepal ranks as one of India's top export destinations. For instance, in 2022, it was India's eleventh-largest export market, right after Germany and Belgium (Indian Trade Portal 2022). Already a decade ago, more than 500 Indian companies operated in Nepal in sectors such as banking, consumer goods, minerals, pharmaceuticals, telecommunications, energy, and automobiles (IANS 2014). These companies had two main goals: first, to earn a profit and send it to their headquarters in New Delhi, and in some cases, to key imperialist centres such as New York or London; and second, to explore and exploit Nepal's resources to identify ways to collect and maximise profit.

In addition to solidifying its presence in the Nepali markets, India has continually sought to ensure unrestricted access to Nepal's natural resources, especially water. As discussed in Chapter 7, the water treaties and agreements between the two countries have been characterised by significant inequalities, largely favouring India's interests over Nepal's. This imbalance is evident in all major water agreements between the two countries, including the Sharada Dam (1927), the Koshi Agreement (1954), the Gandak Agreement (1959), the Tanakpur Agreement (1991), and the Mahakali Treaty (1996). These treaties and agreements not only favour India (see, for instance, Gaudel 2013: 16-17, Chandra & Prasad 2020, Bagale 2020), but they were also signed in haste or under duress when Nepal was in an unstable or transitional political environment (Gyawali & Dixit 1999, 2000, 2001). Moreover, India has been consistently reluctant to follow the terms and conditions of these agreements and compensate Nepal with the agreed-upon benefits. India's motive in these cases has often been to hold the projects and leave them in limbo as a strategy to prevent the entry of a potential third party.²⁵² India has also actively discouraged and thwarted foreign investment in Nepal's hydroelectricity sector, among others, by refusing to purchase electricity produced by companies other than Indian (see Chapter 7).

In addition to hydroelectricity, water, as a scarce resource, has remained a central focus in India's dealings with Nepal. India is already facing water scarcity, and some Indian states are expected to encounter a severe water crisis in the future (Gupta 2008, Gulati & Banerjee 2016). Water and energy scarcity have been identified as two of the most significant constraints for India's economic aspirations (Kumar & Furlong 2012). Among other challenges, India has historically faced domestic issues in hydroelectricity production, partly due to civil society's resistance to dam construction projects (Bharadwaj et al. 2006).

Whether for hydroelectricity, irrigation, or drinking water, Nepal's water resources are a valuable commodity for India. Since water is already scarce in India, ensuring unrestricted access to Nepal's water resources is part of India's strategy to secure future water supplies for its water-scarce regions. With over 6,000 rivers, numerous lakes, springs, and snow cover, Nepal is an appealing destination for water appropriation. Similarly, hydroelectricity has clearly been of interest to India, given that Nepal's potential for economically viable hydroelectric power production is estimated to be between 42,000 and 83,000 MW (Gunatilake et al. 2020: 3). Apart from using Nepal's water resources for drinking water, irrigation, and hydroelectricity, Indian companies have recently been eyeing Nepali rivers for

²⁵² Interview with an expert key informant (interview year 2017, name and interview date redacted).

green hydrogen production as well (Dhungana 2023a, 2023b). Green hydrogen, produced cheaply from Nepali waters, would provide India with two benefits. First, it would generate significant profit for Indian energy firms, and second, it would help India reach its ambitious goal of reducing carbon emissions by 50% by 2030.

In an ideal scenario, Nepal's water resources could have provided mutual benefits to both Nepal and India. Indian capital and technological expertise could have been leveraged, while Nepal could monetise its unutilised water resources. However, India's hydro-hegemonic tendencies (see Hanasz 2014, Bagale 2020, Tandan 2021), reflected in controversial proposals, such as constructing dams in Nepali territory for unilateral control over water flow, have prevented the possibility of mutual benefits.

While water resources are India's primary focus, its resource interests in Nepal are diverse. Indian firms, for instance, are involved in extracting and transporting stone, gravel, and sand from Nepal's mountains (Ghimire 2021). Nepal's rich biodiversity includes 700 flowering plant species with medicinal properties (Pokharel & Ghimire 2017). Many of these plants and herbs are sold or smuggled to Indian firms as raw commodities (Basnet 2019). They are then sold back in Nepali markets and elsewhere at a much higher price, generating a hefty surplus.

In addition to Indian private firms and multinational corporations, government entities in India also invest in and profit from Nepal's natural resources. As discussed in the case of the West Seti Hydropower project and the involvement of NHPC Limited (see Chapter 7), the Indian state operates 277 industrial and business entities, known as central Public Sector Undertakings (PSUs). These PSUs dominate vital industries, such as oil and gas, utilities, mining, heavy engineering, and banking, and have contributed roughly 20% to India's GDP for over thirty years (Chandra & Walton 2020: 191). The primary aim of these PSUs, which also operate in India's neighbouring countries, including Nepal, is to accumulate profit, strengthen Indian state capitalism, and ultimately enhance India's status as a regional hegemon.

11.4.1 The Dual Facets of Domination: Regional Sub-Imperialism and Internal Colonialism

In this thesis, India is examined as a sub-imperialist power in South Asia. As I discussed in Chapter 3, sub-imperialist powers are not major imperialist powers themselves but play a regional 'imperialist' role in exploiting and dominating neighbouring countries while still being dependent on imperialist powers. Sub-imperialist powers are characterised by their intermediary position in the global capitalist system, their relative autonomy from the dominant imperialist centres, and their own expansionist tendencies (Marini 1972). These powers tend to amplify the global economics of neoliberalism and the politics of elite consolidation rather than challenge them (Bond 2013).

In Chapter 3, I also argued that sub-imperialism serves as the best theoretical framework for examining and understanding India's involvement in post-conflict Nepal. Even though previous works on India–Nepal relations have not applied this particular theoretical vantage point, scholars investigating contemporary sub-imperialism elsewhere have highlighted sub-imperialist positions of other so-called middle powers or rising powers of the Global South, such as Brazil, South Africa, Turkey, and Saudi Arabia (see Chapter 3).

India has rarely been examined as a sub-imperialist power, a task this study undertook. India's sub-imperialism is evident, for instance, in its historical and

gradual economic and political subordination of Nepal. Even though Nepal has repeatedly resisted India's domination, its dependence on India remains substantial and multifaceted. India's sub-imperialism in Nepal is expressed in many forms, including perpetual economic and political dependence, unequal treaties, the presence of Indian military troops on Nepali soil, and the exploitation of Nepali men and women as sources of cheap labour. It also manifests through loans and credits, and the systematic attempts to control Nepal's natural resources.

India's role as a sub-imperialist agent is closely tied to its position in the global power hierarchy. As discussed in Chapter 8, although India holds regional dominance in South Asia, it remains subordinate to and dependent on the advanced capitalist economies of the West, especially the United States. In other words, while India seeks to entrap smaller and less powerful countries like Nepal in its web of dominance and exploitation, it is also caught in a similar relationship with global imperialist powers and financial institutions. In a broader sense, India primarily serves as a conduit for the interests of larger imperialist powers, even as it pursues its own hegemonic ambitions and aspirations. This dialectical relationship illustrates the complex and hierarchical nature of the global imperialist system. It also shows how sub-imperialist powers like India both reinforce and are limited by the structures of global hegemony and global capitalism.

As elaborated in Chapter 8, India is indebted to global financial giants such as the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, and the Asian Development Bank. These major financial institutions are Nepal's creditors as well. However, for Nepal, in addition to these neoliberal financial institutions, India is one of the biggest creditors (Rijal 2022). India's dual position as a debtor to global financial institutions and a creditor to small states like Nepal exemplifies its intermediary position within the global financial hierarchy and its sub-imperialist status.

India has a long history of supporting, training, and selling arms to Nepali security forces. The United States and the US military have done the same to the Indian military. For India, Nepal is a lucrative arms trade destination, and for the United States, India holds the same status. Between 2018 and 2024 alone, India bought over USD 15 billion worth of arms and military equipment from the United States (Patel 2024). Historically, India has been one of the largest recipients of US economic aid. For instance, between 1946 and 2012, it received around USD 65.1 billion in economic assistance, making it the top beneficiary of US assistance during that period—surpassing even key allies like Israel and Egypt (Rajghatta 2015). India's role in training and arming Nepali forces, while simultaneously being a major recipient of US military and economic aid, positions it as a conduit for US military influence in South Asia. This arrangement allows India to project power regionally while still remaining dependent on US support.

In Chapter 8, I argued that the gradual 'securitisation' of BIMSTEC was part of India's broader strategy to strengthen itself as a sub-imperialist power in South Asia. India actively forms and maintains its prominent position in regional political and military alliances, such as SAARC and BIMSTEC. However, it also participates in similar mechanisms created by Western powers, particularly the United States. India's active participation in strategic security mechanisms, such as the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue and the US-led Indo-Pacific strategy, is one relevant example. These instances show how India negotiates a balance between regional leadership and alignment with the United States' interests. This balance ultimately reinforces India's sub-imperialist position as it seeks to establish regional dominance within the framework of the US global strategy.

Financial dependency, often manifested through trade, investments, and credit,

plays a significant role in sustaining this relationship. While India is the 10th largest trading partner of the United States, the US is India's largest trading partner (US Census Bureau 2017). India is also a sought-after investment destination for major US corporations. For instance, in 2021 alone, US investments in India stood at over USD 45 billion, whereas foreign direct investment from India in the United States was merely USD 2.95 billion (Statista 2021a, Statista 2021b). This discrepancy makes India susceptible to pressure from the US regarding trade and economic matters. The considerable trade imbalance and differences in foreign direct investment between India and the United States illustrate India's economic vulnerability to the US influence. This economic relationship mirrors the trade deficit and foreign direct investment disparity between India and Nepal. In addition, this also mirrors classic core-periphery dynamics (see Chapter 3), in which India occupies a semi-peripheral position and remains a dominant force in its immediate region but is subordinate to global powers.

Labour exploitation is another key factor in this sub-imperialist relationship. For India, Nepal has been a source of cheap labour for decades. As already mentioned, thousands of Nepali citizens not only fight in India's wars as recruits for its national army, but an estimated 8 million Nepalis also work in mostly low-skilled, low-wage menial jobs across many Indian cities (Sanghera & Kapur 2000, Dhungel 2021, Shrestha A. 2022). While India takes advantage of low-cost Nepali workers primarily in the informal economic sectors, US-based corporations have adopted similar strategies to take advantage of India's 'cheaper' labour force. It is estimated that more than 1,000 US-based multinational corporations have set up their operations in India, employing as many as 1 million Indians in various roles, including back-office IT and call centres (Moschella 2021). India's exploitation of Nepali labour and US companies' use of cheaper Indian labour demonstrate the multi-tiered nature of global labour exploitation. India's role in this chain positions it as both an exploiter and the exploited, a typical feature of contemporary sub-imperialism.

The Indian establishment seeks to portray India as economically and politically ambitious, as well as militarily strong and independent. However, the ground reality tells a different story. India is heavily dependent on the US to fulfil its defence needs (see Chapter 8). India's reliance on US security cooperation and support for US military actions, such as those in Afghanistan, suggests a degree of foreign policy subordination to US interests.

India's regional actions, too, are shaped, at least partially, by its relationship with the United States. India has been obliged to cooperate with the US on issues such as trade and security for a long time. The aim of 'countering China' also brings the two countries together, and for the United States, no other nation compares to India in 'balancing' China. In other words, US foreign policy in South Asia is largely shaped by its ties with India and by India's relations with its neighbouring countries. Thus, in the contemporary international system, India functions as the US's junior partner in South Asia and plays a key role in maintaining and extending the US-led hegemonic world order.

Having acted as a regional proxy for US interests, it has been easier for India to strengthen its own regional influence. However, contrary to the narratives of an independent and rising India—a narrative that New Delhi actively promotes—India remains subordinated and significantly constrained within the US-led global hegemonic order. Nevertheless, like Nepal's efforts to free itself from India's sub-imperialist influence, there are signs that India is also trying to create an independent global identity, occasionally distancing itself from the influence of the

United States. As a result, India's foreign policy sometimes closely aligns with US interests, while at other times, it asserts its own autonomy.

This raises an additional and obvious question: How does India, with its sub-imperialist manoeuvres in its neighbourhood, manage domestic affairs and govern its citizens? As discussed in Chapter 8, India's sub-imperialism in the neighbourhood is intertwined with its tendency for internal colonialism at home. In other words, Nepal's challenges with the Indian political class mirror those faced by ethnic, linguistic, and religious minorities and many other ordinary Indians.

India has been accused of converting itself into a colonial power almost from the moment it became sovereign. Shortly after its independence from the British Raj, India developed the habit of addressing political conflicts using military interventions. It did not hesitate to annexe territories and wage war within its own borders (Roy 2011). Similarly, the Indian ruling class adopted a development model designed to serve corporate interests and facilitated the aggressive growth of corporate capitalism. As a result, amidst an enduring focus on economic growth and the rhetoric of a rising and glorious India, many pressing social and political issues were sidelined and forgotten (see, for instance, Kohli 2012, Bhalariao 2021). In the so-called rising India, internal displacements of massive scale (see Singh Negi & Ganguly 2011) and large-scale land grabs and plundering of natural resources became increasingly common (Levien 2018, Chettri 2020).

Domestically, India's internal colonialism is visible in its treatment of marginalised groups and its ruthless actions in resource-rich hinterlands. Certain regions and populations in India face economic underdevelopment and oppression relative to the core. As explored by Dey (2019), India's internal colonialism is expressed through three main forms: the subordination of ethno-racial and non-Hindu religious groups, the subordination of regions not dominated by the descendants of Ancestral North Indians in North and West Indian states, and the subordination of rural populations by urban elites and an Anglicised India. Particularly under the Bharatiya Janata Party's leadership, India has attempted to reconstruct its identity based on the Hindutva fundamentalist ideology and facilitated the proliferation of extractivist corporate capitalism. As a result, minorities, such as Muslims and Dalits, have been subjected to systemic discrimination and violence (Jaffreot 2021).

While an exhaustive investigation and an analysis of India's internal colonialism is beyond the scope of this thesis, there are clear indications that as Nepal endures the oppression of India's sub-imperialism, ordinary Indians—particularly minorities and people living in economically disadvantaged and marginalised areas—suffer under the Indian state that has increasingly become oppressive and abusive. Against this backdrop, the connection between sub-imperialism and internal colonialism, or the concept of overlapping hegemonies, demands further investigation and analysis, a task that future researchers can undertake.

11.4.2 Autonomy in the Face of Domination: Nepal's Resistance to Indian Sub-imperialism

India's sub-imperialism in Nepal shares similarities with other sub-imperialist cases (see, for instance, Çağlı 2009, Christensen 2013, Bond 2015, Valencia 2017). As is typical in contemporary sub-imperialism, India's sub-imperialism in Nepal, too, is centred around controlling critical natural resources and raw materials, reaping geopolitical and strategic benefits, and reproducing a world system based on neoliberal capitalism and various forms of aggression. However, a key

distinction is that India's sub-imperialism has faced strong resistance and defiance in Nepal—a level of opposition not typically observed in other sub-imperialist projects.

On several occasions, Nepal has challenged and resisted India's sub-imperialist manoeuvres (see Chapter 8). The larger power asymmetry between the two countries and Nepal's vast economic dependence on India have somehow compromised Nepal's ability to fully challenge India's control and domination. Despite this limitation, Nepal has continued to assert its sovereignty and challenge India's dominance whenever possible. In other words, despite numerous challenges, Nepali political actors have used the agency available to them to resist India's sub-imperialist aggression. India's sub-imperialism in Nepal, or contemporary India–Nepal relations, reflects elements of dependency and domination, but also dissent and defiance.

Nepal's dissent and defiance are evident in several key historical events and policy decisions. For instance, as early as the 1970s, Nepal successfully removed 17 out of 18 Indian military checkpoints from its northern border and stood firm on the issue of its sovereignty. During the 1962 Sino-Indian War, Nepal remained neutral despite India's pressure to support it. Similarly, despite India's extensive lobbying against it, Nepal moved forward with its Zone of Peace (ZoP) proposal, though the proposal ultimately stalled primarily due to India's opposition. In regional forums such as SAARC, Nepal presented proposals that were unpalatable to the Indian establishment. In 2006, as the people's movement (*Jana Andolan II*) for peace and the restoration of democracy reached its peak in Nepal, India actively lobbied and put pressure on Nepal's political parties to preserve the monarchy at least in some form. However, Nepali political actors successfully resisted India's pressure and ultimately abolished the 240-year-old monarchy in 2008.

Moreover, as discussed throughout this thesis, Nepal promulgated its 2015 constitution despite India's pressure to refrain from doing so. India responded by imposing an economic blockade, which prompted strong protests from Nepal. Despite multiple attempts, India was unable to shape Nepal's new constitution according to its wishes (see Chapter 6). Particularly after the increased Indian interference in the post-conflict period, Nepal asserted its sovereignty by advocating for the principle of equal sovereignty in its relationship with India. This concept, akin to the principle of sovereign equality in the UN Charter, asserts that all nations—regardless of size, population, or economic power—are equal in their sovereignty and possess the right to self-determination.

In addition, Nepal began to diversify its foreign relations to lessen its dependency on India. The most notable examples include signing new trade and transit agreements with China following India's 2015 economic blockade, joining China's Belt and Road Initiative despite India's opposition, and awarding major infrastructure projects to non-Indian firms. When India's interference and domination were perceived to be excessive, there were anti-India street protests in Nepal on several occasions. These examples of resistance show that Nepal occupies a dual position, both as a target of Indian sub-imperialism and a notable exemplar of resistance against it. Similarly, contemporary India–Nepal relations are characterised by an interplay of cooperation and conflict, as well as episodes of compliance and resistance.

11.5 New Hegemons, Old Problems: The Disappointing Reality of Rising Powers' Ascent

The degree to which BRICS has recently accommodated imperialism—especially in matters related to economic and ecological crises—suggests that critics should more forcefully confront the general problem of sub-imperial re-legitimation of neoliberalism (Bond 2013: 231).

As a handful of countries in the Global South have become economically more prosperous and politically and militarily more powerful, their behaviour has raised both speculation and concern. In fact, in recent years, rising power behaviour has emerged as a distinct field of study. The gradual economic and political rise of a handful of countries in the Global South initially sparked optimism as they were expected to challenge the existing global hegemony and usher in the long-anticipated New International Economic Order. Hopes were also high for South–South Cooperation as these economically empowered and politically emboldened nations were expected to foster collaboration in their regions and beyond.

However, as this case of India's engagements in post-conflict Nepal also demonstrated, contrary to earlier expectations, the so-called rising powers of the Global South have not succeeded in challenging or restructuring global hegemonic structures, nor have they become a beacon of hope for the economic and political emancipation of the Global South. Instead, they have often chosen to align themselves with existing global powers and have resorted to crafting their own hegemonic aspirations and spheres.

As previously mentioned, South–South Cooperation—both as a practical tool and a promising theoretical concept—sparked my interest in conducting this research. Like many other optimists (see, for instance, Mawdsley 2012, Carmody 2013, Cheru 2016, Muhr 2016), I also saw ample promise in South–South Cooperation and believed in its emancipatory potential. However, as this study's findings also showed, the rhetoric of South–South Cooperation adopted by the so-called rising powers in the Global South has turned out to be just that—mere rhetoric. In other words, the SSC rhetoric they use clearly aims to secure a stronger position within the US-centred world order rather than challenge it (see, for instance, Vanaik 2013, Bond & Garcia 2015, Bond et al. 2021). The tendency of rising powers to position themselves as regional hegemons or as sub-imperialist agents for global hegemonic powers has dashed the hopes of many developing countries, including Nepal, that had envisioned a fairer, more equitable global economic and political system.

As scholars studying contemporary sub-imperialism have noted (see, for instance, Çağlı 2009, Bond 2015, Valencia 2017, Bond et al. 2021), the so-called rising powers often position themselves as sub-imperialist agents to support their ascent in the global political and economic hierarchy. As I explored throughout this thesis, India's engagement in Nepal clearly supports that proposition. In their pursuit of emulating Western hegemonic powers, rising powers like the BRICS bloc have adopted repressive policies both domestically and in their neighbourhood. Their economic rise has typically relied on extractivist, exploitative, and repressive policies, and a reckless adoption and expansion of neoliberal corporate capitalism. Similarly, instead of challenging Western domination of global governance and decision-making mechanisms, they have largely focused on ensuring their representation in the existing global governance structures. However, when it

aligns with their economic and geopolitical interests, they have not hesitated to take an independent course. A relatively recent example is India's divergence from the Western stance on Russia's invasion of Ukraine (Menon & Rumer 2022).

Overall, the findings of this study indicate that both the concept and practice of South–South Cooperation require more critical scrutiny. For example, as documented in this thesis, India's actions in Nepal significantly deviate from the principles and practices typically associated with South–South Cooperation. Rather than unwavering cooperation, India's actions in Nepal reflect a ruthless rising-power mentality. Furthermore, while highlighting exemplary cases of South–South Cooperation is valuable, South–South conflicts also warrant greater attention.

As this study has demonstrated, Indian sub-imperialism has encountered persisting resistance and defiance in Nepal. This indicates that a meaningful opposition to the current neoliberal global system is unlikely to emerge from the so-called rising powers of the Global South or the elite coalitions like the BRICS. Instead, it is relatively less powerful countries like Nepal—along with bottom-up grassroots movements and counter-hegemonic networks—that are more likely to challenge both traditional imperialism and the sub-imperial actions and ambitions of emerging powers.

11.6 Power Mediation and Pitfalls of Peace Dependency

This study looked at Nepal's peace process and post-conflict political transition from a peace and mediation research perspective, too. Previous studies show that the global pattern of conflict mediation is uneven. Some conflicts receive excessive attention from mediators and, thereby, are over-mediated, while others are less appealing and remain under-mediated (Greig & Diehl 2012, Svensson & Onken 2015: 69–70; Lundgren & Svensson 2020). Mediation literature also focuses on mediators' motives. The motives 'behind mediation' and the motives 'beyond mediation' are both relevant. Regional powers, such as India in this case, are often considered to be 'power' mediators (see Harris & Reilly 1998, Svensson 2007: 230). Power mediators can exercise a range of strategies, such as incentives and punishments, and can put pressure on conflicting parties to accept a compromise (Harris & Reilly 1998).

India's involvement in Nepal's peace process—which began through an informal facilitation of the Maoist-SPA 12-Point Understanding in New Delhi in November 2005—confirms that third-party involvement in peace processes extends beyond just peacemaking. As critics of third-party involvement in mediation and peacebuilding have argued, while mediators may have some interest in fostering peace, their primary motivation is often to advance their own self-interests (see Zartman & Touval 1996; Cunningham 2010). The findings of this study support the argument that when powerful international actors are involved, mediation often serves as a strategic tool of foreign policy, which can be used to expand influence or to achieve foreign policy goals (see Touval 1992, 2003, Bercovitch 2011, Butler 2018). As this study has proposed, there is also a danger of 'peace dependency', when the third party involved is a powerful neighbouring state, as was the case with India.

As detailed in Chapter 9, after Nepal's 2006 peace deal, India strategically positioned itself as an informal mediator and the de facto architect of the country's post-conflict political transition, despite playing only a limited role in the initial stages of conflict resolution. The strategic narrative framing India as a 'peace broker' helped solidify its presence and expand its influence in post-conflict Nepal.

While India's role in the 12-Point Understanding process was primarily facilitative (see Chapter 5), the amplified narrative of its success as a peace broker strengthened its position in the post-conflict context. As a result, India exerted significant influence over Nepal's post-conflict political landscape, and Nepali political actors began to increasingly rely on India to manage post-conflict political crises in the country.

India, for instance, influenced the 2006 Comprehensive Peace Accord, the 2007 Interim Constitution, the management of Maoist combatants, and the departure of the UN mission, UNMIN. India also unofficially mediated the negotiations between the Nepali government and the Madhesi and other dissatisfied groups. As demonstrated in Chapters 6, 7, and 9, India's influence in post-conflict Nepal permeated major political decisions. This pervasive involvement—often accompanied by 'mundane mediations' and covert operations—allowed India to micromanage Nepal's internal affairs, frequently prioritising its own political, economic, and strategic interests.

India's attempts to shape Nepal's new constitution, its undue interest in Nepal's state restructuring process, and its efforts to reinstate Nepal as a Hindu nation not only prolonged the post-conflict peace and constitution-making process but also compromised the political autonomy of Nepali actors. As India's engagement in post-conflict Nepal deepened, it fuelled anti-India sentiment in Nepal and further strained relations between the two countries.

Building on a detailed examination of India's role in post-conflict Nepal, this study proposes the concept of 'peace dependency' as a framework for understanding the complexities of external mediation and facilitation, and their long-term implications (see Chapter 9). As proposed in this study, peace dependency refers to a post-conflict state's ongoing reliance on its former peace mediators or facilitators to manage subsequent conflicts or crises. This continued reliance enables the mediating entity—or the nations it represents—to expand its influence, advance its interests, and intervene in the domestic political affairs of the state receiving mediation.

Mediators' long-term engagement in post-mediation scenarios has received little attention in mediation research. The concept of peace dependency provides a new and important perspective for examining the long-term effects of external mediation and facilitation in conflict resolution. The Nepali peace process is a compelling case study that demonstrates how Nepal became more dependent on India for post-conflict stability. In turn, India gained significant leverage in Nepal's political negotiations and decision-making processes. This case study also highlights how mediation narratives can be (re)constructed and misused, and external mediation—particularly characterising asymmetrical relationships between regional powers and smaller states—might come with potential long-term risks.

11.7 Lessons from Nepal's Path to Peace

Every peace process, regardless of its level of success, offers valuable lessons. In Chapter 10, I offer a broader evaluation of the Nepali peace process and compile several lessons that can be beneficial for peace and mediation practitioners, researchers, and policymakers.

A successful peace process goes beyond merely ending violent conflict; it also requires a fair and comprehensive transitional justice system (see, for instance, Fletcher & Weinstein 2002), mechanisms of social inclusion or inclusivity

embedded at the core of the peacebuilding framework (see, for instance, Paffenholz & Ross 2015, True & Riveros-Morales 2019), and the integration of human society or processes of life enhancement in the form of 'positive' peace (Galtung 1964: 2, Galtung 1996: 30, Galtung & Fisher 2013).

Successful peace projects also have an emancipatory agenda (Grewal 2003: 6) and aim to foster the development of a stable state and a thriving society (Ahtisaari 2008: 13). At the core of these concepts is the notion that a successful peace process addresses not only conflict and security issues but also aims to resolve broader structural problems. In other words, the overarching goal of a peace process should be the betterment of human lives and the expansion of the freedom they enjoy. Similarly, peace processes should be assessed based on their effectiveness in driving socioeconomic transformation and their capacity to establish inclusive, just, equitable, and flourishing social and political conditions for ordinary citizens.

Nineteen years after the signing of the Comprehensive Peace Accord, Nepal's peace process still stands at a crossroads. Although the armed conflict has ended and the rehabilitation and reintegration of combatants were relatively successful, progress in transitional justice and reconciliation processes has been minimal (see Chapter 10). Institutional arrangements and legislation introduced to address these issues have been slow and controversial. For instance, the Enforced Disappearances Enquiry, Truth and Reconciliation Commission Act, passed in April 2014, faced criticism for its provisions that offered blanket amnesty even for serious human rights violations. The Act was later annulled by Nepal's Supreme Court (Bhetwal 2023).

In February 2015, the Commission of Investigation on Enforced Disappeared Persons Nepal and the Truth and Reconciliation Commission were formed amidst widespread criticisms. In February 2020, it was reported that the TRC, for instance, had conducted a preliminary investigation into less than 10% of the 63,000 requests it had received. However, not a single case had been resolved (HRW & AF 2020). On 14 August 2024, Nepal's House of Representatives finally approved an amendment to the Transitional Justice Act, referred to as the Investigation, Truth and Reconciliation Commission (Third) Amendment Bill, 2024, securing a majority vote (Bhusal 2024). Despite the new legislation, uncertainty remains about its implementation and whether Nepal's war victims will receive justice. The TRC Act aims to address human rights violations that occurred during the armed insurgency, but critics worry it favours perpetrators, allowing up to 75% sentencing reductions for cooperation, undermining accountability for serious crimes (Gupta 2024).

Transitional justice and reconciliation processes are crucial for the successful conclusion of any peace process. At the heart of transitional justice is the belief that there can be no peace without justice (Anderlini et al. 2004) and that 'in the aftermath of massive human rights abuses, victims have well-established rights to see the perpetrators punished, to know the truth, and to receive reparations' (ICTJ 2021). Serious human rights violations, such as extrajudicial killings, torture, abductions, disappearances, rape, and extortion, were daily occurrences during the ten-year conflict in Nepal. Apart from a few isolated cases tried under the regular penal code, most crimes committed during the armed conflict have not been thoroughly investigated or subjected to fair judicial proceedings.

As argued in Chapter 10, the lack of political will is at the core of the stalled transitional justice process and the neglected national reconciliation program. Though included in the CPA merely for the sake of inclusion, these issues were never a priority for the political forces that held power in post-conflict Nepal. The

peace process was deliberately confined to the notion that securing an agreement between the warring parties was all that truly mattered. As a result, the voices and grievances of thousands of civilians affected by the conflict were ignored. Both the Maoists and the parties in the former SPA bloc used the narrative of an 'unfinished peace process' as a tool to reap political benefits. As demonstrated throughout this thesis, India was involved in Nepal's peace process and post-conflict political transition. Nevertheless, it showed no interest in issues of transitional justice and national reconciliation. Instead, its efforts were concentrated on meddling in Nepal's internal politics and pursuing its own interests.

The Nepali peace process had other shortcomings, too. For instance, Nepali women actively participated in the Maoist armed insurgency and the 2006 people's movement (*Jana Andolan II*). However, their participation was neglected in many of the negotiations that took place in the post-conflict context. No female representatives participated in the signing of the 12-Point Understanding in New Delhi in late 2005, nor were they present at the formal peace talks held in Kathmandu in 2006. The peace process also suffered from a centralised decision-making practice in which top leaders of major political parties took important decisions behind closed doors. In the name of expediting the decision-making process, people's representatives, civil society groups, women, and marginalised communities were frequently excluded from key discussions.

The overcrowding of international donors and their widespread yet often mundane presence was another significant issue. As some of the key informants explained, donor agencies rushed to be part of Nepal's success story without realising that they could cause more harm than good. Excessive donor involvement created a scenario in which elected representatives tasked with drafting a new constitution were frequently occupied with attending donor-sponsored seminars, visits, and conferences abroad.

The way the UN Mission in Nepal (UNMIN) was engaged in Nepal's peace process also provides a few valuable lessons. The role of UNMIN in Nepal was to act as an observer and facilitator. Unlike in some other post-conflict countries, the UN did not have an international military mission in Nepal. While UNMIN was, at times, involved in controversies,²⁵³ it nonetheless completed its mandated mission and left Nepal with a success story. While UN missions in some post-conflict societies have lasted for decades²⁵⁴, in Nepal's case, a narrowly defined mandate seemed to ensure both focus and efficiency. However, UNMIN was unable to make a significant impact on transitional justice and national reconciliation processes. While its mandate did not explicitly address transitional justice, it could have utilised its influence more effectively to advance efforts in this area.

As elaborated in Chapter 10, Nepal's peace process achieved technical and partial success through the establishment of a peace accord, cessation of hostilities, and the completion of the Disarmament, Demobilisation, and Reintegration processes. The conclusion of a decade-long armed conflict is undeniably a significant achievement and should not be undervalued. The cultivation of a domestically driven peace initiative and the prevention of conflict relapse are two

²⁵³ Among others, it faced accusations of being overly lenient towards the Maoist rebels and possibly exceeding its mandate.

²⁵⁴ For instance, the UN peacekeeping mission in Cyprus has been operating since 1964, the UN Interim Force in Lebanon since 1978, and the UN Mission for the Referendum in Western Sahara since 1991.

major achievements of the Nepali peace process. Despite these notable achievements, the failure to establish a functional transitional justice mechanism, the absence of an inclusive peacebuilding framework, and the lack of broader socio-economic transformation continue to overshadow the achievements of the Nepali peace process and create a fertile ground for further social unrest and future conflicts.

The Nepali peace process offers valuable insights and lessons also for peace researchers and mediation practitioners. First, the Nepali experience demonstrates that peace processes can begin well before formal negotiations for a peace agreement are initiated. In this case, the 12-Point Understanding served as a de facto peace agreement and laid the groundwork for the 2006 Comprehensive Peace Accord and subsequent agreements. This indicates that recognising and nurturing informal or preparatory agreements is crucial for paving the way towards more comprehensive peace accords and a sustainable path to peace.

Second, the Nepal case shows that peace processes can also emerge from unexpected origins. Unlike the traditional model of negotiations between a government and a rebel group, Nepal's peace process began with an agreement between two opposing forces united by a common goal: the overthrow of a repressive regime. This highlights the importance of thinking creatively and remaining open to diverse approaches to peace. Equally critical is the need to understand and adapt to specific local contexts and political dynamics.

Third—and perhaps most importantly—the Nepali experience serves as a cautionary tale about the risks of peace dependency (see Chapter 9). Both local actors and mediation practitioners should recognise patterns of prolonged ‘peace dependency’ in post-mediation scenarios and should actively work to prevent or mitigate them. For peace and mediation practitioners, too, there are reasons to be careful that the pursuit of peace does not inadvertently compromise the political autonomy of post-conflict states. India's role in post-conflict Nepal demonstrated how mediation, facilitation assistance, or peacebuilding support can be manipulated as political and tactical tools to micromanage internal affairs, reinforce dependency, and advance the interests of the external actor.

11.8 Limitations, Challenges, and Suggestions for Future Research

This study has a definite scope and contains several limitations (see Chapter 2). Completing this study also meant dealing with several challenges, chief among them being the management and synthesis of an extensive amount of archival and interview data. Organising a vast amount of information in a coherent and meaningful way while simultaneously developing ideas, concepts, and theoretical linkages proved to be a challenging and complex task. A particular difficulty arose in providing an insightful analysis of events occurring before and after the focal post-conflict and political transition period, as the study primarily concentrated on developments within a defined timeframe.

Typical constraints of doctoral research—such as limitations on time, resources, and thesis length—required making difficult decisions about which areas of inquiry to examine in depth and which to address more briefly or exclude altogether. These constraints also had an impact on the theoretical and methodological choices, as well as the scope of data collection, to a certain extent. With additional time and resources, the study could have, for instance, included more data and a broader range of perspectives. Despite these challenges, I successfully addressed the

research questions and endeavoured to provide a thorough and detailed analysis of the topic.

This study acknowledges several limitations that warrant consideration. For instance, understanding the complexity of India's influence in Nepal during the peace process years was a major challenge in itself. As a military and economic powerhouse with a long history of involvement in Nepal, India's role has always been complex, multifaceted, and deeply entrenched. This research, therefore, does not claim to be an exhaustive study of India–Nepal relations but rather a focused analysis of India's influence during the specific period of Nepal's peace process and political transition (2005–2017).

Another notable limitation of the study is its heavy reliance on Nepali perspectives. The key informant interviews were conducted solely with Nepali key informants. The initial plan to include Indian perspectives by interviewing Indian leaders and diplomats was abandoned due to logistical constraints and the need to keep a manageable research design. This may have led to potential bias in the data, as the 'Indian side of the story' is underrepresented. Similarly, the secondary data predominantly originated from Nepali sources, with only a marginal representation of Indian scholarly works.

The study's relatively small sample size of 18 key informants, many of whom were political elites, may have also introduced some bias. For instance, these public figures might have felt inclined to portray themselves as strongly patriotic and opposed to foreign interference. Similarly, the use of media materials as secondary data potentially reflects inherent editorial biases. These limitations did not invalidate the study's findings but highlighted the need for careful interpretation.

The findings of this study indicate a need for further research into Nepal's peace process, as well as the broader regional dynamics and geopolitical complexities of South Asia. To begin with, one compelling area for future research would be to provide a more comprehensive picture of India's involvement in Nepal's peace process and political transition by including and analysing Indian perspectives on their involvement. That would offer a counterpoint to the Nepali viewpoint presented in this thesis. A comparative analysis of peace dependency in other post-conflict contexts would be equally fascinating. This could help determine whether the concept is applicable beyond the India–Nepal case presented in this thesis and identify patterns or variations across different regions and power relationships.

Even though scholars have accused India of harbouring hegemonic aspirations for decades (see, for instance, Myrdal 1968, Rose 1978, Ziring 1978, Gordon 1992) and creating its own post-colonial version of the Raj (Upadhyya 2008), India's role as a sub-imperialist agent in South Asia has not been thoroughly investigated. This study initiated an investigation and theoretical discussion on India's sub-imperialism in Nepal. Future research could explore India's sub-imperialist position and its manifestations across South and Southeast Asia, focusing on countries such as Bhutan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Myanmar, and the Maldives. Similarly, a study on India's internal colonial practices and the grassroots movements challenging them could offer equally valuable insights into the dynamics of power, resistance, and social change within the country.

Another promising topic for further research would be the challenges that Indian sub-imperialism faces in South Asia. As demonstrated in this thesis, Nepal has repeatedly challenged and resisted India's dominance and sub-imperialism over the decades, and at times with noteworthy success. Future research could examine how this trend manifests in other South Asian nations and investigate the factors contributing to potential shifts in Indian influence and sub-imperialism

across the region. This could include investigating local resistance movements, changes in geopolitical dynamics, and the effects of economic shifts on India's regional influence.

The escalating China–India rivalry in Nepal—and in South Asia more broadly—and its implications for regional stability present another promising area for future research. Researchers could, for instance, dig deeper into China's hegemonic tendencies—expressed through initiatives like the BRI—and compare them with India's approaches. China and India share a complex and often contradictory relationship. While they collaborate as allies on several fronts, such as through BRICS membership and robust bilateral trade, they simultaneously compete as rivals, particularly in their quest for regional dominance and influence. Future research could delve deeper into this paradox to offer a more comprehensive understanding of the complexities of contemporary China-India interactions.

It is becoming increasingly evident that India is no longer content with its status as a regional power or its role merely as a sub-imperialist agent; rather, it aspires to assert itself as a more prominent and influential global power (Tellis 2016, Ahad 2024). Against this backdrop, future researchers could explore India's own sub-imperialist struggles on the global stage. For instance, they might analyse how India positions itself in relation to other major powers, such as Russia and China, and how it navigates its relationships with Western powers, particularly the United States and the European Union.

Finally, as Nepal approaches the two-decade milestone of its peace process in 2026, researchers could undertake a thorough evaluation of its broader impact. Key areas of inquiry could include the extent to which post-conflict peace and relative stability transformed Nepali society and the lives of ordinary Nepalis. The shifting domestic political landscape—marked by the rise of new parties and the relative decline of traditional ones—also warrants close examination. Similarly, the Maoists' transition from an insurgent group to a mainstream political party offers another crucial research avenue. Perhaps most importantly, a comprehensive evaluation of Nepal's progress—or lack thereof—in implementing transitional justice mechanisms can offer valuable insights with both theoretical and practical implications.

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Appendix 1. Data Sources

List of Key informants and interview dates

[Note: The list includes individuals and their roles at the time of their interviews. Any changes in their professional positions, career paths, or other developments after the interviews are not documented here.]

	Name and interview date	Description of the key informants and their official designations and attributes
1	Pradeep Gyawali 10 July 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Senior leader of the CPN (UML), former MP and minister - One of the three members of the Government team that took part in the formal peace talks with the CPN (Maoists) and negotiated the CPA - Member of the task force that created the draft of the TRC (Truth and Reconciliation Commission) bill.
2	Madhav Kumar Nepal 11 July 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prime Minister of Nepal from May 2009 to February 2011, and Foreign Minister of Nepal from November 1994 to September 1995 - Led Nepal's largest communist party, CPN (UML), for more than 15 years - One of the key participants in the SPA-Maoist negotiations in New Delhi that led to the signing of the 12-Point Understanding - A key figure in Nepal's peace process, credited for initiating dialogue with the Maoists long before the 12-Point Understanding was signed
3	Prakash Bhattarai 12 July 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A research scholar, peace and conflict researcher, has written extensively on third-party coordination in conflict resolution, with ample experience in conducting research work surrounding Nepal's peace process and third-party engagement - Director of Centre for Social Change (CSC), a non-profit research and advocacy institute in Nepal - PhD in Peace and Conflict Studies from the University of Otago, New Zealand
4	Rajan Bhattarai 13 July 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An international relations scholar, a scholar activist, author of <i>Geopolitics of Nepal and International Responses to Conflict Transformation</i> (February 2005) - Chairperson, Nepal Institute for Policy Studies (NIPS), a think-tank working in areas of international studies, securities and democracy - Advisor to the Prime Minister of Nepal on Foreign Policy (from May 2009 to Feb 2011) - An insider of the 12-Point Understanding process, contributed to its prelude as a Nepali scholar-activist based in New Delhi
5	Bishnu Poudel 13 July 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Senior leader of the CPN (UML), veteran MP and Minister - An active participant and mobiliser of <i>Jana Andolan II</i>

		- Member of the Constituent Assembly
6	Beduram Bhusal 14 July 2017	- Senior leader of the CPN (UML), MP, author of several books on philosophy, Marxism, and the development of communist movements in Nepal - PhD in political science from Tribhuvan University, Nepal
7	Bamdev Gautam 15 July 2017	- Former deputy prime minister, veteran MP and a senior communist leader - Known for informally initiating talks with the Maoists years before the 12-Point Understanding - One of the participants of the Six-Point Agreement, which was signed between the Maoists and the CPN (UML) in October 2005 in Rolpa's Gharti Gaun
8	Hari Bahadur Thapa 20 July 2017	- Writer and a senior journalist, an experienced reporter on India–Nepal relations, and Nepal's water resources issues - Editor of Nepal's largest-selling daily, Kantipur Dainik
9	Mumaram Khanal 24 July 2017	- A prominent political analyst, writer and a senior journalist - Former Central Committee member of the CPN (Maoists) - Former leader of the JanaShakti Party
10	Sudheer Sharma 2 August 2017	- A writer and senior journalist, with extensive experience as an analyst and commentator on India–Nepal relations. - Editor-in-Chief of Nepal's largest selling daily, Kantipur Dainik - Author of <i>Prayogshala: Nepali Sankramanma Dilli, Durbar ra Maovadi</i> [Laboratory: Delhi, Palace and the Maoists in Nepal's Transition]
11	Devendra Raj Pandey 2 August 2017	- A prominent member of civil society, writer and a scholar activist - A leader of the Citizens' Movement for Democracy and Peace, which spearheaded the Jana Andolan II (i.e., the People's Movement of 2005/6) - Nepal's former Finance Secretary and Finance Minister - One of the five civil society representatives present as observers in the formal peace talks between the government of Nepal and the Maoist rebels - PhD in Public and International Affairs from the University of Pittsburgh, United States
12	Pampha Bhusal 3 August 2017	- Senior leader of the CPN (Maoists), former MP and government minister - The only female Central Committee Member of the rebel group when they decided to launch the armed struggle in 1996 - Member of the dialogue committee formed by the rebels to negotiate a peace deal with the government of Nepal
13	Bishnu Raj Upreti 3 August 2017	- A research scholar specializing in conflict, peace, security, and the Nepali peace process.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Founder and Executive Director at the Centre for Contemporary Research (NCCR), Kathmandu
14	Bimal Gautam 12 August 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A senior journalist, editor-in-Chief at Lokaantar, an online news portal based in Kathmandu - Press Advisor to the Chairperson of Council of Ministers (i.e., acting Prime Minister), Mr Khil Raj Regmi from March 2013 – February 2014
15	Bala Nanda Sharma 16 August 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinator of the Secretariat of the Special Committee for Supervision, Integration and Rehabilitation of the Maoist Army Combatants (from April 2009 to December 2013) - Former Colonel and Brigadier at the Nepal Army - Former Commander of the United Nations Disengagement Force
16	Deepak Prakash Bhatta 17 August 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A politician and MP, security specialist, a scholar activist - Founding Chairperson of the Nepal Centre for Security Governance (NCSG), a PhD in international relations from JNU, New Delhi. - A member of the Technical Committee and Secretariat of the Special Committee for Supervision, Integration and Rehabilitation of Maoist Army Combatants (from March 2009 to December 2012) - A faculty member at the Department of Conflict, Peace and Development Studies (DCPDS), Tribhuvan University
17	Sujata Koirala 18 August 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nepal's Deputy Prime Minister and Foreign Minister (from 2009 to 2011) - Senior leader of the Nepali Congress Party, long-time MP, Head of International Relations Department, Nepali Congress Party - Daughter of former Prime Minister and de-facto head of state Girija Prasad Koirala, who led the Jana Andolan II and the peace and political process in the aftermath
18	Sekhar Koirala 22 August 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Senior leader of the Nepali Congress Party, MP and member of the second Constituent Assembly of Nepal - A close relative and political aide of former Prime Minister and de-facto head of state Girija Prasad Koirala - An insider of the 12-Point-Understanding process, Jana Andolan II, and the peace and political process that followed

Selected videos (n=12, 360.01 minutes)

1	<p>Video Title: Prachanda on Indian Influence in Nepal Video Type: Speech, Video Length: 32.27 minutes Publication date: 22 September 2013 Publisher: MySansar Video Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IEAB62KsAo</p>
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2	<p>Video Title: Rolpa Chunbang Baithak Prachandako Prastikaran [Prachanda's clarification at the Rolpa Chunbang meeting] Video Type: Speech, Video Length: 18.10 minutes Publication date: 23 August 2020 (Note: the meeting took place in September 2005) Publisher: S.T.M. network Video Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mnJPWcoVrag</p>
3	<p>Video Title: Shanti Prakriyaka 12 Barsha: Maobadi Janayuddhako Purai Swamitwo Linchhu, Baburam Bhattarai [12 years of the peace process, I take full responsibility of the Maoists' People's War, Baburam Bhattarai] Video Type: Interview, Video Length: 25.35 minutes Publication date: 21 November 2018 Publisher: Ratopati TV Video Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IM_sUUhwzIA</p>
4	<p>Video Title: Maobadi Chunbang Baithak, Baburam Bhattarai Bhasan [Baburam Bhattarai speech at the Maoists' Chunbang meeting] Video Type: speech, Video Length: 10.15 minutes Publication date: 27 July 2020 (Note: the meeting took place in September 2005) Publisher: Nabin Bibhas Video Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ye_5RizEGjw</p>
5	<p>Video Title: Smt. Sushma Swaraj's reply on the discussion on situation in Nepal & state of Indo-Nepal relations Video Type: parliament debate recording, Video Length: 32.59 minutes Publication date: 8 December 2015 Publisher: Bharatiya Janata Party Video Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tJ4riGSID6I&t=787s</p>
6	<p>Video Title: Interview: Pranab Mukherjee Video Type: TV interview, Video Length: 22.44 minutes Publication date: 28 January 2009 Publisher: Al Jazeera Video Link: https://www.aljazeera.com/program/riz-khan/2009/1/28/pranab-mukherjee</p>
7	<p>Video Title: Politics Of Nepali Civil War Video Type: documentary, Video Length: 55.47 minutes Publication date: 30 August 2020 Publisher: Nawayug Media Video Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IMGRiCosVo</p>
8	<p>Video Title: Image Sambad - Interview with Dr. Vesh Bahadur Thapa about Nepal & India Relations Video Type: TV interview, Video Length: 31.56 minutes Publication date: 4 November 2015 Publisher: Image Channel Video Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8ObhWvlsyRE</p>
9	<p>Video Title: Pradip Giri on Indian Influence in Nepal</p>

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11	Video Title: Ex-King Gyanendra says seven parties had agreed to retain monarchy Video Type: Media Interview, Video Length: 31.04 minutes Publication date: 9 July 2012 Publisher: News 24 TV & Nepal News (Mercantile Communications) Video Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4bFdFopXync
12	Video Title: Sajha Sawal Anka 1: Pradhanmantri Girija Prasad Koirala [Sajha Sawal Episode 1: With Prime Minister Girija Prasad Koirala] Video Type: Media Interview, Video Length: 50.56 minutes Publication date: 7 July 2016 Publisher: BBC Nepali/ Sajha Sawal Video Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eafYz43zkk

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Appendix 2. Example of How Different Texts Were Coded

Transcript Excerpts	Initial Codes	Themes
<p>“Who should be appointed Vice-Chairperson of the National Planning Commission, or who should work as Kathmandu Valley Police Chief, who should run which ministry, and who should be at which section of the Ministry of Home Affairs. India’s influence was extensive and everywhere.”</p>	<p>Meddling in bureaucracy and security sectors</p>	<p>Micromanagement</p>
<p>"India did not accept that there was a blockade, but people were suffering. India kept saying that it was not behind the blockade and that the problem in the border areas was caused by our own Madheshi people. Okay, there were protests in Birgunj, but why weren't goods coming from the Bhairahawa checkpoint? India would not provide answers to such questions. At that time, I felt like I was fighting alone. People were angry at me on social media. It was not uncommon for the aggrieved masses to be so outraged. I was in an early stage of diplomacy. What happens in diplomacy—which I later learnt—is that no matter how bitter the relationship, you use sweet words. India did not tell us it was going to impose an economic blockade, but it kept giving us pain and grief."</p>	<p>Denial of Blockade</p> <p>Blame on Madheshi People</p> <p>Public Anger</p>	<p>Economic blockade</p> <p>Diplomatic tensions</p> <p>Anti-India sentiment</p>
<p>“From the very beginning, the way he presented himself was not good. He said at the beginning, ‘You are ready to declare the constitution overnight, aren't you? You are violating the entire process and declaring the constitution?’ As a diplomat and an envoy of a head of government, he should not have talked like that. He not only violated diplomatic norms, but also dared to undermine the sovereignty of Nepal and the Nepali people. Going further, he said, ‘I have come to Nepal as a special envoy of the Prime Minister and with a special mission and message. That is, you have to postpone the promulgation of the constitution for now...Otherwise, you will have to kill many people on the day the constitution is promulgated...He added, ‘What happens even when you declare the constitution? What happens even with the support of many countries in the world? Does your constitution work if India does not support it? Yes, you can</p>	<p>Diplomatic threats</p> <p>Disregarding Nepal's national sovereignty</p> <p>India in post-conflict Nepal</p>	<p>Micromanagement</p> <p>Power diplomacy</p> <p>Coercive diplomacy</p>

<p>declare the constitution, but don't you want development? And don't you need India's help for development?"</p>		
<p>"If one looks at the background and India's attitude, it is clear that India's main motive is to use Nepal's water the way it wants. A large part of Nepal is dry due to a lack of irrigation, and India has created a situation where Nepal cannot use its own water resources properly. India has repeatedly foiled Nepal's plans to secure loans and foreign investment for irrigation projects. Loans approved for Sikta and Babai projects stalled due to Indian pressure. Big projects such as Koshi Diversion, Kankai Irrigation Project and Bheri Diversion Irrigation Project, which were studied with colossal investment, got stalled due to a lack of loan support. In the 1980s, the Saudi Development Fund showed interest in issuing a loan of 1 billion rupees to Babai, and a draft of the agreement was also prepared. But later, the Fund pulled out from the project, arguing that it had received an objection from India and that the loan would be processed only if Nepal could secure India's consent."</p>	<p>Water resource control</p> <p>Foreign investment interference</p> <p>India's interests in Nepal</p>	<p>Resource control</p> <p>Economic dependency</p> <p>Regional hegemony</p>

Appendix 3. Interview Guide

Interview Guide

Semi-Structured Key Informant Interviews (June-Aug 2017, in Nepal)

*PhD Project: Mediation, Meddling, and Micromanagement-India in Nepal's Peace
Process and Political Transition*

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Overview

This interview guide serves as a guiding document that will help me complete semi-structured key informant interviews in Nepal as part of the data collection process for my doctoral dissertation: *Mediation, Meddling, and Micromanagement—India in Nepal's Peace Process and Political Transition*. This interview guide has been created per the plans developed in my doctoral research proposal.

The interview guide has been divided into two sections. The first section deals primarily with logistical and somewhat technical issues—scheduling interviews, recording, and storage—supplemented by a reminder note on research ethics. The second section lists a draft of questions that will be used to steer the key informant interviews.

PART I

Contacting the respondents & confirmation of date, time and interview method:

The informants chosen for the interview have partly been already contacted. However, an attempt will be made to contact all the key informants in advance. After consulting the key informants, the interview date, time, and the most suitable interview method (onsite or online) will be decided. However, since I am traveling to Nepal, most interviews, if not all, will be carried out in person. In some cases, phone or Skype interviews can also be conducted.

Language of the interview: I can communicate well in English, Nepali, and Hindi. Respondents can choose any of the three languages. However, since all key informants/respondents are native Nepali speakers, like me, all interviews will likely be conducted in Nepali.

Interview Date & Time: The fieldwork period in Nepal has been scheduled from 1 June to 29 August 2017. Most interviews will take place during this period. If necessary, a supplementary interview plan will be sketched to cover key informants who are available for interviews but not in Nepal during the fieldwork period.

Interview Length: The semi-structured interviews will last approximately 40 to 60 minutes. The focus will be on finding a free and relaxed time, both for me and the key informants. A smooth and conducive interview environment is a top priority. If necessary, due to time limitations or any other reason, more than one interview will be organised with the same key informant.

Meeting Manners: I am mindful that I must be very polite to the respondent I am interviewing, giving him/her enough time to speak, elaborate, ask questions, and express doubts. I am mindful to use appropriate words when asking questions. In addition, I am aware that paying attention to nonverbal communication is also essential.

Data Recording/Storage: Oral permission will be requested to record the interviews in advance. A digital recorder will be used to record each interview. Recorded interviews will be safely stored on a computer and an external hard drive.

Ethical Considerations: Research ethics will be rigorously upheld during fieldwork and data collection. Respondents' rights to privacy, confidentiality, anonymity, and voluntary participation will be fully respected. Informed consent will be obtained, and respondents will be informed about the research aims, objectives, and scope and how their interview data will be used and published.

As stated above, the respondents will be treated with respect, and attention will be paid to

culturally sensitive issues and the need for using respectful language. Respondents will be asked to provide written or oral consent to use interview data in my research.

PART II- INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Since the key informants selected for this interview represent a wide range of backgrounds and unique sets of experience and expertise, a set of questions will be tailor-made before each specific interview. Questions prepared in this section will be used as a starting/reference point to finalise the final questions for each informant. Each interview will contain three parts and cover various thematic areas.

भाग १: सरकार माओवादी शान्ति सम्झौता र नेपाली शान्ति प्रक्रिया

Part 1: Government-Maoist Peace Agreement and the Nepali Peace Process

१- माओवादी जनयुद्धपछिको शान्ति वार्ता र वृहत् शान्ति प्रक्रियामा तपाईंको भूमिका र अनुभव कस्तो रहयो? 1. *What was your role and experience in the peace talks after the armed conflict, and what is your take on the broader peace process?*

२- तपाईंको विचारमा सन् २००६ को शान्ति वार्ता सफल हुनुका मुख्य कारणहरू के हुन्? 2. *In your opinion, what were the main reasons for the success of the 2006 peace talks?*

३- सन् २००६ मा सुरु भएको शान्ति प्रक्रिया पूर्ण भयो कि अझै अपूर्ण छ? र किन? 3. *Is the peace process that began in 2006 complete or still a work in progress? And why?*

४- सरकार-माओवादी शान्ति वार्ता र वृहत् शान्ति प्रक्रियामा अन्तर्राष्ट्रिय समुदायको कस्तो भूमिका रहयो? (भारत, चिन, ईयु, युएन, अमेरिका र बेलायत?) 4. *What role did the international community play in the peace talks and the broader peace process? (India, China, EU, UN, USA, and UK?)*

५- माओवादी र सात राजनैतिक दलहरूबिच भएको १२ बुँदे समझदारीमा भारतको भूमिका के थियो? 5. *What was India's role in the 12-Point Understanding between the Maoists and the Seven Party Alliance (SPA)?*

६- तपाईंको विचारमा नेपाली शान्ति प्रक्रियामा भारतलाई मध्यस्थकर्ता मान्न मिल्छ कि मिल्दैन? किन मिल्छ किन मिल्दैन? 6. *In your opinion, can India be considered a mediator of the Nepali peace process? Why or why not?*

७- नेपालको शान्ति प्रक्रियामा भारतीय मध्यस्थता वा उपस्थितीका नकारात्मक र सकारात्मक पक्षहरू के-के हुन्? 7. *What are the negative and positive aspects of Indian mediation or its presence in Nepal's peace process?*

८- भारतमा हस्ताक्षर भएको १२ बुँदे समझदारीबाट सुरु भएको शान्ति प्रक्रिया चाहिँ सफल हुँदै गयो, तर शान्ति वार्ताका लागि भएका अन्य प्रयासहरू चाहिँ असफल भए, कारण के होला? 8. *The peace process that started with the 12-Point Understanding signed in India became successful, but other attempts of peace talks failed. What could be the reason?*

९- भारतको प्रत्यक्ष वा परोक्ष सहभागिता नभएको भए २०६३ को विस्तृत शान्ति सम्झौतासम्म नेपाल आउने थियो कि थिएन? 9. *Would Nepal have achieved the 2006 Comprehensive Peace Accord (CPA) without India's direct or indirect involvement?*

१०- माओवादी जनयुद्धका बेला भारतको भूमिका नेपालमा कस्तो रह्यो? 10. How was India's role in Nepal during the armed insurgency?

११- नेपालको शान्ति प्रक्रिया र राजनैतिक संक्रमणमा भारतको भूमिकालाई साउथ-साउथ कोअपरेसनको उदाहरण मान्ने कि 'पावर डिप्लोमेसि', नव-उपनिवेशवाद वा क्षेत्रीय प्रभुत्वको आकांक्षा? 11. Should India's role in Nepal's peace process and political transition be considered an example of South-South cooperation, or 'power diplomacy', neo-colonialism, or regional hegemonic aspirations?

१२- नेपालको शान्तिप्रक्रिया र राजनैतिक संक्रमणलाई कसरी मुल्यांकन गर्नुहुन्छ? नेपालको शान्ति प्रक्रियाबाट अन्य द्वन्द्वरत मुलुकहरूले के सिक्न सक्छन्? 12. How do you evaluate Nepal's peace and political transition process? What can other conflict-affected countries learn from Nepal's peace process?

भाग २: शान्ति सम्झौता पछिको नेपाली राजनैतिक परिदृश्य

Part 2: Nepal's Political Landscape After the 2006 CPA

१३- सफल शान्ति सम्झौता पछिका अन्य राजनैतिक सम्झौता र मोडहरूमा भारतको सहभागिता र भूमिका कस्तो रह्यो? (विशेष गरी अनमिनको बहिर्गमन, खिलराज रेग्मीको चुनावी सरकार, र मधेस आन्दोलनमा) 13. What was India's involvement and role in other political agreements and turns after the successful peace agreement? (For instance, in events such as UNMIN's exit, forming Khil Raj Regmi's election government, and the Madhes movement)

१४- नेपाली राजनीतिमा भारतको प्रत्यक्ष प्रभाव रहेको र भारतले नेपालमा 'माईक्रोमेनेजमेन्ट' गर्ने गरेको आरोप छ, तपाईं सहमत हुनुहुन्छ? 'माईक्रोमेनेजमेन्ट' व्यवहारमा कसरी गरिन्छ? 14. There are accusations that India has a direct influence on Nepali politics and 'micromanages' Nepali politics. Do you agree? If yes, how is 'micromanagement' practiced?

१५- नेपालमा विदेशी शक्ति राष्ट्रहरू भारत, चिन, अमेरिका लगायतको के कस्तो चासो छ? 15. What interests do foreign powers like India, China, and the USA have in Nepal?

१६- नेपालमा भारतको प्रभाव अन्य शक्ति राष्ट्रहरू तथा अर्को बलियो छिमेकी राष्ट्र चीनको भन्दा बढी देखिन्छ, कारण के होला? 16. India's influence in Nepal seems to be greater than that of other power nations and another strong neighboring country, China. What could be the reason?

१७- १२ बुँदे समझदारी र विस्तृत शान्ति सम्झौता पछिको नेपाल शान्त त छ तर यसको सार्वभौमिकता निकै कमजोर भएको छ भनिन्छ, तपाईं के भन्नुहुन्छ? 17. It is said that Nepal is peaceful after the 12-Point Understanding and the Comprehensive Peace Accord (CPA), but its sovereignty has become very weak. What do you say?

भाग-३: नेपालमा भारतीय चासो

Part 3: India's Interests in Nepal

१८ - नेपालमा भारतको प्रभाव बढ्नुमा भारतको सुरक्षा चासो र चिन्ता छ भनिन्छ, तपाईं के भन्नुहुन्छ? 18. It is said that India's growing influence in Nepal is due to India's security concerns.

What is your take on this?

१९ - नेपालमा भारतका सुरक्षाका अलावा अन्य के-के चासोहरू छन्? (पानी, बिजुली, ढुङ्गा?) 19. *Apart from security, what other interests does India have in Nepal? (Water resources, electricity, stones?)*

२०- नेपाल भारत सीमामा २ वर्ष अगाडि भएको पारवहन अवरोध वा नाकाबन्दीलाई कसरी हेर्नुहुन्छ? भारत सरकारको इच्छा विपरीत के त्यो सम्भव थियो? 20. *How do you view the transit obstruction or blockade at the India–Nepal border from two years ago? Was it possible against the will of the Indian government?*

२१- पछिल्ला दिनहरूमा नेपाल आफ्नो आन्तरिक द्वन्द्व समाधान गर्न भारतमा निर्भर हुँदै गएको हो? 21. *Has Nepal become increasingly dependent on India to resolve its internal conflicts in recent times?*

२२- १२ बुँदे समझदारी र शान्ति प्रक्रियामा आफ्नो सहभागिताको फाइदा उठाउँदै भारत नेपालमा आफ्नो उपस्थितिलाई बलियो बनाउन चाहन्छ भन्नेहरू पनि छन्, तपाईं के भन्नुहुन्छ? 22. *Some say that India wants to strengthen its presence in Nepal by taking advantage of its involvement in the 12-Point Understanding and peace process. What do you say?*

नेपालको शान्ति प्रक्रिया, राजनैतिक संक्रमण र नेपाल भारत सम्बन्ध सम्बन्धि अध्ययनको लागि अन्य केहि सुझाव र स्रोतहरू छन्? *Do you have any other suggestions and sources for studying Nepal's peace and political transition process and contemporary India–Nepal relations?*

आवश्यकता अनुसार थप प्रष्ट पार्न सोध्न सकिने प्रश्नहरू Clarifying questions to accompany each question (whenever necessary)

- यसको बारेमा केहि थप बताउन सक्नुहुन्छ? (Can you tell me a bit more about that?)
- यसलाई अलि विस्तार गर्न सक्नुहुन्छ? (Could you expand that a bit?)
- थप्नु पर्ने केही कुरा छ? (Do you have anything to add?)
- केही उदाहरणहरू दिन सक्नुहुन्छ? (Could you give me a few examples?)

नाम (Name): _____ मिति: (Interview Date) _____

समयको लागि धन्यवाद! (Thank you for your time!)

Appendix 4. The 12-Point Understanding Reached Between the Seven-Party Alliance (SPA) and the Nepal Communist Party (Maoists) on 22 November 2005, in New Delhi, India.

[Note: The original language of the 12-Point Understanding was Nepali. This is an unofficial English translation provided by Nepal's then Ministry for Peace and Reconstruction.]

The struggle between absolute monarchy and democracy, running for a long time in Nepal, has now reached a very grave and new turn. It has become the need of today to establish peace by resolving the 10-year-old armed conflict through a forward-looking political outlet. Therefore, it has become an inevitable need to implement the concept of full democracy through a forward-looking restructuring of the state to resolve the problems related to class, cast, gender, region and so on of all sectors, including the political, economic, social and cultural, by bringing the autocratic monarchy to an end and establishing full democracy. We hereby disclose that in the existence of aforesaid context and reference in the country, the following understanding has been reached between the Seven Political Parties within the parliament and the CPN (Maoists) through holding talks in different manners.

The points reached in understanding

1. The democracy, peace, prosperity, social advancement and an independent, sovereign Nepal is the principal wish of all Nepali people in the country today. We are fully agreed that the autocratic monarchy is the main hurdle for this. We have a clear opinion that the peace, progress and prosperity in the country is not possible until and full democracy is established by bringing the absolute monarchy to an end. Therefore, an understanding has been reached to establish full democracy by bringing the autocratic monarchy to an end through creating a storm of nationwide democratic movement of all the forces against autocratic monarchy by focusing their assault against the autocratic monarchy from their respective positions.

2. The agitating Seven Political Parties are fully committed to the fact that the existing conflict in the country can be resolved and the sovereignty and the state powers can completely be established in people only by establishing full democracy by restoring the parliament through the force of agitation and forming a power full - party Government by its decision, negotiating with the Maoists, and on the basis of agreement, holding the election of constituent assembly. The CPN (Maoists) has the view and commitment that the aforesaid goal can be achieved by holding a national political conference of the agitating democratic forces, and through its decision, forming an Interim Government and holding the election of constituent assembly. On the issue of this procedural agenda, an understanding has been made to continue dialogue and seek for a common agreement between the agitating Seven Political Parties and the CPN (Maoists). It has been agreed that the force of people's movement is the only alternative to achieve this goal.

3. The country, today, demands the establishment of a permanent peace along with a positive resolution of the armed conflict. We are, therefore, firmly committed to establish a permanent peace by bringing the existing armed conflict in the country to an end through a forward-looking political outlet of the establishment of the full democracy by ending the autocratic monarchy and holding an election of the constituent assembly that would come on the basis of aforesaid procedure. The CPN (Maoists) expresses its commitment to move

foreward in the new peaceful political stream through this process. In this very context, an understanding has been made to keep the Maoists armed force and the Royal Army under the United Nations or a reliable international supervision during the process of the election of constituent assembly after the end of the autocratic monarchy, to accomplish the election in a free and fair manner³ and to accept the result of the election. We also expect for the involvement of a reliable international community even in the process of negotiation.

4. Making public its commitment, institutional in a clear manner, towards the democratic norms and values like the competitive multiparty system of governance, civil liberties, fundamental rights, human rights, principle of rule of law etc., the CPN (Maoists) has expressed its commitment to move forward its activities accordingly.

5. The CPN (Maoists) has expressed its commitment to create an environment to allow the people and the leaders and workers of the political parties, who are displaced during the course of armed conflict, to return and stay with dignity in their respective places, to return their homes, land and property that was seized in an unjust manner and to allow them to carry out the political activities without any hindrance.

6. Making a self-assessment and a self-criticism of the past mistakes and weaknesses, the CPN (Maoists) has expressed its commitment for not allowing the mistakes and weaknesses to be committed in future.

7. Making a self-assessment towards the mistakes and weaknesses committed while staying in the Government and parliament in the past, the seven political parties have expressed their commitment for not repeating such mistakes and weaknesses now onwards.

8. The commitment has been made to fully respect the norms and values of the human rights and to move forward on the basis of them, and to respect the press freedom in the context of moving the peace process ahead.⁴

9. As the announcement of the election of municipality is pushed forward for an ill-motive of deluding the people and the international community and of giving continuity to the autocratic and illegitimate rule of the King, and the rumour of the election of the parliament are a crafty ploy, announcing to boycott it actively in our own respective way, the general public are appealed to make such elections a failure.

10. The people and their representative political parties are the real guardians of nationality. Therefore, we are firmly committed towards the protection of the independence, sovereignty and the geographical integrity and the national unity of the country. It is our common obligation to maintain friendly relations based on the principle of peaceful co-existence with all countries of the world and a good-neighborhood relationship with neighboring countries, especially with India and China. But we request all the patriotic peoples to remain cautious against the false attempt of the King and the monarchists to create confusion in the patriotic people by projecting the illusory the fake ('Mandale') nationalism to prolong the autocratic and illegitimate rule of the King and to raise question mark over the patriotism of the political parties, and we appeal to the international powers and the communities to support the democratic movement against the autocratic monarchy in Nepal in every possible way.

11. We heartily invite the civil society, professional organisations, various wings of parties, people of all communities and regions, the press community, intellectuals all the Nepali people to make the Movement succeed by actively participating in the peaceful People's Movement launched on the basis of these understandings reached by keeping the

democracy, peace, prosperity, forward-looking social transformation and the independence, sovereignty, and dignity of the country in centre.

12. Regarding the inappropriate conducts that took place among the parties in the past, a common commitment has been expressed to investigate the incidents raised objection and asked for the investigation by any party and take action over the guilty one if found and make informed publicly. An understanding has been made to resolve the problems if emerged among the parties now onwards through the dialogue by discussing in the concerned level or in the leadership level.

22 November 2005

Original Source: Government of Nepal, the Ministry for Peace and Reconstruction. The Ministry for Peace and Reconstruction has been disbanded, but the text is available at:

https://www.satp.org/satporgtp/countries/nepal/document/papers/12_Point_Understanding.pdf

Appendix 5. The 40-Point Demands by the United People's Front, Nepal

[Note: Submitted to the Nepal Government before launching the armed insurgency in 1996]

40 Point Demand

4 February 1996

Right Honourable Prime Minister
Prime Minister's Office,
Singha Darbar, Kathmandu

Sub: Memorandum

Sir,

It has been six years since the autocratic monarchical partyless Panchayat system was ended by the 1990 People's Movement and a constitutional monarchical multiparty parliamentary system established. During this period state control has been exercised by a tripartite interim government, a single-party government of the Nepali Congress, a minority government of UML and a present Nepali Congress-RPP-Sadbhavana coalition. That, instead of making progress, The situation of the country and the people is going downhill is evident from the fact that Nepal has slid to being the second poorest country in the world; people living below the absolute poverty line has gone up to 71 per cent; the number of unemployed has reached more than 10 per cent while the number of people who are semi-employed or in disguised employment has crossed 60 per cent; the country is on the verge of bankruptcy due to rising foreign loans and deficit trade; economic and cultural encroachment within the country by foreign, and especially Indian, expansionists is increasing by the day; the gap between the rich and the poor and between towns and villages is growing wider. On the other hand, parliamentary parties that have formed the government by various means have shown that they are more interested in remaining in power with the blessings of foreign imperialist and expansionist masters than in the welfare of the country and the people. This is clear from their blindly adopting so-called privatisation and liberalisation to fulfil the interests of all imperialists and from the recent 'national consensus' reached in handing over the rights over Nepal's water resources to Indian expansionists. Since 6 April, 1992, the United People's Front has been involved in various struggles to fulfil relevant demands related to nationalism, democracy and livelihood, either by itself or with others. But rather than fulfil those demands, the governments formed at different times have violently suppressed the agitators and taken the lives of hundreds; the most recent example of this is the armed police operation in Rolpa a few months back. In this context, we would like to once again present to the current coalition government demands related to nationalism, democracy and livelihood, which have been raised in the past and many of which have become relevant in the present context.

Our demands

Concerning nationality

1. All discriminatory treaties, including the 1950 India–Nepal Treaty, should be abrogated.

2. The so-called Integrated Mahakali Treaty concluded on 29 January, 1996 should be repealed immediately, as it is designed to conceal the disastrous Tanakpur Treaty and allows Indian imperialist monopoly over Nepal's water resources.
3. The open border between Nepal and India should be regulated, controlled and systematised. All vehicles with Indian licence plates should be banned from Nepal.
4. The Gurkha/Gorkha Recruitment Centres should be closed. Nepali citizens should be provided dignified employment in the country.
5. Nepali workers should be given priority in different sectors. A 'work permit' system should be strictly implemented if foreign workers are required in the country.
6. The domination of foreign capital in Nepali industries, business and finance should be stopped.
7. An appropriate customs policy should be devised and implemented so that economic development helps the nation become self-reliant.
8. The invasion of imperialist and colonial culture should be banned. Vulgar Hindi films, videos and magazines should be immediately outlawed.
9. The invasion of colonial and imperial elements in the name of NGOs and INGOs should be stopped.
10. *Concerning people's democracy* new constitution should be drafted by representatives elected for the establishment of a people's democratic system.
11. All special privileges of the king and the royal family should be abolished.
12. The army, the police and the bureaucracy should be completely under people's control.
13. All repressive acts, including the Security Act, should be repealed.
14. Everyone arrested extra-judicially for political reasons or revenge in Rukum, Rolpa, Jajarkot, Gorkha, Kabhrc, Sindhupalchowk, Sindhuli, Dhanusa, Ramechhap, and so on, should be immediately released. All false cases should be immediately withdrawn.
15. The operation of armed police, repression and state-sponsored terror should be immediately stopped.
16. The whereabouts of citizens who disappeared in police custody at different times, namely Dilip Chaudhary, Bhuwan Thapa Magar, Prabhakar Subedi and others, should be investigated and those responsible brought to justice. The families of victims should be duly compensated.
17. All those killed during the People's Movement should be declared martyrs. The families of the martyrs and those injured and deformed should be duly compensated, and the murderers brought to justice.
18. Nepal should be declared a secular nation.
19. Patriarchal exploitation and discrimination against women should be stopped. Daughters should be allowed access to paternal property.
20. All racial exploitation and suppression should be stopped. Where ethnic communities are in the majority, they should be allowed to form their own autonomous governments.
21. Discrimination against downtrodden and backward people should be stopped. The system of untouchability should be eliminated.
22. All languages and dialects should be given equal opportunities to prosper. The right to education in the mother tongue up to higher levels should be guaranteed.
23. The right to expression and freedom of press and publication should be guaranteed. The government mass media should be completely autonomous.
24. Academic and professional freedom of scholars, writers, artists and cultural workers should be guaranteed.
25. Regional discrimination between the hills and the tarai should be eliminated. Backward areas should be given regional autonomy. Rural and urban areas should be treated at par.
26. Local bodies should be empowered and appropriately equipped.

27. *Concerning livelihood* Land should belong to 'tenants'. Land under the control of the feudal system should be confiscated and distributed to the landless and the homeless.
28. The property of middlemen and comprador capitalists should be confiscated and nationalised. Capital lying unproductive should be invested to promote industrialisation.
29. Employment should be guaranteed for all. Until such time as employment can be arranged, an unemployment allowance should be provided.
30. A minimum wage for workers in industries, agriculture and so on should be fixed and strictly implemented.
31. The homeless should be rehabilitated. No one should be 'relocated' until alternative infrastructure is guaranteed.
32. Poor farmers should be exempt from loan repayments. Loans taken by small farmers from the Agricultural Development Bank should be written off. Appropriate provisions should be made to provide loans for small farmers.
33. Fertiliser and seeds should be easily available and at a cheap rate. Farmers should be provided with appropriate prices and markets for their produce.
34. People in flood and drought-affected areas should be provided with appropriate relief materials.
35. Free and scientific health services and education should be available to all. The commercialisation of education should be stopped.
36. Inflation should be checked. Wages should be increased proportionate to inflation. Essential goods should be cheaply and easily available to everyone.
37. Drinking water, roads and electricity should be provided to all villagers.
38. Domestic and cottage industries should be protected and promoted.
39. Corruption, smuggling, black marketing, bribery, and the practices of middlemen and so on should be eliminated.
40. Orphans, the disabled, the elderly and children should be duly honoured and protected.

We would like to request the present coalition government to immediately initiate steps to fulfil these demands which are inextricably linked with the Nepali nation and the life of the people. If there are no positive indications towards this from the government by 17 February, 1996, we would like to inform you that we will be forced to adopt the path of armed struggle against the existing state power.

Thank you.

Dr Baburam Bhattarai
 Chairman
 Central Committee, United People's Front, Nepal

[Source: Deepak Thapa, ed., *Understanding the Maoist Movement of Nepal*, Kathmandu, Martin Chautari, 2003, pp. 391, First published in Dr Baburam Bhattarai, *Barta ra tatkalin rajnaitik nikasko prashna*, Kathmandu: Publication Department, Special Central Command, CPN (Maoist), Fagun 2059 BS (February 2003). Available online at: <https://www.satp.org/satporgtp/countries/nepal/document/papers/40points.htm>]

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